

Wednesday 24/04/2019 at 09:00 - 10:30

Paper Session 1

Cities, Mobilities, Place & Space 1

W622

AGEING, PLACE AND EVERYDAY LIFE

'Kilburn is not Kilburn any more': an analysis of ageing in and out of place

Louise Ryan, Majella Kilkey, Magdolna Lorinc, Obert Tawodzera
(University of Sheffield)

In the context of an ageing society, there is increasing attention on how people navigate and make sense of particular places through the ageing process (Kearns and Coleman 2017). With increasing frailty in advanced age, navigating even familiar places may become challenging (Sixsmith et al, 2014). Ageing, coupled with bereavement and diminishing support networks, may impact on people's sense of belonging in local places (May 2011). Of course places are constructed and dynamic; continually made and remade over time (Massey, 2004). As well as perceived changes, there may also be material changes which impact on long term residents especially older people – so Kilburn no longer feels familiar.

For migrants, ageing may result in additional challenges. For those who arrived in Britain to work, ageing and retirement may raise questions about return to the country of origin (Ryan, 2004). But return is not necessarily easy as 'home places' also change over time and migrants may no longer feel a sense of belonging there – feeling 'out of place' (Valentine and Sporton, 2009).

In this paper, drawing on new data from a large ESRC-funded project (Sustainable Care 2017-21), we explore how older, retired migrants experience ageing in and out of place. Focusing on Irish, African Caribbean and Polish migrants, we examine their relationships to places through intersections of age, gender, ethnicity and class. In so doing, we contribute to understanding older people as active agents in place-making, while also paying attention to changing materialities of place through time.

The making of an 'Irish community': an exploration of nostalgia and identity with retired Irish migrants in East London

Maev McDaid
(University of Sheffield)

This paper uses empirical research from an ongoing ethnographic study to show how, in 2018, East London's retired Irish Migrants socially construct an 'Irishness' reminiscent of 1950s Ireland through regular tea dances in a community hall. Most participants in the main study met at Irish tea dances in London when they first emigrated in the 1960s and 1970s. These events were a right of passage for migrants off the boat to make friends, find jobs and develop relationships. The participants of the study would then work their whole careers and raise families, making the dances harder to attend.

Now in retirement, they seek to return to that era by reproducing this space for their 'community'. Being retired, and no longer connected to work and employment - important to Irish migrants of this generation - has given not only time, but fostered the desire to be connected to a collective idea of Irish identity that is a throwback to times gone by. This paper considers the findings from self-organising individuals who have used nostalgic notions of community and envisioned it to realisation, with the motivation of combatting isolation and loneliness in austerity. It has proven popular and meaningful to those who are ageing in a city they do not come from, and under a state that offers them as older people, and as migrants, very little opportunities in their retirement years.

Digitization of later life and the doings of care

Roser Beneito-Montagut, Arantza Begueria, Nizaia Cassian
(Cardiff University)

This paper analyses how older people inhabit, experience and negotiate their places and practices in social media. It pays particular attention to the sociotechnical arrangements of care and affect through social media and to the emerging everyday life caring practices online in their entanglement with offline life. In doing so, the paper also attempts to shed light on the social constitution of ageing in digital spaces too.

Care and caring practices online do not exist in a vacuum. They exist as social and material arrangements, and there is scarce understanding about how older people resist inequality/equality and negotiate inclusion/exclusion in social media. We present three illustrative vignettes of technologized affective 'encounters' based on empirical data generated for an ethnographic project studying social media and later life. These will describe how people make together with kin networks of mutual and interdependent care which can be partly sustained, not without problems, by social media, but these networks of care have multiple and very different shapes.

We suggest that care on social media might be able to deal –to some extent- with the socio-emotional dimension of care (Milligan, Roberts & Mort, 2011) and social connectedness but we need to understand the 'affects' and problematics of a digitalized later life too. The model of care emerging in this context is interdependent and based on mutual-care; yet, organized around relationships that matter.

Cities, Mobilities, Place & Space 2

W610

GLASGOW

Something like a nest: Glasgow School of Art, Red Road and the inscription of cultural value in the city

Daryl Martin
(University of York)

This paper takes the recent fires at the Glasgow School of Art as the starting point for a reflection on the ways in which cultural value is inscribed in, and projected through, urban spaces. I analyse reporting of the GSA fires in 2014 and 2018 across a variety of media, and link the depth of emotional responses to this building to those we more typically associate with places of home and practices of home-making. This affective charge is similarly discerned in the somewhat heroic efforts to keep the ruined structure upstanding, with the current scaffolding resembling something like a nest, holding the building together with great care. By way of contrast with the response of local authorities and cultural organisations to the GSA fires, I track the lack of care in the demolition of the city's Red Road flats, and the political indifference shown to their latter-day residents. The comparison is instructive and uncomfortable, given the disparity in cultural value ascribed to both sites by authorities at local and national levels. In this paper, then, I seek to use architecture as a lens that allows us to open up the wider socio-material politics enfolded within buildings, the means of their ruination, and the obdurate social inequalities that shape the contemporary city.

Escapist urbanism: tensions, politics and class reproduction in a Glaswegian urban meadow

Helen Traill
(LSE)

In an era of increasing inequalities, spaces in which to retreat from the pressures of the capitalist city and its violences become crucial. Communal growing spaces can present one such retreat. Drawing on evidence from an ethnography of an urban meadow in Glasgow, I argue that communal growing presents an ambiguous site of escape: a retreat for some, but often not those who experience the most structural violence. Growing spaces can allow for a reprieve from the pressures around the expectation of consumption and production. They also offer a space where some differences can be negotiated, particularly promoting a narrative of inclusion. Nevertheless, this is partial and incomplete. Engaging with the debate around the potential radicalism of communal gardening spaces, I want to suggest that growing sites can be understood as presenting a mode of escapist urbanism as a way of situating the ambiguous politics of such spaces. John Urry argued that the question is not with whom resistance starts, but 'does it move?' Given evidence that gardening works in many different contexts, there is room for the possibility of a broader practice of inclusivity and solidarity. Yet the case study presents a boundary politics: a culturally middle-class space encroaching north into working class Glasgow. This acts as a limit to any potential radicalism; through the reproduction of social exclusion, particularly along the axis of class. In this way, escapist spaces can capture the political ambivalence of urban retreat.

Understanding consumer coping assemblages, within the context of food insecurity in Royston, Glasgow.

Karen Scott
(University of Strathclyde)

Food insecurity within the UK is recognised within public, private, and government sectors, as a substantial societal concern. Within Glasgow alone, the delivery of food aid is diverse, transient, and provided by a plethora of suppliers.

Existing research, which surrounds food insecurity, can be found in relation to income, expenditure, drivers and demand for services. However, research is largely absent about understanding the impact, severity, and strategies employed by individuals and organisations in order cope with the prevalence of food insecurity.

Within this research, food insecurity is considered a particular form of consumer vulnerability, which can result from individual consumer experiences, highlighted by its own set of social practices and values. This paper is based on ethnographic research in Royston, Glasgow. Royston comprises five SIMD data zones, four situated within the most deprived decile. Data collection includes interviews with representatives who either contribute to, or are the recipient of, the provision of food aid.

This research comes in the form of a consumer coping assemblage. Assemblage theory originates from the work of Deleuze and Guattari, and refers to the bringing together of heterogeneous components, allowing the study of interactions and relations occurring between different capacities. The findings explore (1) under what conditions coping assemblages become stabilised/destabilised, (2) how material, expressive and imaginative capacities interplay within consumer coping assemblages, and (3), the ways that coping assemblages become transformative.

'Regenerating' Glasgow? Dispersal, Asylum and Accommodation

Emma Hill, Nasar Meer, Tim Peace
(University of Edinburgh)

Focusing on Glasgow, this paper empirically explores the ways in which housing can be understood as a technology of government, specifically in the management and regulation of accommodation options for asylum seekers. Glasgow has participated in the Dispersal Scheme since 1999 and today is one of the main recipients of asylum seeking people in the UK and the only recipient in Scotland. Though this initial part of the Dispersal process has received considerable attention, it is not the only act of dispersal to which asylum seeking people in Glasgow are subject. In the two decades since the Scheme started, asylum seeking people have also experienced 'secondary' and 'tertiary' dispersals from the sites in which they were initially accommodated (Piacentini 2012). These additional displacements have been related to local and devolved activities, which have sought to 'regenerate' areas of existing multiple deprivations. Drawing on research from the GLIMER Project, this paper examines the relationship between the Dispersal Scheme, Glasgow-based regeneration initiatives and the displacement of asylum seekers in the city. It argues that the relationship between Dispersal and regeneration is not coincidental but incidental and finds (1) that the governance of Dispersal accommodation directly contributes to regeneration efforts and the displacements that they cause and (2) that regeneration efforts combine with neoliberal priorities of the Dispersal governance to contribute to secondary and tertiary displacements. Based on our findings in Glasgow, this paper finally argues towards an approach that thinks multilaterally about how patterns of displacement materialise in local sites.

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W727

UNIVERSITIES IN AND OUT OF PLACE

Signalling the 'multi-local' university? The place of the City in the growth of London-based satellite campuses, and the implications for social stratification

Rachel Brooks, Johanna Waters
(University of Surrey)

Around 2009, some UK universities (based outside of the capital) began to open 'satellite campuses' in London. There are currently 13 such campuses, which have been developed primarily with an international student market in mind. Concerns have been raised, however, about the quality of teaching on these campuses and the fact that student attainment is ostensibly falling significantly below that for the 'home' campus. This paper is the first of its kind to investigate, systematically, the ways in which universities are representing themselves in relation to these campuses. We discuss the role that the city of London plays as a pivotal backdrop to these developments, and the way it serves to substitute and compensate for lower levels of resources provided directly to the student from the university – here we consider accommodation, the outsourcing of teaching, the absence of a substantive campus environment and a general lack of focus on 'pedagogical' matters in almost all marketing materials. Instead, the universities place London at the front and centre of attempts to 'sell' the campus to potential students. The paper makes some innovative conceptual links between work in migration studies on the role and function of global cities in attracting workers and the way in which the city functions in this case, to attract international students. These campuses feed into debates about the increasing inequalities evidenced as a consequence of the internationalisation of higher education, even when such developments are ostensibly 'domestic'.

Accessing Higher Education: The experiences of 'estranged students' beyond entry point

Yvette Taylor, Cristina Costa, Sidonie Echochard, Claire Goodfellow
(University of Strathclyde)

This paper is focused on the experiences of 'estranged students' in Higher Education (HE). The term 'estranged students' has been used by policy makers and support groups to refer to students whose relationships with their biological/adoptive parents and/or wider family have broken down (OFFA, 2017). In England, the status of 'estrangement' was first introduced in student funding policy in 1997. In Scotland, however, the same status was only recognised in 2016, thus creating an almost 20 year gap between the two countries where the enactment of policy and practices aimed at supporting estranged students are concerned. 'Estranged students' continue to face numerous and specific hardships not only in accessing HE, but also in completing their studies, hardships that remain unaddressed and which encompass not only financial pressure, but also experiences of homelessness, discrimination and mental health problems amongst other issues, during their time at University (Bland, 2015). The scale of these challenges arguably extend beyond understanding of socio-economic struggles and set 'estranged students' apart from other under-represented groups. In 2016, the Stand Alone Pledge was launched to help HE institutions improve the support they provide to estranged students. The pledge has now been signed by 50 institutions UK wide, but only four institutions endorsing this cause are Scottish. The research project addresses a need for in-depth knowledge and discussion of the experiences of 'estranged students' in HE, in particular in Scotland, given its late engagement in estrangement statutory support.

Working with Community Researchers to challenge urban inequalities

Dr Aleksandra Grzymala-Kazłowska, Dr Lisa Goodson, Dr Sara Hasan, Dr Peter Lee
(University of Birmingham)

The paper will discuss the challenges and opportunities of working with over 60 local residents trained as community researchers in the project "Unlocking Social and Economic Innovation Together" (USE-IT!) to shape and enact the urban development process in the Great Icknield area of Birmingham. The project aims to involve diverse and divided communities in the process of urban regeneration as well as equip and empower local residents experiencing various forms of intersecting inequalities to take advantage of different assets and undertake active roles to influence the change. USE-IT! tries to unlock the potential innovation within the project area for the purpose of addressing urban poverty and inequalities as well as helping to deliver sustainable urban development that is beneficial to local people. The presentation will consider different aspects of the USE-IT project including social intervention, capacity building and co-production. It will focus on power structures and the role of academics in "mediating" between local communities and institutional stakeholders as well as debating the possibility of challenging hierarchies and inequities between different partners.

The paper analyses the problem of inequalities within diverse urban communities, unused assets and barriers in development as well as opportunities for urban change analysed from the sociological perspective.

Culture, Media, Sport & Food 1

W709

MEDIA, HEALTH & LIFE COURSE

A Time of One's Own? Young people's use of social media platforms in the context of neoliberal governmentality

Susan Batchelor, Justine Gangneux
(University of Glasgow)

The paper explores the meanings that young people ascribe to social media platforms in a context characterised by temporal desynchronisation, the individualisation of youth transitions, as well as the commodification of leisure. Drawing on contemporary qualitative data from two research projects conducted in Glasgow, Scotland, the paper examines how young people, aged 13-25 years, accounted for their engagement with social media platforms. The analysis illuminates how social media platforms were often understood in relation to time (e.g. as a means of procrastinating, managing time, or being productive) and described as 'tools' to micro-manage the everyday, maintain relationships and create professional opportunities. Such understandings indicate the ways in which participants internalised broader neoliberal narratives about the need to be enterprising, self-improvement-orientated choice-makers – but also highlight possibilities for resistance, or at least different modes of engagement.

Hard Knock Life: Media discourses of causality and responsibility following a diagnosis of Chronic Traumatic Encephalopathy.

Gregory Hollin
(University of Leeds)

'Chronic Traumatic Encephalopathy' (CTE) is a form of neurodegenerative disease associated with head injury and linked to a range of mood and motor disturbances. Most frequently sustained during sporting activity, there is growing concern about a 'silent epidemic' of dementias associated with CTE and there have been recent, high profile, calls to modify sporting practice; ranging from proposed rule changes in soccer to the banning of contact rugby in schools. This paper examines CTE with reference to the case of Aaron Hernandez. A successful player in the National Football League (NFL), Hernandez was found guilty of murder in 2015 before dying by suicide in prison in 2017. Upon his death, Hernandez's family donated his brain for medical research and post-mortem examination revealed evidence of advanced CTE. Focusing on coverage immediately follow the murder (2013), conviction (2015), death (April 2017), and post-mortem diagnosis (Nov 2017), this paper analyses US media coverage of Hernandez's case in order to examine how a diagnosis of CTE affects media discourse surrounding violent acts performed by athletes. Particular attention is paid to the re-distribution of causality and responsibility on the part of the key actors such as the NFL and Hernandez himself. Through this analysis, the paper examines how the brain becomes entangled with, and diffracts through, other facets of US and football culture such as domestic violence, prison reform, and structural racism in order to consider what social justice within sporting arenas might mean in the wake of CTE.

Digital media and mothers' emotional wellbeing: Balancing optimism and caution

Ranjana Das

(University of Surrey)

This paper draws from empirical work on the role of digital media in the perinatal period (including pre-natal and post-natal periods) in British women's lives, to produce a set of recommendations on the role of new technologies in maternal well-being, particularly in the context of the National Health Service in the UK and its Digital Strategy. The 'perinatal' period, before and after birth, is mediated by a range of media technologies, like all other societal institutions, and increasingly digitally so. The policy context in the UK, in terms of a series of austerity measures affecting public funding for mothers of very young children on the one hand, and the NHS Digital Strategy on the other - draws attention both to the emerging gaps in provisions for mothers, and promises, expectations and possibilities around the digital as it is often hailed for its many benefits. But as yet, poor understanding remains, on the brighter and darker sides of the digital mediation of the maternal, and the deeply contextual ways in which this needs to be approached. Drawing upon conclusions emergent from empirical work with mothers online and offline, this paper moves forward from empirical research to produce a set of recommendations for mothers as well as the national health service in the context of its digital strategy, for appropriate, constructive and careful uses of digital media to support maternal well-being in the critical perinatal years.

Culture, Media, Sport & Food 2

W308

FOOD, DRINK, CONSUMPTION & SUSTAINABILITY

Highbrow and Ordinary: The Emergence and Obfuscation of Cultural Capital in the UK 1897-2016

Aaron Reeves, Sam Friedman

(University of Oxford)

There is a long sociological tradition outlining the various ways advantaged groups use cultural capital. Yet this literature has struggled to speak to the historical development of this capital and whether its specific contents may have changed over time. Addressing these questions has been difficult because of the relative scarcity of historical data capable of documenting the emergence of the different modes of elite consumption. Our paper draws on a unique catalogue of British elites (Who's Who) which collects data on elite culture in an unusual way, using a free-text question rather than the 7 or 8 standard survey items. This freedom to input whatever respondents want adds a degree of richness to our data uncommon elsewhere. The results reveal three distinct stages of elite culture in the UK over the last 120 years. First, a dominant mode of aristocratic practice forged around the leisure possibilities afforded by landed estates but which waned significantly in the late 19th century. Second, a highbrow culture dominated by the fine arts and a romantic appreciation of the natural world which increased sharply in the early 20th century before beginning to gently recede in the most recent birth cohorts; and, third, a contemporary mode increasingly characterised by the blending of aristocratic and particularly highbrow pursuits with more ordinary forms of cultural participation. These shifts not only reveal important changes in the nature and contents of elite culture but they also chart wider developments in the emergence and development of cultural capital in the UK.

The social metabolism of food waste in Taiwanese's household

Yi-Ping Cheng

(National Changhua University of Education, Taiwan)

In this research, I aim to focus on the footage of food to food waste. I appropriate the concept of social metabolism, material trajectory and cultural biography of things to catch the dynamic footages of how food turns into leftover and food wastes. After a small scale pilot study, I designed a food-waste diary to seize the visual image and material flow of an enormous variety of food waste which are produced from the most ordinary domestic practice. In this research, I interviewed 21 Taiwanese households which were asked to record their household food-waste diary for at least 30 days. To sum up my research, first, food waste is a social process relates to the concept of 'freshness and perishability' in culinary context. Second, food-waste reveals the temporal-spatial aspects of everyday practice at home, especially in their material paths. And the last, how the recycling policy in Taiwan influence the ways of dealing household food wastes in practice.

Transgressive Drinking Practices and Social Inequalities: The Role of Colonial Government's Alcohol Policies and Drinking Culture

Emeka Dumbili

(Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka)

In traditional Nigeria, locally-produced alcoholic beverages had strong symbolic values and culture defined the rationales for drinking, the functions alcohol performed, and drinking time and space. While alcohol consumption was for pleasure and social bonding, intoxication was taboo and punished in most communities. Following the arrival of European traders and subsequent colonial rule (between 1914 and 1960), drinking culture altered.

Drawing on qualitative research, including archival material analysis, interviews and observation, this study explores the historical evolution of transgressive drinking cultures/practices and social inequality in Nigeria. It focuses on how the drinking culture and practices which the Colonialist introduced to the Natives (between 1914 and 1960), through the importation/marketing, unique consumption styles and idolization and fetishization of European-made alcoholic beverages redefined the local drinking culture and engender social exclusion, inequalities and transgressive consumption norms. The study explores how these are reproduced in contemporary Nigeria and the implications of such reproduction for the contemporary drinking cultures.

The study argues that contemporary drinking cultures, where Nigerian youths construct social/gender identities with heavy drinking, normalize the 'culture of intoxication', idolize/venerate foreign and/or expensive alcoholic beverages and jettison locally-made beverages are resilient drinking cultures traceable to the colonial era. The study discusses the implications of these findings, suggesting measures to decolonize drinking culture.

Medicine, Health & Illness 1

W002

Assaying surrogacy laws in India: body politics, market and cultural revivalism

Madhubanti Sen

(Central University of Gujarat, India)

The paper focussed on how in an attempt to concentrating solely on the dominant forces, the substantial rights and autonomy of surrogates have been overlooked. Reproduction and motherhood is both a biological as well as social endeavour. Human reproduction is filled with cultural meanings. The main underlying factor of reproduction is that women bear babies and men are exempt from those roles. This kind of gender difference confers the responsibility of childbearing solely on women, leading to ignorance of other important aspects in a woman's life. While reproduction holds different kind of values in women's lives from that of men, the meaning of reproduction varies according to social context. Whereas for rural women, children are a source of income; the upper caste Brahmin or mercantile families hold onto tradition and customs where the demand for a male child is related directly to the concept of dowry. It is important to carry out a systematic study of women's health in a broader spectrum while narrowing down the focus on reproductive health. The demand for technologically-assisted conception made adoption a complex alternative, pushing people towards options such as surrogacy. This paper attempted to study the legal dimension of surrogacy catering to the interests of different dominant forces which reveals the Janus-faced image (tradition and modern) of Indian state and examine state from the standpoint of the women especially surrogates from subaltern backgrounds. The phenomenon of new reproductive technologies and its growing market ignores the subaltern population and their reproductive rights.

Psycho-Social & Economic Problems of Parent's of children with Epilepsy: A Study of the Children's Hospital & the Institute of Child Health Multan, Pakistan

Kamran Ishfaq, Junaid Raza, Imtiaz Ahmad Warraich, Bareera Fyiaz

(Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan, Pakistan)

The parents of children with epilepsy faced numerous psycho-social and economic problems that are often neglected. These children required regular attention on daily basis. Parents of children with epilepsy often have to leave from their jobs. The objective of study is to investigate the psycho-social and economic problems faced by parents of children with epilepsy. The study is conducted at the Children's Hospital & the Institute of Child Health Multan, Pakistan. Total number of 100 parents recruited in this study. Interview schedule is used as a tool for data collection through convenient sampling. Epilepsy patients' parents recruited and the other types of disease patients' parents were excluded from the study. Of the 100 respondents majority of respondents were male 71(71.0%) while 29(29%) were female. About 50(50%) of respondents were aged between 25-35, while 32(32%) of the respondents were age between 36-45, and 18(18%) of respondents were aged between 46-55. Of the 100 respondents, majority of the respondents family monthly income were 15000-25000 PKR, while 32(32%) of the respondents family monthly income were 26000-35000 PKR, 19(19%) of the respondents family monthly income were 36000-45000 PKR and 12(12%) of the respondents family monthly income were 46000-55000 PKR. Parent's daily social activities were significantly affected; they had been experiencing frustration, depression, guilt and helplessness, decreased visiting friends, relatives, watching TV or videos. Results indicated that parents of children with epilepsy had faced many problems. Suitable intervention must be required to support these parents so that they can improve their social life.

Integrating new biomedical technologies in IVF treatment: the case of time-lapse imaging

*Alina Geampana, Manuela Perrotta, Josie Hamper
(Queen Mary University of London)*

Time-lapse imaging has recently been introduced in fertility treatment and represents a controversial, yet potentially revolutionary tool for IVF practice. Time-lapse technologies take pictures of embryos at regular intervals (every 5, 10, or 20 minutes) and produce a large amount of images for each embryo. This data, in conjunction with computer algorithms, is meant to help professionals pick the best embryo to be implanted. Embryo selection is essential in IVF practice for increasing pregnancy rates and reducing the negative effect of repeated failures. Nonetheless, a significant number of clinics charge additional fees for this new, yet clinically unproven technology. Our research asks: How is time-lapse technology currently integrated in clinical practice? How is it advertised to patients? How is it perceived outside professional circles? Using ethnographic data collected from 5 UK clinical sites (observations in IVF labs and interviews with professionals) and document analysis (medical literature, manufacturers' and clinics' websites, public documents produced by stakeholders), we argue that the case of time-lapse reveals several shortcomings in the development and uptake of new technologies in IVF practice. More specifically, we critically explore three inter-related influential areas: patient expectations, IVF marketing and technology trends, and IVF professionals' integration of technological innovation in medical practice. We conclude that the development, use and marketing of new medical technologies must be sensitive to the perpetuation of inequities in health access. The use and cost associated with time-lapse technology is important in shaping inequalities of access to health care services in the global fertility market.

Medicine, Health & Illness 2

W003

Dying in the Margins: How socio-economic deprivation effects end of life experiences in the UK

*Naomi Richards, Dr Emma Carduff
(University of Glasgow)*

There is consistent evidence that people in more socio-economically deprived areas in the UK are less likely to die at home than people living in more affluent areas, are less likely to die in a hospice and to access specialist palliative care than people in more affluent areas, and bereaved relatives report less satisfaction with care provided than do more affluent families. The wider context to this picture is that there is clear evidence that socio-economic deprivation is associated with worse health outcomes across the lifecourse. Poorer people die younger and there is now some evidence that the inequalities and disadvantages they have experienced throughout life extend to their end of life experience. There is generally little research on the reasons for these end of life inequalities, and indeed, we have little insight internationally into the overall end of life experiences of those who are socio-economically deprived. In this talk, we outline the current state of knowledge about this inequality, including speculation as to the reasons for it (which in some cases may be value-laden). What do we know about the specific needs, wants and experiences of people dying in socio-economic deprivation? And how can researchers access the life-worlds and day-to-day experiences of people dying in socio-economically deprived circumstances in order to answer this question? This talk seeks to open up an important discussion about equality of access to home dying and other end of life supports for different socio-economic groups.

'Sometimes there are, what seems like, no words... sometimes it is just reaching out and holding someone's hand': Reacting to and engaging with suffering in palliative care work.

Natalie Richardson

(University of Sheffield)

Suffering is an emerging field of sociological thought. Much has been written about how suffering is experienced by chronically or terminally ill individuals, refugees and groups living in poverty. In this, we can understand that suffering often involves a renegotiation, or a loss, of personhood (Cassell 1991, Charmaz 1983). However, little is known about the caregiver's perspective and their experiences of attempting to alleviate patient suffering. This paper will draw upon the findings of an ethnographic research project conducted over six months in a hospice in the North of England. I will explore the day-to-day experiences of palliative care workers as well as the relationships, interactions and engagements between the palliative care workers and their patients. I will argue that the palliative care professionals seek to maintain the personhood of their patients, wherever possible, by engaging in humour, intimate dialogue and by simply getting to know their patients' lives as well as their idiosyncrasies. Physical touch, through the holding of hands or embracing, is often a method of reacting to and engaging with patient suffering for the professionals. In highlighting these relationships between caregivers and patients, the paper seeks to provide an alternative contribution to the sociology of suffering. Furthermore, the paper will reflect on the ways in which palliative care professionals experience, engage with and understand suffering within their place of work.

Covering Euthanasia and Assisted Dying in Australia: The case of David Goodall

Sam Han

(The University of Western Australia)

While the debates on euthanasia and its complementary term 'assisted dying' can be traced back to the mid-19th century in Europe and the United States, more recently, it has reached global proportions—spreading to East Asia (e.g., South Korea and Japan) and Australia. Much of the existing social scientific literature on euthanasia and assisted dying has focused on the legality of euthanasia, particularly in European nations that have enacted various measures allowing it to some degree. This paper proposes to shift that focus both geographically—looking at an Australian case—and substantively, by examining the dynamics of media coverage of a highly-publicized case of euthanasia, namely that of Perth-based scientist David Goodall, who flew to Switzerland in May 2018 to end his own life at the age of 104. His decision galvanized media coverage regarding not only his decision but also the fact that he was crowdfunding part of the expenses and had spoken so publicly about his desire to end his own life. This paper, therefore, analyses Goodall's death as a 'media event,' as recently theorized by Nick Couldry and Andreas Hepp in relation to 'mediatization' theory, examining Australian media sources (e.g., the Australian Broadcasting Corporation) and social media.

Bourdieu and public health reform

Louise Wilson,

(NHS Orkney)

How can the public health community best respond to change associated with reform of public health in Scotland? Pierre Bourdieu, a late 20th century philosopher and sociologist, provides an interesting framework with which to explore practice.

Three key concepts of Bourdieu are: habitus – durable, transposable dispositions; field- structured social space; and capital – value within a field, cultural, social, symbolic and economic in nature. In addition hysteresis – the sense of disconnection when major change occurs in a field, is important. The rules and capital of specific fields are changing with the work of the Scottish Government and Local Government on the public health reform programme and priorities.

In Scotland the practice of public health delivered by specialists has, in part, coalesced with those of the dominant player Scottish Government, with performance standards and access to public resources. For others working in the public health arena there is alignment with local government. Arguably the habitus for public health agents in these two arenas is different. There is a risk, despite engagement events and consultation, of hysteresis, of a sense of imposed external forces beyond the discipline and challenges to the field and to capital.

Considering the Public Health reform agenda through a Bourdieusian lens enables review of the fields in which public health is valued and may allow a position of enhanced resilience for those working in public health and new opportunities for the discipline.

Methodological Innovations 1

W009

Rhythms, pains and pleasures: Capturing sensual and affective experiences through alternative methodologies

Emily Falconer
(University of Westminster)

Capturing the momentary, sensory experiences of social life beyond verbal narrative opens new opportunities and challenges for social research. This paper explores the alternative methods employed in my research that move beyond structured interview data, to make way for new, interdisciplinary approaches to social research methods. To do this, I will focus on three separate research projects spanning over six years (2012-present): Firstly, my doctoral research into the embodied experiences of independent women travellers, for whom spatial and temporal bodily rhythms were central to capturing the 'hidden moments' of their daily encounters. Secondly, the affective ethnographies of commuter train travel from my post-doctoral research *Feeling the Commute: Affect, affordance and communities in motion* (Falconer 2017), where the chosen methodologies were greatly influenced by the seasonal and daily rhythms of everyday life and affective atmospheres. Finally, my current ethnographic research into male choir singing and the affective belonging of collective song. This project brings together the sociology of gender, masculinity and feminist theory with the emotional and sensual geographies of sound and the role of rhythm in everyday life. These seemingly disparate projects are linked by a common pull towards a methodology of rhythm. Methodological innovations in sociology can significantly benefit from borrowing theories of affect, rhythm and movement from human geography and musicology. Theoretically, this paper seeks to create a lasting framework for thinking about how music, the use of voice and bodies, and an analysis of rhythm has the potential to reflect changing theories of gender and social life.

The sexual in the interview: exploring sexual arousal in in-depth interviewing

Jaime Garcia Iglesias
(University of Manchester)

How do researchers negotiate their participants' or our own sexual arousal during interviews? How can an informative intimacy be established through and/or despite of sexual feelings? Previous research in the ethical quagmires of in-depth interviewing has focused on issues such as participant safety, capability of consent, and the management of relationship expectations. The work of Plummer, Ellis and Tillmann has served to advance meaningful considerations of the emotional challenges of interviewing. However, remarkably little work has been produced particularly exploring the development and management of sexually arousing emotions during interviewing. In this work, I respond to Plummer's 2003 call for an ethnography of the body that takes into account lustful and erotic desires.

This paper collects methodological anecdotes from my fieldwork which consisted in fifteen online in-depth interviews with men about their sexual fetishes and practices. The autoethnographic analysis of these methodological challenges reveals how sexual arousal frame the informational and emotional exchanges inherent to research: at times, these sexual flows facilitate communication while, at others, they problematize consent-giving and expectations. Overall, this exploration serves to highlight the ways in which sexual emotions need to be openly considered and explored as part of the dynamics at play in interviewing, their role in researcher training and wellbeing and in the capacity of participants to sustain consent throughout the process.

Speed Bumps, Stop Signs & Diversions: Emotions in Research

Sharon Greenwood
(University of Glasgow)

Denzin (1984: x) explained that emotions occupy a place 'at the intersection of the person and society', and as such, 'to be human is to be emotional'. Emotions pervade our personal and professional lives; thus, arguably, are unavoidable within research. However – the extent to which emotions are acknowledged by researchers varies widely, and often the decision to account for the role of our emotions falls along disciplinary lines, with much of the literature emerging from the feminist canon (Watts, 2008). The dominance of feminist commentary on this relates to the ideological values related to feminism – namely, the importance of experience in the construction of knowledge, and 'the impossibility of the Cartesian rationalist project which set up the dualisms on which much of western thought has been based—the separation of mind from body, nature from culture, reason from emotion and the public from the private' (Holland, 2007: 196).

My doctoral research explored the lived experience of young adults (aged 16 to 30) affected by parental substance use – something that I was personally affected by growing up. This paper shares an autobiographical account of my relationship to the research, where I discuss the issues faced during the process. In particular, I discuss the difficult decisions made in relation to my position as a researcher – to my data, my participants, and my past. This paper concludes by emphasising the positive impact that 'emotionalising' our work can have in challenging dominant hierarchies that continue to oppress marginalised groups in society.

Race, Ethnicity & Migration A W011

MIGRANTS AND THE HOSTILE ENVIRONMENT

Immigration relations and perceptions in the UK: An ethnographic 'ride along' with the British lorry driver.

Anna Waistnage
(University of Leeds)

This research will investigate the current state of immigration relations in the UK. In recent years, immigration has played an important role in the making of key political decisions, decisively the EU referendum in 2016. Migration issues played a significant part and is one of the key issues which led voters to choose to leave (Devine, 2018). Days after the referendum results the media reported on a spike in hate crime, immigrants were being specifically targeted for verbal and physical abuse (Corcoran and Smith, 2016). The current trend of higher than usual levels of hate crime in the wake of key events (Hanes and Machin, 2014) raises questions about how prejudice towards immigrants is being developed and manifested in Britain. This research will review immigration since the introduction of New Labour into governmental power in 1997, who brought with them an openly hostile attitude towards certain types of immigrants (Schuster and Bloc, 2005) The immigrant has been demonised by a political system wishing to deflect their own failings and produce a suitable scapegoat for the working class to blame. This research will investigate these ideas by giving voice to those who live in and experience life in an area suffering from high levels of social deprivation. The area of Grimsby in North East Lincolnshire is considered to be amongst the most socially deprived areas in Britain; according to figures released in 2015 (Departments for Communities and Local Governments) and voted 70% in favour of leaving the EU. For this reason, this will be utilised as the ethnographic field.

Long term Caribbean migrants: a continuum of rights and restrictions

Elsa Oommen
(University of Warwick)

The paper will draw from findings arising from my ongoing pilot study which analyses long-term Caribbean migrants' experiences of rights (political, civil, legal) and restrictions (political, civil, legal) in the UK. Drawing from Foucauldian methods of analysis, my paper will focus on 'dividing practices', to explore the ways in which 'the subject is either divided inside himself (sic) or divided from others' (Foucault, 1982: 777-778) in the context of migrant/citizen binary in the current hostile environment. Interrogating such practices of bordering in immigration regimes inevitably links to histories of racism and colonialism (Jones et al, 2017: 207).

Citing Hall (1996), Benson argues that postcoloniality goes 'beyond formal relationships of colonisation, recognising that its reach extends even into contexts that were not directly colonised' (Benson, 2013: 316). This understanding of 'postcoloniality' is useful in exploring both historic and contemporary lives of Commonwealth nationals structured by disparate geometries of colonial power – from the white settler dominions to colonies. Exploring whiteness, Lundström (2014: 12) places emphasis on 'whiteness as a fluid, contextual and relational construction with unstable boundaries'. This conception of 'whiteness' enables an investigation into the embodied and transformative potential of whiteness in contexts of bordering – such as in the UK state immigration regime. In using a theoretical framework that is attentive to dividing practices, postcoloniality and whiteness, this paper will contribute to conceptualising a 'continuum of rights and restrictions' in the lives of long-term Commonwealth migrants within the contemporary UK immigration regime.

Family Histories: whiteness, national belonging, and the politics of home

Hannah Jones
(University of Warwick)

This paper investigates how people use family heritage and movement to make connections across national identities, and relates this to histories of racialised border control. The discussion focuses on narratives of Australians tracing their ancestors' migration from Britain, and British citizens planning to relocate permanently to Australia. In doing so, the particularities of whiteness in this specific diaspora-building are brought to light, and brought into conversation with attitudes and policies towards (non-white) migration, and histories of settler colonialism. What does an intentional (and optional) identification with migrant identity mean for these groups' sense of belonging – particularly in the context where a 'hostile environment' for immigration is powerful and popular in both countries?

Race, Ethnicity & Migration B W324

INDIGENEITY, INEQUALITY, DEVELOPMENT AND WELLBEING

'Labrador is a place where they pick our bones': Indigenous Inequalities and Resistance in Labrador, Canada

Jessica Penney

(University of Glasgow)

The historical and contemporary context of Labrador, Canada is informed by settler-colonialism and a legacy of imperialism, particularly in relation to natural resource extraction. Today, this is represented by the Muskrat Falls project, a hydroelectric dam being built to both generate electricity for the province and to sell abroad. The dam is anticipated to threaten local health through increased levels of methylmercury in the surrounding waters, and by altering access to traditional food and lifestyles by changing local ecology and limiting access to the land and river.

This paper explores the ways Indigenous activists perceive of inequalities faced by Indigenous people in Labrador and how they challenge them through their resistance to the Muskrat Falls project. It considers themes of meaningful consultation, consent, and participation, in the context of world-wide reflection on Indigenous peoples' rights and reconciliatory efforts in Canada.

Indigenous Research Methods were used to undertake this study, as the researcher is Inuit, participants have Indigenous ancestry, and the research took place on Innu and Inuit Indigenous land. Semi-structured interviews, questionnaires, and a focus group in the form of a sharing circle took place in summer 2018. Main findings suggest that conceptions of health and cultural changes were understood in relation to a changing environment, closely connected to Indigenous notions of health and wellbeing. Participants were frustrated with the democratic processes that allowed the project to go forward and felt as though they were experiencing ongoing colonialism.

Decolonising white settler subjects: becoming Treaty partners

Avril Bell

(University of Auckland)

As a settler colonial society, New Zealand was developed (as far as possible) in the image of Britain, a project that involved the assumption of white (Pakeha), western superiority and the relegation of Maori people, culture and knowledge to the economic, social and political margins. But since the 1970s the monocultural, Pakeha-centric vision of the society has been displaced by a conception of biculturalism that – rhetorically and symbolically at least – revises the society as fundamentally comprised to two, equal peoples, Maori and Pakeha, a vision founded on the history of the Treaty of Waitangi, signed between Queen Victoria's representative, William Hobson, and over 500 Maori leaders in 1840. Since the advent of biculturalism, and even more since reparative settlements began to be made to Maori tribes in the 1990s, talk of 'Treaty partnerships' has become widespread. At the macro level, Maori and the Crown are partners to the Treaty, but this idea also operates at the level of institutions and individual interactions. What does it mean for Pakeha New Zealanders to operate as Treaty partners? What changes in their ways of seeing, being and acting are required to interrupt the sedimented assumptions of white superiority that they/we have inherited from our colonial history, to decolonise ourselves? In this paper I will report on early data from a research project involving interviews with Pakeha working across a number of sectors of New Zealand society, exploring how they enact the role of Treaty partner in their work with Maori.

National Pride and Sense of Belonging in Multicultural Canada: Understanding Differences among Canada's Ethno-racial Communities

Monica Hwang

(St. Thomas More College, University of Saskatchewan)

We use data from the 2013 General Social Survey of social identity to assess national pride and sense of national belonging, with a special focus on Canada's three principal minority communities: French, Indigenous Peoples, and visible minorities. Analyses are conducted both before and after controls for: immigration status, religion, language, education, income, age, gender, region of residence, community size, and experience with discrimination. Findings reveal that national pride and sense of belonging are comparatively low among French respondents, with these patterns mainly traceable to their residential concentration in Quebec and their being predominantly Francophone. Indigenous Peoples express a high level of national pride, equal to that of any other group in the study; sense of belonging among Indigenous Peoples is slightly below average, although this result is almost entirely because they are relatively young, and young people tend to indicate lower national pride and sense of belonging. Visible minorities express a comparatively high level of both national pride and sense of belonging, with both sentiments stronger among those who are longer-term and older immigrants. These patterns hold even though two groups --- Indigenous Peoples and visible minorities --- report above-average experience with discrimination. Possible explanations for these patterns are discussed.

Race, Ethnicity & Migration 3

W525

WOMEN AND INTERSECTIONAL IDENTITIES AND PREJUDICES

The Politics and Complexity of Silence in the Marginalised Lives of Young Gypsy/Traveller Women in Scotland

Geetha Marcus

(University of Glasgow)

In this paper, I critically explore different forms of silence encountered throughout my research with Scottish Gypsy/Traveller girls. Gypsy/Traveller experiences in Scotland reveal an intricate, convoluted narrative of many silences. First, they suffer from the 'normative absence and pathological presence' of the 'Other' in policy discourse. The absence of history and identity of the Gypsy/Traveller in Scottish academic and cultural discourse renders their alternative knowledge and modes of thinking absent from mainstream recognition. The lacuna in the existing literature on Gypsy/Traveller women exacerbates their silence through the complexity of censorship, but also ensures they are represented as pathological victims when they do appear. Using a black British feminist framework, the aim of this paper is to chart the counter-narratives and memories of Gypsy/Traveller young women in Scotland highlighting the pernicious lack of recognition of the particular, yet diverse, accounts of the experiences of racialised Gypsy/Travellers girls. In conclusion, while silence among Gypsy/Traveller young women can be a belittling impediment, silence when used in defiance can also be empowering.

Estrangement and Ambivalence? Women's Accounts of Negotiating an Irish Catholic Heritage in Glasgow

Paul Goldie

(University of Glasgow)

There has been much scholarly interest in researching the Irish diaspora in Scotland in recent years. This has been conducted largely by quantitative sociologists who seek to ascertain whether structural disadvantages still impacts on the life-chances of one of Scotland's largest ethnic groups. However, to date there has been little in the way of qualitative studies examining the actual experiences of people from an Irish Catholic heritage. This study has sought to address this methodological imbalance by conducting 25 life history interviews with women in Glasgow. Interviews were conducted using photo-elicitation techniques as it is considered an effective way at gaining insight into participant's 'life-worlds'. Currently in the final stages of writing up, the talk will share some of the findings related to the themes of belonging. In particular, I will demonstrate that an anti-Irish-Catholic prejudice can create: ambivalence, or estrangement to participant's sense of cultural identity. For example, some of those who took part shortened their names to avoid being identified from an Irish Catholic background. Other participants told stories of strategically selecting when they would reveal their faith in public spaces. Overall, it is hoped that this paper will add to a greater understanding of the lives of the Irish diaspora in Scotland.

Delving Deeper into the Category of 'Lone Mother': Exploring Experiences of Pakistani and Bangladeshi Lone Mothers

Sarah Akhtar Baz,

(University of Sheffield)

There has been much academic and public focus on lone mothers in the UK exploring their positions as welfare subjects, workers and mothers. However, with the notable exception of Duncan and Edwards (1999), there has been a failure to fully consider diversity of identity (e.g. ethnic and class identities) within the category of 'lone mother' which can result in diverse experiences of lone motherhood. In particular, lone motherhood amongst Pakistani and Bangladeshi women has been overlooked. Pakistani and Bangladeshi women's racialized, ethnic, cultural, religious, gendered and classed identities are noted in literature as producing distinct barriers and experiences of marriage, motherhood, employment and divorce. Experiences also differ across age, migration status, generation and educational backgrounds. Consequently, in addition to facing policy pressures to commit to employment which all lone mothers face, Pakistani and Bangladeshi lone mothers may have unique experiences of lone motherhood associated with these identities.

Adopting an 'intersectionality' framework my doctoral research seeks to bring forward the lived experiences of Pakistani and Bangladeshi lone mothers and the barriers, disadvantages and opportunities they face associated with their multiple identities and positionalities. Which identities are significant in shaping their experiences of lone motherhood? The presentation will introduce the study and present initial findings from observations and in-depth interviews with lone mothers attending a South Asian women's organisation. Their subjective lived experiences cannot be focused on in isolation; how they are shaped by wider structures, institutions, inequalities, cultural norms and collective identities will also be brought forward.

Rights, Violence & Crime 1

W004

Rethinking Human Rights: humane, you what?

Jana Králová
(University of Greenwich)

It has been evidenced that human value is called into question under circumstances of structural violence, dehumanisation and intersectional discrimination, especially for those with compromised access to human rights. This paper discusses three theoretical contexts positioned at the extreme end of social exclusion, in the epistemological region of diminished legal protection where agency is inconsequential, and in the ontological debate about differential human value. It will establish an onto-epistemic gap 'beyond human rights'. In doing so, it will critically challenge the notion of "human" in the Human Rights Act 1998 and suggest a paradigm shift in its conceptualization. The paper argues that the notion of 'ontological insufficiency' should be embedded within the concept of 'human' in Human Rights. This is because the epistemology of 'ontological insufficiency' has reversed logic: unlike all the epistemological assumptions above about 're-duced' human value, ontological insufficiency looks at where, due to structural circumstances, human value has never been 'fully achieved'. Thus, ontological insufficiency is positioned in the epistemological gap between diminished legal protection, inconsequential agency and structural impossibility. This gap may be termed: social death.

Key words:

Humane Rights instead of Human Rights, Ontologically Insufficient Being (OIB).
#OIB, #CureSocialDeath, Twitter: @KralovaJ

The human rights city: an idea and a practice

Michele Grigolo
(Nottingham Trent University)

Human rights scholars are paying increasing attention to actions and policies within cities which appropriate the language of human rights. In this paper I move from a sociological perspective to offer an overview of the practice of human rights in cities by appropriating the idea, produced within the practice, of the human rights city. My goal is to cast a light on dynamics of collaboration and competition which go on between different social agents towards determining the meaning and use of human rights in the city. Based on these premises, I argue that cities do not simply passively appropriate given notions of human rights formulated in the international sphere; human rights are also reworked and sometimes reinvented, but also manipulated, via their association with the urban context and the government of the city. To begin with, I discuss the genesis and characteristics of this concept, while offering it as a useful tool for understanding different ways in which human rights are currently practiced in cities. Subsequently, I examine the use of human rights in cities for community organising as well as urban policy. Finally, I reflect on the nexus between human rights and the right to the city emerging from human rights cities. In the end, human rights (in) cities emerge as practice that shift and potentially innovate human rights, this process however implying also the subjection of human rights to the logic of government that drive the engagement of municipalities in human rights.

Challenging the State Failure Concept: The Inequality and Hierarchy of Interstate Relations

Alexandra Scott
(University of Edinburgh)

From the perspective of mainstream Western foreign policy and academic discourse on state failure, weak or failed states are a source of regional and global insecurity, safe-havens for the preparatory stages of terrorist attacks and for organised crime groups. Through analysis of drug crime along the Central Asian trafficking route, this article illustrates the conceptual flaws of the 'failing state' narrative. State-building capability of external actors remains an area of uncertainty. Looking at the ideological underpinnings of state-failure, its weak to collapsed classification, the article argues that it appears not only to maintain, but advance power and hegemony of contemporary political hierarchies. The problems of such states are real, but theories that promote Western idealised notions of statehood stop serving as mere tools of understanding reality and become normative theories. The concept of failed statehood is used in justifying interventions that make empirical reality of such states conform to the model of West's state-building agenda.

There is an emerging body of evidence that it is time to develop concepts which are better suited to analyse existing states and develop alternative non-state centric approaches to governance and to widening the perspective in understating the weak or fragile states.

Science, Technology & Digital Studies 1 **W007**

Breaking Gender Code: Stereotypes as a barrier to women entering programming cultures in online spaces

Sian Brooke

(University of Oxford)

The visible absence of women in online coding forums has led to widespread assumptions about gendered ability and creative capacity (Ford et al., 2016; Tanczer, 2015). Despite claims of hacking being an informal meritocratic community, there are fewer women in hacking than in any other computational field (Adam, 2004; Jordan, 2016; Toupin, 2014). This project utilises Lessig's (2001, 2006) definition of hacking in terms of creation, as a practice that requires the invention and repurposing of code in unintended ways. I have chosen the term creative coding to examine the hacking phenomenon beyond the masculine stereotypes commonly associated with the culture (e.g., Jordan, 2016; Levy, 2010; Raymond, 1996). I argue that widespread assumptions and discourse about hackers and creative coders as being masculine and as performing masculinity are simultaneously a cause and a result of the exclusion of women in these communities.

Stereotypes can influence personal performance and entry practises through perceptions of the masculine insider. Even exposing women to stereotypical computer science objects (such as Star Trek posters and video games) actively deters women from participating, as they serve as a reminder that it is a hostile male dominated field (Cheryan et al, 2009). The project presented here is the first of three complimentary studies that examines women's absence in creative coding. Using survey-based data, the project modelled the relative contribution of gender-based stereotypes in erecting barriers to women entering coding. The project answers two questions; (1) do gender-based stereotypes effect perceptions of hostility across platforms? (2) Are gendered assumptions apparent/different in seeking and offering technical help in anonymous spaces? Overall, the research quantitatively demonstrates that masculine dominance of technical spaces is produced by hostile environments and stereotypes, rather than by a person's own gender.

Software development, communication, and social inequalities

Edison Bicudo

(School of Global Studies, University of Sussex)

Software development is sometimes depicted as a realm of cooperation, abundance, and equality. For the abstract, intangible nature of software would provide software developers with an endless and easy access to the immaterial resources they need, such as computational memory space, programming platforms, and others. Moreover, it is sometimes assumed that with the dissemination of the internet, programmers would become involved in open communities where data and knowledge sharing would be the prevailing rule.

Although such expectations are to a considerable degree valid, software development is also, and on crucial occasions, marked by unexpected and hidden manifestations of inequality and exclusion. It is important to understand such phenomena in order to see how digital technologies are contributing towards the formation and consolidation of divisions and hierarchies in contemporary society.

To unravel these processes, this presentation focuses on the development of neuroimaging software, used to analyse data produced by magnetic resonance scanners to depict the human brain and study neurological processes and diseases. The unequal conditions experienced by neuroimaging software developers based in different institutions will be highlighted.

The presentation draws on a study conducted from 2014 to 2018 as post-doctoral researcher of the University of Sao Paulo and Visiting Fellow of King's College London. In addition to quantitative analyses, this study entailed fieldwork in Brazil, the UK, Netherlands, and Portugal, with interviews with 57 neuroimaging researchers.

The study showed that, frequently, software development is characterized by the formation of hierarchies in terms of research funding, academic prestige, and programming knowledge.

Social Divisions / Social Identities A

W110

SOCIOLOGY Journal EVENT

Meet the editors of *Sociology*

Vanessa May, Andrew Balmer and Tarani Chandola

Come and meet the Editors of BSA's flagship journal, *Sociology*! Three of the current Editors of *Sociology* will be present to answer your questions. We will give a short introduction to the kind of papers that *Sociology* welcomes and provide guidance on how to ensure that your paper is sent out to review and eventually accepted. A significant portion of the event will be devoted to questions from the audience.

Social Divisions / Social Identities B

W828

Precarious citizens: Citizenship, fractured identities and belonging among Eastern European young people in Brexit Britain

Daniela Sime, Naomi Tyrrell; Marta Moskal
(University of Strathclyde)

This paper explores the ways in which young people aged 12-18, who moved to the UK from Eastern Europe as children, experience their fractured sense of identity and belonging in the context of Brexit. It draws on findings from the largest UK-wide study with this group, which included a survey with 1120 young people after the Brexit Referendum, focus groups and case studies. We consider young migrants' precarity in three senses: insecurity in relation to their rights, given their unclear status post-Brexit; a precarious sense of identity, given their racialisation and Othering in the context of an increasingly hostile environment; and a precarious future, which they cannot plan as they find themselves in limbo in terms of options available. For this group, the age at the time of experiencing Brexit as transition is crucial to understanding how they make decisions about becoming involved in society- or end up being marginalised. The supra-national identity of being European, which enabled their free-movement, is now implicated in their feelings of uncertainty and precarity. We show how young people are negotiating multiple identities, including European, national (e.g. British/Polish) and regional (e.g. Scottish/English). While young people feel that they belong in the UK, their everyday experiences of hostility and xenophobia are reminders that they are not allowed to belong. The paper questions the representation of EU migrants as privileged. Understanding migrant youth precarity through an identity and belonging lens leads to a more nuanced conception of hierarchies of citizenship and increasing inequalities in Brexit Britain.

'The British do not want us here' – Integration and Cohesion strategies in times of hostile environment and Brexit.

Loreen Chikwira
(Edgehill University)

Immigration policies, Brexit and the hostile environment created by the current government have brought debates on identity and belonging to the fore. These debates frame constructions of inequalities for transnational migrants (Anthias, 2016).

The UK government published an Integrated Communities Strategy (2018), whose purpose is to have a holistic approach to tackling social inequalities and divisions. The government also calls on leaders of Local government, organisations, and communities to work together and do more to promote integration and tackle social inequalities. For some local authorities, who have never prioritised integration due to perceived lack of 'enough' migrant population, there are additional systemic and structural barriers that need tackling before the Integrated Communities Strategy can be effectively implemented at a local level.

I draw from Feminist standpoint theory (Hill Collins, 2000; Harding, 2009) and use my personal experiences as a Cohesion manager at a Local authority and Feminist to provide a critical analysis of the process of developing an Integration strategy for such a local authority. In addition, I discuss the challenges I have faced in implementing the strategy for the local authority that has no previous experience in issues of social divisions, identities and belonging for transnational migrants. Feminist theory argues for situated knowledge production. Hence, my positioning as the 'expert' in the role intersects with my ethnicity, gender, social positioning to inform the approach to implementing the strategy.

Grayson Perry, Divided Britain (C4) and the role of the cultural operative

Lisa Taylor
(Leeds Beckett University)

One disadvantage of deliberative democracy, argues Prentoulis (2017), is that to achieve consensus from reasoned argument, it ignores the 'emotional and symbolic aspects' of political debate. Brexit heralded a conflicted public in need of a space to articulate the affective dimensions of political change. Agonistic politics conceives conflict as an energy with the positive potential to work through differences in democratic discussion. Mouffe (2013) argues that if passions and resentments are suppressed, they may be channelled in violent outbursts; the reported increase in hate crimes post-EU Referendum offers an example. I show that the documentary 'Grayson Perry: Divided Britain' (C4, 2017), provides an arena to articulate differences about what it means to be British post-Brexit.

Perry's public participants are invited to the Serpentine Gallery to view and discuss A Matching Pair – two vases that barometer the nation's cleaved identity. This moment offers radical potential for opposing views to be worked through from each camp. Prentoulis argues that the EU Referendum brought, 'the recognition ... that spaces are needed for a

more agonistic politics if we are to revive and radicalise democracy – less reliant on 'rationality' and more sensitive to symbolic meanings' (2017). 'Divided Britain' forms such a space: using the totemic power of art, the vases push the participants to note the limits of their positions and make new alliances. In this way, Perry's use of the documentary medium allows the work of the cultural operative the potential to heal, save and revitalise democracy.

Sociology of Education 1 **W823**

Finding one's way or being steered through vocational education? Educational choices of young people in French-speaking Switzerland

Christophe Delay

(Haute école du travail social et de santé EESP Lausanne)

Starting with a discussion of Willis's (1977) research as well as with the work of other sociologists who built upon it (McLeod 1987; Brown 1987), this presentation will revisit the issue of post-compulsory educational choices made by youth within the realm of vocational education. Founded upon an ethnographical study conducted in a school in Western Switzerland, it shows the ways in which, at the end of compulsory school, choices made by young students stem from a form of pragmatically rational decision-making (Hodkinson & Sparkes 1997); these choices are themselves inscribed in the context of distinct types of working class habitus – the latter being structured by a range of principles characteristic of different segments of the working classes.

The presentation then questions the role played, in Switzerland, by the highly selective school system (Meyer 2009); it analyses, within this track-based system, the importance of practices and discourses of the teaching staff that shape the choices made by youth and participate in the process of lowering expectations; finally, the specificities of the Swiss educational system are discussed and compared to the more comprehensive systems of United Kingdom and Nordic countries, in which orientations are proposed and expectations revisited on a basis more closely related to the autonomous decisions, poor results and intrinsic motivations of students (Furlong & Biggart 1999; Walther, 2006; Hegna 2013). This will lead to a discussion about what might be done by teachers to reduce school choice inequalities at the end of compulsory schooling.

Chinese rural students' mobility trajectory within the field of rural education: from 1980s to 2010s

Jiexiu Chen

(Institute of Education)

Since the Reform and Opening-up policy launched in 1978, China's social, economic and political environment have gone through significant changes. In terms of the higher education sector, the expansion of university admission and the ongoing development of privatization and marketization, together create an increasingly stratified higher education system in China. Meanwhile, the urban-rural divide keeps intensifying the unequal distribution of basic educational resources, and the meritocratic selection (Gaokao, college entrance examination), is widely accepted as a fair way to allocate educational opportunities. Therefore, layers of disadvantages should be considered, along with specific historical and social contexts when analysing rural students' social mobility experiences in China. This research has interviewed 50 rural students who graduated in 1980s, 1990s, 2000s and 2010s respectively. Through life history approach, this research intends to explore how social changes, higher education policy reforms have influenced rural students' social mobility experiences, and how rural students perceive the differences between urban and rural contexts (if there is any).

The presented work focuses on how rural students' educational opportunities are shaped and how they navigate their mobility trajectories towards higher education within the rural educational field. As the 'rural' is often discussed as a unified field, the presented work emphasises on the explorations of the complexity and hierarchy within rural educational field through first mapping out the fields that influence the rural educational field and second, analysing the cross-field effects among those interlinked fields. Then, through analysing participants' narratives about their parents' educational strategy, the presented work discussed the type and amount of capital that rural students generate from their positions in the field and how they utilise their resources (or not) to manage their trajectories. Moreover, the presented work reveals the interactions of rural students' habitus and rural educational field and the involvement of rural students' transforming desire for higher education.

P1 'We don't fall into those traditional statistics' P2 'We upset that, we sway, we upset them': Widening participation in neoliberal times

Sarah Leaney, Shadreck Mwale

(University of Brighton)

Within the socio-political context of increasing tuition fees, widening participation is centre stage in Higher Education (HE) policy and practice. Widening participation in HE is often positioned as key to resolving social inequality, it

underpins arguments that increasing levels of education lead to reduced levels of poverty as it catalyses the enhancement of marginalised individual's social and economic life chances. Located within the tension of duty and need, widening participation is positioned as both the responsibility of the University and a financial imperative.

This paper considers the student experience of this tension, specifically the contradictions between discourses of equality and diversity and neoliberal conceptualisations of HE as market. Drawing upon qualitative research on the closure of a widening participation programme, the paper explores the consequences of the withdrawal of HE provision for 'local' students. Utilising focus groups to develop a methodology for 'thinking with' this community of students, the research explored individual and group narratives and their development across three thinking sessions.

Located within the 'spatial turn' of class analysis, this paper questions the delegitimization of 'emplaced' HE provision, exploring the material, social and affective contexts within which students experience university in their 'home town'. This paper outlines the construction of the university as a space of stability and transformation, and the students' narration of the closure within their broader critique of austerity, inequality and struggle. We explore the formation of student identities, within a context of the participants' critical reflexive struggle of pursuing a devalued degree.

Theory 1

W323

Toward a theoretical framework of the (re-)production of domination and dominance

Dermot O'Reilly,
(Lancaster University)

I develop an outline theoretical framework that explains how social and organizational domination are produced, by drawing on a critical realist perspective and the theoretical constructs of activity theory. In particular, I introduce three inter-related germ-cell models of domination – interpersonal domination, sociocultural domination and inter-system domination. I also elucidate the underlying relational processes and outcomes that comprise the essence of domination in each germ-cell model, and clarify their moral-relevant aspects. In particular, the framework sheds light on the role of domination in producing asymmetry and inequalities, and addresses the admixture of domination and other modes of social relationship in the 'conflicted collaboration' inherent in the dynamic of contemporary social and organizational life. By articulating the sensitizing, analytical and moral-evaluative aspects of the theory of domination I contribute to the development of a central and critical concept in sociological and organizational theory and analysis. I encourage future research into social and organizational domination and discuss some of the avenues and issues inherent in developing it.

Institutional Democracy as an Antidote to Hierarchy and Inequality

Mike O'Donnell
(University of Westminster)

The argument of this paper is that an integration of the concept of community, both theoretically and in terms of policy, into socialist/social democratic practice is necessary to achieve a durable new social settlement based on an expansion of democracy and an increase in equality. Historically the dominant form of socialism has tended to oppose class to community and state power with national and local 'communal' hierarchy: the state being seen as the necessary means for achieving greater material equality and equality of cultural opportunity. In general, it is the Right that appeals to the notion of community, particularly, national community. Teresa May's ploy that Conservatism is the 'party of everyone', not 'just the many and the few' articulates this sentiment. 'Community' in these terms simply glides over fundamental inequalities. On the left, the largely distinct socialist and anarchist traditions, has tended to leave the later with the more active focus on building non-hierarchical. And yet it is inherent to socialism that it seeks to establish a democratic society far reaching than liberal democracy. Ironically, the populist surge offers an opportunity radically to advance this cause. 'Left' populism has a strong 'grass-roots' base and is characterized by community activism and an anti-hierarchical orientation. Several works, including my own, have demonstrated that local institutions and local branches of national institutions - economic, social/environmental and cultural - could be reformed to increase democratic participation and in a way that responds positively to diverse, including inter-sectional forms of inequality.

Playing a double game: The framing strategies to mobilise rebels of different status in their organisations in China's premodern rebellions

Zhen Wei
(University of Edinburgh; Academia Sinica)

This paper presents my initial findings from studying the framing that was used to mobilise rebels, as recorded in the 397 confessions of the rebels who participated in the White Lotus Rebellion (1796-1803) in Qing Dynasty China.

Reading through the lens that these confessions were constructed by interrogators, rebels, and the state power, I conducted quantitative and qualitative analysis. I suggest that the rebels can be divided into four groups according to the levels of status in their organisations, and the framing in the oral statements by which they were persuaded to join the rebellion correlates with their status. The most influential members of rebels were more likely to be persuaded by assuring them a high official post in future. The second level tended to be enticed by both opportunities to get benefits and to avoid the future disaster. The third level of rebels were mobilised by the promise of victory and threats of violence, while participants in the fourth level were mostly coerced to join.

The results present the possible framing strategies used to persuade rebels in China's premodern rebellions, which were seldom investigated by previous studies. In addition, while the rebellions in China are often researched with reference to their millenarian characteristic, which promotes creating an equal utopian world after the disaster, my research indicates that the attitudes of rebels towards this perception may also vary according to their status. This finding may contribute to sociological debates on why Chinese rebellions have failed to bring about revolutionary transformations.

Toward a Theory of Resistance Movements

*Benjamin Abrams,
(University of Cambridge)*

With the recent strengthening of populist authoritarianism around the globe, a new trajectory of global resistance has taken shape in countries such as Turkey, Poland, Hungary, and the United States. This wave of new 'resistance movements' is but one of three major instances of resistance in world history, each with their own sets of movements: the anti-Fascist resistance of the 1930s, and the anti-colonial resistance movements of the mid-20th Century.

This paper develops the theoretical groundwork for the further study of resistance movements, conceptualising them as 'movements which orient themselves around the refusal and subversion of an imposed order,' drawing together knowledge from these three world-historical instances of resistance movements. Resistance movements are highly distinct from social movements, not only in their mission, but also in their underlying dynamics. In particular, I identify three key attributes which characterise resistance movements across history, yet are exceptionally rare among conventional social movements.

Extensiveness: Resistance movements, unlike conventional social movements, are loosely structured, stretching across sectors of society and the state which commonly abstain from contentious politics, such as media organisations and state bureaucracies.

Irregularity: Rather than being primarily comprised of concrete movement organisations and highly mobilised activists, resistance movements are predominantly populated with actors who engage in movement activity only irregularly, informed by a broader sense of identification with the movement and its goals.

Volatility: Resistance movements are highly responsive to contextual changes. The constituent parts of such movements can rapidly transform, or re-mobilise for alternative causes, particularly revolution.

Work, Employment & Economic Life 1

HANGING LANTERN ROOM

The Politics of Food Banking in the UK

*Alan Connolly
(Lancaster University)*

This paper examines views on the political aspects of the burgeoning of the food bank sector in the UK in the period from 2010 to 2017. An estimated 8.4m people in the UK are 'food insecure', and food bank use has increased 384% since 2012 with up to 1.3m people now using them annually. There is a repetition in public discourse of the food bank as a symbol of 'Britain gone wrong', and this has frequently been used to criticise successive Conservative-led governments regarding perceived drivers of food bank use. Analysis of interviews I conducted with food bank staff, people using food banks and other stakeholders in the Liverpool City Region show that most participants are critical of the government in this way. My research, however, also found that their opinions on the wider political factors of food bank provision are complex and varied. They range from criticism of government social security policies to beliefs that the system is too generous; and from critiques of negative stereotypes of those receiving social security payments to arguments employing such stereotypes. Views on the relevance of issues such as immigration and foreign aid are similarly diverse. The political and historical backdrop of the issues raised, as well as the roles or positions of the participants, will be considered in order to put these views in context, and other academic literature and press reporting on food banks will also be discussed.

Time, the work ethic and social justice in social production - the case of community based food and energy production in Scotland

Gavin Maclean, Kendra Briken
(Edinburgh Napier University)

How will society frame its relations to work in a 'post-capitalist' mode of production? Recent crises - such as the financial crisis, austerity economics and the climate crisis - have increasingly led researchers, academics and activists to advocate alternative approaches to managing the economy and to consider 'post-capitalist' alternatives. Post-work arguments tend to emphasise embracing technology and automation in order to recast our relationship with employment (e.g., Srnicek and Williams, 2015). Yet these accounts often downplay the necessary forms of social reproductive labour required to maintain society and the social inequalities embedded within people's relationship with work and time. Our argument is that access to resources goes beyond very material relations and hence includes questioning existing ideas of good work and social justice within communities.

This paper seeks to critically debate how we can understand time, the work ethic and the possibilities of social justice within the context of alternative social forms of production. This paper presents initial findings from this ongoing research into work within social economies based around community energy and food production in Scotland. These communities are especially attuned to time - in terms of work-life balance, daylight and seasonality - based on the specificities of their labour and could provide a model for understanding future modes of production. This paper seeks to understand, through researching existing social economies, who will have time in a 'post-work' society and what will our relationship be with work in future modes of production.

Corporate social responsibility and private employment regulation: a challenge to precarity and inequality in neo-colonial supply chains?

Jill Timms, David Bek
(Coventry University)

Engagement in global discourses of corporate social responsibility (CSR) has become standard practice not only for transnational corporations, but increasingly for smaller businesses too. As we face the incompatibility of perpetual production growth and ecological crisis, claims of responsible, ethical, sustainable, good and philanthropic business behaviour pervade ever more areas of our everyday life. We can support the provision of clean water in far off countries through our choice of bottled water, sponsor child immunisation through the nappies we buy, support sustainable fishing via the carrier bags we use, or reduce landfill by using a reusable cup for our coffee. How does this expanded understanding of social responsibility in a global context address issues of inequality and exploitation at work? Can it? Should it? This paper explores the professionalisation and growth of CSR, particularly in relation to workers' rights and the proliferation of private regulation, and asks whether these can seriously challenge corporate social irresponsibility within global production networks. Empirical research on certification and employment standards in textile, flower and wine supply chains, is used to argue that instead of overcoming precarity and exploitation of the disconnected workers within these complex chains, corporate-dominated CSR agendas, together with the spread of soft regulatory systems, can reinforce rather than overcome neo-colonial power relations. Investigating the tangled lines of responsibility in such global production networks is important, as the continued growth of the CSR and standards industry suggests substantial incentives for those able to influence the agenda, and losses for those who cannot.

'Alternative' food networks as a Weberian ideal-type: findings from a survey of food and drink enterprises in Scotland

David Watts, J. S. McKenzie
(University of Aberdeen)

It has been argued that alternative food networks have the potential to deliver greater social, economic and environmental justice than the currently dominant global food system. However, their ability to do so remains contested. Attempts to address one issue, such as the inequality of access to healthy food or access to foods with a lower carbon footprint, can highlight or even exacerbate other aspects of social inequality (e.g. attempts to widen food access being categorised as a new form of philanthropy) and economic exclusivity (e.g. more environmentally sustainable food tending to be more expensive). Moreover, the very notion of 'alternative' food networks has been challenged, with some arguing that they are little more than a 'post-Fordist' variant within a dominant capitalist food system.

This paper analyses whether it is meaningful to conceptualise 'conventional' and 'alternative' food networks as distinct entities by considering them as Weberian ideal types. From the academic literature, it constructs ideal-typical characteristics of both types of food network, on the basis of their commitments to social, economic and environmental justice. It then reports on the findings of a survey of 6,000 food and drink enterprises in Scotland, which asked about the values (e.g. commitment to paying the living wage, to fair trade, to animal welfare etc.) by which they run their

business. The survey data are then analysed to determine whether, and to what extent, they provide evidence for the existence of 'conventional' and 'alternative' food enterprises and networks related to their ideal types.

Funding: The Scottish Government funded the research from which this paper was developed through its 2016-21 Strategic Research Programme (RD 3.3.3)

Work, Employment & Economic Life 2

W001

Sharon Elley
(University of Leeds)

Struggling with and challenging patriarchy in academia: reflection from career histories of Pakistani female professors

Fouzia Sadaf
(Durham University)

In career literature, gendered and patriarchal structures of organizations have been flagged up as a well-featured explanation for the impeded women's access to leadership positions (Walby, 1986; Acker, 2010; Baker, 2012; Khwaja et al., 2017).

My research has focused on to reveal the ways in which female professors struggled with and challenged the organizational patriarchy at various levels their en route to senior academic positions. For this, I interviewed 25 female professors.

Analysis of the career biographies signifies that female academics continue to face patriarchal mindset in their interpersonal, and organizational terms. They narrated that stereotypical attitudes and misogynistic behaviors of male colleagues engendered taxing relationships and conditions in the workplaces.

At the organizational level, female academics encountered exclusion from the benefits, and decisions of the male-dominated networks and administrative committees. Alongside, some of the female professors experienced delays and discrimination in their chances to promote to the most senior leadership positions due to the patriarchy in the ethos of evaluation criteria that continued to reassert women are not sufficiently capable to lead universities.

Female professors in my study get engaged to challenge these patriarchal contexts across their career course. In junior positions, they competed and excelled gender neutral and meritocratic promotion criteria to shift stereotypical perceptions about women's abilities. While after succeeding to authority positions, female professors (not all interviewed women) do this by initiating women networking, by ensuring to improve women's presence in decision-making bodies and by voicing for the policies to address gender discrimination at different forums.

Wednesday 24/04/2019 at 11:00 - 12:30
Paper Session 2

Cities, Mobilities, Place & Space 1
W622

COMMUNITY, INEQUALITY, AGEING AND URBAN CHANGE

Ageing in place over time: examining unequal ageing in contrasting urban communities

Camilla Lewis, Ruth Webber, Vanessa May
(University of Manchester)

This paper discusses findings from an ESRC funded study of secondary longitudinal data which explores ageing in place, over time. In the project we will analyse 70 life history interviews with people (aged 50 and over) living in four different locations in Greater Manchester. Two areas are characterised by high levels of deprivation and rapid population change (Crumpsall and Ancoats) and two more affluent neighbourhoods with relatively stable populations (Hale and Chorlton). The meaning of and attachment to place is considered especially significant for older people due to the length of time they are likely to have spent in the same locality. However, despite evidence for the value of place attachment in old age, much less is known about the extent to which older people differ in the way that place and community are experienced. Social care policies promote the idea of 'ageing in place,' aimed at encouraging people to remain in their own homes and communities for as long as possible. However, the places in which older people experience ageing often proved to be hostile and challenging environments (Buffel et al. 2015). This paper reports on empirical findings about the experiences of older people living in four localities in the same city. The analysis explores how ageing identities are constructed in biographical accounts within a particular place and across time. The aim of the paper is to suggest that we have to include a focus on inequalities in ageing in order to understand communities in rapidly changing urban contexts.

Developing 'age-friendly' communities in unequal environments: creating new forms of social engagement

Chris Phillipson, Sophie Yarker
(University of Manchester)

An important debate is taking place on how to develop supportive urban communities for older citizens, given pressures from global forces transforming the physical and social context of cities. This paper provides a critical perspective on the development of 'age-friendly cities' and communities by exploring this approach in the context of strains associated with gentrification, the impact of austerity, and restrictions on public spaces within cities. This theme will be explored by examining problems facing the 'age-friendly' approach given widening inequalities within urban environments. The paper will develop the argument that new approaches are needed to strengthen what Klinenberg (2018) terms the 'social infrastructure' of communities. This theme will be explored by focusing on the potential of neighbourhood-based interventions in building social connections within areas undergoing economic and social change. The paper will summarise different approaches, analysing their strengths and weaknesses in responding to social divisions within and between communities. The paper will consider specific examples of interventions which attempt to empower groups of older people experiencing social isolation, notably those living in inner-city communities and those from minority ethnic groups. These examples will draw on work in Greater Manchester working with a range of local authorities and community groups. The paper will conclude with a summary of the implications of the findings for work on age-friendly issues.

Rival theories of community change

Graham Crow
(University of Edinburgh)

The study of 'community' has had fluctuating fortunes but is back in vogue. At times criticised for functionalist bias (questioning the assumption that constituent parts fit together purposefully) and at other times criticised as under-theorised (the old criticism that community research is merely descriptive), community researchers have been revitalised through engagement with a range of rival theories. This paper sets out how the concept of 'social capital' has been used drawn upon extensively in recent community research, although not necessarily with the same theoretical foundations, with Bourdieu, Putnam and Coleman's versions sitting uneasily alongside each other in terms of the conclusions to which they point regarding community change. Similar points can be made about other concepts such as 'social networks', 'social support' and 'social solidarity', along with the point that a shared terminology does not necessarily imply a shared methodology. The analysis then goes on to consider the different things that researchers look to a theory of community change to deliver in their analyses, including explanations of the patterns of

change, the pace of change, the drivers of change and the mechanics of change. Inequalities and hierarchies relating to social class, gender, ethnicity, age and other dimensions of diversity now routinely figure in explanations of community change that are advanced by researchers, deepening, extending and bringing up to date currents in thinking about community that go back a long time.

Cities, Mobilities, Place & Space 2

W610

GENTRIFICATION: A WORKING-CLASS PERSPECTIVE REVISITED. A WALKING TOUR

Kirsteen Paton

Culture, Media, Sport & Food 1

W709

MEDIA, CULTURE AND GENDER

Television News Media in Contemporary India

Sudeshna Devi

(Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi)

Indian television news media has witnessed gigantic growth in the last two decades. Challenging the age-old monopoly of the state broadcaster Doordarshan, many private news channels both at the regional and national level have mushroomed resulting in a crowded electronic media market. Along with the rapid increase in numbers, the ever changing content in news channels paves the way for more research. Based on a series of structured interviews conducted with journalists associated with electronic media in India, an attempt will be made in this paper to map out the changing nature of Indian television news. The paper will deal in a detailed examination of vital trends like pre-reforms media scenario, changing notion of news, ratings based content, formation of public opinion, impact on social media, changing business model and a host of other trends to develop a broad narrative on the changing Indian media ecology. This narrative will be juxtaposed with the liberal understanding of the role of media in democratic societies to develop a coherent understanding on how Indian media operates and the kind of role it plays in sustaining Indian democracy.

Re-reading “Desi-ness” and gender politics through sports films

Aarti Ratna

(Leeds Beckett University)

Reflecting upon the material embodiments of race, gender and sexuality, and the performativity of national pride, in this paper I offer an original analysis of two sporting films: Bend it Like Beckham (British production) and Dhan Dhanna Dhan Goal (Bollywood production). Through a post/colonial and feminist deconstruction of the key narratives – and, concomitantly, the politics and processes of cultural production - I re-read desi-ness across both films. I add to this analysis by drawing upon empirical research to position the gendered and sexual ontologies of Desi women, in and across the private/public spaces of sport, home and the nation.

The reproduction of gender inequality in the age of postfeminism

Xintong Jia

(City, University of London)

The research is about the constructions and developments of female's gendered subjectivities through diverse media representations under the circumstance of neoliberalism and postfeminism in contemporary China. Inspired by Foucault, I propose the sexualised women figures represented in media can be regarded as a 'docile body', that is, a kind of subjected and practiced body produced by discipline and is in the grip of power in society. The central research questions are: How do the process and practices of media representation work to produce ideas about what it means to be a woman? How does (male-dominated) neoliberal capitalism appropriate postfeminist ideas to sell women an image of 'empowerment'?

Feminism is a transnational movement and China has witnessed its domestic operation. Since the 1980s, the postfeminist discourse has been broadly visible in Western countries. However, there is little agreement about the exact meaning of postfeminism. Whether postfeminist discourse can ultimately empower or disempower women

remains a question. This research seeks to fill the gap between the postfeminist discourse and the sexualised female figures appeared in contemporary China's media representation. This research aims to explore the cultural currency of the represented women figures and try to find a new female subjectivity created by the Chinese importing of 'Western' postfeminism.

Conditional Belonging of Feminist Science Fiction Female Fans

Neta Yodovich

(University of Manchester)

Even though belonging is traditionally associated with well-being and comfort, it also creates tensions among individuals and communities through its inherent processes of inclusion and exclusion, which determine who belongs and who does not. Therefore, scholars like Wemyss (2006), discuss "hierarchies of belonging", which (1) distinguish between those who automatically belong and those whose belonging is conditional; (2) scrutinize one's prioritization of their identities, emphasizing the ones who will ensure their belonging to a certain community. While most scholars study belonging through issues of race or immigration, this research implements the concept in the everyday practice, identity and community of science fiction fandom. Based on 30 in-depth interviews with self-identified feminist female fans of science fiction, I argue that in order to keep fandom exclusive to male fans, men restrict female fans' inclusion according to their own terms and values. This leads to female fans' conditional and partial belonging which disrupts their identification process and brings them to doubt the authenticity of their identity as fans. To avoid being excluded, interviewees learned to focus on fannish practices male fans value more, whilst silencing their feminist critique of the fanned content. Thus, despite being able to participate in physical and online fandom spaces, female fans' belonging was found secondary to that of male fans' and conditional to them censoring their feminist identities. Through this presentation I will demonstrate the latent tensions, hierarchies and conditioning behind the process of belonging in an everyday practice such as fandom.

Culture, Media, Sport & Food 2

W308

SPORT, GENDER AND EMOTION

'It's the sound of laughter I like': the role of emotions in Sport for Development projects

Mark Doidge

(University of Brighton)

Sport is an emotional experience. Despite this, little is written about the importance of emotions in sport generally, and undertaking sporting activities specifically. In particular, Sport for Development projects can place project workers into emotionally difficult situations, but also provide opportunities for joy and happiness. Emotions can be motivating factors, as well as vehicles for friendship (Doidge and Sandri 2018). Fieldwork requires a significant amount of emotional labour to manage one's emotions whilst engaging with others (Hochschild 1983; Lumsden 2009; McQueeney and Lavelle 2017). Frequently, ethnographies omit the emotional aspects of fieldwork (Kleinmann and Copp 1993; Coffey 1999; Thomson et. al. 2013). Similarly, interviews can also provoke difficult emotions (Dickson-Swift, James and Kippen 2007). Despite this, emotions are rarely explored, nor explicitly asked about in monitoring and evaluations of Sport for Development projects. This research is based on five years of monitoring and evaluation interviews and fieldwork with student volunteers, project partners and participants of the University of Brighton's Football 4 Peace project in the Gambia, South Korea and Ireland. This project is a vehicle for conflict resolution and peace building in divided societies (Sugden 2008). This paper will assess the role of emotions in Sport for Development projects, identify where they emerge in monitoring and evaluation and suggest ways that emotions can signpost significant knowledge within Sport for Development projects.

Gender Inequalities and Sport: the experiences of female tennis coaches

Urszula Wolski

(University of Northampton)

Sporting opportunities for females continue to grow, which include what are seen as masculine sports, such as football, rugby and cricket. Despite this, sports remain gendered and stereotypical with greater participation for females in sports such as gymnastics and dance that emphasise grace, fluidity and artistic interpretation, whereas females wanting to participate in sports such as rugby or football are likely to be labelled as 'tomboys' (Craig and Beedie 2010: 129), or 'lesbians' or as 'masculine'. This gendered division is even more apparent when looking at coaching in sport. The focus of research is to explore gender inequalities in coaching within one particular sport: tennis.

Female tennis coaches are still vastly under-represented with the majority of coaches being male. According to the LTA, 'there are currently 800 women in LTA Coaching roles across the country, however the LTA aims to double the number of women on coaching programmes over the next five years, creating more female role models to deliver tennis sessions nationwide'. A recent coaching partnership between Andy Murray, former British men's No1 and Amélie Mauresmo, created much interest and conversation, but not so much on Mauresmo's actual coaching ability, but more so on her sexuality (coming out as lesbian in 1999) or whether a woman could coach an elite male tennis player.

Forthcoming research aims to explore the role of women tennis coaches, the barriers that may exist, the inequalities and discrimination such as sexual harassment that women may experience.

'it's all about one-upmanship': Conspicuous consumption and the 'trickle-down effect' in professional football.

Graeme Law

(York St John University)

Association football is regarded as an extremely lucrative professional sport for the players involved in the game. The financial rewards on offer are often widely considered to be a significant factor in attracting a number of players to the sport. However, very little empirical work has been carried out on the lifestyles of professional footballers. This paper examines issues of money that are central to professional footballers' workplace experiences. Based on interviews with 34 current and former professional football players, results indicate that image plays an important role in establishing power and respect within the changing room. Using Veblen's (1899) concept of conspicuous consumption to help explain the players' attitudes to money and their relationships with others within the footballing environment, it is clear that players, since the early 1990s, commonly try to gain 'one-upmanship' and advertise their perceived earnings in an environment where open discussion of wages is frequently seen as a 'taboo' subject. Footballers are constrained to fit the image required to be 'seen' as a footballer within the network of a football club through having to buy certain clothes and accessories in order to be accepted by the changing room regardless of their actual income.

"Balls to Borders": Informal football spaces and the everyday lives of refugees and people seeking asylum.

Chris Webster

(Leeds Beckett University)

In early 2018, the Windrush Scandal highlighted to the public how a network of immigration controls known as the 'hostile environment', was designed to make remaining in the UK for both citizens and those with leave to remain as difficult as possible.

Rather than being confined to the temporary nature of a 'crisis' or 'scandal', the hostile environment exemplifies a deep rooted set of social policies that manifest in everyday interactions, across various institutional contexts and public arenas. It is clear that the border guard no longer sits on the geographical boundary of the nation-state but has shifted into the everyday, with their roles increasingly being pushed upon and adopted by teachers, doctors, landlords and the wider general public. The repercussions are not exclusive to the Windrush generation; they are felt sharply by newly arrived migrants who are forced to negotiate the UK's ruthless asylum process. In relation to a Leeds-based football 'project', I explore how forms of resistance not only kick "balls" against borders, from within this hostile environment, but also fosters intra- and inter-racial friendships, senses of belonging, (physical) pleasures, and agency.

Lifecourse 1 W003

Becoming a Legitimate Sexual Subject in Later Life: Ex-Soviet Women Pensioners in Russia and the UK Reflecting on Romantic Intimacy

Hanna Shadryna

(Birkbeck, University of London)

The paper offers an analysis of how the welfare trends in Russia and UK affect the popular imagination about romantic intimacy in later life. The paper argues that in the context of different welfare regimes in Russia and the UK the same cohorts of ex-Soviet women over sixty years old tend to occupy positions of different intimate subjects.

Contemporary Russia has the lowest in Europe pensionable age for women of fifty-five years old. The generations of current pensioners, formed by the Soviet planned economy, are not required to compete in the new labour market. Rather, older age is socially constructed as a period for disengagement from public sphere and social protection. The

welfare is designed to offer the role of a dedicated grandmother, an unpaid care giver, as a core identity for older women. By contrast, the UK exemplifies a neoliberal approach in regulating the risks associated with ageing.

Based on thirty biographic narrative interviews with ex-Soviet women pensioners based in Russia and the UK, my study examines how the experience of growing older in different cultures of ageing informs expectations and norms of romantic and sexual intimacy. While ex-Soviet women in Russia, who participated in my research project, avoided being seen as having sexual desires, the women from the UK-based sample avoided being seen as deprived of sexual desires.

The paper will present a comparative analysis of two case studies by focusing on identity work undertaken by my interviewees in reflecting their attitudes towards romantic intimacy in later life.

Now we are married: what is the impact of marriage and civil partnership on how same-sex couples address challenges linked to ageing.

Michael Thomas

(Brunel University London)

This paper reports on a qualitative study on the impact of marriage and civil partnership for same-sex couples, focusing on the ways in which couples understand their legal and social status as a factor in navigating lifespan challenges associated with ageing. These challenges may relate to working life or retirement, income, housing, health, social connections, social care and bereavement.

Whereas marriage and civil partnership may enhance the visibility of same-sex couples, they may be justifiably apprehensive about encountering homophobia and heteronormativity when they access services. Health and social care may be seen as particularly problematic, whether in terms of being out to practitioners, allowing formal carers into the private sphere of their home, or in entering residential care. In line with the theme of the conference, the paper investigates the ways in which same-sex couples understand their legal and social status and their evolving position in social hierarchies. The intersections between sexuality and ageing and the enduring nature of social inequalities raises important questions about identity, solidarity, community and citizenship.

Drawing on qualitative interview data with same-sex couples in the UK, the paper explores the ways in which sexuality may be visible, hidden or problematic as couples face the challenges commonly associated with ageing.

Understanding of Menopause: Issues of power and agency in Iranian Muslim menopausal women's lived experiences

Elham Amini

Conducting my fieldwork among Muslim (Shiite) menopausal women in Iran raised the question of the relationship between ageing, sexuality, the body/embodiment and gender in the way that they understand their menopausal time. I will argue that socio-cultural structure of Iranian society, medicalisation and the gender order have a significant effect on the process through which women understand their menopause.

This paper by exploring the gendered experiences of these women and taking a biographical narrative approach; will discuss the ways in which individual biographies are shaped by cultural, social structures; and the different agentic ways in which such women may respond, in turn, to these social structures. It is both a statement on and an exploration of agency as it relates to a group in society that is commonly perceived to have little, or even none.

I addressed menopause as a gendered, embodied and lived phenomenon by which we can view individuals' engagements with cultural meanings concerning the ageing body, and women's understanding of it as a significant life event. Also, I will articulate that medicalisation of menopause has double aspects. This also creates women's perception about their bodies and transforms their bodies as an environment of profound consumer culture.

This paper, by highlighting the importance of subjectivity and agency of the participants, as women living in constrained social milieus which structure their gendered and sexual practices, challenges 'passive' accounts of Iranian Muslim menopausal women's lives.

The Social-Realities and Social-Performativities in the Formation of Social Identity by Older Gay Men in Northeast of England, United Kingdom

Paul Simpson, Patrick Mthombeni

In the past ten to fifteen years, the northeast of England (in the United Kingdom) has experienced an improved attitude from mainstream society towards the lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender (LGBT) community. This improvement rarely embraces the social realities of older LGBT generations who, on a daily basis have to intersectionally negotiate their daily social existence based on age, sexuality, class, race or financial status. Overall loneliness, stigma, ageism, homophobia, the lack of social mobility, and the lack of social engagement experienced by older LGBTs continuously affect their social interactions and social-Performativities. In using Judith Butler's concept of

'performativity' and drawing from thirty (N=30) in-depth face-to-face interviews from older gay men, we evaluate the social-realities and social-Performativities of older gay men who reside in the northeast of England. The paper captures the narratives of older gay men demonstrating how they have compartmentalized their social realities (into various categories), that is, categories that either obey the social-constraints presented to them or follow certain types of gay cultures/lifestyles as a form of resistance.

Medicine, Health & Illness 1

W002

Equality of opportunity and mortality in Europe

Alexi Gugushvili, Caspar Kaiser
(University of Oxford)

In this study we investigate if equality of opportunity – which, as we argue, can be tracked by relative intergenerational status mobility – is linked to mortality across European societies. Two theoretical mechanisms could explain such an association. First, assuming that individuals' health is at least partly affected by psychological factors, limited relative social mobility may be perceived as unfair, cause stress, and hence be detrimental to individual health. Second, perceptions of greater mobility chances in more socially fluid environments may increase aspirations in individuals from less advantaged backgrounds, and thus lead to greater individual investment in health. The unavailability of reliable cross-national social mobility data so far prevented scholars to investigate an association between the level of intergenerational social mobility and mortality rates across European societies. Taking the Socio-Economic Index of Occupational Status (ISEI) scores as our measure of social status, we utilise the first five waves of the European Social Survey (2002-2010) to derive estimates of relative intergenerational status mobility. We compute several measures of relative mobility for 5 year age-groups in each country and wave, which yields rates for 1,200 country/wave/age groups. For each of these country/wave/age groups, we obtain mortality rates from Eurostat. Using country- and year-fixed effects models, we demonstrate that there is a statistically significant negative association between relative social mobility and mortality rates, even after a wide range of control variables are accounted for. We conclude that equality of opportunity may indeed be a matter of life and death.

The continuing impacts of welfare reform on food insecurity: the roll-out of Universal Credit in the UK

Aaron Reeves, Rachel Loopstra
(University of Oxford)

The roll-out of Universal Credit has generated considerable concern that issues with benefit payments are forcing people to rely on food aid to help them make ends meet. According to the Trussell Trust, foodbanks in areas where the full service of Universal Credit has been implemented (covering single people, couples, and families) have seen a far higher rise in referrals for emergency food than the national average. However, it is unclear whether the results drawn from this narrow set of areas is indicative of other parts of country. We explore in more detail then whether the roll-out of Universal Credit is associated with more food bank usage using data at the postcode district level. We seek to unpack whether foodbank referrals are potentially driven by the problems associated with roll-out (i.e., early administrative difficulties) or whether they are more systemic (i.e., rooted in the long waiting period for the first payment).

How Does Social Class Affect Post-Stroke Patients in Rehabilitation Units?

Muriel Darmon
(EHES, CNRS, France and University of Cambridge, visiting scholar (January-July 2019))

This paper explains an epidemiological finding: that the extent of recovery following stroke is class-based and that patients from the working classes and lower socioeconomic groups are more vulnerable to functional impairments following stroke than those from higher socioeconomic groups. Based on a 15-month ethnographic study of neurology and rehabilitation units, the article first shows that hospital rehabilitation after stroke can be interpreted as a process of secondary socialization shaped by a 'school form', and that it therefore proves far more efficient with patients who have scholastic dispositions, more frequently associated with people from the middle and upper classes with considerable cultural capital. Second, the article demonstrates that the concept of 'school form' can in fact be useful outside the school context per se when it comes to understanding social inequalities. It can, in this case, explain the class-based processes through which inequalities in outcomes arise. 'What is lost' during a stroke and 'what is regained' after is not only a question of location in the brain and how serious the neurological incident was, but also correlates with class-based dispositions and attitudes towards practice, as well as language and learning situations.

Methodological Innovations 1

W009

Making unheard voices heard: Ethical and methodological challenges in designing research with children about their experiences of food insecurity

John McKenzie, David Watts
(University of Aberdeen)

Feminist scholars have long contended that social researchers have a responsibility to make heard the least powerful voices in society. However, carrying out such work presents researchers with unique problems, particularly when it explores sensitive issues. Rarely is this more pertinent than when conducting qualitative research with children concerning the impacts of food insecurity on their lives. Food insecurity is increasingly prevalent in high income countries and one of the starkest markers of social inequality. Whilst robust data has not been routinely collected in Scotland until recently, evidence suggests that there are increasing numbers of people experiencing food insecurity, including large numbers of children. Our research into the lived experience of food insecurity in Scotland includes a study of adults and another of children. It is the latter that will be the focus of this presentation. It has been established that children can experience food insecurity differently from adults and in ways that care providers may be unaware of. Therefore, we contend that listening to children about their experiences of food insecurity is paramount if a full understanding of it is to be developed. This paper discusses: the ethical and methodological challenges that confronted us; how we aimed to deal with them; and the implications this had for the design of research into the ways in which children engage and manage this severe form of social deprivation.

Funding: The Scottish Government funded the research from which this paper was developed through its 2016-21 Strategic Research Programme (RD 3.3.3)

Relational autonomy as a way past the zero sum debate over whether children have enough capacity to be participatory research actors

Janice McLaughlin
(Newcastle University)

The now well established call for children to be seen as having rights to have a say in things that effect their lives is based on arguments that they are actors able to understand their lives and make judgements. Such arguments have also been taken up in research practice, in particular participatory action research. However, children as rights holders is challenged by various writers who query whether any child can have the capacity to be such an agent and instead focus on their inherent vulnerability. However, is the notion of individual capacity the appropriate measure to judge whether children have rights; including rights and capacities to be involved in participatory research? In the presentation I will suggest it is not by drawing on two sets of argument. First, I will draw from sociology of childhood arguments to recognise that all children are situated actors emergent in their social worlds. Second, I will then make use of feminist advocacy of relational autonomy to suggest that understanding children as situated does not mean they are unable to be active agents. Instead their situatedness is the basis for seeing them as able, in the company of others, to be participatory research actors. This is because relational understandings of capacity are very much in keeping with the values of participatory action research.

Race, Ethnicity & Migration 1

W011

CRIMINALISATION AND POLICING OF RACIAL MINORITIES

Securi(tizi)ng Diversity: Planning, Affect and Blackness in Berlin

Giovanni Picker
(University of Glasgow)

This paper contributes to research on the relationship between race, planning and urban spaces. Drawing on my ongoing historical and ethnographic research on urban planning in Görlitzer Park, Berlin, I bridge emerging scholarship on the emotional politics of racism and the urban sociology of planning and public spaces.

Located in the iconic multicultural district of Kreuzberg, Görlitz was built in the 1980s as a tolerant and culturally inclusive public space. Since the early 2000s, the park has increasingly been at the centre of media and political campaigns calling for more security due to the presence drug dealers, mainly black male citizens of a number of sub-Saharan African countries. This steadfast historical shift from “culture-led-planning” to “security-led-planning” mirrors

the contemporary oscillation of most urban planning actions between securing the multicultural ethos of the park as a social space and securitizing the park as a public space. This oscillation is largely the result of decisions which explicitly build on a certain fear among a number of middle-class residents of the district about walking in the park, especially at night. In documenting how fear is the main rationale of contemporary urban planning over the park, I argue that its ultimate ground is the figure of the Male-African-Drug-Dealer standing at the park's gates that local media have largely popularized. The paper ultimately shows how racist thinking, first systematized in the late 19th-century proliferations of 'perils' (i.e. black peril, red peril, yellow peril) still contributes to the 21st-century making of affluent urban societies.

Race, Citizenship and Reform: Attitudes toward Police and Policing among Israelis of Ethiopian Descent

Ofir Abu, Guy Ben-Porat and Fany Yuval
(Kinneret Academic College)

Attitudes toward police reforms may provide an insight into how members of a minority group view their civic status. We examine this proposition by focusing on the perceptions about police and police reforms among Ethiopian Jews in Israel, a racial minority. Drawing on data from public opinion survey, focus groups, and interviews with community activists, our analysis indicates that while Ethiopian Israelis strongly believe they suffer from police racism and discrimination, they have equal or even more positive judgements about the police than veteran Jewish-Israelis (the control group). We suggest that Ethiopian Israelis' perceptions about the police reflect their ambivalent status as Israeli citizens: they recognize themselves as part of the Jewish dominant group in Israeli society while they feel that state institutions (including the police) continue to view them as a distinct group who needs special treatment. This ambivalence also shapes their perceptions about police reforms. For example, Ethiopian Israelis support recruitment of Ethiopian police officers, because they believe that representation is important, but nonetheless prefer a professional police force that abides by the principles of good policing regardless of ethnic origin. Ethiopian Israelis also believe that training of police officers should recognize the Ethiopian community not as a distinct cultural group who requires special accommodation, but rather as legitimate and equal members of Israel's mainstream society. The attitudes toward police reforms among Israelis of Ethiopian descent demonstrate their desire to be fully recognized as Israeli citizens while minimizing the police's discrimination and stigmatization toward them.

Resisting State Racism in Scotland; A Case study of the Sheku Bayoh Justice Campaign

Smina Akhtar
(University of Glasgow)

Sheku Bayoh a 31 year old gas engineer from Sierra Leone was killed whilst being arrested by 9 police officers in Kirkcaldy, in Scotland on 3 May 2015. He was held face down on the ground whilst CS gas, batons, leg and ankle restraints and handcuffs were used. Since the killing Police Scotland have repeatedly attempted to smear both Sheku and his family. It has taken the Lord Advocates office 3 years and 5 months to announce that no police officer involved will face prosecution.

This paper uses qualitative interviews with activists from the Sheku Bayoh Justice Campaign to critically analyse the extent to which the campaign has displayed the characteristics and behaviours of a social movement (Cox and Nilson, 2014). A radical social movement framework is used to critically examine how activists conceptualised and shaped campaign activities based on their assessment of what would work and what action was needed to challenge the actions and power of repressive state institutions and bring about social change.

I develop the argument that nation states and state institutions do not exercise power in a neutral way which allows an understanding of how state agencies like the police can both carry out racist practice while formally (and to a certain extent actually) being opposed to racism at the level of policy/legal requirements - which allows Police Scotland to say 'we're not racist' and lead campaigns against racist/Islamophobic hate crime.

Race, Ethnicity & Migration 2

W324

Muslim women's organisational leadership

Hengameh Ashraf Emami,
(Nottingham University and Northumbria University)

This paper will focus on and highlight the significance of Muslim women in leadership roles in Britain through drawing on the organisation 'Everyday Muslim' in London as a case study. There is a lack of research that explores and explains the role of Muslim women and their engagement at organisation levels. The paper aims to provide an insight into everyday Muslim women's leadership and construction of their identity in the post Brexit era. It will discuss sociological debates and perspectives on how Muslim women participate in public engagement activities and apply

their leadership and their agency in the current situation of modern Britain. The case study organisation focuses on cultural heritage as an important aspect of everyday lives of Muslims, providing a platform for Muslim immigrants to preserve their cultural identity in British context. This study aims to examine the work of women's leadership within Everyday Muslim organisation to explore the shift of the politics of identity and its gender dimension, while highlighting the intersection of race and class, gender, citizenship and immigration. It will explain and demonstrate the challenges and opportunities as well as the methods the organization apply through women leadership for tackling the issues and enhancing their progress.

How #MeToo movement has sparked debates around Islamic feminism and identity amongst British Muslim women

Saima Ansari

(University of Salford)

At a time where exposure and justice for sexual violation is forefront in socio-political debates, this paper explores the discussions taking place amongst British Muslim women on this issue. This paper explores a theme of my findings which makes a link between identity, the #MeToo movement and Islamic feminism which forms part of a larger research study of an intersectional look at the identity of Muslim women. The #MeToo movement has gained vast amounts of support in exposing sexual assaults amongst many women. This led to the #MosqueMeToo movement which also challenged sexual assaults in sacred worship spaces for Muslim women. Through the assistance of standpoint feminism, Islamic feminism and black feminism this paper explores deeply sensitive conversations amongst the women on issues that they raise. The study used focus groups and semi-structure interviews to discuss the intricacies of everyday lived experiences among the women. It highlights how these women are navigating their own identities towards an 'Islamic feminist' attitude which challenges the patriarchal form of religion through conversations of the #MosqueMeToo movement.

Race, Ethnicity & Migration 3

W525

When the nation becomes louder: Everyday nationalism and the 2014 Scottish independence referendum

Minna Liinpa

(University of Glasgow)

2014 was a politically interesting and eventful year in Scotland due to an independence referendum taking place. The referendum also provided a sociologically interesting moment: as the 'Scottish nation' was widely debated and reflected upon, this political context provided an opportune moment to consider how nationalist narratives are constructed, expressed and experienced both from above and below – that is, the 'edges of the nation' (Fox 2017) became newly visible. Drawing on data collected before and after the referendum, this paper considers how ethnic and racialised minorities experienced and made sense of the nation on an everyday level around the time of the referendum. Literature on everyday nationalism in the UK has particularly focused on those whose national belonging remains beyond question, that is on those perceived as 'white'. However, I argue that by shifting the focus on those whose national belonging may become under challenge, or who do not 'unproblematically' belong, we can uncover important ways in which the 'edges of the nation' are experienced and noticed in different ways in the hustle and bustle of the everyday. Crucially, the findings shed light on ethnic minorities' complex and often contradictory experiences of nationalist narratives — indeed, the findings support Smith's (2016) argument that the capacity to experience the everyday as unreflective is a privilege. Ethnic minorities encounter continuous implicit and explicit challenges to their sense of belonging to the nation — consequently, in a 'hyper-nationalist' context (such as the referendum) the nation merely becomes louder.

Multiple Identities of the Irish Diaspora: The Case of the Gaelic Athletic Association in London

Kyosuke Sasaki

(N/A)

This paper explores relationships between identity, a sense of belonging and sporting practice through a case study of Gaelic sports players in London. The formation of Irish national identity through Gaelic sports has been a central tenet of sport sociology and sport historiography in Irish studies. Sport sociologists and historians have conventionally shed light on the pivotal role of the Gaelic Athletic Association (GAA) on Irish nationalist politics in the late 19th century. Moreover, sport practice in Northern Ireland has been described on the basis of a sectarian division; British-Protestant identities articulated through playing rugby and soccer, in contrast to Irish-Catholic identities, which did so through Gaelic sports. These exclusive forms of identity formation culminated in the maltreatment of GAA members from Loyalist paramilitary groups or British security forces in Ulster during the Troubles in the late 20th century.

Rather than focusing on these 'hot' and 'exclusive' types of nationalism from a macro-historical point of view, I will expand Billig's (1995) 'banal' perspective of nationalism, and examine a more individual perception of nationhood. Through participant observation and semi-structured interviews with players of Gaelic sports, including the Irish, Northern Irish, and Anglo-Irish in Britain, this paper will clarify the ways in which they consume and exhibit nationalism in their everyday lives.

The finding suggests the multiplicity of Irish national identity beyond an assumed dichotomy between Irish-Catholic nationalists and British-Protestant unionists. Finally, this paper proposes how everyday consciousness of nationalism can be understood in a wider socio-cultural context.

Understanding sectarianism as a form of racism

Maureen McBride
(University of Glasgow)

Dominant explanations of sectarianism in Scotland have traditionally emphasised the religious (intra-Christian) aspect, and underplayed the interrelation of religion with historic colonial relations, racialization, national identities, and social class. Relatedly, claims of anti-Irish Catholic racism are frequently dismissed as not 'real' racism. Such common sense understandings of sectarianism consider racism and sectarianism to be separate phenomena, and this has implications for how these social issues are responded to by the state and civil society.

Recent work on conceptualising sectarianism in Northern Ireland (Gilligan, 2017) argues that understanding sectarianism as a form of racism can help to reveal the complexity in power relations that is neglected in simplistic 'Catholic-Protestant divide' narratives. In this paper, I argue that this is also the case in Scotland given current debates around the existence and character of anti-Irish racism. Furthermore, I argue that as well as having analytical value, there are important implications for policy and practice. Common sense understandings of sectarianism and racism, and where and how these overlap, shape policy and legislation. This paper demonstrates how a shift in conceptualisation could impact on how these social issues are responded to in contemporary Scotland.

Rights, Violence & Crime A

W004

Violence and Social Inequalities: A Sociological Exploration of Internally Displaced Persons' Camps in North-Eastern Nigeria

Emeka Dumbili, Ebere Florence Nnanwube
(Nnamdi Azikiwe University)

Nigeria has experienced protracted violence/conflicts orchestrated by the Boko Haram terrorist group and Farmers and Fulani Herdsmen. The unbridled use of sophisticated weapons among these groups has led to the extermination of innumerable lives across Northern Nigeria, the displacement of individuals, particularly women and children, and the widening of social hierarchies.

Drawing on social conflict and inequality scripts, this study explores how the persistent violence/conflicts create/widen social inequalities across North-eastern Nigeria.

The findings show that between January and December 2017, 279000 persons were displaced because of the conflicts/violence. Between January and June 2018, additional 417, 000 persons (mostly women and children) were displaced due to Farmers/Herders conflicts. Our analysis shows that, while the number of persons displaced is increasing, the provision of food and other essential amenities is decreasing in various Internally Displaced Persons' (IDP) camps, where they were forced to flee.

For example, between 2015 and 2016, 3.9 million people were in need of urgent food/medical supplies, but less than 20 percent of the \$248 million needed was provided. This shortfall orchestrated by inadequate/unfavorable government policies, official corruption and mismanagement of fund provided by donor agencies, facilitated insufficient food and medical supplies. This has resulted in malnutrition, diseases and deaths of children in these camps. As part of coping strategies, illicit drugs sales/consumption, prostitution, child trafficking and sales of new-born babies are increasing in IDP Camps. The study argues that while these conflicts and violence create social inequalities in this region, official corruption and mismanagement sustain/widen the social hierarchies.

'He reduced me to a walking vagina': Understanding Bisexual Women's Experiences of Violence

Sally-Anne Beverley
(University of Leeds)

This paper will explore bisexual women's experiences of physical, psychological, and sexual violence. This study was motivated by crime survey data from the UK and the US showing that bisexual women report experiencing higher rates of violence compared to straight and lesbian women. Drawing on 28 narrative interviews with bisexual survivors, this paper situates their experiences within feminist understandings of violence and bisexual theory. This paper argues that understanding the specific ways in which bisexual women are conceptualised within society is key to understanding the violence perpetrated against them.

Female Genital Mutilation (FGM) and the Intersections of Patriarchal Cultures, Gender Inequality and Religion: Views from the Front-line

Christina Julios

(Birkbeck, University of London)

Against a backdrop of over 200 million girls and women worldwide affected by FGM, this paper examines stakeholders' views on prevailing socio-cultural hierarchies, gender inequality and religious beliefs underlying the practice. The author draws on original empirical research from her new book *Female Genital Mutilation and Social Media*, including twenty-one fieldwork interviews with international anti-FGM activists, front-line practitioners and survivors.

The cutting of female genitalia remains prevalent in thirty African nations and some Middle Eastern and Asian regions. Migration has however seen FGM spreading globally, with three million girls affected yearly in the UK alone. The complex nature of FGM encompasses issues relating to gender and power, cultural identity and control over women's sexuality. Tackling FGM therefore requires feminist intersectionality approaches that acknowledge the complex hierarchical social systems and structural barriers disadvantaging girls and women.

The paper highlights three key challenges identified by those interviewed for the book: first, entrenched patriarchal cultural norms oppressive to women, yet often internalised by them. Second, the role played by community and religious leaders, many of whom condone and encourage FGM. Third, lack of awareness, knowledge and resources, particularly among rural communities, leading to misconceptions about FGM and its health implications. Faced with these challenges, examples of good practice are examined. By highlighting the barriers anti-FGM activists encounter, the paper advances knowledge of the socio-cultural hierarchies and gender inequality inherent to FGM. Drawing on a feminist intersectionality perspective, moreover, serves to illustrate a relevant sociological approach able to capture and address such challenges.

Rights, Violence & Crime B – Special Event

W727

Book launch - No Friend but the Mountains: Writing From Manus Prison

Ala Sirriyeh,

(University of Liverpool)

Behrouz Boochani is a Kurdish journalist who was detained by the Australian government in the 'Manus Regional Processing Centre' (Manus Prison) in 2013 after travelling to Australia to seek asylum. Typed on a smart phone and smuggled out of Manus Prison using text-messaging, the book provides a unique insight into the ruthlessness of Australia's border regime, depicting and critically analysing the systematic torture inflicted on refugees banished by the Australian Government to Manus Prison (in Papua New Guinea and officially called the Manus Regional Processing Centre). The book is an exposé and condemnation of Australia's ruthless detention industry and an exploration of the interlocking systems of domination and subjugation governing what Boochani calls Manus Prison; a matrix of violent systems that also pervade Australian society, culture and politics. Boochani's book narrates and examines how these systems function and multiply by introducing use to what he calls 'The Kyriarchal System'. He describes in vivid detail the techniques of torture designed and implemented by the detention centre on Manus Island: excruciating and pulverising queues; continuous acts of degradation; daily humiliation causing irreparable psychological damage; aimless and empty bureaucratic rituals; and technologies aimed at starvation, sleep deprivation, sickness and insanity. By drawing on and appropriating diverse genres such as political analysis, philosophy, psychoanalytic examination, myth, epic and folklore, Boochani reveals the multifaceted mechanisms of systematic torture. He also invites his readers to catch glimpses of the lived experience and endurance of incarcerated refugees on Manus Island and sense something of their physical, psychological and emotional affliction.

Book launch - No Friend but the Mountains: Writing From Manus Prison

Ala Sirriyeh,

(University of Liverpool)

Dr Ala Sirriyeh is a Lecturer in Sociology and will be a discussant for the book launch. She is the author of *The Politics of Compassion: Immigration and Asylum Policy*. Alongside analysis of US and UK immigration and asylum policies,

this book draws on research on the Australian government's use of offshore detention on Nauru and Manus and the resistance that has been mounted against this policy by detainees and their supporters.

Book launch - No Friend but the Mountains: Writing From Manus Prison

Omid Tofighian

American University in Cairo

Mr Behrouz Boochani, the author of the book, is a Kurdish journalist who has been detained by the Australian government on Manus Island since he was captured in 2013 when he travelled to Australia to seek asylum. During his time in detention Mr Boochani has published regularly in the Guardian and in other media outlets. In 2018 he became a non-resident Visiting Scholar at the Sydney Asia Pacific Migration Centre (SAPMiC) at the University of Sydney. He will record a video message about his book.

Dr Omid Tofighian is an Assistant Professor in Philosophy at the American University in Cairo. Dr Tofighian is a lecturer, researcher and community advocate, combining philosophy with interests in citizen media, rhetoric, religion, popular culture, transnationalism, displacement and discrimination. He is also the translator of *No Friend but the Mountains*. He will introduce the key themes in the book and reflect on how the writing and translation process he experienced with Behrouz introduced philosophical and artistic discussions pertaining to epistemic justice, classification and performances of refugeehood.

Book launch - No Friend but the Mountains: Writing From Manus Prison

Hannah Lewis,

(University of Sheffield)

Dr Hannah Lewis is a Vice Chancellor's Fellow at the University of Sheffield and will be a discussant at the book launch. Dr Lewis is interested in understanding how policies shape the daily lives of people who migrate and has undertaken research in the UK and Australia. She has explored how asylum seeker dispersal, the destitution of refused asylum seekers, and immigration status shape community, family and transnational relationships among migrants and people seeking asylum. Her recent work has centred on concepts of precarity and contingency and how the social and legal status of migrants can create insecurities that may increase susceptibility to poverty, exclusion and forced labour.

Book launch - No Friend but the Mountains: Writing From Manus Prison

Victoria Canning,

(University of Bristol)

Dr Victoria Canning is senior lecturer in Criminology at the University of Bristol and will be a discussant for the book launch. She has spent over a decade working on the rights of women seeking asylum, specifically on support for survivors of sexual violence and torture. As part of her recent ESRC fellowship, Victoria undertook research in immigration detention centres, asylum centres and deportation centres in Denmark and Sweden. She argues for the abolition of such spaces, and campaigns with various activist groups across the UK and Europe in regard to this. She is also author of the British Society of Criminology book prize winning monograph *Gendered Harm and Structural Violence in the British Asylum System* and consultant on the Bafta award winning documentary series *Exodus: Our Journey to Europe*.

Science, Technology & Digital Studies 1

W007

'I don't want to see myself as a disabled person': CPAP devices and the emergence of (dis)ability as subjectivity

Dana Zarhin

(University of Haifa)

This article explains how the most recommended treatment for obstructive sleep apnea (OSA), the continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) device, acts and interacts with users' bodies, sleep partners' bodies, and cultural discourses to produce emotions and practices that generate the subjectivity of a disabled or abled person. Drawing upon in-depth interviews with OSA patients, this article illustrates how introducing CPAP devices into patients' lives may disturb their sleep and breathing, diminish their independence, disfigure their appearance, and problematize intimacy with bed partners, thereby disrupting both the fleshy body and the culturally preferred image of a healthy, independent, and attractive individual. In response, many patients reject this treatment. (Dis)ability as a subjective state is shown to emerge from associations in a network composed of heterogeneous entities that have agency. That is, disabled

subjectivity emerges when the device prevents individuals from accomplishing what they consider to be the essential and socially significant aspects of sleep and primarily its disembodied and interembodied aspects.

Socialising expertise: people-centred data governance in the Great North Care Record

Stephanie Mulrine, Madeleine Murtagh, Joel Minion, Mwenza Blell, Mavis Machirori, Denis Martin
(Newcastle University)

Technological advances and innovation are enablers and facilitators of societal change, particularly in areas of health and illness. Progress is being undertaken in the North of England to revolutionise the access and sharing of patient data both within and outside the NHS. The benefits of enhanced information sharing include better patient care, greater NHS efficiency and improved access for those otherwise marginalised. In order to achieve such change, however, individuals must be informed and give their consent or preferences. Work is underway to provide and assemble the necessary legal and technical expertise. Yet without public and patient perspectives on the use of their data, the potential for unsuccessful, dangerous or discriminatory consequences is a real risk.

The research presented explores findings from a series of 15 focus groups conducted across the North East and North Cumbria. Participants were members of the public who were presented with basic information about the Great North Care Record, a new way of sharing medical information accessed by authorised health and social care practitioners, and researchers. Emergent themes suggest that whilst there is hope for such a technological solution, the public have concerns that need be addressed through acknowledgement of and adherence to a set of key values. A clear ethical framework of values emerged: respect, reciprocity, fairness, agency, privacy, transparency and trust. Further work is currently underway to build upon these findings and to develop a co-production approach that will inform, design and govern the evolving process of health information exchange and access.

Complexity and Simplicity: A Critique of Simulations and Modelling in Pandemic Preparedness and Response

Elisa Pieri
(University of Manchester)

In this paper I draw on sociology of knowledge and science and technology studies to theorise the role of complexity and simplicity as driving forces always in tension, in formulating plans to respond to a future pandemic outbreak.

Such plans are generated at various scales, and especially those generated at national and international level are accompanied by substantial investment in a preparedness infrastructure and in exercises. Whilst the nature of the pathogen(s) that may cause an outbreak is still unknown, experts agree that novel lethal infectious diseases are continuously emerging and crossing species and that even pathogens already known are found to re-emerge in variants that are more virulent and resistant to known medical treatment. The disruptive effects of high consequences events such as the emergence of a novel respiratory virus, spreading across countries rapidly, like SARS or MERS did, or of a new pandemic avian influenza spreading globally, injects urgency to the drive towards securitising against such threats. Yet, under conditions of radical uncertainty, policy makers and responders are increasingly deploying techno-scientific tools of modelling and simulation to inform decision-making. This practice, however, may raise more questions than it purports to answer. The tension between keeping complexity in the picture, to account for multiple outcomes and confounding factors, and achieving a simplification of the picture, for the sake of agility and transferability of plans from one crises to the other, means that important dimensions are overlooked. This may undermine the very feasibility of the plans developed.

Health Networked Communities as Resilient Issue Publics

Stefania Vicari
(The University of Sheffield)

Social science research has shed light on the potential of mainstream social media platforms for the emergence of experiential health knowledge on the basis of which individuals join networked communities to share information on specific health issues. This research is providing in-depth explorations of the emergence of non-traditional forms of storytelling, where visual content -for instance -plays a key role in sharing personal experiences of health and illness. However, research aimed at thoroughly assessing the potentially different types of information produced and shared on mainstream social media platforms in general and Twitter in particular is still underdeveloped. In other words, is storytelling - textual, visual or multi-format - the only element used by lay actors to learn and share information about health on mainstream social media platforms? Do lay actors only rely on their experiential knowledge to talk about health and illness? These questions – centred on the nature of the discursive work produced on social media platforms - lead us to approach health networked communities as resilient publics forming around issues that have to do with the everyday experience and understanding of health and illness. By employing a digital methods approach to BRCA-focused Twitter data, this paper questions the notion of 'lay expertise' in the production of knowledge around hereditary cancer conditions and sheds light on the need to explore inter-group power dynamics in health information sharing on social media platforms.

Social Divisions / Social Identities

W828

Decades later: the ghosts of childhood habitus

Carole Binns

(University of Bradford)

This paper expands upon previous work around the concepts of 'habitus' (Bourdieu 1986) and the 'emotional underworld' (Reay, 2015). It focusses on a small qualitative study of 14 academics from a working-class heritage who have, by virtue of their education and career (at least), been able to acquire cultural, economic, and social capital. My participants were employed in one UK university either as a Lecturer, Senior Lecturer, Reader or Professor, and had thus journeyed from the traditional expectations and social identities of their working-class family backgrounds to those associated with a middle-class profession. After theming and analyzing the data, these academics could be placed into one of three group types, depending on their later (sometimes decades later) experiences of the academy. Participants who had experienced the most unease were often those who had expressed negative experiences and unequal treatment in their childhoods which, in this study, has been loosely termed as 'curbed childhood capital'. This appears to have had a reverse effect upon their later experiences, as the more of it that they were exposed to, the less the positive effect it had, and the more it appeared to contribute to a divided habitus in their later career. As such this paper focuses on the proportion of the research sample who reported a reflective awareness of on-going discomfort, unease, or emotional ambivalence in their lives and careers, and which in some instances could be decades after entering the profession.

Cultural Capital and Social Mobility in the UK: a Life Course Perspective

Andrew Miles, Adrian Leguina

(University of Manchester)

While a positive association between cultural consumption and social position has been established in a range of studies (e.g. Bourdieu 1984, Peterson and Kern 1996, Bennett et al 2009), the effects of cultural socialisation and participation on social mobility have rarely been subjected to systematic analysis. In the UK, the most thorough examination to date (Scherger and Savage 2010) finds a positive, multi-level relationship between cultural background, educational attainment and intergenerational social mobility. However the cross-sectional nature of this study limits what can be said about the temporal dynamics of this relationship: when, how and in what contexts are different dimensions of cultural capital mobilised to facilitate success or to protect against failure? In this paper, we address these questions by combining quantitative panel data on cultural participation and mobility with qualitative biographical accounts of the same from the 1958 National Child Development study. The rich data available in the NCDS are used to index different dimensions of cultural capital, including the significance of 'everyday' cultural practices, (Miles and Gibson 2016, Leguina and Miles 2017), and to trace their impact on life course transitions and mobility outcomes, paying particular attention to the ways in which these are both classed and gendered. Using text analysis to interrogate the narratives of a sample of 170 panel members interviewed for a 2008 qualitative sub-study, we are further able to assess how the processes of intergenerational and career and mobility are handled, explained and justified in terms of cultural disposition and identification.

Looking South, Looking North: what can Youth Studies in the Global North learn from research on youth and policy in the MENA countries - and vice versa?

Hannah King, Professor Rob MacDonald

(Durham University)

This paper attempts to see what can be learned from bringing together sociologically-oriented research on youth and youth policy from the Global North (the field known as Youth Studies) with studies about young people's lives in the Middle East and North African countries (often conducted by scholars working from Area Studies and International Relations disciplinary perspectives). Thus, the paper seeks to bring together research and theory from different disciplines/ fields and from different regions/ states so as to consider how we might better research and theorise about 'youth' (as a socially constructed life-phase) and about the empirical realities of young people's lives (as they play out in social, political, cultural and economic contexts). This is within the global context of young people challenging social hierarchies and inequalities (from the Arab Spring to 'Youthquake').

Drawing on the EU Power to Youth programme of research (in Egypt, Tunisia, Morocco, the Palestinian Occupied Territories, Turkey and Lebanon), and our experience in UK Youth Studies, we suggest ways that researchers in these different fields and places might benefit from each other. To do so, we focus on five sociological themes about youth and young people: variation in dominant state/ social constructions of 'youth'; how youth is divided, especially by gender; the flaws in human capital-based youth policies; the significance of informal and non-standard work for young people; and the meaning of insecurity for young people.

When professional self and class background clash: Identity dissonance amongst Scottish lawyers and the mediating role of gender.

Esme Terry, Abigail Marks
(Heriot-Watt University)

Drawing on data collected during fifty interviews with fee-earning lawyers in the central belt of Scotland, this paper explores the class backgrounds and professional identities of lawyers working in Scottish law firms. Previous research has emphasised the dominance of the advantaged middle classes within the legal sector (Ackroyd and Muzio, 2007; Ashley and Empson, 2013, 2017; Cook et al., 2012; Sommerlad, 2008, 2012, 2014). However, this is a somewhat simplistic picture. Other research has highlighted the value placed on working class capital (Bradley, 2014) within the Scottish legal sector (Terry and Marks, 2018), suggesting that there is scope for individuals to embody habitus reflexively to their professional advantage (Harrington, 2017), therefore establishing the value of their resources, despite their outsider status (Sommerlad, 2012).

However, findings to be reported in this paper show that, whilst fee-earning lawyers from either working class, or lower and squeezed middle class family backgrounds, often recognise their value to their organization, many experience a degree of identity dissonance between their professional selves and their previously held class identities. The current study also finds that gender plays an important role in mediating the phenomenon of 'imposter syndrome', with women more likely to experience class-related professional identity dissonance. Women from the 'wrong class' may have a greater awareness of the construction of difference as deficit in the eyes of 'existing power elites' (Sommerlad, 2012, p.2512). This is symptomatic of the complexity of intersecting identities, the rarity of structural reform and the persistence of inequalities (Tomlinson et al., 2013).

Sociology of Education

W823

Resilience: An educational buzzword for our time?

Neil Kaye
(University of Cambridge)

Successive governments have placed increasing emphasis on 'resilience' for the positive development of children as they negotiate their academic careers. It is a ubiquitous buzzword that pervades current policy interventions aimed at all levels of the educational system. Resilience, promoted as a key skill that young people must acquire in order to thrive in today's world, is defined as an individual's ability to 'bounce-back' from adversity or to overcome adverse circumstances. Overcoming these risks or circumstances, however, involves more than being taught 'how to be resilient' as part of the curriculum.

Using quantitative data from a large-scale students' survey and qualitative data collected through teacher focus-groups, this paper highlights the importance of young people's access to support and resources to cope with and surmount the challenges they face.

Drawing on Bourdieu's theory of social reproduction, I engage with the literature on risk/resilience (Rutter, 1985; Masten, 1990) to frame the process of promoting support for students who might otherwise be expected to struggle academically in terms of 'buffering' them against adverse circumstances to promote resilience.

In particular, I show that teachers are uniquely-placed to impart support and guidance to their students, providing a catalyst for a longer-term process of developing resilience through consistent supportive relationships.

My analysis challenges the government's unfair emphasis on developing resilience through 'character education', which serves only to individualise academic 'success'. Instead, a more holistic whole-child approach in schools is needed, along with complementary social policies to mitigate the structural inequalities that persist in the education system.

'It's about trying to get round the systems': Institutional concerted cultivation and the reproduction of social class inequality.

Jessica Abrahams
(University of Bristol)

Sociology, and in particular Bourdieusian sociology, has a long history of research highlighting the ways in which social class inequalities (amongst others) are produced and reproduced in society. Political responses to inequality have often focussed on parenting practices and family circumstances, something which has been largely critiqued for

individualising inequality and placing the blame on the victims. Sociological work has instead demonstrated the structural and material realities which contribute to different parenting practices and unequal familial transmission of valuable and symbolically recognised forms of capitals. Whilst there exists tools and concepts for exploring the practices of individual agents in society, there remains a need to develop and refine sociological tools for exploring and explaining the inequalities prevalent in the practices of institutions. In this paper, building upon Anette Lareau's widely influential concept of concerted cultivation, I introduce the concept of institutional concerted cultivation. This concept is used as a tool to explore the intricate ways in which educational institutions can be seen to be picking up where parents left off in their work to cultivate particular dispositions towards success, giving some young people an advantage over others. This paper develops this concept through drawing upon empirical data collected from three contrasting schools in one city in England. Data includes qualitative interviews with pupils in years 7, 9 and 11 and careers advisors alongside observation of careers events.

Looking forward to school? School choice, aspiration and future-building

Catt Turney

(Cardiff University)

Sociologists of education in the UK have documented extensively the strategies of middle-class parents to secure access to the 'best' schools for their children. Although such work is vital in understanding how educational inequalities are entrenched, the voices of middle-class parents tend to dominate. The absence of such voices, or their framing in relation to middle-class strategies for securing educational advantage, risks reproducing parents and children who do not 'play the game' as lacking the knowledge, dedication or agency to engage appropriately. This is shaped by and contributes to individualising discourses that frame marginalisation as the result of 'bad choices' and lack of aspiration, rather than structural inequality.

This paper will draw on my PhD research on families' expectations and experiences of children's transition from primary to secondary school. Building on the work of Diane Reay and Helen Lucey, I will examine the narratives of parents and children who did not 'play the game' in their selection of a secondary schools, instead selecting schools that were demonised, or those presented as inferior by others within the research. I will discuss the complex emotional landscapes of their choice narratives, and how these participants navigated their own memories of education, the reputation and representation(s) of the secondary school, and the 'social spatialisations' of these schools and their local areas. Additionally, I will consider how these families' school choice narratives drew on and reproduced the individualizing discourses of aspiration and mobility that currently dominate UK education policy, but also challenged and resisted these.

Theory W323

Theorising neoliberalism: Lessons from France

Charles Masquelier

(University of Exeter)

France often conjures up images of striking workers, heavy taxation, large public expenditures and highly constraining labour rights. Upon closer inspection, however, one discovers that despite lacking the kind of neoliberal revolution visible in Latin American countries, the US and the UK, France began its neoliberal transformation almost as early as its Anglo-Saxon counterparts. Rather than marking a radical break with the past, though, the neoliberalisation of France came to assume a 'pragmatic' (Fourcade-Gourinchas and Babb, 2002) form, responding to economic crises and various pressures exerted by globalising processes through piecemeal concessions. France, therefore, could be said to mark a distinctive neoliberal model. But what exactly can we learn from the French neoliberal experience? In order to answer this question, I propose to review some of the key political-economic developments taking place since Francois Mitterrand's 'U-turn' in 1983, up until Emmanuel Macron's presidential mandate. A particular emphasis will be placed on policies aimed at reforming the labour market, given their centrality to the neoliberal project and labour legislation's historical role in making France so 'French'. A case will be made for qualifying the oft-assumed singularity of French neoliberalism, despite the pronounced and distinctive involvement of the Left in its implementation. Lessons will then be drawn for making sense of such dualisms as state/economy, security/freedom and individualism/collectivism in the development of neoliberalism broadly speaking.

The Fallen NobleMen and the Spirit of Neoliberalism - on the sociological origins of one type of neoliberal attitude

Tim Winzler, Tim Winzler

(Glasgow University)

There is no shortage of sociological critique of the neoliberal society we live in – in economic sociology, its theoretical, economic foundations are critically examined. In the sociology of stratification or education, its malevolent effects on disadvantaged groups and classes, both statistically and in the everyday, are exposed. However, what is rarely attempted - perhaps also due to the rather visceral aversion against the proponents and trailblazers of such a way to organise society - is to rigorously understand and to explain how these proponents and trailblazers came to their worldview in the first place. This is where the current paper begins: using a Bourdieusian field-theoretical approach, it attempts to draw a theoretical sketch of understanding one group of persons that is arguably susceptible and likely to take a neoliberal worldview in our day and age: people of bourgeois or grand-bourgeois origin that have, in one way or another, lost forms of privilege (capital). This loss prompts them to aggressively assert their distinction (the disposition to which they are used and adapted) in purely symbolic ways (the only way left to them). I will use both historical examples (the cases of neoliberal Economists Friedrich Hayek and Ludwig Mises) and results of an empirical study of successful German economics students to show that a particular form of neoliberal ethic is for these groups a way to assert their distinctiveness vis-à-vis other groups. This of course also implies other ways to adopting the neoliberal attitude.

The Resonance of Resonance: Critical Theory as a Sociology of World-Relations?

Simon Susen,

(City, University of London)

The main purpose of this paper is to examine Hartmut Rosa's account of 'resonance'. The first part focuses on the concept of resonance, including Rosa's differentiation between horizontal, diagonal, and vertical 'axes of resonance' and their role in the construction of different 'world-relations'. The second part centres on the concept of alienation, notably the degree to which it constitutes an integral part of modern life forms and, in a larger sense, of the human condition. The third part grapples with the dialectic of resonance and alienation, shedding light on the assumption that they are antithetical to each other, while contending that their in-depth study provides normative parameters to distinguish between 'the good life' and 'the bad life'. The fourth part scrutinizes Rosa's attempt to defend his outline of a sociological theory of resonance against objections raised by his critics. The fifth part comprises an assessment of Rosa's plea for a resonance-focused sociology of world-relations. The paper concludes by suggesting that, notwithstanding its limitations, Rosa's approach represents one of the most promising developments in 21st-century critical theory.

Work, Employment & Economic Life 1

HANGING LANTERN ROOM

The regulation of corporate takeovers: prospects for challenging inequalities in voice and representation

Chris Rees, Michael Gold

(Royal Holloway, University of London)

The paper is grounded in current debates concerning corporate governance reform and the regulation of takeovers in the UK, addressing: (i) how target firms might develop more adequate defences against hostile takeovers; and (ii) how workers might gain more effective voice and representation in the takeover process. Based on a critique of the UK 'market for corporate control', the paper applies a 'regulatory space' analysis to examine key agents and instruments in takeover practice: i.e. the Companies Act 2006, the UK Takeover Panel's Code, corporate actors, and the EU Takeover Directive. It then considers how the balance between levels and types of regulation might shift, through a process of re-regulation, to fill the identified governance gaps.

Currently, directors and managers have no effective way of exercising discretion in favour of preserving jobs by resisting hostile takeovers, and labour has no formal participatory role in decision-making during restructuring. Various mechanisms for protecting employee and target firm interests are examined: e.g. the extension of collective bargaining, employees' dual role as workers and shareholders (through pension funds), direct voice mechanisms such as board-level employee representation, strengthening employee rights in the Takeover Code, and establishing a merger & takeover commission. The paper offers both theoretical and policy-oriented conclusions. In terms of the latter, it argues that employee voice can provide a corrective to the social costs created by the UK's 'shareholder value' model, and the most effective approach will require multiple complementary mechanisms, including robust collective bargaining and enhanced employee involvement in corporate governance.

Workplace hierarchies and sex based division of labor: Industrial dispute in an automotive factory, Turkey

Burcu Saka

(COMU (Canakkale 18 Mart University))

This presentation will focus on how women workers re-evaluate their life stories in the context of workplace struggle by putting particular emphasis on their relation with their mothers. By focusing on women's stories, the study will

question the connections between workplace hierarchies and the sex based division of labour at home. Relation between workplace hierarchies and sex based division of labour will be held in two ways. On the one hand the study will problematize how sex based division of labour operates within the shop-floor and how it is politicized among supervisors and workers within the unionization struggle. On the other hand the study will ask how the struggle for better working conditions have affected women's considerations on household labour. The study will elaborate these questions on the basis of semi-structured interviews conducted with 14 women workers who participated the two-day protests including a slow-down strike and occupation at an automotive factory (MATA Automotive) in Tuzla Free-Trade Zone in Istanbul, Turkey.

Gender Differences in Job Attribute Preferences: A Czecho-Slovak comparison

Alexandra Matejková
(Institute for Sociology of SAS)

The aim of the paper is to capture the differences in the opinions of men and women about the individual characteristics of work in the two countries of the former Czechoslovakia. Two mechanisms are traditionally provided to explain gender-based differences in career preferences: a) different gender-based socialization creating a contrast between gender roles of men and women and b) the position of women in the labor market in the existing social structure. According to the model of gender socialization, men are considered to be the breadwinners, while the main role of women mostly refers to the care of children and household. Therefore, we expect that the characteristics that represent the material conditions will be of key importance for men. On the contrary, the most important characteristics for women will be the features enabling to combine work with family care related duties. The model of social structure expects the existing gender-based differences in the preferences of individual characteristics of work to reflect the differences between men and women in the labor market as well as their structural positions and their approach to the rewarding system in the workplace. Our analysis based on the 2017 European Values Study as well as on recent data from the ISSP "Work orientations" module finds only minimal differences in job attribute preferences among men and women. The notion of women not willing to put as much effort into work as "the breadwinners" due to other priorities therefore seems to refer to a rather outdated gender stereotype.

Work, Employment & Economic Life 2

W001

Formal-informal wage differentials and education-occupation mismatch: Evidence from India

Shweta Grover, Ajay Sharma
(Indian Institute of Management Indore)

Using the nationwide sample survey on labour market particulars from India, the paper attempts to intertwine the two labour market aspects – formal-informal jobs and education-occupation mismatch (EOM). We examine the difference, if any, in the returns to EOM among formal and informal workers both in terms of employment and sector. The analysis finds that formal jobs experience a higher incidence of overeducation than informal jobs. Also, we document that while EOM does not play a significant role in the wage determination in informal sector and informal employment, it remains crucial for formal sector and formal employment. Further, the paper finds that EOM alters the contribution of other wage determining characteristics especially education and occupation in explaining the formal-informal wage differentials. This study highlights that policies that solely facilitate formal employment will lead to higher overeducation. Thus, a finer strategy should be focused on generating not only formal jobs but also adequate jobs.

Barriers to Employment for Migrants from the Middle East and North Africa in the UK

Narjes Mehdizadeh
(NA)

This paper aims to explore barriers to the employment of migrants from the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) to the UK. This paper is drawn from a wider ongoing study on the experiences of migrant families from MENA countries in the UK. MENA migrants in the UK frequently have high levels of skills and training, and wish to work and contribute to the UK economy. However, many are unable to find work or are engaged in employment for which they are over-qualified. There are a number of barriers to their employment. These barriers are identified through interviews with MENA migrants throughout the UK and recommendations made for ways in which they may be overcome.

Job Search, Transition to Employment and Discouragement Among Older Workers

Anton Nivorozhkin
(Institute for Employment Research (IAB), Germany)

Many studies found that differences in job search strategies affect labour outcomes of older unemployed workers. Behind this suggestion is an implicit assumption that all older workers are actively searching for jobs. This paper takes

a different perspective and analyse decision of older workers to search for a job. It quantifies the importance of job search on the probability of reemployment and estimates the share of older workers that give up job search and become discouraged. Empirical analysis is based on the sample of older unemployed welfare benefit recipients in Germany covered by the Panel Study 'Labour Market and Social Security' (PASS). The results suggest that employment transition rates are low for older workers: around ten percent found a job within a year. Active participation in job-search was decisive factor for the transition to employment. Furthermore, around thirty percent gave up job search and around twelve percent became discouraged in the sense of having obligations to search for a job, but not actively searching.

Do referrals rule out stigma effects from long-term unemployment in recruiting processes?

Martina Rebien

(Institute for Employment Research)

Hiring processes are subject to inequalities when it comes to the labour market chances of long-term unemployed: First, there is the stigma of long-term unemployment that leads to unequal chances on the labour market. It includes negative assumptions on qualifications, resilience or motivation. Second, long-term unemployment can lead to social isolation, because helpful social contacts to employees and employers disappear. Nevertheless, recommendations should be a desirable job search strategy for these people, because they may counteract the stigma effects that arise from long-term unemployment.

Only few research on the use of social contacts focuses on the demand side of the labour market. However, stigmas and unequal treatment take effect in firms hiring processes. Therefore, my contribution focuses on two questions: First, how do firms judge the work-related (soft) skills of long-term unemployed? Second, do referrals rule out stigma-effects in the hiring process?

I use data from the IAB Job Vacancy Survey, which is a representative survey on German firms. It contains information on the recruiting process with regard to long-term unemployed. Firms are asked whether they had applications from these persons, whether they invited them to an interview and whether they finally employed them. For all three steps in the recruitment process, it is possible to identify firms that recruited through recommendation or without it.

First results indicate that using social contacts does not influence the number of applications from long-term unemployed, but increases their chances to be hired, even if a firm judges their skills negatively.

Wednesday 24/04/2019 at 15:30 - 17:00

Paper Session 3

Cities, Mobilities, Place & Space 1

W622

Prefab sprouting? The return of 'pop-up' housing to the UK

Andrew Wallace

(University of Leeds)

As the 2018 summer heatwave parched the grass of London's public parks, one curious effect was to reveal the markings and arrangements of post-war 'prebab' houses, erected to meet housing demand and long since removed, a ghostly reminder of the long history of 'temporary urbanism' (Ferrerri 2015). This neat metaphor coincided with resurgent talk amongst architects, policymakers and builders about the merits of pre-fabricated housing construction, now more likely known as 'off-site' construction. This talk emerged out of particular conditions: the UK's crisis in housing supply, especially at an affordable level, potential post-Brexit skills shortages in the construction sector and revolutions in digital technology. Off-site housing is now big business. Ikea build 'flat-pack' homes, whilst insurance firm Legal and General now has a 'modular homes' arm. The outcome of this is a spectrum of developments ranging from shipping container homes to 'Grand Designs' self-build drawing in a range of groups including homeless people, young, mobile professionals and community-led housing enthusiasts. In this paper, aspects of the sociology and geography of new off-site housing is explored: might this herald the end of 'bricks and mortar' housing? What kind of lives, places, communities is this build method enabling? How does it align with other trends in urban life? And what are the continuities with those ghostly 'prefabs'?

(Inter)generational Geographies and Housing (Dis)advantages Between Older and Younger Adults in Urban Areas

Albert Sabater, Nissa Finney and Elspeth Graham

(University of St Andrews)

Age is a feature not just of individuals but also of urban spaces or neighbourhoods. Spatial (or residential) segregation, particularly in terms of ethnicity or class, has long been of social and political concern and debate is now emerging about the extent and consequences of residential segregation by age. Combining harmonised population data (2001-2011), housing information from the 2011 Census, along with house price and income data for small areas, we investigate the relationship between residential separation (sorting) between older (aged 65 and over) and younger (aged 25-44) generations and housing (dis)advantage in contemporary urban spaces within the UK context. Our findings indicate that the level of congregation of older groups (65 and over) has increased across most urban neighbourhoods since 2001, and such pattern of residential segregation has been accompanied by a reduction on the level of interaction between older and younger adults (aged 25-44) during the same period. Housing unaffordability has had a significant deleterious effect on the possibility of interaction between older and younger adults in urban areas. Home ownership has also had a detrimental effect for the age mix of urban neighbourhoods, whereas the opposite is true for the private rental sector. The results also indicate that ethnic diversity exerts a positive effect for the possibility of interaction between older and younger adults. Since housing (dis)advantages between older and younger groups play a crucial role in shaping (inter)generational geographies, the potential challenge to policies of social cohesion between generations underlines the importance of further research.

Do children need a minimum mobility standard when accessing services?

Sarah Brooks-Wilson,

(University of Birmingham)

The Youth Justice System of England and Wales is statically conceived, with an abundance of clearly demarcated locations attempt to resolve illicit behaviours and their causes. This means convicted children become temporarily catapulted into highly mobile lives when punished, helped and reintegrated into society. Yet applying a mobilities lens to youth justice for the first time reveals children are not equally equipped, with simultaneous mobility constraints and demands producing contradictory mobilities that criminalise and cement social adversity for a 'kinetic underclass'.

Contrasting with the 'backseat generation', evidence in this paper suggests children's capacity to be present and punctual is severely impeded by a broader set of factors including personal problems, family problems, locality settings, transport use and the provision of services. This paper will be supported by evidence from 28 children and 33 practitioners based in two case study areas that contain some of the highest neighbourhood deprivation in the country. In particular, intergenerational mobility problems, partially completed journeys and compulsory attendance

requirements will be demonstrated as adversely impacting convicted children. This paper will conclude with two propositions that can improve policy and practice responses to service (in)accessibility. A new impact project-led visual resource will be suggested as having the capacity to support journey problem identification through the engagement 'hard to reach' voices. A new 'minimum mobility standard' will be suggested as plugging the prevailing policy gap on service access, with a minimum journey support offer representing progression from highly prescribed or discretionary treatment.

Culture, Media, Sport & Food A

W308

Thuggery in the Stands: Spectator Violence in Canadian Sport

Curtis Fogel, Kevin Mongeon
(Brock University)

Much of the literature on spectator violence in sport focuses on European football hooliganism. Very little research has been conducted on spectator violence in a Canadian context, exploring commonalities and differences to football hooliganism. This paper examines spectator violence in Canadian sport, drawing on legal case files and media reports to determine the prevalence and causes of spectator violence in Canada, which have involved spectators assaulting players, coaches, referees, mascots, other spectators, media, security, and police, as well as rioting behaviours involving the destruction of property. The analysis considers various contributing factors including alcohol consumption, over-identification as part of the team, over-conformity to the ethic of sport spectatorship, socio-economic status, social tolerance, and masculine identity maintenance. Finally, we identify the response of Canadian hockey organizations and legal officials and offer various prevention strategies.

'It used to be brutal, now it's an art': Changing negotiations of violence and masculinity in British karate

Chloe Maclean, Chloe Maclean
(Abertay University)

In most western (and indeed eastern) cultures, fighting is seen as an ultimate symbol of masculinity – an embodied display of dominance, control and violence (Bourdieu, 2001). As a space legitimising and praising performances of mimetic violence (Dunning, 1999), combat sports provide an arena where the virtues of dominance and power at the heart of conceptions of orthodox masculinity (Anderson, 2010) or hegemonic masculinity (Connell, 2005) can be symbolically presented by men through bodily displays of strength, physical aggression, and the taking and overcoming of pain (Bourdieu, 2001; Messner, 1990; Wacquant, 2004). Yet, over the last twenty years the focus of karate in Britain has been perceived to shift from aggressive acts of 'hitting hard' to developing and displaying controlled, acrobatic and technically precise movements. Drawn from a nine-month ethnography and 7 semi-structured interviews, this chapter explores how British male karate practitioners re/negotiate ideas of masculinity and embodiments of a masculine identity in the context of karate's changing emphasis on, and practices of, 'violence'.

This paper suggests that a 'civilising' shift (Elias and Dunning, 1986) in the competition rules, increases in women's participation in karate with men, and subsequent negotiations of mimetic violence, complicate the use of violence as a symbol of praised masculine identity within British karate. A praised masculine identity is crafted by carefully blending traits conventional deemed feminine such as technical precision, elegance and agility alongside displays of strength and dominance. Such performances challenge conceptions of an orthodox sporting masculinity and notions of hierarchical gender distinction.

'I didn't even know women did that' - Re-shaping horizons of possibilities through corporeal knowledge

Charlotte Branchu,
(University of Manchester)

The naturalisation of sexed social divisions is at its plainest form within the context of sport, where bodies are considered in their mechanical and 'biological' (medicine-informed) form and women presented as a unified less-able category. In this paper, I rely on my two-year ethnography among women rugby players to suggest the importance of a corporeal approach to understand how my participants re-shaped their 'horizons of possibilities', as I describe them, afforded by having had space for critique (in regards to gender expectations and women's bodies more generally). Two factors contribute to creating this space: the use of their bodies required by the sport that goes against prescribed and regulatory norms; and belonging to a closed social group with a strong collective identity. Calling it a space suggests that participation indeed can lead to resistance behaviour, but also accounts for cases where it does not, and, on the other hand, medical and gendered norms are perpetuated. Providing examples of both critique and the infiltration of misogynistic or homophobic behaviour, I aim to provide a nuanced analysis based on a pragmatist and phenomenological approach.

Civilising Students: Problematizing Lad Cultures, University Sport and Gender Relations

Philippa Vellja
(Solent University)

In this paper I critically discuss the concept of lad culture on university campuses how university sport is placed in a wider understanding of lad culture. This paper seeks to explain; a) the role of sport in the wider literature on lad culture and UK university campuses 2) provide a long term historical analysis of sporting subcultures and lad cultures to demonstrate a shift in power relations between men and women and to explain why this behaviour is now considered problematic 3) consider universities responses to behaviours that are identified as lad culture and what the identification of behaviours tell us about expected social norms. This paper draws on data from the everyday sexism project, media articles and policies from 108 student unions, to consider what these policies tell us about changing gender relations in sport and expected standards of behaviours.

Families & Relationships A W709

Maternal anxiety: Objects, spaces and the perinatal ideal

Ranjana Das
(University of Surrey)

This paper takes a sociological entry into maternal perinatal anxiety, as it adopts the idea of the perinatal ideal to explore the integrated macro and micro sociology of maternal anxiety in the critical early years of parenthood. Historically, and particularly in recent years in the UK, maternal anxiety has come into focus as part of a scrutiny of support for women in the perinatal period. Much of the research and discourse focused on maternal anxiety as an individual condition, impacting foetal and infant wellbeing. I draw upon interviews with native and migrant new mothers in the UK, and from Twitter discussions on three months of a weekly hash-tagged discussion hour, to make sense of the mediation and social construction of maternal anxiety in the perinatal period. My findings, organized in two strands, consider the appearances and spaces of maternal perinatal anxiety. I suggest in this paper that we need to move beyond individualized, and infant-centered approaches to maternal anxiety, which contributes to and arises out of the inseparability of mother and child underlying the logic of intensive motherhood. I conclude, that the perinatal period through its overt focus on infant futures and wellbeing permeates objects, spaces, cultural policy, institutional discourse and lay talk, manufacturing the perinatal ideal, generating ripe conditions for producing and maintaining perinatal maternal anxiety.

Anxious Reproduction? Case Studies from Reproductive Sociology and Parenting Culture Studies

Charlotte Faircloth, Dr Zeynep Gurtin
(UCL)

In a recent article, and in response to Almeling's call for a more 'processual' study of reproduction, we make the case for the cross-pollination of the fields of Parenting Culture Studies and studies of Reproductive Sociology (Faircloth and Gurtin 2017). Both of these bodies of scholarship are concerned with the begetting and raising of children, yet so far there has been little dialogue between them.

In that article, we focus on four themes by which to illuminate similarities between the two fields, and thereby help us understand the contemporary Euro-American context of reproduction better: Normativity, Gender, Expertise and Stratification. A discussion of each of these themes leads us towards a conclusion that we are living in an era in which relentless demands are placed on parents (and intending parents), making them more anxious than ever.

In this presentation, we provide empirical research by which to elucidate this theoretical assertion, drawing on case studies from our respective research projects, including studies of egg-freezing, IVF, lesbian and gay families and infant feeding. In conclusion we point to some of the paradoxes (and anxieties) presented by reproduction in an era of 'individualisation'.

'We do this too': Black mothers' engagements with attachment parenting in Britain and Canada

Patricia Hamilton,
(University of Johannesburg)

This paper examines black mothers' engagements with attachment parenting (AP), an increasingly popular parenting philosophy. AP promotes the development of secure attachment between parent (mother) and child, through practices such as breastfeeding, babywearing and bed-sharing. Coined by William and Martha Sears in the 1980s, AP has garnered increasing attention in a neoliberal context, a political rationality that centers the economic and emphasizes self-responsibility, consumption and individualism as defining features of 'good' citizenship. In the context of neoliberal retractions in welfare state spending, AP emerges as a particularly apt parenting philosophy as it identifies childrearing

as a solution to social ills. However, AP's emphasis on the importance of childrearing also offers the opportunity to undermine neoliberal values of economic productivity. This paper explores this tension from the perspective of black mothers. Using a black feminist theoretical framework and drawing data from interviews conducted with nineteen black mothers living in the UK and Canada, I examine the gendered, raced and classed dimensions of AP and the broader ideology of intensive mothering it represents. I identify three themes that capture black mothers' engagements with AP: 1) expertise, 2) belonging, and 3) the division of parenting labour and find that black mothers negotiate these themes in an effort to claim 'good' motherhood. In their varying interactions with AP, black mothers conform to the norms and standards set by neoliberal rationality and upend them, articulating an oppositional or resistive model of good black motherhood that centers black children's value.

Mothers' understandings and endorsement of 'parental determinism'

Hillary Collins, Shona Hilton; Daniel Wight
(MRC/CSO SPHSU, University of Glasgow)

Writing at the turn of the 21st Century, Frank Furedi argued that political problematising of parenting was creating a state of 'paranoid parenting'. This relies on the notion of 'parental determinism': that parenting practices critically shape children's outcomes, which, later, shape society. In *Parenting Culture Studies* (2014), Furedi and others argue that parenting has become a contemporary focus of intense social, policy and political interest, with policy makers ignoring other social issues.

This project seeks to better understand mothers' views of 'parental determinism', with particular reference to expressions of endorsement, rejection and resistance to the apparent widespread acceptance of causality between their actions and their children's and society's future. Data collected in semi structured interviews and from an online parenting forum are used to examine perceptions of the framing of good motherhood, children and contemporary parenting practices, particularly in terms of the evaluation of risk, understandings of child development, individuality, surveillance and the influence of class.

Families & Relationships B **W727**

MIGRANT FAMILY DISPLAY: NEGOTIATING THE GAZE OF MULTIPLE AUDIENCES.

Julie Walsh
(The University of Sheffield)

This paper draws on the narratives of ten migrant families and thirty British born individuals living in a predominantly white British northern UK city, and builds on previous analysis that identifies Finch's concept of 'family display' to be a strategy employed by migrant families. Previous applications of 'family display' have, however, raised questions relating to who counts as the audience of display and if external others may play a part in confirming displays as successful. By uniquely examining migrant family display and the responses of indigenous populations to these displays, this paper shows that migrant families can be subject to the gaze of multiple audiences, and that each can have conflicting display requirements. Audiences can, for example, consider culturally located, sometimes unfamiliar family displays as unsuccessful in achieving familial legitimacy. Subsequently, it is revealed that migrant families make pragmatic decisions about which of these audiences they prioritise when engaging in displays; they create a hierarchy of audiences. This paper, therefore, contributes by providing a new way of understanding migrant family lives, and the responses of indigenous populations to migrant families. Analysis also advances the concept of family display in three clear ways: by showing that migrant families do display family to multiple audiences and that these audiences can have conflicting display requirements; by expanding understanding of how families make decisions about which audience to prioritise; and by arguing that broader narratives influence those related to 'family' and impact on how indigenous populations react to migrant families.

Marriage-related abuse in transnational cousin marriages: Narratives of abuse among British Pakistani Muslim women of Azad Kashmiri origin

Zahira Latif,
(King's College London)

This paper explores the lived experiences of British Pakistani Muslim women of Azad Kashmiri origin who undergo violence and abuse in transnational consanguineous marriages. It draws on data from an eleven-month focused ethnography with five older first-generation spousal migrants who stayed in abusive transnational consanguineous marriages and semi-structured interviews with ten younger women who left their marriages who were British-born or recently arrived spousal migrants. The paper explores the shaping of abuse narratives in the frameworks of conservative patriarchal cultural ideology and ethnic minority women's status within families, communities and wider society. Being at the confluence of these positions, abused Azad Kashmiri women encounter a heightening of cultural

patriarchal ideology as families and communities react to a progressively more threatening British society. The consequence of such actions, combined with the complexities of abuse in transnational consanguineous marriages binds some women to abusive marriages. Older first generation and recently arrived spousal migrants have limited opportunities to gain control of their lives whereas their British-born counterparts are able to tap into ethnic-cultural transformations in migratory contexts and, in so doing, find positive routes to moving on and rebuild their lives.

Effects of defection: familial challenges for escaped North Koreans

Hyun-Joo Lim

(Bournemouth University)

This paper examines the challenges and opportunities faced by UK-settled forced migrants from the Democratic People's Republic of Korea (DPRK) in maintaining transnational familial ties and relationships. The findings are drawn from research on 16 defectors using life history interviews. Narrative analysis was applied to the data. The findings suggest new digital social media play a vital part in retaining cross border familial relations and ties among some defectors whose families are scattered outside North Korea. However, many, especially those whose families remain in the totalitarian state, face extreme challenges, fraught with tensions and anxiety over the safety of their relatives. Moreover, the paper illuminates the examples of 'invisible' families left in North Korea and China, such as children born out of trafficking, raising serious questions on justice. Drawing on these, the paper argues that owing to their unique circumstances, conceptualizing family and kinship for these forced migrants is highly complex, which demands new ways of studying them. As such, it argues for a broader approach towards the conceptualization of transnationalism, rather than defining it narrowly based on the presumption of transnational migrants as having free access to their home countries. Additionally, the paper proposes the concept of 'traversing' to describe the strenuous transnational familial experiences of North Korean escapees, instead of 'frontiering' suggested by Bryceson and Vuorela (2002), which rather highlights the agency of migrants settled in Europe.

Lifecourse A W003

Beyond Generational Conflict or Class Inequality in the Study of Youth: Updating the sociology of generations to trace the reshaping of economic inequality

Dan Woodman,

(University of Melbourne)

The housing crisis, insecure work, Brexit, the Trump Presidency and most recent UK election have all been interpreted through the lens of generational conflict. Influential voices within sociology of youth and inequality counter that a focus on generations obscures continuing inequalities (particularly related to class); Resources to succeed are unequally distributed, as they have always been. This echoes earlier debates within the sociology of youth between functionalist and subcultural approaches to understanding youth: youth as culture and structural position of its own, or subgroupings of larger classed cultures. However, the best contemporary work on generations draws on and updated Mannheimian framework that facilitates asking important questions about the remaking of class inequalities (or gender or other structures of inequality) in the context of change. Using this framework, this presentation will draw on data from a 26-year mixed-methods longitudinal study of two cohorts of Australians, tracked through their 20s, 15 years apart (from leaving school in 1991 and 2006). Comparative survey data and data from qualitative interviews and workshops will be used to show, using a generational framework, the shifting interaction of economic, cultural and social capital that is reshaping young lives and transitions. Between the two cohorts, access to economic capital has become more important to utilising cultural capital to navigate contemporary insecurities, highlighting changing life chances between generations at a societal level (and potentially encouraging generational conflict) but enhancing the importance of intergenerational solidarities and transfers within the family.

'The inner me hasn't been allowed to develop': exploring the resonance of youth in later life

Penny Tinkler, Resto Cruz, Laura Fenton, Anne McMunn, Baowen Xu

(University of Manchester)

Reflecting on her life, 71-year-old Sam concluded sadly that 'the inner me hasn't been allowed to develop' and that she has never felt equal to her husband of fifty years. Her current situation she attributed to her lack of qualifications; this inhibited her pursuit of a career and opportunities to develop confidence, and hastened her decision to start a family. For Sam, teenage experiences continue to shape her later life. This paper focuses on the relationship between youth and later life of women born 1939-52. This cohort are part of the largest group of over 60s in Britain; they are redefining ageing. While this cohort's approach to later life has been attributed partly to their youth experiences in decades marked by profound social change (Edmunds & Turner 2002; Biggs et al 2007; Gilleard & Higgs 2007; Phillipson 2007), there has been little close scrutiny of this relationship. Our discussion draws on research conducted

for the ESRC project 'Transitions and Mobilities: Girls growing up in Britain 1954-76 and the implications for later-life experience and identity' (Reference: ES/P00122X/1). This research is mixed methods and includes: secondary quantitative analysis of longitudinal survey - the English Longitudinal Study of Ageing (ELSA) and the National Survey of Health and Development (NSHD); qualitative analysis of survey data from ELSA and NSHD; archival research; in-depth qualitative interviews using innovative elicitation techniques. Presenting our initial findings, we propose 'resonance' as a fruitful way of conceptualising the relationship between youth and later and reflecting on its significance.

Medicine, Health & Illness A

W002

Disparities in the health of caregivers of preschool children with disabilities compared with other mothers

Sarah Masefield, Dr Stephanie L. Prady; Prof Kate E. Pickett
(University of York)

Mothers of children with developmental disabilities, such as autism spectrum disorders and cerebral palsy, experience greater ill-health than mothers of typically developing children. This health disparity has been attributed to the physical and psychological challenges of caregiving, which include adjusting to the caregiving role, social isolation and disability stigma. Whether differences in the health of caregivers compared with other mothers emerges during the child's preschool years has, however, received little attention.

A systematic review and meta-analysis was conducted with the aim of examining differences in ill-health in mothers of preschool children with developmental disabilities compared with typically developing children. The secondary aim was to examine the effects in subgroups of disability diagnoses and socioeconomic status.

Fourteen studies (including 12 longitudinal and 11 cross-sectional analyses) met the inclusion criteria. The results showed significantly greater ill-health in caregivers for symptoms of stress, depression, fatigue, and general health, with a pooled estimate (standardised mean difference) of 0.87 (95% confidence intervals 0.60, 1.15).

Mothers of children with Down syndrome had the least ill-health (0.38; -0.29, 1.04) and mothers of children with mixed diagnoses the greatest (1.36; -0.80, 1.29). There was insufficient evidence to examine the influence of socioeconomic status on ill-health. Study quality was fair for 13 studies and heterogeneity high.

This review found evidence that adverse ill-health associated with caregiving emerges during the disabled child's preschool years. Interventions that address caregiver burden to prevent the development of ill-health are required from the point at which the child receives the disability diagnosis.

Pokémon Go and Well-being of Older Adults: A Case Study in Hong Kong

Ka Yi Fung, Professor Gina Lai
(Caritas Institute of Higher Education)

This paper investigates the impacts of new friendship ties on the well-being of older adults. Studies on social network and health have demonstrated that network members contribute to our health by providing resources to satisfy our needs. Network members in these studies are usually pre-existing ties, for example relatives, friends, and ties that are organisationally based, for example, coworkers. However, people also develop new social ties and some ties are not organisationally based, such as new ties developed during causal encounters. What are the impacts of new and non-organisationally based network on health? To find out the answer, this paper observes the network formation process of a group of older adults and records the impact of this new network on members' health. This group consists of around 30 older adults who develop friendship with each other by playing PokémonGo in a working class neighbourhood in Hong Kong. Observational data shows that these players encourage each other to exercise (walking), share emotions and health information, provide material support, and accompany other players. These contribute to players' physical, mental and social well-being. The health promoting mechanisms are explored. Negative impacts of this new network on players' health will also be discussed.

Population Ageing and Chronic Non-communicable Diseases in South Africa: Consequences for Development

Priya Buldeo,
(Human Sciences Research Council)

Chronic non-communicable diseases are significantly rising across sub-Saharan Africa thereby impacting individuals, families, health systems and society. This trend further threatens the social, cultural and economic landscape of the African population. Focusing the lens on South Africa, I explore population ageing and chronic non-communicable diseases in relation to the third sustainable development goal to unpack 'healthy' living and the promotion of good health and well-being for all at all ages. Qualitative data is presented using narratives obtained from 18 focus group

discussions with three generations (children, adults, older person's) who are living with one or more chronic conditions in two Western Cape communities. Herein, I identify the consequences for development in South Africa to better understand the dynamic pathways for tackling chronic diseases across generations.

Methodological Innovations - SE

W009

TIME ON OUR SIDE. METHODOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENTS IN SOCIOLOGICAL RESEARCH USING TIME USE DATA

This workshop aims to present and discuss recent developments in quantitative Time Use research, highlighting its contribution to innovation in both substantive and methodological areas. Such stock-taking at a BSA conference took place last in 2000 (Crow and Heath 2002), and the time has now come to update BSA audience about the research happening in the field, this time from a methodological angle.

Time use research has a relatively short history, but at the same time has been at the forefront of methodological innovations in the social science. Researchers in the field pioneered the use of time diary in large scale surveys (Szalai 1973), within household allocation of time, measurement of experienced wellbeing. More recently time use studies have been pioneering innovative data collection techniques, with wearable devices camera accelerometers and geopositioning. These have mostly been used to answer applied social science questions such as studying physical activity and energy consumption.

These methodological innovations are obviously not devoid of theoretical implications. The goal of the workshop is therefore to illustrate how some of the new methods brought about by time use research help question the consensus in a number of areas such as non monetary measurement of poverty ie time poverty (Vega); within couple or relationship-level definition of work-life balance and its determinants using sequence analysis (Vagni and Sullivan); how we understand subjective wellbeing and the way it is impacted by economic policies (Payne). This event is jointly organised by the Centre for time Use Research at the University of Oxford and the Social Statistics Study Group of the BSA.

A brief history of Time... Use Surveys and their application

Pierre Walthery

(UCL Institute of Education)

The aim of this presentation is twofold: to introduce the audience of the special event, especially non specialists, to time use surveys (TUS) and time diary data, as well as to provide a brief overview of a few recent applications. Large scale representative time use surveys have a relatively recent history in social sciences, with the first of its kind conducted in the UK in 1961, and the first international study carried out in 1965-66. Since then TUS surveys have spread across the world and contributed to improving knowledge in a number of key areas such as the sociology of leisure, working-time, eating habits and the gendered division of paid and unpaid work. The Multinational Time Use Study, which is managed by the Centre for Time Use Research, gathers harmonised TUS data from more 30 countries over 55 years will be also introduced. It is the main reference for international comparative time use analysis Using mainly the latest 2014-2015 UK TUS the presentation will present the instruments that are commonly used by TUS researchers: individual questionnaires, the 24h Time Diary – the main source for time diary data – the week long Work Schedule which take an accurate photography of respondent work patterns. Illustration of the potential of the data for sociological research will be provided, with examples from the area of work and employment.

A New Look at Poverty Revisited: Operationalising Time Poverty

Margarita Vega Rapun

(UCL Institute of Education)

The paper focuses on individuals who experience significant limitations in their lives due to time and income constraints. It proposes an operationalisation of the concept of time poverty for sociological analysis and policy making . Conceptually, time poverty can be understood as the situation in which individuals do not have enough time for rest and leisure after accounting for the time spent on paid and unpaid work: ie labour market, caring, household maintenance.

Although both time-related and financial constraints have been recognised as two of the main hurdles that can affect one's lives (Burchardt, 2008) well-being and poverty measurement have been dominated by neoclassical economics, which assume that income is the variable that best represents well-being. The importance of time stems from the understanding that the welfare of individuals and households is also of their freedom in allocating time (Wodon & Blackden, 2006). Poverty is multidimensional and that lack of time aggravates consumption or income poverty (Bardasi & Wodon, 2010). Furthermore, whereas free time has increased in the recent decades in the majority of Western societies (Gershuny, 2018), explicit analyses of inequalities in free time thus available remain less common (Bitman & Wajcman, 2000; Sayer, 2005).

This paper will focus mainly on Spain using the latest two time use surveys for 2002/ 2003 and 2009/2010. The measures is based on the traditional poverty measures (Foster et al., 1984) using a relative poverty line. It also examines the joint relation between income and time poverty and the main factors that affecting time poverty using a probit model.

“I’ll do it at the weekend”: Couples’ weekly employment schedules and the timing of domestic work and care.

*Oriel Sullivan,
(UCL Institute of Education)*

We use weekly paid work schedules to construct a typology of couples’ weekly paid work, providing a methodology for examining the relative level and timing of couples’ domestic work/care. Previous research has touched on the question of how individuals compensate or substitute for their own and their spouse’s time in these activities across weekdays/weekends. Hypotheses usually relate to constraints arising from the weekly hours and distribution of paid work. But there is question about the appropriate way of measuring paid work; by joint employment status, weekly paid work hours, or paid work on the diary day. We address the debate on constraint, specialisation and compensatory effects based upon the sequence analysis of weekly paid work schedules. Using the UK 2014-15 TUS, including diaries and weekly work schedules from each spouse, we find that controlling for the effect of partner’s paid work hours on the diary day removes the effect of spousal joint employment status, and the positive effect of a ‘weekend’ diary day, on domestic work time. We then use sequence optimal matching and propensity score matching to match couples’ weekly paid work patterns with each partner’s contribution to domestic work on weekdays and weekends. We find specialisation among some spousal joint paid work schedules, compensation across weekdays and weekends in others, and gender effects in yet others. Our findings point to weekly work schedules as a potentially important method for assessing how couples’ paid work patterns affect the distribution of spousal time in housework and care across the week.

How does time-use relate to subjective well-being and how do economic policies affect time-use? An exploration across households in the UK

*Chris Payne
(UCL Institute of Education)*

How does time-use relate to subjective well-being and how do economic policies affect time-use? An exploration across households in the UK", Chris Payne, (University of Oxford/Office for National Statistics)

The links between economic policy, measurement and subjective well-being have been a matter of academic concern for some time now. Within that literature, it is often highlighted that Gross Domestic Product (the primary measure of the economy) was never meant to be a measure of welfare and growth often comes at some social or environmental expense (See Mishan, 1967; Hirsh, 1977; Easterlin, 2002; Coyle 2014). Until recently, a lack of available data has meant that quantitative analysis to explore the precise nature of the relationship between economic growth and subjective well-being has been limited. However, the recent publication 2014/15 UK Time Use Survey (Gershuny and Sullivan, 2017) has filled a data gap, providing individual level time-use information and subjective well-being measures such as life-satisfaction, happiness, sense of worth and anxiety.

In the development of the Office for National Statistics Measuring National Well-being (MNW) Programme the main factors determining subjective well-being were noted as our ‘health’, ‘relationships’, ‘personal finance’, ‘education’, ‘what we do’ and ‘where we live’ (Beaumont, 2011). Of those six factors, five (health, education, relationships, personal finance and where we live) are directly affected by time-use, and the 6th (what we do) is our time-use. In the same model, the economy is noted as one of the three contextual domains where these factors are nested (the others being governance and environment). Therefore, based on this model, it can be reasoned that (a) our time-use is likely to be an influential factor on our subjective well-being, and that (b) any economic policy which changes how we use our time will also change our subjective well-being. Early stage results of research are presented here, exploring how individual time-use and well-being may be affected by economic policy and economic performance measurement. Economic policies such as (a) increasing employment and (b) increasing economic growth by increasing consumer spending are addressed to explore the impact they may have on individuals use of time and, in turn the impact this may have on their levels of well-being.

Race, Ethnicity & Migration A W011

‘Who is worthy of these walls?’ Challenging the Silence of Race in Higher Education

*Akile Ahmet
(Middlesex University)*

Universities are sites of power. The knowledge produced and reproduced is textured by inequalities because knowledge itself is highly racialised, gendered and classed. Karim Murji and John Solomos have argued that

'universities like all other major institutions, are sites where social order, including whiteness and white privilege, is reproduced' (2016:408). I argue that higher education institutions need to see the barriers to full and equal participation in university life as something to be dismantled rather than overcome; that is, we need to challenge the processes and practices that uphold traditions of privilege, inclusion and discrimination in university contexts. In this paper I present the written and photographic narratives of unbelonging by black and minority ethnic postgraduate students in London. I explore how affect, belonging and space are interfused. I argue that experiences of institutional dynamics, micro-aggressions and feelings of unbelonging within the space of the university are part of the 'everyday' at university for black and minority ethnic students.

Black Sociology for Change: The impact of Black Studies on sociology

shey Grant,

(Birmingham city university)

This paper discusses the transformative potential of Black studies and its development of a Black sociological approach. Black sociology is described as an epistemological approach to sociological analysis that highlights the western bias of mainstream sociology's conceptions of race and ethnicity (Ladner, 1977). This position identifies the university as a site of Eurocentric knowledge production, and critiques sociological narratives created and maintained by these constructions.

This paper will, in discussion of the validity of knowledge, asks: Whose truth? In the analysis of the positivist and interpretivist origins of sociology, highlighting the implications that these perspectives have had upon academia's role in the creation of a societal racial hierarchy to truth. In the process of de-colonialising academic knowledge, this paper will argue that the empowering potential of Black sociology for change lay in an academic commitment to engaging with, and embedding Black community knowledge into sociological discourses of Black experience. This, in addition to the ideological reflexivity and integrity of Black studies scholars; and the continued, unapologetic recognition and application of criticality towards the overarching 'whiteness' in mainstream sociological theorisations of race.

From white privilege to whiteness as governance: challenging racial hierarchies in contemporary Britain

Joe Rigby,

(University of Chester)

White privilege has become one of the most significant frames of reference through which the persistence of racial hierarchies in contemporary Britain has been analyzed and exposed. Whilst the refocusing on whiteness in discussions of racialized inequalities has acted as a powerful corrective to assumptions surrounding the myths of a 'post-racial' society, this paper explores some of the limitations of the framework of white privilege for challenging racial hierarchies. Drawing in particular on the work of Theodore W Allen in *The Invention of the White Race* and Satnam Virdee's account of race and class formation in *Racism, Class and the Racialized Outsider*, this paper argues that discussions of white privilege tend to overlook the important role which whiteness has played as a racialized form of governance targeting 'white' populations. As both Allen and Virdee have shown in different social and historical contexts, whiteness has played an important role in securing racialized class coalitions decisive to the broader maintenance of class inequalities both within and between racialized groups. An effective sociological challenge to racialized hierarchies and inequalities today, the paper argues, would need to illuminate both whiteness as privilege and whiteness as governance.

'The most dangerous racism today is the white man in the suit who's got positions of power to employ people': White privilege, racial exclusion and the silencing of racism

Madeline-Sophie Abbas,

(University of Manchester)

The upsurge of racial and religious hate crimes following the Brexit vote has brought these more tangible expressions of disadvantage affecting racial and religious minorities in Britain to the fore. Yet whilst overt acts of hate, although highly disturbing, can potentially be more easily identified, named and countered, implicit and more covert acts of racism that underpin structural inequalities provide a more complex terrain in which to address persistent exclusions facing Britain's minorities within predominately 'white spaces' characterising Britain's institutions. Drawing on interviews with British Muslims, I examine practices of silencing around acts of racism, the intangibility of racial exclusions which are often implicit, unspoken, and denied, and how these enable white privilege, and the racialised hierarchies on which it is premised, to persist. I argue that structural inequalities that permeate spaces such as work propose a more long-standing danger by maintaining hierarchies of social inequality and disadvantage, both economic and social, by denying opportunities for British Muslims to succeed. I show that where British Muslims name acts of racism, their claims are often forcibly denied by a failure to 'see' racism: 'surely racism doesn't still exist?' Whilst policies addressing racial and religious inequalities provide some recourse to counter exclusionary practices, I interrogate their 'non-performativity' (Ahmed, 2004) and the emotional and psychological costs that British Muslims experience to be heard as well as acts of resistance that they engage in.

Race, Ethnicity & Migration 2

W324

Transnational convergence, transnational distinction or individualised transnationalisation? Attitudes toward transnational intermarriage in China

Yang Hu,
(*Lancaster University*)

In an increasingly interconnected world, understanding the formation of transnational orientations is of great importance. Attitudes toward transnational intermarriage tell of people's view of the transnational world and their perception of the social distance between countries and regions. The purpose of this research is to identify the holistic formations of Chinese people's transnational orientations in relation to distinct countries and regions, and examine the individual- and province-level correlates of the distinctive profiles of transnational orientations in order to test theories of transnational convergence, transnational distinction, and individualized transnationalization. This research draws on individual-level data from the China General Social Survey (N= 3,000) and province-level data from the China Statistics Yearbook. Latent class analysis and multilevel multinomial random-intercept models are used to analyze the data. A fourfold typology of attitudes toward transnational intermarriage is identified, namely cosmopolitan, pro-West, pro-East Asia, and anti-transnational. The results support the theory of transnational distinction rather than transnational convergence, as macro-level difference ? instead of convergence in the level of transnational activity and, particularly, socioeconomic development between countries ? fosters support for intermarriage. The thesis of as individualized transnationalization is also supported, individuals' region-specific cultural consumption positively predicts their exclusive support for intermarriage with people from these regions. The findings reveal the ways in which uneven socioeconomic development, globalization, and individualization configure people's transnational orientations in a development context.

Race, Ethnicity & Migration 3

W525

"Low skilled became a euphemism for Eastern European": skill level and nationality in constructing hierarchies of EU migrants in the UK, in the context of Brexit

Alexandra Bulat
(*University College London, School of Slavonic and East European Studies*)

Research has consistently shown more positive attitudes towards highly skilled migrants over their lower skilled counterparts. Other studies concluded that attitudes towards migrants are differentiated by migrants' region of origin. However, quantitative methods dominate the study of attitudes towards migration and there has been little qualitative research on how these attitudes are constructed. There has been even less research into how certain pre-established categories used for migration, such as high and low skilled are defined and understood by both migrants and non-migrants.

This paper draws on 80 in-depth interviews with British, Romanian and Polish citizens living in two UK local authority areas to examine attitudes towards EU migration in the context of Brexit. It shows how migrants' skill level and their nationality usually intersect when participants express their views on migration. It is Eastern Europeans (and often specific nationalities, notably Romanian and Polish) who are perceived as low skilled. The narratives of Romanian and Polish participants, in particular about the "downskilling" they experienced in the UK, also show how the highly vs. low skilled distinction needs to be seen through a more critical lens in migration research. The localities compared in this study are the London Borough of Newham, an area of high migration and the local authority of Tendring (Essex), with much lower migration. Despite the various differences between these case studies, participants' attitudes remain broadly similar.

Borders, Migration and Class in an Age of Crisis: Producing Immigrants and Workers

Tom Vickers,
(*Nottingham Trent University*)

This paper examines how categories of 'workers', 'migrants', and associated subcategories have been structured and mobilised in recent years within representations of 'migrant crisis' and 'welfare crisis', to facilitate capitalist exploitation. The paper situates mobility in relation to class formation and exploitation through the concept of labour process, which

highlights the importance of capitalist control over movement, at a micro and macro scale, in order to extract surplus value from living human subjects. This analysis is tested and further developed by drawing on a programme of empirical and theoretical research between 2012 and 2017, concerning patterns of migration and settlement, labour markets, state policy and implementation, the media, and activism.

The paper focuses on Britain in particular. This goes against the grain of the general turn toward a transnational frame in many studies of migration and bordering practices, but has value given the persistent national organisation of capital, and the continuing significance of national divisions and connected racial boundaries in governing migration and migrants' rights. This has added importance in the context of Brexit, and the wider international turn toward protectionism and unilateralism supported by populist movements. Yet the British economy remains heavily reliant on international investments and service export of services, and key sectors are structurally dependant on migrant labour. Through an analysis of this case, theoretical insights are developed that have international relevance. The paper concludes by proposing alternative, counter-hegemonic understandings of the relationship between borders, migration and class that are informed by grassroots movements and foreground solidarity.

From informal to formal economic exploitation: Roma migrant workers and what the state enables capital to do

*Ashli Mullen,
(University of Glasgow)*

Roma migrants in the UK occupy a precarious position within the labour market, which is exacerbated by the UK government's policy of welfare conditionality for EU nationals. Excluded from any 'safety net', then, these measures further expose those at the sharp end of poverty to economic exploitation, such as within the 'informal economy'. Yet dominant conceptualisations of the 'informal economy' elide the role of key actors and institutions beyond the margins who enable such practices (Slavnic, 2010); in this case, the state. As capital's strategies adapt in line with new opportunities for appropriation, this results in changing forms of racialised labour exploitation. Drawing on ethnographic fieldwork with Roma migrants in Glasgow, who, as workers, are concentrated within low-paid and insecure work, I will argue that beyond informalisation, a newer practice of 'formal exploitation' has emerged. Welfare conditionality, as an instrument of state racialisation, creates the conditions and structural (dis)incentives necessary for this form of labour exploitation to operate. Yet far from being blind to their exploitation, Roma recognise this injustice, but adopt a pragmatic-realist disposition towards the labour market and enact the strategies they see as necessary to secure their material survival. Simultaneously constrained and enabled, this paradox reflects the contemporary experience of Roma throughout Europe that Yildiz and De Genova (2017) theorise as a fundamental condition of '(un)freedom'.

Dominant Language Acquisition in destination countries: Structure, Agency and Reflexivity

*Gina Netto, Maria Hudson, Nicolina Kamenou-Aigbekaen, Filip Sosenko
(Heriot Watt University)*

Although acquisition of the dominant language used in destination countries plays a central role in the adaptation and settlement of migrants to their new environment, including in education and the labour market, little sociological attention has been paid to how such languages are acquired. This article advances understanding of the structural and agentic factors which influence how migrants in low-paid work reflexively acquire the dominant language of destination countries. Bourdieu's theories on the symbolic power of language and habitus, and theories of reflexivity by Archer and others underpin our analysis of how migrants to the UK acquire English, a language whose symbolic power is reinforced through its international status. Analysis of data generated from in-depth qualitative interviews carried out as part of a multi-site study with thirty-one migrants from EU and non-EU countries in low-paid work reveals that migrant agency in increasing proficiency in the language is shaped by access to resources, conscious and unconscious reflexive processes, aspects of embodiment and perceptions of identity by the self and others. We argue that closer attention to the social, political and economic context in which migrants acquire the dominant language of destination countries is needed, as well as greater awareness of the multi-dimensional nature of linguistic reflexivity and the constraints on agency. More generally, the paper provides valuable insights into the complex nature of migrant integration and reflexivity in a key area which has received considerable policy and public attention, but which has been under-researched.

The well-being of migrants in rural areas -Bridging the 'Migration-Development Nexus'

*Philomena De Lima,
(University of the Highlands & Islands- Inverness College)*

The last decades have witnessed an increase in the range and scope of literature on international migration, including to so called 'non-traditional locales' - i.e. rural regions, and some regions and countries with little or no previous experience of international migration. The debate on migration in the EU including the UK has privileged two parallel discourses reinforcing an instrumental view of migrants: the role of migration and migrants in contributing to 'development' and poverty alleviation in their countries of origin; and their contribution to economic growth and

addressing skills shortages/gaps in the context of demographic changes. These discourses underpin two contrasting and persistent tropes of migrants in rural areas: as essential to plugging labor shortages/ skills or as taking jobs and resources away from 'locals'. This has resulted in an obsessive interest in how best to 'integrate' migrants from destination country perspectives and at the expense of social justice considerations related to their wellbeing and human rights. Rurality is not a neutral space but is conceptualized as relational embodying varied notions related to race, nationhood, gender, age, etc., impacting on migrants' lives in rural communities. Drawing on empirical research undertaken on EU mobile citizens and international migrants in rural areas of the UK and Scotland and a synthesis of a literature review of rural migrants in the EU the paper will outline a critical approach to understanding and researching rural migrant experiences that places their wellbeing and human rights at the forefront.

Rights, Violence & Crime 1

W004

Gender and Class in the Blaming and Shaming of Women in Sexual Violence

Karen Lorimer, Lesley McMillan
(Glasgow Caledonian University)

This paper draws on data from the DeMaSH study (Deprivation, Masculinities and Sexual Health), in which 116 women and men, aged 18-40 years, were recruited from areas of high deprivation in and around Glasgow, Edinburgh, Dundee and Highlands to individual, semi-structured interviews and focus groups. We explored a range of sexual health topics, including sexual violence and coercion, via a masculinities lens. Gender as 'a structure of social relations' (Connell, 2002) interacts with, sustains and alters other social structures, such that to only focus on gender inequality obscures the lived realities of violence against women from low income backgrounds. Women's accounts of the production of gendered selves reveals the distinct structural elements of both gender and class inequalities. We discerned a consistent pattern of men's hostility towards those deemed to have transgressed gender norms of appropriate femininity. Arising out of tightly policed practices of 'proper' femininity, we heard repeated disgust towards those perceived as excessively loud, drunk, fat white working class women by many men, with an associated lack of empathy for, and attribution of responsibility to, survivors of gender-based violence. Nevertheless, some women also helped support a hegemonic masculinity through victim blaming narratives, revealing a hierarchy of femininities. How femininities and masculinities are shaped and sustained within particular contexts needs to be understood in relation to class structures as well as how they are discernibly entrenched in patriarchal systems of oppression.

Secondary victimisation: challenging and articulating sexual violence and harassment in UK workplaces

Poppy Gerrard-Abbott
(University of Edinburgh)

Research on 'secondary victimisation' suggests that women who report sexual violence and harassment experience dismissal, disbelief and re-traumatisation from UK Criminal Justice System (CJS) processes and practitioners. Linked to historically low reporting and conviction rates, mistreatment is thought to inhibit women's equal participation in legal and public life, damage their trust in legal authorities and have long-lasting impacts on their mental and emotional health. Secondary victimisation acts as a vehicle for misogynistic institutional 'cultures', where mythical ideas about sexual violence are sustained and shape our attitudes and practices.

Despite CJS reform, secondary victimisation is thought to persist. Public and political attention around the mistreatment of women challenging sexual abuse has recently extended beyond the CJS to other institutional contexts. Studies on UK universities, surveys on workplace sexual harassment, the Westminster scandal and journalistic investigation on media industries expose the prevalence of misconduct, contradicting beliefs that Western societies have achieved gender equality in 'law'. In the #metoo era, our heads are turning towards institutions in our 'everyday' lives, where allegations are circulating the corridors of our workplaces, universities and lawmakers.

I will be presenting my PhD research and objectives as a working project, in conversation with my previous research around institutional sexism and feminist activism around sexual violence. This will explore my proposed mixed methods approach, consisting of online data collection and interviews, asking questions around how we should approach the recent surge of testimonies, situate them in wider discussions on gender equality in the UK, and articulate sexual violence.

Education as Justice: Learning From Sexual Violence Victim-Survivors

Hannah King, Professor Nicole Westmarland, Professor Clare McGlynn
(Durham University)

Is 'justice' for sexual violence victim-survivors conceivable or possible within contemporary society? What roles do education and prevention play in victim-survivors' conceptualisations of justice? This paper proposes that education

and prevention 'as justice' are fundamental to victim-survivors' perceptions of justice. Developed from an empirical investigation with 20 victim-survivors of sexual violence and 15 specialist practitioners, the paper builds upon the concept of 'kaleidoscopic justice', which sees justice as an ever-evolving, nuanced and lived experience. It engages with the 'justice paradox', as victim-survivors express a sense of the impossibility of justice within the current societal and criminal justice contexts yet are still seeking it. The paper proposes education and prevention 'as justice' as a first step towards addressing this paradox. For the victim-survivors in our study, existing social inequalities and hierarchies must first be challenged and changed, before 'justice' can be imagined. In essence, they are seeking little less than a transformation of society; towards a society that recognises the harms of sexual violence and actively seeks to reduce its prevalence. We suggest that it is only by better understanding victim-survivor perspectives on justice, that we can begin to address the sexual violence 'justice gap'.

Science, Technology & Digital Studies 1 **W007**

Sociology of Science in Low Earth Orbit: Assessing the "Scientific Value" of the International Space Station

Paola Castano
(Cardiff University)

As the most expensive and sustained effort to put humans in space, the International Space Station (ISS) responds to heterogeneous and often incompatible criteria of evaluation. These criteria encompass international cooperation, commercial development, public support, educational inspiration, technological advancement, and scientific research. And, as a platform for science, the station brings together fields that diverge in their goals and logistical requirements: particle physics, plant biology, human physiology, genomics, and materials science, among others.

This paper examines a series of assessments of value about the ISS as a platform for scientific research. Based on ethnographic, archival and interview data, the paper characterizes a group of experiments that exemplify the wide range of scientific goals and the scale of objectives that coexist in ISS science; and examines three evaluation settings of the ISS program: congressional program reviews, scientific advisory panels and media reports. I address the following questions: Who makes assessments about the scientific value of the ISS and its particular experiments? What evidence is considered and what are the particular domains under scrutiny? What is the underlying general understandings of science and of the particular experiments in these assessments? How are the impacts of ISS research characterized for ordinary people on Earth, for space exploration, and for specific scientific communities? What does it mean for research to "pay off" on the ISS? More broadly, the paper proposes a general methodology for the sociology of science to categorize understandings of science and its worth in complex institutional settings.

What Comes After Entanglement? The mundane ethics of exclusion within anti-capitalist protest infrastructures

Eva Giraud,
(Keele University)

There has been a frequent emphasis on the affinities that exist between protest movements – particularly anti-capitalist and environmental activism – and work within feminist science studies (e.g. Haraway, 2008; Pignarre and Stengers, 2012). Conversely, theoretical work that has emphasised entanglement and interdependency has been used in productive ways to analyse the dynamics of activist infrastructures (Feigenbaum et al, 2012; Shea et al, 2015). Yet despite this traffic, important questions have been raised about the capacity of the situated, relational forms of ethics that are advocated in theoretical contexts, to support the forms of critical action and intervention pushed for by activists (Puig de la Bellacasa, 2017; Shotwell, 2017).

In this paper I elaborate on some of these tensions, by drawing together participatory and documentary research about two case-studies associated with the construction of protest infrastructures: alternative media networks and food provision in protest camps. I, firstly, explore the contrasting provocations that each case offers for relational ethics. Then, secondly, address these provocations by elucidating the value of shifting focus away from an ethics based on relationality and entanglement, towards an ethics of exclusion, which pays attention to the entities, practices and ways of being that are foreclosed when other entangled realities are materialised through activist infrastructures. This approach, I argue, can help to foster accountability towards the constitutive exclusions that are bound up with political and ethical action.

From paper ledgers to 'data provider': The impacts and omissions of the Land Registry's digital turn

Timothy Monteath,
(London School of Economics)

The Land Registry has been collecting data on the ownership of property in England and Wales since its founding in 1862 and, while its remit and purpose has changed little over the past 156 years, the means through which property data is collected and deployed has radically altered. This paper provides an account of the Land Registry's digital turn and argues that the specificity of technological change and the structuring of registration data has played a crucial role in the shaping of this institutions contemporary form. In particular, this paper will focus on the Land Registry's switch to 'electronic conveyancing' in the early 2000s and its ongoing efforts to transform into a 'data provider'. This case will be used to explore the broader set of tensions at play as administrative knowledge is transformed into 'big data'. And, it will be argued that the means through which these transformation are mediated is both specific, to the historical context and remit of the institution, and ubiquitous, in the logics of datafication now being applied wholesale to knowledge production. Viewing the Land Registry, and its data, in this way reveals both the transformative impacts that this engenders and the omissions which it entails - resulting in a set of ambiguities which, it will be argued, continue to cloud perceptions of land ownership and the property market, both for researchers and the state.

Digital Fakery and Boundary-Work by the Civic Truth-Claims World

Ella McPherson

(University of Cambridge)

At the core of the fake news frenzy is the fear that citizens will become dupes, and that this is bad for democracy. Both this fear and this myopic focus on fake news are misplaced. I explain how fake news is just one manifestation of a broad and proliferating category of digital fakery, best thought of as a communication practice produced, transmitted and received. It is in the reception process that fakery is revealed and, if made public, triggers reactions. The more prevalent consequences of digital fakery for our societies, I argue, arise not because we are duped but because of these reactions - what we do to distinguish ourselves from the dupes and the dupers. I make this argument through an analysis of denunciations, drawn from my ethnography of digital human rights reporting, published by members of the civic truth-claims world in response to three cases of digital fakery: a fake civilian witness video, a fake app, and a fake NGO. These denunciations prominently feature boundary-work that uses binaries contrasting 'pure' characteristics and practices with 'impure' counterparts to establish walled gardens of truth in the wilds of the internet (Alexander 2006; Gieryn 1983). These binaries position pure insiders as conscientious, expert and fact-finding in contrast to impure outsiders positioned as callous, inexperienced and deceptive. Ironically, this boundary-work, which aims to protect the pure insiders of the civic truth-claims world, can in fact harm the pure outsiders on whose behalf it acts – and, in doing so, can exacerbate inequalities.

Social Divisions / Social Identities 1

W828

The Rise of Free Food Places

Kate Haddow,

(Teesside University)

Prior to 2009 the word foodbank was one that rarely entered our everyday language (Butler, 2017). Foodbanks have now become ingrained into political and cultural discourses around welfare or austerity and have very much become the norm. In 2014/15 for the first time, over one million Trussell Trust food parcels were distributed (Garthwaite, 2016). The sharp rise in foodbank use has been dubbed by many as a national disgrace.

Yet we have no accurate way of measuring food insecurity in the UK, we rely on Trussell Trust statistics to give an estimate of how many people are food insecure in the UK. A major limitation to this measurement concerns those who have never used a Trussell Trust foodbank, as they currently remain under the radar in terms of food insecurity. In recent years we have seen a growing body of research on nationally run forms of food aid like the Trussell Trust and Fareshare examples include Garthwaite (2016) and Lambie-Mumford (2017).

This paper will explore what it is like to be permanently food insecure and to be reliant on localised forms of food aid such as breakfast clubs, community meals and independent foodbanks. Consisting of nine months of ethnography with male participants using semi-structured interviews set in Middlesbrough, one of the poorest parts of the UK (IMD, 2015), this paper will address the need for charitable food and look at the limitations of food aid.

Free School Meals: The Influence of Stigma on the Take up of Entitlement

Samia Addis, Professor Simon Murphy

(Cardiff University)

Background: Free school meals supplement the diets of children from low income families to ensure adequate nutritional status and healthy growth and development. However, a sizable proportion of those entitled don't register, or once registered, don't take the meal.

Objectives: Using a Socio-ecological approach, this research is a qualitative exploration of factors across a range of analytical levels (Policy, Community, Organisation and Individual) which influence parents and pupils in registering and using free school meal entitlement in secondary schools.

Methods: Semi-structured interviews with parents or carers (n=13) and pupils (n=19) were undertaken in four secondary schools within one Local Authority in Wales. Schools were selected to represent a range in terms of level of entitlement and uptake of free school meals and data were analysed using a framework approach.

Results: Participants reported that the targeted and means tested nature of free school meal entitlement will impact on some families, also that there was potential for stigma, although this varied according to level of entitlement within the community. Within the school setting (organisation) the processes in place to ensure anonymity for free school meal pupils were highlighted as factors which influenced uptake. At the individual level, the ability to conform to the consumption patterns and practices of the wider pupil population was important for free school meal pupils.

Conclusion: For pupils with entitlement, the nature and implementation of free school meal policy will result in pupils on free school meals struggling participate in the food practices of the wider pupil population.

Teacups, tatt and thrift: siting charity shops in the 'welfare mix' after austerity

Alida Payson
(Cardiff University)

Recent research has begun to explore lived experiences of rising inequality, poverty and precarity in the UK post-2008, but has overlooked charity shops, despite their ubiquity (over 11,200 in 2017), as significant sites in an austerity economy. The Charity Retail Association boasts that shops bring people together, draw foot traffic to depressed town and city centres, recycle tonnes of goods, help people living on low incomes, provide job training, involve hundreds of thousands of people as volunteers and bring in hundreds of millions in revenue. Scholarly research has yet to fully interrogate these claims, however, or investigate how they might be changing in a context of rising social inequality. In order to understand how charity shops matter in this context, therefore, this paper reviews key debates around charity, welfare, thrifty consumption, giving back and making do. I argue that charity shops need to be understood as part of a broader constellation of informal, ambivalent and affectively charged spaces of making do and being together under austerity, especially as welfare entitlements are slashed and other forms of collectivity erode. I ask how we might understand these spaces in terms of the everyday pressures and "relational", 'emotional', and 'symbolic' injuries' of the present economy (Pemberton et al. 2017, p. 1157), as well as the ways people survive and make 'everyday life liveable' within it (Back 2015, p. 820). As part of the first phase of a three-year project, the paper sketches out future trajectories and open questions for research into these spaces.

Access to Drinking Water in Indian Villages: A Study of Social Disparities and Factors

Shamsher Singh
(FLAME University)

This paper is a study of access of households to source/s of drinking water in rural India. The main focus of the paper is to discuss the differential access to sources of drinking water across different social groups and to discuss the factors and processes behind these outcomes.

The study is based on household level surveys conducted in eleven selected villages across five Indian States. The study uses mixed method research techniques. Other than quantitative data, qualitative data were also collected by conducting focus group discussions, analysis of panchayat and local development records, interviews with panchayat (village council) representatives, local development officials and key respondents in the study villages.

The paper extends the existing knowledge of the centrality of the caste and notions of 'purity-pollution' with respect to access to water in Indian countryside. The paper uses the conceptual framework of social exclusion to highlight issues such as household incomes, occupation, class, land ownership, participation in decision making and implementing, government interventions, habitation pattern along with the issue of caste and ethnicity. The paper argues that the issue of access to water is multi-dimensional and requires a holistic research approach yet emphasizes on the importance of caste in deciding outcomes.

Sociology of Education 1 **W823**

'What I've learned is not to beat up my missus and kids': Gender Equality and the Facilitation of Caring Masculinities through a Relationships Project.

Michael Ward, Susanne Darra
(Swansea University)

Non-formal educational settings have been an often neglected area within the Sociology of Education. Young people who attend these settings are much more likely to be suffering or have suffered multiple adverse childhood experiences [ACEs] than the rest of the population and be from lower class backgrounds and BME groups. The local authority services that they access are often disjointed. One approach to challenge this in Wales has been the adoption of multi-agency units working collaboratively to create a team around a marginalized young person. These teams include a range of health and social care professionals such as midwives, early years practitioners, family facilitators, social workers, youth workers, early language development workers and teachers. Drawing on a yearlong qualitative study of one such multi-agency team in a coastal city in Wales, UK, this paper focuses on an ethnography of a six-week relationship education project. We explore how non-formal educators promote healthy relationships through teaching men (aged 16-24) about toxic displays of masculinity and gender-based violence, promoting values of care, respect, stability and reliability. In this paper we argue that it is through such practices that the more damaging displays of masculinity can be challenged. We suggest this study can add to the emerging concept of 'caring masculinities' and how non-formal educational settings could be at the vanguard of having a positive impact on gender equality 'downstream'.

'It was just constant mayhem' - setting by behaviour in an English secondary school

Lucy Wenham,
(IoE / UCL)

With the relentless increase in the number of new kinds of schools, the already fragmented English secondary school system is fracturing further. Since branching points, partitions and choice are all known to contribute to inequalities, there is a pressing need to fully understand the roots of marginalisation. This ethnography addresses the experience of marginalisation of a small group of secondary school students, giving them a voice as a way of understanding the triggers and effects of disengagement from mainstream education. These participants have all spent some time in a withdrawal-unit, most commonly following a period of sustained low-level disruption. The research is primarily based on semi-structured interviews, with some participant observation and small group teaching undertaken by the researcher within this unit. The data is analysed using grounded theory techniques and the emergent categories indicate a range of factors that students perceive as fuelling marginalisation within the secondary education system. Some emergent themes touch on in-school structures, which divide or group students. The focus here is on one such factor - setting by behaviour - which students cite as the reason for their allocation to and movement between sets. While close monitoring of setting policy in practice may alleviate this source of marginalisation, to really take the students' experience seriously, entails moving beyond reforms and adaptations, to think about education differently. What is needed to tackle this marginalisation is to eliminate setting, as part of a wider shift to a radically comprehensive education system structure.

Artistic Production and (re)production: 'dis-engaged' young people's educational experiences of Arts Award programmes

Frances Howard, Frances Howard
(Nottingham Trent University)

Theories of reproduction are a useful tool for investigating, often unacknowledged sources of social inequality. Artistic Production and (re)production is a concept which brings together the works of Pierre Bourdieu and Paul Willis as a way of exploring the tension between the social hierarchisation within arts education and its assimilation of common culture. This framework is used to describe opportunities for young people to become agentic and entrepreneurial arts producers, within the constraints of the practices, capitals and dispositions on offer.

This paper will explore the forces of production and reproduction at work within the Arts Award – a nationally recognised vocational qualification, and its particular 'offer' to young people who are regarded as 'dis-engaged' from mainstream education. It draws on findings from a doctoral study where ethnographic case studies were conducted in five sites, capturing the experiences of young people accessing the programme. This study found that the Arts Award represented an unequal offer for young people who were offered different practices, capitals and dispositions due to the socially streamed programmes.

Whilst Artistic Production offers hopes of transformation, in particular in relation to working-class and marginalised groups, paradoxically these groups demonstrate a subordinate variety of production, which leads to (re)production. Highlighting issues of equity, this paper demonstrates that despite changes to the ways that young people access arts education, and the mobilisation of programmes such as the Arts Award with a commitment to social justice, there continues to be the (re)production.

The Risk Matrix, An Educational Policy Tool: Amber Alert!

Nighet Riaz,

(University of the West of Scotland)

Despite having the highest levels of educational attainment, people from minority ethnic (ME) communities are twice as likely to be unemployed compared to those from white communities. Race equality employment initiatives designed to address this disparity are scattered across a number of Directorates in the Scottish Government and its delivery agents, with no consistency or co-ordinated approach by other public bodies to implement and action race equality into employment initiatives (Lyle, 2017). This paper explores policy levers and tools used in school to close this 'employment gap' as ME young people transition out of compulsory education, through semi-structured interviews with teachers and young people. The findings illustrate the dualistic approach taken by schools, where the 'ordinary majority' is overlooked (Roberts, 2011:5). This strongly suggests that the resources to support ME young people is inconsistent, and which is not prioritised due to lack of interest in the 'missing middle' by academics and policymakers.

Theory 1 **W323**

Locating social hierarchies and inequalities as central to the study of practices

Emmet Fox

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Second wave Practice Theory (PT), which locates practices as the ultimate unit of research, continues to downplay the role of social differentiation. This is despite social differentiation being a central social force in the earlier practice theory of Bourdieu. Where social differences and inequalities are studied in contemporary PT they are mainly studied in relation to the practice, such as how economic inequalities can exclude people from or trap them in socially (dis)advantageous practices. Social differentiation is not, however, studied as central to practices. However, social differentiation has enormous effects on how practices are shaped, distributed, and performed, with added consequences for maintaining and/or reconfiguring social hierarchies and inequalities through the amassing of resources within practices. I discuss this further through theoretical insights on social differentiation which include: (1) what I call 'the dynamics of social differentiation' from Bourdieu where social differences wield a symbolic and material effect on each other through emulative, homogenistic, repellent, (etc) mechanisms; (2) 'the commodification of social differentiation' through the production of space from Neil Smith and (3) Schatzki's "orchestration" which, describes how practices contain non-independent differences (e.g. competing goals). Combined, these insights offer ways to study social differentiation as central to practices with an added effect of better explaining power in practices – something for which PT is criticised - through recognizing social hierarchies.

What Bourdieu might tell us about a 'game' defined by a logic of co-production

Andrew Passey

(Leeds Beckett University)

Co-production is increasingly seen as a means to increase the role of users of public services by drawing on the strengths and assets they are seen to possess. The literature points to benefits, including improved outcomes, increased social capital, and reduced costs. Little attention has been paid, however, to how co-production shapes ideas of professionalism and professional practice of staff working in public services.

Bourdieu conceptualised field as a social space of competition between actors occupying different social positions. This struggle is akin to a 'game', in which players possess and deploy forms of capital to gain power and influence. This paper uses Bourdieu's 'thinking tools' to ask what happens when a game is defined by a logic of co-production. A co-productive logic fits within a relating mode of professionalism, where the focus is on the ways in which professional staff build collaborative relations with others, including those in other professions and services users. This contrasts with normative understandings of professionalism that prioritise specialised knowledge based on individualised understandings of expertise, and which in part define professionalism by professional boundaries and/or jurisdictional disputes. The paper draws on my ongoing PhD, which is a case study of children's mental health services. Based on a qualitative methodology, data are being generated through semi-structured interviews, documents and observation. The paper considers whether the field of children's mental health services may be conceptualised as an area of collaboration (rather than conflict) and whether co-productive professionalism can be regarded as a form of symbolic capital.

Pierre Bourdieu's Theoretical Analysis of Resistance and Change

Bridget Fowler

(University of Glasgow)

Pierre Bourdieu is justly praised for his innovative theory of practice. In particular his objectivist analyses of the structural determinants of social power, combined with the exploration of agents' subjective 'illusio', have proved a very powerful instrument for sociological advance. He has been particularly important in showing subaltern actors' deference to cultural capital in order to explain the stability of class inequalities and hierarchy in the period since World War II. But it is commonly argued that his theoretical fruitfulness has certain limits – notably, that the notion of habitus or habitus clivé is a theoretical black box lacking adequate criteria for rigorous application (Burawoy in Burawoy and Hardt (2012), Fabiani 2016). Moreover, many critics have contended that his account of social reproduction is too broad to allow any theory of revolution or large-scale social change (Swartz 2012 (1997), Boltanski 2011). This paper will show that such a theory of resistance and social transformation does exist in Bourdieu's works. More predictably, it will draw on his analyses of symbolic revolution in cultural fields (eg Manet: A Symbolic Revolution), 2015). But it will also claim that a wider theory of historical change has been sketched out by Bourdieu, although buried in his analyses of prophetic movements, intellectuals, the contraction of the welfare state and reflexivity. I shall draw particularly here on his recently-published lectures (On the State (2015), and Sociologie Générale vols. I (2015) and II (2016)) as well as Pascalian Meditations (2000).

Work, Employment & Economic Life 1

HANGING LANTERN ROOM

Theorizing Varieties of Banking Systems: Coordinated Banking System in Canada and Liberal Banking System in the US

Dean Curran, Tim Bauer, Andrew Bauer
(University of Calgary)

The Varieties of Capitalism (VoC) literature provided an important analytical step in forward in differentiating within capitalism systemic, durable differences between types of economies that within the broader rubric of capitalistic. The 2008 financial crisis though, while originating in the heart of LME countries, the US and the UK, also wreaked havoc on highly leveraged, lightly regulated banks in CMEs. As many scholars have argued, in the lead-up to the crisis there was a significant convergence of different capitalist banking systems, at least in liberal democracies, towards a more liberalized form of finance. While not denying certain trends towards convergence the paper argues for the robustness of certain varieties of banking systems (VoBS) through an analysis of key differences between the banking systems of two LMEs, the Canadian and US systems. Building upon interviews with bankers and accountants in the US and Canada this paper proposes that Canada and the US exhibit fundamentally different relations between banks, regulators, market structure, and culture such that, while both are capitalist and profit maximizing, they can be said manifest Coordinated Banking Systems for the Canadian System and Liberal Banking System for the US. Beyond showing two different types of banking equilibrium that a capitalist banking system can pursue, the paper then proceeds to question the idea of 'best practices' for regulating a financial system across varies of banking systems.

Financial capability as a form of governmentality: social housing, welfare, and dependency

Emma Wainwright, Ellen McHugh
(Brunel University London)

Housing Associations operate at the community level between the state, market, and individual, and in a political context of austerity, state roll-back, and welfare reform, have been increasingly tasked with focusing on the 'welfare' of their tenants. The financial capability of social housing residents has emerged as a priority in response to changes in the amount of, and mode of receiving, state benefits, as well as the reduced state funding received by social housing agencies. This paper focuses on research exploring a pioneering financial capability programme operated by one large housing association in the South East with the aim of 'educating' residents out of debt. It draws on interviews with housing directors, and programme mentors and participants, to explore narratives of debt and trajectories to 'independence'. Framed by discussions of neoliberal welfare restructuring and discourses of personal agency and responsibility, we argue that financial capability can be seen as a form of advanced liberal governmentality and a substantive governing project. By exploring the ways tenants are engaged and assessed we argue that a critical reading of these programmes is necessary. However, by tracing tenants' own narratives of debt, we highlight the need to better understand the lived experiences of welfare reform, including the role such programmes have in 'supporting' tenants.

Sticking to traditional masculine business culture and practices or casting aside them? - A comparative study between Japan and selected Scandinavian countries

Kuniko Ishiguro
(Tokyo International University)

This research discusses the issue of gender-(in)equality in business entities based on empirical research using qualitative methods focusing on life-history interviews. It argues that the prevalent masculine business culture seen in Japan ignores the humanity of employees, both men and women, and saps the energy of people, as well as organisations and society. Consequently, those static organisations and the society lose the fundamentals of innovation and competitive power for the future.

The cases of Japan show gender inequality based on the masculine corporate culture where not only gaps between men and women, but also big gaps among women in employment processes have caused many problems for individuals as well as for companies. In contrast, the Scandinavian cases show a fundamental respect for humanity and acceptance of diversity in the society and business, which have resulted in creation of more resilient and flexible businesses and societies.

By comparing the case of gender (in)equalities in Japanese companies and Scandinavian companies, the research has found that the discussion on the issue of gender equality is not merely about the advancement of women in the economy, but it also encompasses much wider problems regarding perspectives on, and approaches towards, the meaning of work in one's life, for men and women alike.

The presented comparison in this research will pose a further question of how government, society and businesses can flourish by respecting people in other countries as well.

Work, Employment & Economic Life 2

W001

Effective Routes to Employment for Young Disabled People

ANDREW WOOL,
(University of Leeds)

The underemployment of young disabled people in the UK is a problem that is seldom discussed by policymakers or academics, however, it has a very significant impact on those with disabilities and those who work directly in this area. Whilst a number of researchers have sought to explore the routes to employment for young disabled people generally, there is a lack of research regarding the experiences of young disabled people in the UK who, arguably, are at the greatest disadvantage. This is as a result of a perfect storm of factors such as legislation having the unintended impact of discouraging employers to recruit disabled people, cuts to support payments which would enable disabled people to travel to and from work, and practical barriers regarding simple elements such as completion of online application forms or participating in job interviews. This study adopts a novel perspective, synthesising the experiences of young disabled people with those of facilitators, and employers who actively look to recruit disabled people.

The aim of the research is to understand what can be done to create better employment opportunities for such people.

Using an interpretivist philosophy the design and strategy for this study is to be that of survey research, to encompass in-depth interviews with research participants.

With regards to population sampling, snowball sampling is to be used. I have a daughter with cerebral palsy & as a result I have connections to a number of people with disabilities, facilitators and employers of young people with disabilities.

NEET young people's social networks: pathways in and out of poor work?

Liam Mark Wrigley,
(University of Sheffield)

Over the last 21 years, young people identified as not in education, employment and training (NEET) have remained of great significance in policy, media and academic debates. Commentators such as MacDonald and Shildrick (2018), Holland (2012) and Ryan (2016) have all commented on the importance of social capital networks of family and friends in dealing with issues of poverty and lack of education, employment and training in disadvantaged communities and neighborhoods. This presentation will give a critical commentary of why young people identified as NEET stay in communities marked by opportunities low paid/ low quality work opportunities, and how 'network poverty' (Perri 6, 1997) and so called 'weak social ties' (Granovetter, 1977) can paradoxically provide informal work opportunities for young people living in such communities and neighborhoods. The presentation will also give a critique of current policy regarding unemployed or inactive young people, and suggest what alternative thinking can be deployed in holding central government to account in understanding how young people develop strategies of belonging to neighborhoods and communities in challenging social exclusion and unemployment.

Thursday 25/04/2019 at 11:00 - 12:30
Paper Session 4

Cities, Mobilities, Place & Space 1
W011

Highly skilled migrants in the City of London: Applying the concept of embedding to understand responses to Brexit

Louise Ryan, Dr Jon Mulholland
(University of Sheffield)

This paper draws upon the concept of embedding (Ryan and Mulholland, 2015) as a way of understanding how EU migrants resident in the UK are responding to Brexit. We draw upon a rich, longitudinal dataset of French highly skilled migrants whom we have interviewed repeatedly over a 7 year period. Having interviewed them before and after the referendum, we examine how their experiences and evaluations of life and work in London changed in response to the 2016 referendum.

Mostly working in the financial sector in London, these are a relatively privileged, 'low-visibility' group who tended not to see themselves as migrants. Now, following the referendum, their attitudes have changed considerably. They expressed novel feelings of rejection, being defined now as outsiders and immigrants. Some said they are reluctant to speak French in public places through fear of abuse. Others are now uncertain about their future rights and security in the UK, and have started to explore career opportunities elsewhere.

Our framework of embedding as an active process of developing belonging and attachment over time is useful in helping to analyse these reactions to Brexit. Although, our participants had seemed to be successfully embedding in the labour market and in the diverse cultural life of London, now, in response to Brexit, some appear to be 'disembedding', while others are adopting new strategies of 'civic embedding' by applying for British citizenship. This shows the dynamic, conditional and contingent contexts of belonging and attachments, even for the most privileged migrants.

Uncertain belonging: EU migrant lives since the Brexit vote

Chris Moreh, Derek McGhee
(York St John University)

This paper presents the first analysis of data from a recent e-survey project (2018, N=908). It discusses the effects of the Brexit process on the lives of EU nationals living in the UK, focusing in particular on whether Brexit has affected migrants' sense of belonging. First, it presents a quantitative assessment of the Brexit effect on 'belonging', conceptualising the latter as a combination of emotional closeness toward the country of residence and a sense of acceptance by the country of residence. Second, it offers a qualitative insight into individual narratives of experiences, fears and hopes related to the Brexit process, based on answers to an open-ended survey question (N=874). The article argues that the emotional effect of Brexit on the lives of EU migrants is not singular but differential: it has had both an alienating and an integrative effect. The article examines how these two opposing effects shape processes of ethno-national boundary-making, contributing to the theoretical understanding of boundary-making phenomena during times of radical socio-legal restructuring.

Cities, Mobilities, Place & Space 2
W610

Today's Urban Development is Tomorrow's Ruin: Liverpool One as Spatio-Temporal Fix

Paul Jones,
(University of Liverpool)

Sites of 'failing' urban capitalist activity become the very experimental terrains on which new speculative forms are embedded. Such 'spatio-temporal fixes' (Harvey, 1974) have a distinctly architectural character; the designed environment's status as fixed capital - and role in meaning-making concerning such - is key to this significance. Opened in 2008, Liverpool One is a mixed-use development occupying 400,000m sq of central urban space, which is controlled by a major landowner on a 250-year lease. Architecture is key to reconfigurations of temporality and urban use and scale that underpin the scheme. The key argument here is that as a speculative, entrepreneurial project in which past economic crises are offset - albeit for many hundreds of years - the architecture of Liverpool One both: i)

owes much to the active political construction of past crises; and ii) is a spatio-temporal fix developed in response to such.

The missing middle are still (mostly) missing

David Byrne
(Durham University)

In an editorial in a special issue of *Sociology* in 2005 concerned with 'class and culture' I reflected on 'absences against presences' - to the lack of attention paid to the 'missing middle' in the social structure. People who live in households in the upper 45% of the household income structure are not much addressed in social investigation. Investigation which looks at them in relation to the places in which they live have been very little done since the 1960s and the last work of the Institute for Community Studies. A particular and notable absence is the lack of studies in the South East Region and Eastern Region outwith London which together contain 25% of the UK's population, many of whom work in Greater London and commute there. In this presentation I will draw on what we know about these people from statistical sources and argue that failure to explore their lives, and in particular how they 'live class' means that accounts of the contemporary social world and class relations in the UK are seriously deficient. There are Ph.D. studies which have explored aspects of these life worlds but there is a serious need for a new set of 'community / locality' studies which address how class is lived in places in post-industrial capitalism after the financial crash and in the era of austerity. An especially important theme is what is meant by aspiration in this context.

Culture, Media, Sport & Food 1

W308

Respectability and Religiosity: Tying Together the Tensions of Wearing the Hijab

Katherine Appleford, Fatima Rajina and Sonya Sharma,
(Kingston University London)

Using the example of Nadiya Hussain who won British Bake-Off in 2015, this paper explores notions of respectability and femininity vis-à-vis a Muslim woman's dress in the public sphere. It addresses aspects of belonging through the shifting towards the turbanisation of the hijab as a means of making Islam and Muslimness more 'palatable'. Drawing on qualitative focus groups with young Muslim women, we discuss the impact of turbanisation on the visibility of Muslimness and whether this form of veiling was considered more 'modern'. Themes from the data demonstrated how young Muslim women reconfigure their bodies through religious dress and its intersection with experiences of Islamophobia and popular culture. In particular, the latter have been significant to young Muslim women in shaping their sense of belonging and self-expression. This highlights a tension that can exist between religiosity and recognition in different social spaces.

Talking about the 'rotten fruits' of Rio 2016: the discursive power of the L-word

Adam Talbot,
(Abertay University)

This paper will examine the way the public conversation regarding Rio's emerging Olympic legacy has been framed as the projects implemented by the local authorities. Based on ethnographic fieldwork with Olympic critics in Rio, conducted in 2016 and 2018, I will offer a brief analysis of the emerging Olympic legacy in the Cidade Maravilhosa. In particular, this paper explores the way 'legacy' provides a discursive framework that limits discussion of negative impacts and missed opportunity costs, even among those at the sharp end of the negative impacts. The PR campaign which emblazons these projects as legacy projects serves to limit our thinking about what has changed in the city because of the event. I will therefore argue for a more expansive definition of the term legacy, rethinking what we mean by this term to include missed opportunities and negative impacts, giving a fuller picture of the impact mega-events have on cities.

Given Things: Towards a Sociology of Poetry ... or a Poetry of Sociology?

Andrew Smith
(University of Glasgow)

In this paper I offer some first thoughts in response to the question: what might a sociology of poetry look like? For the most part, sociologists have had very little to say about poetry as a distinctive kind of social utterance, or about its social and historical characteristics. This is the case even though, from time to time, prominent figures in the discipline (Bauman, Lemert) call for sociologists themselves to take on the social role of the poet and come close, indeed, to conflating poetry with sociology. Drawing on evidence from a study of poetry readers and readings amongst working

class communities in Glasgow, I try to suggest something about the peculiar sociological characteristics of poetry, and about why it is that it seems to constitute a particular challenge to sociological understanding. The answer, I propose, has something to do with the encounter which poetry forces upon us with an experience of 'given-ness', and the difficulty that sociology has often had in making sense of such encounters and experiences.

Culture, Media, Sport & Food 2

W007

Families and Food in Hard Times: comparing food practices in low income families in Austerity Europe

Rebecca O'Connell,

(Thomas Coram Research Unit, UCL Institute of Education)

Food poverty is an urgent moral and social concern in Austerity Europe. However research examining the reasons for families' food poverty often neglects its multidimensional nature and the multi-layered specificities of social contexts and personal resources that help explain it. Our European Research Council funded study of Families and Food in Hard Times (2014-2019) has adopted a mixed methods embedded case study design to examine food practices in low income families in three European countries - the UK, Portugal and Norway – that were selected to provide for a contrast of contexts in relation to conditions of austerity. In this symposium, we discuss the affordances and challenges of the research strategy, present qualitative cases from the three countries and comparatively analyse some of the conditions in which families go without adequate food across the three countries.

Families and Food in Hard Times: comparing food practices in low income families in Austerity Europe

Julia Brannen

(Thomas Coram Research unit, UCL Institute of Education)

A contextualist approach sits between a nomothetic or generalising approach and an idiographic approach (Mjoset 2009). It is typically associated with the conduct of case studies and with qualitative methods. In cross-national research cases need to be situated in multiple layers of reality that require integration in the data analysis. Case-based research requires clarity in the dimensions for comparison e.g. a country, a school, an individual.

A contextualist comparative approach that focuses upon cases permits the researcher to move from understanding and interpretation towards explanation and generalisation (in a non statistical sense). As Ragin (1994) argues, it allows us to see 'how different causes combine in complex and sometimes contradictory ways to produce different outcomes' (p138). Thus we may examine instances of a social phenomenon and whether similar instances occur in different societies and contexts.

Families and Food in Hard Times, conducted in the UK, Portugal and Norway, examines how far, at the macro level, policies support (or not) those on low incomes; and whether low family income leads to food poverty and among which types of families. At the meso level, it examines how school meals mitigate the effects of food poverty for children and their individual experiences of school food. At the micro level, it examines the experiences of parents and children as they contend with constrained budgets.

Through this approach we hope to suggest how particular lives might be led if policies, economic and social conditions were to change and resources differently distributed (Brannen and Nilsen 2011).

Families, poverty and food in three European count

Rebecca O'Connell,

(Thomas Coram Research Unit, UCL Institute of Education)

Drawing on the Families and Food in Hard Times study (ERC grant agreement n° 337977), the final talk in this special session adopts a mixed methods approach to compare similar family types in the UK, Portugal and Norway and how they manage food on a low income. Focussing on the example of lone parent families, it draws on secondary analysis of international data (European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions) in addition to qualitative research with 133 families in each country. Across Europe, lone parent families are at greater risk of poverty and food poverty than dual parent families. However there are differences between countries in the prevalence and poverty rates of lone parent families, lone parents' labour force participation, the generosity of social benefits and the types of households they live in. Drawing on qualitative cases of lone parent families in each country, the talk examines the particularities of family circumstances – e.g. life course events (family breakdown, ill health) and local conditions (shops, transport, housing) - and how they constrain families' ability to eat in ways that meet needs for health and social participation in the context of global forces (markets, migration), national conditions (welfare and school food policies). It concludes by reflecting on the difference that the specificities of social contexts and social policies make to the extent and experience of food poverty and the utility of food as a lens with which to explore how families are faring in Austerity Europe.

Becoming and being ‘food poor’: mothers’ accounts of living in food poverty in the UK

Abigail Knight

(Thomas Coram Research Unit, UCL Institute of Education)

A relative and multi-dimensional concept, poverty is not a static nor homogenous state (Townsend, 1979). Families experiencing food poverty do so for a multitude of reasons and the effects of living in poverty on food and eating are varied. This paper draws on a cross-national study called ‘Families and Food in Hard Times’ (ERC grant agreement n° 337977) about food poverty as experienced by children aged 11-15 and their parents in the UK, Norway and Portugal. In-depth interview data were collected from 45 families in the UK and Portugal and 43 families in Norway.

In this talk we examine the interview accounts of mothers in the UK sample to explore the dynamics of poverty and food poverty. The accounts were elicited as part of a methodological approach that was concerned to understand mothers’ current situations and experiences in the context of their particular life trajectories and wider circumstances.

Analysing three cases we examine the conditions and life events that led to the mothers’ current constrained circumstances and influence how they manage in the present. These include the effects of migration, major life events and benefit changes as well as long-term challenges such as their own experiences of childhood poverty and disability. We also examine mothers’ current experiences of food poverty as a temporal process and the ways they manage to feed the family in the context of fluctuating incomes and needs. The paper thus contributes to literature on the dynamics of poverty and food poverty by considering the importance of different dimensions of time – historical, biographical and the routines and rhythms of everyday life - for food practices in low-income families.

Experiences of long and short term food poverty among Portuguese families

Monica Truninger,

(Instituto de Ciencias Sociais da Universidade de Lisboa)

Austerity policies in Portugal led to a wave of cuts on welfare benefits, tax rise and labour market reforms. Academic scholars identified strong evidence of the aggravation of social inequalities putting into question the widespread idea that the middle class suffered the most. Some studies showed that families already at risk and with children were particularly affected by the aggravation of poverty and material deprivation. Based on qualitative data (45 cases of low income families with children) collected under the project Families and Food Poverty (ERC grant agreement n° 337977), we draw on two cases that illustrate how austerity measures and the consequent transformation of the social-economic context influenced the family’s management of food practices and young people’s lives. The first case addresses a 2-children household whose middle class parents were affected by sudden unemployment, downgrading their social position and having to deal with material and symbolic violence experienced through their newfound situation as ‘poor’. The second case shows a persistent situation of food poverty where economically constrained periods coincide with the loss of employment. Through the analysis of these two cases we show existing family dynamics in situations of food poverty. The paper contributes to characterizing the contours of two different food poverty experiences: one that is sudden and more transitory, and another that shows persistent poverty. These translate different ways of coping with low food budgets and organizing everyday life food practices that affect parents/carers and children.

How ‘work as a route to welfare’ affects food poverty in Norway

Silje Elisabeth Skuland,

Child poverty has been increasing in Norway despite many and plentiful benefit schemes provided by the Norwegian welfare state. While reasons for this growth are complex, low work attachment has a significant impact. Meanwhile, work as a route to welfare has gained political momentum. As a result, enrolment in work-related activities has recently been applied as a criteria for receiving welfare benefits for the unemployed. Based on qualitative data (43 cases of low-income families with children) from the project, Families and Food in Hard Times (ERC grant agreement n° 337977), this paper discusses three cases that illustrate how social policies to get people into work affect food and eating in families. The first case involves a 5-child household, whose parents are enrolled in work praxis and prescribed activities (Norwegian course). The case shows what happens to food and eating when the family fails to fulfil the prescribed activity and benefits are withheld. The second case addresses a 3-child household whose unemployed single mother is enrolled in work praxis, discussing how the mother is dealing with the humiliation of working in a food store while managing a very tight food budget. The third case shows how food habits are managed in a 3-child family where the mother struggles to secure enough work hours in the health sector amidst demands for diplomas and maternity leave that significantly decrease the family income. All three cases address how current policies of work as route to welfare affect families’ food in material and social ways.

Families & Relationships 1

W709

'I'm not their parent but they have a right to know where they came from:' How identity-release gamete donors 'do' non-parenthood in relation to their donor-conceived offspring.

Leah Gilman,

(University of Manchester)

Recent work on the Sociology of the Family has often begun from Morgan's (1996) assertion that families are something which is 'done' rather than something which simply 'is.' Families are actively and continually reproduced through, often routine and taken-for-granted, practices. In this presentation, I draw on 24 in-depth interviews with UK identity-release sperm and egg donors to demonstrate how particular social contexts can also require people to, quite actively and carefully, not 'do family'. Whilst almost unanimously supportive of any donor offspring's right to contact them in the future, donor participants were keen to qualify the nature of this potential relationship in order to make clear that they were not really family to donor offspring, and certainly not their 'real' parent. Occupying an ambiguous and unscripted role in relation to their offspring, donors did this limiting work in highly creative ways, beyond simply screening out or ignoring their relationship to people conceived with their gametes. These discursive strategies included re-framing the donation as a gift or public act, emphasising their relationship to recipients or expressing their relationship to offspring indirectly. Using these examples, I demonstrate that not constructing kinship connections can be as active and creative a process as constructing them and that 'not really being family' or 'not being the real parent' also need to be continually reproduced through reference to family practices and discourses.

The Gendered Construction of Exemplary Middle-class identity: The Hegemony of Chenggong (success)

Kailing Xie,

(University of Warwick)

Despite the mounting pressure that China's well-educated urban professional women feel to get married, and the practical difficulties of fulfilling this social expectation (To, 2015), married family life remains a crucial aspect of obtaining personal happiness for these women. In this paper, using data collected through 42 semi-structured interviews with post-80s well-educated urban young professionals, I illustrate how their pursuit of personal success is shaped by growing up in a hyper materialistic culture (Croll, 2006), which drives them to live up to the imagined middle-class ideal of 'economic security and cultural superiority' (Miao, 2017). Since the happily married heterosexual family model based on free choice monogamous love has been interwoven into ordinary Chinese's perception of a happy and fulfilling life, for women particularly, their desire to secure the gendered exemplary middle-class identity through a happy marriage reflects the neoliberal self-fashioning permeating contemporary Chinese society. It exacerbates their determination to find an ideal spouse through individual efforts of cultivating an 'enterprising self' (Rose, 1992) and 'desiring self' (Rofel, 2007), which establishes their *suzhi* and middle-class superiority. Analysing their narratives, I firstly illustrate what future seems to be desirable to them, and secondly I uncover their gendered strategy of embodying this middle-class ideal. Furthermore, I discuss the political implications of their gendered constructions of subjectivity in contemporary Chinese society.

A cohort perspective on traditional gender stereotypes in countries of the former Czechoslovakia: A legacy of Soviet-style women's emancipation?

Alexandra Matejková,

(Institute for Sociology of SAS)

The paper focuses on transformations in perception of gender-based roles of women in post-communist countries using the example of Slovak and Czech Republics. Women's employment and women's emancipation affect not only the labour market but the family life as well. Europe, and the countries of the former Czechoslovakia in particular, have experienced several decades of high labor market participation of women. This was a result of an imposed duty of women aimed at increasing the wealth of the countries not of a choice directed at gaining economic independence. During communism, women in the former Czechoslovakia grew up in a situation where a high labor market participation of women and a two-career family was the norm. The emancipation of women was expressed not as a right to work but as a 'duty to work'. Becoming a housewife was not a real option. Against this background, we ask whether women socialized during communism have a different view on their gender roles and careers than women who grew up after its demise and whether this gap is diminishing 30 years after the fall of the Iron curtain. Our results, based on data from four waves of the European Values Survey, point out an interesting feature of the post-communist societies of the former Czechoslovakia – a turn to traditional values. Slovak and Czech women seem still fascinated by their traditional roles of a wife and a mother and have ambiguous attitudes towards their occupation and professional careers.

Families & Relationships 2

W727

A Table for One: the Homosexual Single and the Absence of Romantic Love

*Dr Aliraza Javaid,
(University of East London)*

I attempt to make sense of the single, often stigmatizing, identity that is socially and interactionally accomplished. I use the metaphor, 'A Table for One' borrowed from Lahad (2017), to metaphorically signify the sheer loneliness, solitude and invisibility that some single homosexuals embody in the midst of individualism and secularization. It refers to the position that singles either take up or do not take up and matters regarding their legitimacy and (in)visibility in public life. We have entered a social world that is occupied by digital apps that make the arrangement of casual sexual encounters so much more easier and fluid; the formulation of these 'digital worlds' seemingly leave romantic love for gay singles unproblematic and unquestionable. In this paper, I attempt to offer some critical engagement of the homosexual single, situated in a confused world where 'offline/online' becomes blurred.

Equality, Identity and Kinship in Lesbian Led Donor Conceived Families

*Sheila Quaid, n/a
(University of Sunderland)*

This research explored underlying complexities in creation of lesbian led families. The respondents embarked upon a new form of motherhood. Thus, a process of change, flux and fluidity began. I found that impactful changes are brought to collective understandings of family and kinship by new transgressive developments in family formation. Lesbian parental couples, for example potentially disrupt normative heterosexual meanings of family, parenting and gender. Respondents could potentially subvert the meaning of motherhood and gendered parental identities. The problems they faced were both cultural and structural. These processes were underpinned with the material realities of class differences. Also, differences of cultural capital and access to social and economic resources shape this experience and deep in the cultural definers of self lies constructions of race and ethnicity. Evidence from this study revealed a firm base of egalitarian ideals amongst respondents. Other definers of identity caused contradictions and tensions. These included culture, disability, ethnicity, class, gender and religious background. Intersections of identities in their negotiated families presented potential sources of tension for the respondents. Through detailed considerations, their decision making, they negotiated their own maternal and parental identities. My study revealed the complexity of intersectionality in their negotiated families. These issues presented sources of tension for the respondents. This research included detailed accounts of their internal and external struggles to resolve their own maternal and parental identities in relation to class and other definers.

Rethinking Social Hierarchies in Intimate and Family Lives: A Qualitative Study of Chinese Lalas' Paths to Family Formation

*Iris Po Yee Lo,
(Department of Sociology, The University of Oxford)*

This study examines the processes of family formation among Chinese non-heterosexual women, who are commonly known as lalas, in China. By drawing from semi-structured interviews with 35 lala-identified women in Beijing, where homosexuality remains heavily stigmatized, this study reveals how lalas' decisions to conform to or challenge social hierarchies affect their conception and formation of families in various ways.

On individual level, the majority of informants faced great difficulties in coming out and disclosing their intimate relationships due to their stigmatized identity as sexual minority women. On familial level, since families of origin and the government continue to treat heterosexual marriage as the only respectable form of family life in China, informants reported that it was very difficult to maintain stable relationships and gain social recognition even though some of them had registered same-sex marriage outside China. On community level, informants who had children through the use of assisted reproductive technology formed their own social groups and shared information about childbearing to resist inequalities faced by lala families. The findings also exposed structures of cross-cutting inequality associated with lalas' different social locations, including their gender, class, and age, which impacted on their freedom to build the family they wanted.

The study signifies the first key step to provide empirical evidence of lalas' experiences of family formation in China. It aims to challenge social hierarchies, especially those related to gender and sexuality and those differentiating 'normal' families from 'abnormal' ones, which are embedded within and outside intimate and family lives.

Lifecourse 1 W003

The Impact of Contextual Effects on Offending Trajectories: Exploring Criminal Careers Through Social and Political Change

Stephen Farrall, Emily Gray and Phil Jones
(Univ of Sheffield)

Research on the causes and correlates of offending had been a key preoccupation of sociologists, psychologists and criminologist for around a century. Criminal careers research has endeavoured to unpick why an individual starts offending, why they continue and why they might cease offending. Scholarship has percolated into criminal justice interventions which have sought to deter individuals from becoming involved in crime; that have diverted people towards more successful sentences and to assist rehabilitation. The individual 'offender' has been the main focal point of such research, although scholars have recently sought to 'locate' the individual in wider relational structures (such as families, schools and neighbourhoods). Using data from the British 1970 Birth Cohort Study (BSC70), we develop a model that incorporates individuals, families and schools, but which tries to take account of national-level economic policies (which were driven by political ideas and which had social consequences). Employing a longitudinal lens, we track the BSC70 sample from childhood to adulthood through a period of dramatic industrial and social change in the UK during the early-1980s. Our paper suggests that processes of economic restructuring were a key causal factor in offending during this period. This broader framework also emphasises the importance of considering political and economic forces in criminal careers and related research.

Transport deprivation, access to a car and experiences of Loneliness among older Europeans in Rural Areas

Stefanie Doebler
(University of Liverpool)

Loneliness poses a serious health and mortality risk to older people. The majority of the literature on loneliness at older ages thus far has focused on social contact, mainly family networks. Some studies looked at the role of wealth in reducing loneliness, but there is a dearth of literature on transport deprivation and how access to transport can reduce experiences of loneliness among older people, especially in rural and remote areas. This paper examines the role of transport deprivation (e.g. not having access to a car in rural areas) as a predictor of loneliness experiences of older people living in rural areas. The analysis is based on statistical analyses of European survey data such as the Survey of Health and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) and its UK equivalent, ELSA. The paper argues that having access to transport, e.g. a car, and being affluent reduce older peoples' likelihood of experiencing loneliness by facilitating access to friends who live further away than walking distance and by facilitating participation in social activities such as volunteering. The author thus hypothesizes a mediation effect: Being transport deprived is a cause for loneliness through limiting access to friends and social activities. The car as a means of transport helps many older people who live in rural and remote areas retain friendship contacts, a social life and their personal independence and autonomy.

Starting out in social care: young adults' experiences of gendered work in Teesside

Duncan Fisher,
(Teesside University)

Adult social care in the UK is beset by myriad workforce issues. One of these is a significant, continuing labour shortage, and in response the sector needs to do more to attract and retain underrepresented groups, such as young people. Very few studies have examined young adults' involvement in this heavily gendered sector, or how their experiences can contribute to understanding of the UK welfare state and care regimes. This paper draws on semi-structured interview data that followed young adults on a six-week care training course in Teesside, north-east England, to subsequent employment within the care sector. Influenced by Skeggs' (1997) seminal work on class, gender and care, the paper also draws on literature around youth transitions and the sociology of Teesside. The sectoral approach enables comparison with other low-paid service work, and illuminates the gender, class and spatial specificities of social care work for young adults in this locale. Additionally, it presents a platform to consider questions around young people's motivations, planning, and non-paid work responsibilities, and how they interlink with structural opportunities and constraints. This paper also contributes to understanding of the continuing effects of austerity policies, as manifested through cuts to social care provision, and the disproportionately negative impact of austerity on women and young people.

Methodological Innovations 1

W008

New (or old?) principles of causal analysis: identification via "directed acyclic graphs" and "minimal/sufficient sets"

David Bartram

(University of Leicester)

Sociologists who use quantitative analysis often neglect to explain coherently why particular control variables should be included in their models. One commonly sees notions of a "standard set" of controls, or the "usual suspects", etc. These notions are not coherent and can easily lead to results that are biased, sometimes quite substantially.

This paper reiterates some core principles for making effective decisions of this sort. The specific contribution is to present a framework (the "causal revolution", e.g. Pearl 2018) unfamiliar to most sociologists (though well established in epidemiology), and to show how it can be put into practice for empirical analysis of causal questions. In simplified form, the core principles are: control for confounding variables, and *do not* control for intervening variables or colliders. The more comprehensive approach uses "directed acyclic graphs" (DAGs) to discern models that meet a minimum/efficiency criterion for identification of causal effects.

The paper demonstrates this mode of analysis via a stylized investigation of the effect of unemployment on happiness. Most researchers would include all "key determinants" of happiness as controls for this purpose. One such determinant is income – but income is an intervening variable in the path from unemployment to happiness, and including it leads to substantial bias. Other commonly-used variables are simply unnecessary, e.g. religiosity and sex. From this perspective, identifying the effect of unemployment on happiness requires controlling only for age and education; a "small" model is evidently preferable to a more complex one in this instance.

Using Photovoice with Working-Class Men: Affordances, Contradictions and Limits to Reflexivity

*Paul Simpson, Dr Mike Richards
(Edge Hill University)*

Photovoice, which involves participant-generated images, has grown steadily in popularity in social and health-related research since the late 1990s. It has commonly been situated within participatory action research (PAR), which itself involves community groups in studies of the socio-economic, political and cultural issues affecting/constraining them. Much photovoice-based research (within PAR) has been claimed as empowering for disadvantaged participants and, consequently, has neglected a more critical appreciation of the method. Based on experience of photovoice (though not within a PAR strategy) deployed with focus groups of disadvantaged men representing their health/well-being practices in Northwest England (N=20 and based on over 100 images), we contribute a more balanced evaluation of its possibilities. We begin by recognising advantages of the method as identified in the literature and add some of our own concerning its capabilities for illuminating the hidden emotional reflexivity of working-class men, their socio-political criticism and health-seeking behaviours. Stereotypically such practices are seen as the opposite of brute working-class masculinity. However, we focus more on the structural-hierarchical and discursive-ideological limits to reflexivity and critique concerning men's understandings of class and food/diet, which also indicate limits to the empowering potential of the method and the contradictory knowledge it can produce.

Probabilistic methods for combining traditional and social media migration data

*Arkadiusz Wisniowski, Guy Abel, Dilek Yildiz
(University of Manchester)*

Official migration statistics are developed and published by national offices of statistics and collated by international organisations. These statistics are based on rigorous internationally harmonised principles, but they come with a considerable time lag. New data sources offer opportunities to complement traditional sources for migration statistics. In particular, the availability of high quantities of individual geo-located data from social media has opened new opportunities. In this research, we develop probabilistic methods to combine traditional and social media bilateral migration data to estimate timelier and potentially more accurate migration statistics.

A Multilevel Dynamic Approach in Scientific Networks

*Alejandro Espinosa,
(The University of Manchester)*

Social Network Analysis is one of the approaches used to analyse scientific networks. However, in recent years one of the areas highly developed in empirical studies is the multilevel approach. An approach that allows understanding and explaining some of the connections within and between scientists. In this presentation, I will explore three different typologies that synthesise this approach. Also, I will use a case study to exemplify each of the typologies using a dynamic scientific network in a statistical network model. The main conclusion is that dimensions such as temporality, actions, context and local relation structures in networks can represent some of the strategies that scientists use to create their scientific networks in a multilevel approach.

Race, Ethnicity & Migration 1 W011

Populism and the mainstreaming of the far right

*Aurelien Mondon, Katy Brown, Aaron Winter
(University of Bath)*

Much has been written recently about populism, the rise of the far right and their growing impact on mainstream politics. While the campaign and election of Trump was the most covered event, the strong performance of the Freedom Party in Austria, the Front National in France, the Lega in Italy and the victory of Brexit in the UK amongst others have made such discussions ubiquitous. Countless books and articles have focused on the ways in which the discourse of parties and movements once considered toxic has evolved or been adapted. While the concepts of 'mainstream' and 'mainstreaming' have become commonly used, their definition has been elusive, or rather evaded by scholars and experts on the topic. This is partly due to the fact that defining the mainstream is itself a challenge.

In this paper, we aim to provide a comprehensive framework to understand the mainstreaming of the far right by moving beyond electoral politics. Key to our approach is a particular focus on discourse, moving away from electoral politics qua politics, towards a more holistic approach to politics, although one which is harder to quantify and thus less appealing to traditional and mainstream political science, punditry and the media in general.

Racism in the name of liberalism: the post racial and the mainstreaming of the far right

*Aurelien Mondon, Aaron Winter
(University of Bath
University of East London (Aaron Winter))*

In the past decade, we have seen the rise and fall of post-racial thinking, which celebrates the alleged historical overcoming of racism in favour of an enlightened egalitarian and colourblind approach. This discourse or narrative often portrays racism as a thing of the past, illiberal or extreme, with fascists and the far right being its most obvious representatives. In addition to overdetermining how successfully western societies fought racism, it ignores continuing institutional racism, racial inequality and discrimination. In this paper, we argue that the self-righteous rejection on illiberal racist articulations allows for the ignoring and strengthening of what we term liberal articulations of racism, based on culture and the apparent illiberal and unenlightened values and behaviour of the 'other' (most notably Islam and Muslims). To do this, we build on our work on liberal and illiberal articulations of Islamophobia (Mondon and Winter 2017), and examine how liberal racism has been enabled by the post-racial and allowed for the legitimisation, normalisation and mainstreaming of racism and the reconstructed far right. To illuminate our argument, this paper will discuss examples from the US, the UK and France.

When Eurosceptics Become Europhiles: Far-Right Opposition to Turkish Involvement in the European Union

*Katy Brown,
(University of Bath)*

Turkey's involvement in the European Union has long provoked controversy among Europe's elites, particularly regarding its prospective accession. Recently, in the context of the so-called 'migrant crisis', coupled with the mainstreaming of Islamophobia and rising Euroscepticism, the issue of Turkey has acquired renewed significance in European political debate. For example, the 2016 EU-Turkey Statement to reduce the number of refugees reaching Europe proved highly contentious and Turkish accession featured heavily in the 'Brexit' campaign, with Nigel Farage declaring that 'Turkey in means Britain out'. While many scholars have linked hostility towards Turkey with the desired construction of a supra-national European identity, few studies have noted the role it plays in the discourse of parties that explicitly reject the EU. Adopting a mixed-methods approach to Critical Discourse Studies, combining the Discourse-Historical Approach with elements of Discourse Theory and Corpus Linguistics, this paper seeks to investigate the contemporary construction of Turkey as a dangerous 'other' by far-right parties in the United Kingdom (UKIP) and France (FN/RN). Drawing on theories of Orientalism and Islamophobia, it exposes the contradiction inherent in the strongly Eurosceptic positions adopted by these parties, while simultaneously rejecting Turkish involvement based on its supposed 'non-Europeaness'. As such, in pursuit of their racist agendas to reinforce dualistic divisions between East and West, these parties become defenders of Europe while at the same time undermining the supra-national EU project.

Race, Ethnicity & Migration 2

W011

There is not a straightforward way to be Mapuche and middle-class: experiences of social mobility of Mapuche indigenous people in Chile
denisse sepulveda,

(The university of Manchester)

This article focusses on Bourdieu's notion of 'fish out of water' in relation to the experience of upward social mobility of the Mapuche indigenous people in Chile and how they negotiate their class and indigenous identities during university period and later at work. This article draws on 40 life history interviews, focusing on Mapuche people, who are the first generation attending university and who were living in the cities of Santiago and Temuco at the moment of the interviews. The findings suggest that class and ethnic identity are complexly entangled, because the experience of upward social mobility represented a challenge to the respondents' sense of their class position and identity, as they had to manage social relationships and identities between their social class of origin and their class of destination. But the experience of upward social mobility also provided a challenge to respondents' ethnic identities, as they had to manage social relations and indigenous identity claims across their social origins and destinations. Therefore, middle-classness was sometimes perceived - by the respondents' social connections, but also sometimes by themselves - as being problematically connected with their Mapuche identity.

Hierarchies of national belonging: Unpicking white middle-class constructions of belonging in northeast London

Amy Clarke,

(Queen Mary University of London)

Belonging has long been a concept of interest to social scientists and it is increasingly recognised that belonging divides hierarchically and is not merely a question of either/or. The existence of hierarchies of belonging is documented from the perspective of ethnically minoritised and migrant groups, however, what characterises, produces and underpins these hierarchies is largely unaddressed within this literature. Expanding on existing work, this paper, based on in-depth qualitative interviews with white British middle-class people in the northeast suburbs of London, identifies three constructions of belonging within white British narratives of integration, belonging and nationhood. Although not always recognised as hierarchical, I argue that in their differing connections to whiteness, as well as notions of authenticity, the elucidation of these different constructions of belonging helps to explain the exclusion from a full sense of national belonging described by Britons of colour. In focusing on the production and maintenance of hierarchies of belonging by relatively privileged groups, the paper provides new empirical insight into the power-laden politics of belonging in Britain and makes an important conceptual contribution to research on belonging.

The Racial Politics of Cultural Capital: Perspectives from the Black Middle Classes in a London Comprehensive

Derron Wallace,

(Brandeis University)

Based on 27 in-depth and three focus group interviews with Black middle class young people and their parents, this article highlights the strategic deployment of Black cultural capital to challenge white hegemony in school curricula in a large state comprehensive in South London. The findings underscore the racial politics of cultural capital. Such perspectives are often missing in traditional class analyses that prioritise the study of economic inequality but offers little, if any, sustained consideration of the influence of race on the formation and distribution of cultural capital in an increasingly diverse society. To limit the racial blindspots of traditional class analyses, this article complements a new wave of scholarship in cultural sociology both nationally and internationally that seeks to underscore the analytical purchase of a raced class analysis for understanding the nuances of inequality and the production of racialised capitals in schools and society.

Race, Ethnicity & Migration 3 **W525**

The adventurers?: Standing in the way of control

Sarah Walker,

(Goldsmiths, University of London)

The narratives of child protection and immigration law at force in the US and Europe reinforce the notion of these states as sources of protection and that any problems stem from outside the state boundaries, revealing how the discursive practices in migration control rely on and perpetuate hierarchies of age, nation and culture. In this discourse, the role of immigration controls in producing vulnerability or as the source of the problem itself is not acknowledged. Yet, as other scholars contend, hierarchies of mobility and belonging are produced by migration regimes, themselves based on racialised colonial histories. Adopting a mobility framework, and drawing upon data captured through multi-modal ethnography with separated young people in Italy, this paper will critically explore how separated young people resist or negotiate what Susan Coutin refers to as 'spaces of nonexistence', to challenge the forms of (im)mobility placed upon them and contest hierarchies of belonging to make their own space. It examines their secondary migration tactics within Italy as mechanisms of negotiating the migration regime and resisting

immobility, temporal suspense and the racialisation of their bodies, thus contesting inequalities they are subject to through the assertion of their subjectivity. Through examining the subject positions of young people and the notion of 'adventurers', the paper address issues of agency and temporality in young people's lives through autonomy of migration

Challenging the era of hidden inequality: The emergence of Everyday Cosmopolitanism

On Hee Choi, On Hee Choi
(University of Bristol)

The longitudinal study explores how international students as sojourners challenge diverse modes of inequality they encounter in a foreign context with the emerging sense of everyday cosmopolitanism. International students are under the influence of institutionalised cosmopolitanism imbued in higher education curriculum and social media platforms which spark the sense of belonging to a more extensive global community. Such transnational spaces in the era of globalisation are unbound to locality, but open to diversity in culture, race and religion. In reality, however, an abstract and ideal cosmopolitanism is diversely interpreted according to individual dispositions as well as contextuality. Instead of initial cosmopolitan aspirations, international students have developed into modified cosmopolitanism focusing on their everyday lived experiences.

In this sense, this study deals with a wide range of existing discourse about cosmopolitanism from Nussbaum (1994) and Appiah (1996) to the currently discussed everyday cosmopolitanism. I am most interested in linking the recent literature to international students' lived experiences as a case of 'cosmopolitanism below' (Kurasawa 2004; Appadurai 2011).

This presentation will portray changes in international students' perceptions of cosmopolitanism and their own identification as cosmopolitan through multimodal data collected for two years. The study's findings show that international students produce their own third space unfettered to the institutionalised idealism by practicing individualised cosmopolitanism. This study will also address how international students deal with invisible inequality over physical and digital space through consistent efforts to integrate with others in a globalised society.

Rights, Violence & Crime

W004

From culturalist to structuralist perspective for understanding and challenging violence against women

Emmaleena Kakela,
(University of Strathclyde)

Scholars and international actors have increasingly drawn attention to the violence which characterises women's migration journeys. In the public debate, cultural manifestations of gender-based violence have not only been framed as a cause of migration, but also as a barrier for integration. In the context of increasing global instability and Western fortress mentality, representations of violence against women have become increasingly employed as a discursive tool to reproduce the savagery of the 'Third World' and to justify anti-immigration sentiments. This paper argues that by disregarding the multiple forms of domination which intersect in the lives of women, culturalist explanations fail to fully recognise the sociological complexity of violence against women. By reflecting migrant women's experiences of departure, displacement and resettlement in Scotland, this paper advocates for locating violence against women in the context of intersecting welfare inequalities. In efforts to challenge the simplistic representations of women's journeys from the patriarchal South to emancipatory West, this paper traces the socio-economic conditions which perpetuate trauma in the lives of displaced women. Women's experience of the UK asylum system forces them to re-evaluate and re-negotiate their culture and sense of self in a context which frames them simultaneously as a victim and as a threat. Through tracing women's experiences of violence both before and after migration, this paper illuminates how, regardless of the surrounding culture, women's vulnerability to violence becomes harnessed as a form of control over not only women's sexualities, but also their social and economic mobilities.

Resisting rape kit backlogs: Victim rights, and the bureaucratization of anti-rape activism

Andrea Quinlan
(University of Waterloo)

News of hundreds of thousands of untested sexual assault kits in police storage facilities and forensic labs across the United States has sparked public interest in sexual assault forensics and criminal justice responses to sexual assault. Non-profit victim rights organizations have taken a leading role in the fight for new legislation and increased funding to reduce rape kit backlogs across the country. This paper examines the rise of non-profit activism around rape kit backlogs, and considers how some prominent victim rights organizations have narrowly framed rape kit backlogs as threats to public safety, justice, and healing for victims of crime. Situated in the sociology of technology and feminist

technoscience studies, the paper explores how this framing reflects a broader faith in science, technology, and the forensic industry to uphold victims' rights. Drawing on data from thirty qualitative interviews with rape crisis advocates, law enforcement, and hospital staff in New York and California, as well as a range of unobtrusive data, the paper examines the non-profit industrial complex behind the rape kit backlog movement and its role in the current narrowing of critical dialogues about criminal justice responses to sexual assault. This paper sets these contemporary trends against a historical backdrop of the bureaucratization of anti-rape activism and considers possible implications for future anti-violence activism.

An analytical study of the phenomenon; Domestic Violence against women in the region of South Punjab Pakistan

Farhat Zafar, Sidra Kiran

(The Women University Multan, Pakistan)

This research investigates the women domestic violence against women in the region of South Punjab Pakistan. Domestic violence is directed mostly against women and girls, due to the belief of the executors that the victim has brought dishonor upon the family. Domestic violence has been researched widely in Pakistan and abroad. Multan (South Punjab) is selected as universe. Population of universe consists on its rural areas. The main objectives of research would be to explore the causes, impact and policy measures to control domestic violence against women. However, this study look into the issues from an academic perspective. It explore the causes of domestic violence against women in the name of honor and examine influences of this practice on the families of those women who have been victimized of domestic violence. This research is qualitative in nature and carried out in rural areas of Multan by using a purposive sampling method. Interviews is conducted from the families of the victims of honor killing. The data is analyzed by using thematic analysis. The sample size depend on the availability of domestic violence cases. This study is expected to bring forth rich data on the phenomenon of which domestic violence be help to build on the existing literature on this issue especially from the Pakistani perspective.

Social Divisions / Social Identities

W110

Young women's feminist activism and the politics of difference: 'I was instinctively aware that all of those girls were being called names'

Grainne McMahon,

(University of Huddersfield)

This paper is based upon biographical and 'expert' interview data collected with 18-25-year-old feminist activists, and data collected from an ethnography of online feminist spaces, street activism and feminist events, as a part of a Europe-wide study on young people's political participation. Drawing upon Iris Marion Young's ideas of the 'politics of group difference', the paper argues that young feminist activists reject traditional and patriarchal political structures and engage instead with fair, open and inclusive political spaces that foreground women's needs, rights and interests. By making political claims 'asserted from the specificity of social group position' (Young, 2000, 82), young feminists actively challenge relational structures of power and structural inequality and celebrate 'cultural and experiential specificity' (160) through grassroots political activism that is explicitly gendered. This activism is biographically relevant, politically purposeful and focused upon the key cornerstones of feminist activism of consciousness-raising, 'speaking bitterness', and building coalitions. Considered alongside global feminist movements such as #MeToo and #TimesUp, and their impacts, the paper suggests that contemporary grassroots feminist movements, across a range of spaces and contexts, continue to have the crucial capacity to unsettle structural injustice through activism that is based on group difference and an explicit naming of gender inequality and injustice.

'There are no girls on the internet', Gender performances in Advice Animal memes

Sian Brooke, Sian Brooke

(University of Oxford)

Online anonymous forums are valued as spaces of freedom which facilitate open expressions of identity. Advice Animals are a particularly prevalent genre of meme, popularising the format of a captioned image that is now synonymous with the term (Massanari, 2015b; Milner, 2016; Wiggins & Bowers, 2015). Research in this area has addressed the construction of insider and outsider in pseudonymous spaces (See Massanari, 2015b, 2017; Nakamura, 2013), but the shared formation of gender and associated social hierarchies is little studied. I unmask how memes perpetuate existing gender power structures in spaces where users are only known by pseudonyms. In contributing to the investigation of gendered collective identity, I ask: What work do highly gendered performances and representations do in pseudonymous spaces? I apply qualitative visual and textual analysis of content and comments surrounding Advice Animal memes. This shows the gendered nature of memes and how they can

perpetuate oppressive power structures. Memes show the potency of normative gender roles and associated power structures. Gender power structures are reproduced by performances of gender through jokes, humour, and memes, even on pseudonymous sites. A feminist approach to online media requires a lens that accounts for expressions of power.

With Reddit as the site of study, the focus is on a subcommunity dedicated to sharing and creating Advice Animal memes (*r/AdviceAnimals*). Overall the study examines the uneven distribution of power in representations of gender and feminists. The study finds that while women are highly sexualised, obsessive, and clingy, male characters are a default central character, used to express non-specific ideals of behaviour. As feminists, men are portrayed as legitimate, whilst women-feminists are epitomised as hypocritical, demanding, “Nazis”. The analysis of memes highlights the difficulties for equality of representation in anonymous and pseudonymous spaces. The main contribution of the study is highlighting the gendered nature of memes, and call attention to the unequal representation in pseudonymous space.

Challenging European constructions of the gendered ‘Gypsy Other’: Epistemic injustices, feminist complicities, and decolonial futures

Marta Kowalewska,
(University of Edinburgh)

Antigypsyism is a widespread, complex, deeply embedded, and gendered phenomenon that operates structurally and systematically throughout contemporary Europe (Alliance Against Antigypsyism 2017). The root of antigypsyism lies in how Roma have been socially, historically, and discursively constructed as 'Other', as unwanted and invisible except within the distorted, and gendered, ideas and stereotypes of 'Roma' and 'gypsy' that exist in the European imaginary (Kóczé & Trehan 2009; Clark 2004). The 'Other' is produced through knowledge, rather than through a failure of knowledge (Ahmed 2000).

Through theoretical analysis, I explore how the crux of antigypsyism lies in how hegemonic knowledge – including hegemonic feminist knowledge – is (re)produced to maintain the distorted image of the gendered 'Gypsy Other'. I posit that Romani agency and subjectivities, and particularly the vulnerabilities and practices of resistance of Romani women and feminists, are ignored and repressed through such discursive practices. I explore the concepts of complicity and resistance, rooted in decolonial feminist theories and methodologies (following Brooks 2015), as a way of critically challenging these hegemonic epistemic practices and injustices.

Social Divisions / Social Identities

W828

Nudges and neoliberalism. A micropolitical sociology of behavioural interventions

Nick Fox, Elise Klein
(University of huddersfield)

Behavioural approaches are used increasingly as a means to effect government policy. These interventions aim to shape or 'nudge' choices made by members of the public, by applying incentives to encourage, or employing punitive measures to enforce, desired behaviours. While these approaches have been criticised from political science perspectives, in this paper we apply an innovative mode of analysis of behavioural policy approaches founded in a new materialist ontology of affects, assemblages and capacities. This perspective enables us to explore the micropolitical impact of these interventions on those who are their subjects, and also upon the wider sociocultural contexts within which they have been implemented.

We examine two different behavioural interventions: the use of vouchers in the UK to incentivise new mothers to breastfeed their infants (a practice associated with improved health outcomes in both childhood and later life), and cashless debit card (CDC) technologies used in Australia to limit welfare recipients' spending on alcohol, drugs and gambling. In each case, we employ a materialist methodology to analyse precisely what these interventions do, and what (in)capacities they produce in their targeted groups.

We conclude that the use of behavioural interventions to effect policy objectives may have significant negative impacts on the well-being of their immediate targets and upon wider communities. Neither of these cases represent benign 'nudges', but rather place target individuals in circumstances that they would not have chosen and may pose threats to physical, social or economic well-being.

Borrowed identities: class(ification), inequality, and the role of credit-debt in class struggle and configuration

Matthew Sparkes,
(University of Cambridge)

Personal credit is ubiquitous in contemporary Britain. Research has revealed how austerity, precarious and flexible work, and stagnating incomes are forcing lower-income households to take on unsecured debt to meet essential consumption. Yet statistical data highlights that the proportion of British households with unsecured debt is higher in middle-to-upper-middle income groups, who also have larger unsecured debts as a proportion of household income. This presentation applies the class scheme of Bourdieu developed by cultural class analysis to provide significant insights into the high proportion of debt held by those with modest incomes. Drawing on interviews with 21 individuals managing problem debt, I will detail how class inequality emerges through affective states that include anxiety and feelings of deficit; and show how these experiences motivate participants to rely on debt to consume cultural goods in a struggle against their class position, with the intention of enhancing how they are perceived by others. I further detail how these processes entangle individuals into complex liens of debt - which can lead to over-indebtedness, crisis, dispossession and financial expropriation. These findings help illustrate how investigating credit-debt, states of indebtedness, and financial capitalism more broadly, can better inform understandings of class inequality, exploitation and struggle.

Sociology of Education A **W823**

Educational Inequalities in Northern Ireland: an in-depth study of three GCSE cohorts

Erin Early,
(Queen's University Belfast)

Educational inequalities across social groups remain at the forefront in contemporary society across the UK. In Northern Ireland, educational attainment differences are apparent across gender, socio-economic background and religion. To explore these differences in more depth, this study uses the first dataset in Northern Ireland to combine the School Census, School Leavers Survey and Census (2011) to explore GCSE attainment across three Year 12 cohorts (2011-2013). GCSE attainment is explored according to gender, religion and socio-economic status to illustrate the continuous inequalities apparent in educational attainment accordingly. This provides an opportunity to determine the varying level of influence the named socio-demographic factors have on GCSE attainment across the different school structures of grammar and non-grammar schools. This presentation will discuss data analytics of the study including cohort sizes, attainment measures, socio-demographic measures and the multilevel modelling construction and execution. The results from the multilevel analysis will be presented to discuss attainment inequalities that remain across different social groups according to gender, socio-economic background and religion. This analysis allows the relative effect of each socio-demographic to be considered both individually and collectively. The direction and magnitude of each effect will be determined to conclude if there is consistency across cohorts in the factors resulting in the greatest attainment disparities between pupils at GCSE level. Findings will be reflected upon to explore whether these results support wider UK trends in GCSE attainment, to determine if there is consistency in educational inequalities across the UK.

The over-representation of grammar school pupils at prestigious UK universities

Queralt Capsada-Munsech, Vikki Boliver
(Durham University)

Recent empirical research suggests that pupils from more advantaged social class backgrounds and certain ethnic minority groups continue to be overrepresented in grammar schools in England (Cribb et al., 2013). Those educated in grammar schools are among the highest achievers nationally at GCSE, but this appears to be due to the academic and social selectivity rather than to any 'school quality' effect (Gorard and Siddiqui, 2018). Similarly, the disproportionately high rates at which grammar school pupils attend prestigious UK universities is explained by prior attainment and social background characteristics, rather than being a direct effect of school type (Sullivan et al., 2014). However, this latter evidence presenting a null effect of grammar school attendance on access to prestigious UK universities relies on data for those who came of university-age towards the end of the 1980s, immediately prior to the second-wave of higher education expansion and the subsequent proliferation of university league tables (Boliver, 2011, 2015). This paper draws on data for much more recent cohorts who came of university-age in a context of a 50% higher education rate and a highly prestige-stratified university system, in which the previous null grammar school effect might now be relevant. Using NPD and HESA data, we analyse the contemporary impact of attending a grammar school on access to a prestigious UK university, controlling for pupils' prior attainment and social background characteristics. We also explore how school type, prior attainment and social background characteristics interact so to establish who benefits most from grammar school attendance.

'Here we are all the same': Subjectivity construction and plural habitus in socially diverse schools

Manuela Mendoza,
(UCL - Institute of Education)

Drawing on a global context of tension between national ideologies driven by democratic values and the challenges posed by increasing levels of social diversity, the paper reflects on the ways social diversity in a school may shape particular subjective dispositions to otherness on students and parents. The paper discusses literature around school mix (the school's social diversity) and school mixing (the interactions between students/parents from different backgrounds), and their possible relationship with the development of democratic and inclusive attitudes. Studies addressing the possible effects of school mix on democratic learning argue that both inclusive and exclusionary dispositions may emerge depending on the form heterogeneity takes, particularly depending on whether there is school mixing or not. Based on Pierre Bourdieu's concept of habitus or dispositions and further interpretations of its multi-layered or plural configuration (e.g. Decoteau, 2016; Lahire, 2003), the paper outlines an analytical sociological framework to conceptualise the possibilities for subjectivity to change and, eventually, for inclusive dispositions to emerge through the experience of social difference. This discussion will be illustrated by the case under study in an ethnographically oriented research about friendship in socially diverse schools: the Chilean educational system. Chile is a key country to observe not only an exceptional socioeconomic educational segregation (the most segregated among OECD countries) but also an unusual process of educational reforms attempting to promote inclusion and diversity of school populations, which renders it a privileged lab scenario to explore potentialities and limitations to take advantage of such a diversity.

Sociology of Education B **W002**

Technocratic and sociological approaches towards reform in higher education: A discourse analysis of a key concept.

Elisabeth Simbüerger
(University of Valparaíso)

From the Humboldt reform, via Córdoba, 1968, Bologna, new public management and more recent public funding cuts in universities all over the world, reforms are a common phenomenon in the field of education and higher education studies. Yet, hardly every the notion of reform is analysed. This paper examines the epistemological underpinnings of the concept of reform by means of a two-fold methodology. First of all, we analysed the varied meanings of the concept of reform and similar terms (e.g. 'restructuring') in the literature of higher education research. Thereafter, we carried out qualitative interviews with 15 international scholars in the field of higher education research with regard to their respective conceptualisations of reform.

By means of critical discourse analysis, we identified a technocratic and a sociological approach towards reform. The technocratic approach frames higher education as an object of study that can only be studied and discussed by technical experts. Besides, higher education is presented as if it was a non-ideological space outside of normative discussions. The sociological approach towards reform recognises that the university is part of society and as such a political space and subject of ideological dispute. Our preliminary analysis demonstrates the predominance of the technocratic discourse towards reform, particularly in the literature analysis. The results allow us to embark on a discussion about the epistemological transformation of the field of higher education research.

Parent Choice Discourses in Irish Primary School Patronage Policy Reform: How traditional and cultural legacies influence outcomes.

Michelle Starr, Michelle Starr
(University of Limerick)

School choice is a central tenet of education policy internationally, since the 1980's, for creating better schools via competition and equitable school systems via providing the opportunity for all parents to choose (Chubb and Moe 1990; Moe 1994; Bosseti 2004). Conversely, a large body of scholarship challenges school choice and point to influencing factors imbued in parents' identity and values that are intertwined in their prospects for economic and social success and create a stratified school system (Ball, 2002; Ball & Vincent 2001; OECD 1994; Bloomfield Cucchiarra & McNamara Horvat 2014).

In the Irish context, parent choice is a contemporary policy practice implemented in education policy to reform the primary school patronage system. It is recognised that the present denominational Irish primary school system that has 90 per cent of schools under Catholic patronage requires reforming to meet the needs of a more diverse Irish society (DES 2013). Choice and diversity discourses facilitate parent choice practice in Irish education policy reform, but also creates a divisiveness between diversity discourses that represent progressive reform and traditional schooling discourses.

This study explores parent choice practice in patronage policy for reforming the Irish primary school system. Findings from parent interviews about their primary school decision-making processes, using a Foucauldian influenced analysis approach shows that traditional cultural knowledge of choice of primary schools is unchallenged and unreflected upon

by Irish Catholic parents. This 'doxic' knowledge engendered in cultural knowledges/power creates legitimacy for choice and produces limits for non-Catholic parents.

Work, Employment & Economic Life A

HANGING LANTERN ROOM

Karl Marx Class Theory and Contract Employment in Nigeria: An Exploration of the Manifest Causes and Consequences

Peter Kalejaiye, Obatunde B. Adetola
(*Olabisi Onabanjo University*)

The rate at which employers recruit contract workers is increasing and alarming in Nigeria. The Nigeria labour unions are protesting against the precarious working conditions meted on contract workers in many organisations. However, their efforts tend to be waning as employers have strongly relied on the continuous use of contract workers, without strict regulations on the part of the Nigeria government. Worst still, since the cheapness of labour means profit to the employers, thus the presence of contract workers are becoming a treat to the jobs of permanent employees. As a result, this paper explored the manifest causes and consequences of contract employment in Nigeria using Karl Marx Class theory. It was observed that, the government and employers are keen promoters of contract employment in Nigeria. This is evidenced in the high rate of unemployment, poor standard of employment regulations and obsession to make profit respectively. The consequences of these factors are poor social, economic and psychological benefits cum poverty for contract workers in Nigeria. The trade unions should work much harder to protect the interests of the contract workers through constant struggle with the government and employers as well as create awareness for the contract workers to know their rights in employment relations. More so, the government and other policy makers should ensure that labour laws are carefully implemented and evaluated to protect contract workers from the exploitation of foreign and local employers in Nigeria.

'I don't' want to work, I want to be a billionaire': Imagining a better future amongst the London precariat.

Jacob Nielsen, Jacob Nielsen
(*University of Liverpool*)

This presentation will examine the everyday processes that shape the hopes of a better present and future amongst people living and working in precarious circumstances in London. Different aspects of precarious work conditions have received considerable attention from policy makers, charities, businesses, and academics whether through government policies on labour exploitation and modern slavery or through moral debates around the consequences of zero hours contracts and the gig economy. What constitutes the problems and what the appropriate solutions for the precariat should be is at the centre of these policy assemblages whose discourses and practices tend to cluster around ideas about the inherent moral value of wage labour and that improving working conditions through objectively measurable standards such as increased minimum wage and guaranteed working hours will also deal with the issues experienced by the precariat.

Based on ethnographic fieldwork working and living with people in precarious circumstances over a year in London, this talk will examine how people who are the target of these policies themselves perceive their lives and how they imagine a better future for themselves. I will argue that people's values and future aspirations are inherently processual and embedded in everyday social relations and morality and that they often challenge the idea that wage labour in whatever form it takes should or could be a part of a better life.

The lack of protest against social inequalities in young people's lives

Vera Trappmann, Alexandra Seehaus
(*Leeds University Business School*)

Across Europe, social inequalities have been increasing. Besides a general divide between rich and poor, young people have been particularly affected by precarious or insecure working conditions (Eurostat 2015, Standing 2009, Murgia and Poggio 2014, Kretsos 2010, Inui et al. 2015, Feltrin 2017, Khosravi 2017, Côté 2014).

Despite the increasing insecurity and social inequality, young people have shown comparably little criticism let alone protest against social inequalities or against the increase since the crisis in 2008/09 in countries as the UK or Germany.

Our contribution is concerned with resolving this puzzle questioning 1. what social inequalities are at all perceived by young people, 2. what leads to protest against social inequality, 3. what factors contribute to criticism of social inequality into collective action. We particularly take into account the role of education, gender as well as migration background.

The empirical basis of our contribution consists of biographical interviews with young people between the age of 18 and 35 in various forms of temporary, fixed-term and low-paid jobs, as well as unemployed in the UK and Germany.

The micro-sociological analysis of the life worlds and attitudes of young people leads us to a critical diagnosis of protest. Instead of finding revolutionaries, many of our interviewees have internalized the neoliberal regime. There is no vision of an alternative world of work for most of them and as much as structural reasons for inequality remain unrecognized, collective interpretations and actions are an exception. There is little potential for solidarity.

A Study of the Working Experiences of Hotel Housekeeping Operational Staff in London

*Quasirat Hasnat,
(University of Brighton)*

Hotel housekeeping, often stigmatised as women's unskilled work, remains under-researched, even though it provides the largest share of a hotel's profits through enabling guestrooms' retailing. The hotel housekeeping is renowned for entailing prolonged and antisocial working hours, limited career progression, exploitation of generally younger female migrant workers, and for being characterised by a high staff turnover rate. My research, which aims at understanding the working experiences of hotel housekeeping staff in London, tells a slightly different story.

Using a mixed-methods approach, I collected data from 57 three-and-over star rated hotels located in different quarters of London. I interviewed 53 housekeeping managers and got 106 housekeeping staff to complete a survey questionnaire.

From this, a sense emerges that housekeeping work could be said to share features of Taylorism in that that the jobs tend to involve low variation, lack of autonomy on the part of the worker, minimal learning time, solo working with hardly any interaction with other human beings. In addition, each task is highly standardised, given the use of SOPs (Standard Operating Procedures) - meant to eliminate accident risk factors as well as to save time and effort, thus implying 'lean management'.

Despite the tasks being SOP bound, in order to be able to accomplish them, workers must have a set of cognitive skills (thinking, remembering and reasoning), soft skills (attention to detail, time management, self-organisation, quick learning) and physical ability.

The question arises: how do these alleged unskilled workers experience hotel cleaning work and what drives them?

Work, Employment & Economic Life B **W001**

Making Feminist(s) Work Through Out The Career Course

*Madeline Breeze
(University of Strathclyde)*

Situated within a time of increasing debates on the purpose of The University, and the inequality regimes it perpetuates, this paper offers fresh analysis of doing feminist work in higher education. It foregrounds conversations between the authors and across career stages, and attends to the repetitions of feminist academic work. We speak across the career course, as differentiated career categories are themselves entangled in academic structures, sentiments and subjectivities; solidified in entry and promotion schemes, funding calls and job descriptions. Career categories ask us to identify with particular stages of 'being' or 'becoming' academic, while arguably interrupting the possibility of ever arriving. Academic career categories offer a framework through which academic spaces, resources, and authority can be claimed and contested by feminists. Inhabiting career categories uncritically can, however, serve to reproduce stratifying academic structures that we also seek to resist and rework. Collaboration across career stages represents a significant empirical case for understanding how feminists occupy – and stretch – academic spaces, unpicking the knot of how feminist work in higher education can claim, disrupt, and be invested in the neoliberal logics of competitive individualism. We draw on our own interdisciplinary feminist collaborations, and use auto-ethnographic methods to develop collaborative conversations between the authors, to explore feminist repetitions and interruptions across career categories.

'They think I'm a PR stunt' - Young women's experiences of gendered ageism in football leadership

*Amee Gill,
(Durham University)*

This paper will present findings from a study on women's experiences of working in leadership in men's professional football, focussing on the intersection of gender and age in workplace inequalities. Women remain critically

underrepresented in leadership roles in football; therefore, this study aimed to explore how women in senior roles made sense of, and experienced, being a woman in this 'man's world'.

Data from in-depth interviews with women working 'above the glass ceiling' in football suggests that women still faced challenges to their leadership. One such challenge for young women leaders was that of gendered ageism. Often used to explore older women's experiences of work, gendered ageism presented a unique challenge for the young women in this study. The intersection of age and gender in the burgeoning literature on women and leadership has rarely been addressed; however, findings from this study suggest that age is a meaningful factor in young women's experiences of sexism and gender inequality in leadership roles.

Taking the world of men's professional football as a study site, this paper will present case studies of young women working in executive roles. This paper will reflect on the challenges they faced as they navigated the realities of being young women in the 'spotlight' – changes to career, family and relationships; media scrutiny; online abuse; and lookism. This paper will also highlight the complex ways in which these women negotiated femininity in the workplace and will consider how young, successful women are re-signifying femininity in a fourth-wave feminist era.

Work/Family Arrangements across the OECD: The Emergence of the Female-Breadwinner Model

Helen Kowalewska, Agnese Vitali
(University of Southampton)

Comparative studies of the welfare state tend to compare work/family arrangements by the extent to which they embrace a 'male-breadwinner' or a 'dual-breadwinner' family model. Yet, there is an alternative set of labour-market arrangements that is becoming increasingly common across all welfare state regime types, whereby the female member of the couple is the main or only breadwinner. Such families have received limited attention within comparative social policy analysis, which typically assumes that men in couple-households are in full-time employment. Hence, to stimulate discussion within this literature of this increasingly widespread family model, we aim to shed light on the economic characteristics of, and gender division of unpaid work within, female-breadwinner couples. To this aim, we carry out regression models, controlling for socioeconomic confounders, using data from the Luxembourg Income Study and International Social Survey Programme on advanced economies representing a range of welfare state and gender regimes. We show that families in which the woman is the only wage-earner are, on average, poorer than other family-types, including male-breadwinner ones. Furthermore, women in female-breadwinner families continue to perform the majority of domestic and care duties within their couples, thereby contributing to a double-shift of paid and unpaid work for these women. Thus, social policy analysis should pay greater attention to female breadwinners, as our findings suggest that many of the 'new' social risks associated with postindustrialism (e.g., in-work poverty, work/care conflicts) impact disproportionately on these women.

Re-examining the Gender Gap in Competition and Risk Taking: Evidence from Qualitative Research on Women in Elite Leadership

Marina Yusupova, Prof Sharon Mavin
(Newcastle University)

This paper advances the recent analyses of the gendered aspects of competition and risk taking by examining the discursive construction of competition among women in elite leadership. Stereotype threat phenomenon and sex role congruence remain predominant theoretical lenses for understanding the gender gap in competitiveness and risk taking. Our contribution is to overcome the self-evidence of the term 'competition' by pointing to a multiplicity of meanings individual people attach to it. Based on analysis of in-depth semi-structured interviews with 81 women in elite leadership (executive and non-executive directors in FTSE 100/250 companies and influential leaders from a UK region), the study reveals that the research participants creatively balance between presenting themselves as competitive and non-competitive at the same time. They do so by manipulating the meaning of competition and differentiating between different kinds of competition. We argue that it is the multiplicity of meanings the individuals attach to competition that tends to go under research radar. Our data brings us beyond sex-based expectancy theory and stereotyping-based processes to a more nuanced understanding how doing gender intersects with doing competition. Our study contributes to an already abundant, but often ignored, evidence that women are as competitive and willing to take risks as men, however much depends on how you define risk, what you mean by competition and how you study them.

Theory

W323

Decolonizing Theory I: Culture and Justice

Gurminder Bhambra,
(University of Sussex)

Calls to decolonise universities have become more insistent in recent months. This has included both a growing concern with the Eurocentric nature of the curriculum and the ways in which disciplines are implicated in this. This session – alongside the one on Decolonising Theory: Culture and Justice - asks what it would mean to decolonise theory. How could we do theory differently and what sort of different theory would we need to participate effectively in the conversations around decolonising knowledge. This session orients specifically around issues of race and social theory.

Nasar Meer, Race in the Decolonial

Angela Last, Teaching anti-racist materialisms

James Trafford, The Racial Conditions of Homo Economicus

Chair / Discussant: Gurminder K Bhambra

From Progress to Reparations: The Necessity of Decolonising Theory

Gurminder Bhambra,
(University of Sussex)

Critical theory sees itself as an inheritor of the Enlightenment tradition and as providing critical responses to questions emerging from the turn to modernity and the constitution of modern societies. The idea of moral progress central to the conceptualization of critical theory's normative project is based on an idea of historical progress as embodied in our standard sociological understandings of modernity. However, the idea of the modern that is central to critical theory is not simply the modern, but is better understood as the colonial modern. The colonial modern is the empirical context within which claims for moral political advances are made; thus, these claims are made by ignoring, or failing to regard as significant, the processes of dispossession, appropriation, extraction, elimination, and enslavement. In this paper, I argue that we need to give up a commitment to historical progress as the central normative dimension of critical theory in favour of redressing the identified wrongs of the past through a commitment to epistemological justice and to reparations.

The Problems and Paradoxes of Anglocentrism in Decolonizing Social Theory

Sarah Victoria Burton,
(City, University of London)

This short intervention explores issues of decolonial/postcolonial futures of social theory from the perspective of multilingualism, Anglocentrism, and 'the intellectual' – how do these linked concepts inflect the ways that social theory/theorists create and legitimate knowledge? And to what extent can they reveal imbricated and hidden ways that knowledge and knowledge production is racialised and classed, even within more intersectional frameworks of understanding? Whilst there have been frequent challenges to the hegemony of whiteness and Europe in the construction of sociological knowledge, there is relatively little attention paid to the ongoing imperial power of English. This is particularly key given the position of English as the de facto language of a putatively 'global' academy, and the way this excludes and disadvantages researchers working in other languages. Conversely, being multilingual is often associated with the privilege of high cultural capital, thus suggesting ideas of a 'cosmopolitan intellectual' with the (linguistic) sophistication to read academic works in the 'original' language or undertake fieldwork in multiple languages – but which languages 'count' here and in what context? Using ethnographic fieldwork with sociologists - including on citation, publication, and conference practices - this paper reveals how colonial/imperial language hegemony shapes the ways researchers are taken seriously as intellectuals; it further argues that a sharper focus on the centrality of language to decoloniality and knowledge-making enables a more precise analysis of the actions of belonging, borders, exclusion, and inclusion which characterize the relationship between 'the intellectual' and social theory.

Affective Practice as Embodied Decoding: Politics, Culture, & the Resurrection of the Subject

Lisa Kalayji,

(University of Edinburgh)

Affect is generally theorised as an 'autonomous' force (Massumi, 1995) which 'circulates' between 'bodies' (Ahmed, 2004), conferring on them the 'capacity to act' (Fox, 2015). By locating affect in bodies (animate and otherwise) rather than subjects, influential formulations of affect under-theorise its relationship to multiple and contested cultural meanings, implicitly universalising white, male affectivity (Garcia-Rojas, 2016) and obscuring social agents' active world-making through affecting and being affected. This forecloses sociological understandings of affective resistance, agential responsibility, the causal inter-relationships between the corporeal and the symbolic, and the heterogeneity of feeling subjects. Disputing the declared 'death of the subject' (Terada, 2001), I aim to show that affect is not as autonomous from cognition and cultural meaning as has been widely suggested, and that the feeling subject is indispensable for explaining affective relations. Extending Margaret Wetherell's (2012) concept of 'affective practice', and rethinking it as an embodied form of decoding (Hall, 1973), I argue that affect is a site of cultural articulation and struggle which cannot be understood apolitically. By highlighting the roles of reflexivity and political contestation in affective experience, affect can be re-theorised to better explain heterogeneity and illustrate how social change enacted through affect is deeply entangled with, rather than radically independent from, historical legacies. This approach maintains the critiques of power intended in deterministic formulations of affect theory while also accounting for reflexive agency and political responsibility at the level of the individual feeling subject.

Thursday 25/04/2019 at 13:30 - 15:00
Paper Session 5

Cities, Mobilities, Place & Space A
W622

Freedom of settlement, freedom of movement. Different experiences of urban squatting of migrants and refugees in Rome, Italy

Margherita Grazioli, Nicola Montagna
(Gran Sasso Science Institute
L'Aquila, Italy)

The shortage of public, affordable housing for urban poor and migrants is ingrained in Rome's urban development since the immediate post-IIWW. As a response, the proliferation of informal settlements, shantytowns and squatted accommodations configured Rome's as a makeshift city where 'official planning' had to adjust to these new autonomous geographies.

Current forms of inhabitation in Rome have two major critical intersections: the contested management of borderscapes; the neoliberal reorganisation of the urban space since 2008 crisis unleashed. The patterns of spatial and social segregation stemming from it led migrants with different statuses to 'adopt' squatting and informal settlement practices with or without the support of local housing rights movements and anti-racist networks to different purposes: fostering settlement and mobility; accessing affordable housing outside of the privatised market or the increasingly exclusionary (and residual) social housing circuit; escaping the circuit of fostered, forcible housing as part of the border management process.

The current paper analyses the new forms of urban squatting enacted by migrants in the city of Rome in order to argue for their importance as support networks and safe spaces for those incoming migrants and people on the move who do not want to be restrained within the circuit of reception and the Dublin rules by considering three distinct cases. Drawing on empirical research, the paper scrutinises three different types of experiences housing squats affiliated to Housing Rights Movements; the urban migrants' camp Baobab Experience; the informal settlement inside the former Penicillina Leo industrial relict.

Diverse trajectories of Non-EU migrants: A bottom-up qualitative analysis of the hidden narratives of refugees and forced migrants.

Rumana Hashem, Paul Dudman, University of East London
(University of Warwick, UK.)

This paper reflects on the work we have undertaken with the Refugee Council Archive at the University of East London in 2015 and 2016. We examine how a bottom-up approach to oral histories and narrative research can contribute to the documentation and preservation of the genuine voices and testimonies of displaced people. Drawing on a civic engagement research and an outreach work with documented and undocumented migrants and refugees from non-European countries in London, we argue that a bottom-up approach to traditional life history method enables researchers to understand the diverse trajectories and paradoxical narrative of displaced persons of different ethnicities e.g. refugees from the global south and non-EU states. The paper also discusses the major challenges in applying oral history approach to forced-migration studies. We demonstrate that despite the challenges, the power of oral history is irrefutable, especially in the context of refugee research, because life narrative of the displaced person does not only help to recognise the hidden agency but also enables archiving and the [re]construction of 'moving memories' of the displaced.

By way of illustrations, we also show how the voices of refugees and migrants of different ethnicities and 'race' are often marginalised or left un-heard within the Archive, and even deliberately overlooked in favour of the dominant narratives of the nation. We conclude by addressing how these people themselves resist and continue to debunk the dominant notion of nation through the making of or giving meanings to their temporal and spatial aspects of displacement.

The 'Brexit' effect on the life satisfaction of EU migrants in the UK

Chris Moreh, Derek Mcghee
(York St John University)

The 2016 EU Referendum in the United Kingdom has set the country on the path to leaving the European Union on 29 March 2019. Some of the most immediately affected by the 'Brexit' process are the millions of EU citizens living in the

UK. But what exactly is the 'effect' of Brexit on EU 'migrants' lives, and how could it be measured? We have previously addressed this question by measuring the degree to which free-moving EU citizens are being pushed towards national legal integration through measures such as naturalisation (Moreh et al. Forthcoming; McGhee et al. 2017). In this paper we focus on findings from a new follow-up original e-survey completed in October 2018. Here we frame the 'Brexit effect' more narrowly in terms of life satisfaction and future outlook, using measurement variables comparable to those adopted in cross-national surveys such as the European Social Survey. Examining a sample of Polish (N=637), Spanish (N=107) and German (N=60) EU nationals living in the UK (N=804), we test the effect of the Brexit process on the 'life satisfaction' of our participants. Our results present a complex picture of the negative effect of Brexit on the lives of members of the largest EU 'migrant' community in the UK. Through this analysis, we make two original contributions: first, to a classical area of the study of human well-being (Veenhoven 1984); and second, to the understanding of the individual-level effects of de-Europeanization.

Cities, Mobilities, Place & Space B **W610**

More than just a 'poor door'. Exploring the polarisation of housing tenures through mixed tenure communities towards an applied definition for housing design and planning policy guidance.

Natasha Kinloch,
(UNIVERSITY OF SURREY)

This paper will examine how housing tenures are spatially mixed within a mixed tenure community's physical building(s) and surrounding physical environment.

The idea of increased interactions which create opportunities for natural surveillance is perhaps an overinflated assumption in UK policy documents and existing literature. Murie and Rowland (2008) discovered that there is more commonly a clustered layout dependent on tenure type, whereby different tenures exist on different floors in a single building or in separate buildings altogether. This has been echoed further in British and American media to suggest tenure residents are segregated deliberately through amenities, design principles including entrance and communal facilities. Whilst guidance exists to argue that any external visibility of a mixed tenure community should not be explicit and with no visible features signifying particular tenure type. Nor should the external visibility indicate to an offender that a tenure's physical surroundings present a greater opportunity to offend than another. Existing literature is sporadic and without agreed definitions as to what criteria is statutory, and advisory, for inclusion into mixed tenure communities. This paper aims to examine the characteristics of mixed tenure communities towards creating an applied definition for future planning and policy design guidance which follows the conceptual understanding of their inclusion into British housing neighbourhoods.

Lessons from (or for) 'Red Vienna': social housing beyond the 'right-to-buy'

Sarah Leaney,
(University of Brighton)

The hyper-commodification of the housing market and resultant processes of gentrification, dispossession and rising homelessness have become viscerally present across UK cities. Contemporary critiques of 'Right-to-Buy' policies highlight the consequences of the ongoing dismantling of social housing and mark a change in dominant conceptions of home which have been defined by an aspiration for home ownership.

This disruption of the connection between home and ownership may be central in redefining housing beyond the logic of accumulation, where property has become defined by its market value rather than its use value. Through a comparison of Brighton (UK) and Vienna (Austria), the research considers the impact of the social and material conditions of social housing on those socially housed. Drawing upon qualitative interviews with residents from three social housing case studies in Vienna, this paper explores how the social, economic and architectural provision of social housing transforms residents' experience of home.

This paper argues that whilst the social housing provision in Vienna remains substantially decommodified, a tiered system of 'municipal' and 'social' housing; discourses of deserving and undeserving residents; and the introduction of a limited 'right-to buy', reflects similar processes of the stigmatisation of social housing in the UK. The paper locates residents' everyday practices of home making within the context of 'Red Vienna', a city branding of housing for all, and explores the construction of boundaries, exclusions and difference within Vienna's social housing policy.

Culture, Media, Sport & Food

"It's like being on a tightrope" – Stand-Up Comedy as 'Edgework'

Thomas Hurdsfield
(University of Salford, Manchester)

The lives of stand-up comedians is a curious yet under-researched topic. Previous research has demonstrated something of a preoccupation with studying their personalities, typically orbiting around two central conceits; how alleged anxious and depressive tendencies may contribute towards stand-up comedians successes as performers and how personality structure may be used to explain performer's comedic prowess. Little scholarly activity has sought to study stand-up comedians' working lives and experiences through direct observation in its natural context.

This study employed an ethnographic approach to explore the working lives and experiences of stand-up comedians. The study recruited nineteen participants - all professional, full-time stand-up comedians performing on the UK comedy circuit. This study deployed participant observation as the main data collection method. The researcher travelled with participants to, from and between gigs, observing on-stage performances, backstage activity and conversation. A small number of face to face interviews were also conducted with participants.

Preliminary findings suggest that the working lives and experiences of stand-up comedians are characterised by unpredictability, uncertainty and unexpectedness. This sees stand-up comedians continually weighing-up audiences, wondering what they will be like and how they will respond to their on-stage performances. The contrast between the different experiences at multiple gigs in a single night demonstrated this unpredictability at its most palpable. This unpredictability and stand-up comedians' resultant sense-making suggests the potential for a framing of stand-up comedy as a form of 'edgework'.

Drag as a creative industry: Dynamism, performance and heteronormativity

Mark McCormack, Liam Wignall
(University of Roehampton)

While drag performance has a long history in the UK, both in British theatre and Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual and Trans cultures, it has tended to occupy a marginalised position within the British cultural scene. Yet in a social context of decreased homophobia alongside the success of hit TV show Rupaul's Drag Race, drag is undergoing a renaissance with the present time even labelled a 'golden age' of drag. Drawing on in-depth interviews with 24 drag performers, this paper argues that drag has moved from a sub-cultural pursuit to being a creative industry. The paper examines drag performers' experiences of how drag has changed, becoming more visible and profitable, and finds two key reasons for the vibrancy of the current drag scene. First, changing cultural attitudes and discourses means there is a bigger audience for drag, with more acceptance of drag as an art-form. Second, continued heteronormativity in the creative and cultural industries more generally means that highly talented performers feel excluded from mainstream music and theatre roles and see drag as a more viable career choice. Given concerns about the permanence of this shift in drag performance, the policy implications of drag as a creative industry are addressed.

'There's no way that you get paid to do the arts'. Classed narratives of unpaid labour in cultural and creative work

Orian Brook, Orian Brook; Dave O'Brien; Mark Taylor
(University of Edinburgh)

Unpaid labour is an important element of how precarity has been theorized. It is also an issue that is often seen as endemic to cultural and creative work. Questions as to the role of unpaid work, including but not limited to unpaid internships, have become central to understanding how the social exclusiveness of many cultural and creative jobs is reinforced through their precarity. This paper uses survey and interview data to outline the differing experiences of unpaid labour in cultural occupations. It compares and contrasts the meaning of 'free' work for range of creative workers, historicising the impact of unpaid labour on the creative sector and showing how it has been stratified by social class, age and career stage. By exploring the stratification of unpaid work as a form of precariousness in cultural jobs, along with the hierarchical and classed distribution of benign narratives of unpaid work, the paper offers new empirical evidence for those challenging the negative impacts of precarious working conditions in the cultural sector.

The Only True Philosophers: Boundaries, Distinction and Meaning among Unofficial Philosophers in Communist Czechoslovakia

Dominik Želinský,
(University of Edinburgh)

This paper explores the phenomenon of unofficial philosophy seminars in Czechoslovakia during the communist past. Focusing on Prague, this paper explores how academics, marginalized and ousted from official institutions due to their

unwillingness to submit to the official doctrine of 'normalisation', or re-introduction of Marxist-Leninist agenda post the 1968 occupation of the country by Soviet forces, organised unofficial academic life. Since the late 1970s, the fragmentary system of 'seminars' – discussion groups ranging from philosophy to information science, received institutional support from the West, in particular, Oxford University, which set up a foundation to support Czechoslovak academics. The effort of British academics brought world famed academics such as Jurgen Habermas, Jacques Derrida or Charles Taylor to lecture in flats of Czechoslovak dissidents. To reconstruct the case, I draw on biographical interviews, archival research of both the British Jan Hus Educational Foundation and archives of the secret police and textual analysis of unofficial samizdat production.

My paper investigates the ways in which unofficial philosophers understood their activities. In particular, I focus on their boundary-work with regard to official academic production. I argue that the ways in which unofficial philosophers thought about their struggle were underpinned by strong moral binary of sacred and profane that they actively interpreted and polished in order to develop a specific 'free' philosophy contrary to the Marxist dogma. At the same time, this distinction not only produced a sense of exclusivity but also endowed their daily life with a sense of historical meaning and significance.

Environment & Society

W525

Cross-sector collaboration to incorporate environmental values: action research, interests and inequalities

Elizabeth Woodcock,
(Bangor University)

A healthy natural environment is essential for personal and national well-being, yet biodiversity in the UK has halved over the past 50 years. In Wales no ecosystem has all the characteristics needed for sustainability. However, legislation for Wales, the Well-being of Future Generations Act, 2015, sets out 7 goals and 5 principles for the nation's sustainable development. But how can the environmental goal of 'a resilient Wales' hold its ground against goals for health, economy and social cohesion?

Cross-sector collaboration offers an opportunity to enhance the influence of less-powerful interests. Nevertheless, collaborating organisations tend to place a monetary value on Nature, perpetuating the subservice of environmental values. To learn how to achieve balanced integration of environmental interests, I facilitate action research with public bodies and third sector environmental groups in Gwynedd & Anglesey, North Wales. The practical action and deliberation of the action research group and reflection with strategic leaders enables me to build on experiential knowledge of a range of public and third sector partners and contribute to public debates around implementing the Act.

In this presentation I invite delegates to experience for themselves the action research process. We will deliberate over a way to integrate environmental interests into the development of a scheme to reduce health inequalities. We will adopt a critical systemic approach to understand how the hierarchies established by the Act interact with dominant interests to exclude environmental groups. We will reflect on the potential of cross-sector collaboration as a democratic alternative to current decision-making processes.

Understanding public-private partnerships at the food-energy-water-environment nexus

Pete Barbrook-Johnson,
(University of Surrey)

In this talk I will present; (i) a critical review of public-private partnerships (PPP) used for the provision of food, energy, water, and environmental (or 'nexus') infrastructure and services; and (ii) reflections on my ongoing research with one particular nexus PPP, the South Lincolnshire Water Partnership.

The review focuses on nexus PPP in the UK which do not use the much-maligned 'Private Finance Initiative' or 'Private Finance 2' project models, but instead are based on trust, voluntary agreements, multiple partners, and shared goals. These types of partnerships do not appear in most official public records or data sets, are often not well-documented, and are thus not well-understood, despite representing an important governance structure for the provision of food, water, energy, waste, and environmental infrastructure and services. I will focus first on overviewing what partnerships exist in these domains. Second, on how the specific environmental domain PPP operate in, and the level to which this is perceived normatively as a service or infrastructure that only the public sector should provide, affects feasibility, acceptance, and outcomes for partnerships. Finally, in keeping with the conference theme, I will reflect on environmental justice and social justice implications of these partnerships, stemming from how they operate, where and how they are set up, and who is able to partner in them.

I will add colour to the review, and conclude the talk, by reflecting on learning from my ongoing co-produced research with one specific PPP in the water sector, the South Lincolnshire Water Partnership.

Forest Conservation, Forest Dwelling People and Construction of Environmental and Gendered Subjects- Case of REDD+ and Adivasis in India

shubhi sharma, shubhi sharma
(University of Edinburgh)

This research is based in the Khasi Hills district of Meghalaya (India) which is a matrilineal but deeply patriarchal Adivasi (tribal) society where a conservation project (REDD+) was initiated by an all-male Adivasi leadership and an international group of actors. This project is closely intertwined with one male Adivasi's personal life trajectory and charismatic leadership, which makes for an interesting tension as REDD+ is all about impersonal markets. The society is also rife with tensions between predominantly tribal and minor non-tribal groups.

It is within this context that I aim to assess how the 'technologies' of REDD+ foster, maintain or entrench the past histories of dispossession; inequalities; gendered identities and conflicts, and create different kinds of 'environmental and gendered subjects'. I am also analysing the agency of the Adivasis in these processes, whilst not losing sight of the structural inequalities at work. I am conducting a one year long ethnographic study informed by feminist and governmentality methodology whilst looking at notions of personal and impersonal domination in Max Weber's work and am half way through with the fieldwork.

Conservation-induced dispossession is an under-researched topic in India and is required for ensuring environmental justice in the context of increasingly market-based conservation. This research will bring attention to and document persisting as well as new forms of dispossession of Adivasi people and gender inequality in the context of shifting forest governance arrangements; with a view to informing forest conservation policies that put environmental justice and gender equality at their heart.

It's like Mad Max, but without politics: Considering the (absent) role of social agency in climate conflict narratives

Stephen Jackson
(University of Leicester)

Anthropogenic climate change is undoubtedly one of the greatest risks to human society. In seeking to highlight the urgent need to respond to the crisis, many now underscore the growing potential for climate change to exacerbate inequalities, deepen poverty and spark widespread social conflict. In such accounts, climate change is conceptualised as an extra-social agent poised to exert an increasing influence over human affairs. However, attempts to make causal connections between climate change and social crises are not without their critics, many of whom view these as reductive accounts of climate-society interactions that neglect how social, political and economic practices shape people's vulnerability to environmental stressors. Debates between these positions are ongoing. And although much is made of the need to reconcile them, little progress has materialised. This paper argues that this impasse exists not because of empirical or analytical differences, but because these two competing 'voices' are trying to highlight qualitatively different sets of issues. The former seeks primarily to underscore the dangers of failing to mitigate climate change, while the latter seeks primarily to underscore the consequences of failing to redress power imbalances. Drawing on examples from both academic and non-academic sources, I demonstrate how these two objectives lead to fundamentally opposing ways of envisaging the societal impacts of climate change. Moreover, I contend that climate conflict narratives are compelling precisely because they diminish the active, wilful political (re)production of social arrangements that are the primary causes of conflict and suffering.

Families & Relationships A W709

Organizing Openness: How UK Policy Defines the Significance of Information and Information Sharing about Gamete Donation

Leah Gilman, Petra Nordqvist
(University of Manchester)

'Openness' is increasingly held up as a self-evident virtue, presented as inherently positive and progressive in both the public and personal sphere. This presentation examines how this ideal is realised in the regulation of gamete donation in the UK; what exactly is it that people are expected to be open about and with whom? Through an analysis of the policies and texts via which information about gamete donation is managed, we demonstrate that sharing information about the donor with donor offspring is prioritized, whilst other trajectories of information often remain forbidden or unconsidered. We argue that these policy discourses and decisions both reflect and reproduce a dominant framing of gamete donation as significant in terms of its reproductive consequences and specifically the interest donor offspring

may have in their origins. However, as we demonstrate, this is not the only way in which donation information can be significant to those implicated. It can also, for example, be viewed as a gift or form of bodily donation connecting donors and recipients. We argue for closer analysis of the ways in which social policies organise openness along particular trajectories and how this in turn shapes the social and relational significance of the events being disclosed.

Social Support And Coping Strategies of Women Attending Fertility Clinics In Lagos State Nigeria

*Folake Lanre-Babalola,
(Redeemer's University
Ede, Osun State. Nigeria)*

Infertility is a medical condition that can touch every aspect of a woman's life – from the way they feel about themselves, to their relationship with their partners, families & friends and the overall perspective on living. Infertility is faced by an estimated 20-25% of women of childbearing age in Nigeria. This study explores the coping strategies adopted and the support received by 194 women seeking infertility treatment in selected fertility clinics Lagos state. Nigeria,

With the aid of quantitative research technique, this study looked into the different coping strategies and social support of women experiencing fertility problems in Lagos state. A total number of 255 questionnaires were randomly distributed among women attending fertility clinics and 194 were considered suitable for research.

The result of the study showed that majority of the women preferred to keep their fertility problems to themselves because of the stigma associated to infertility especially. Further, the majority of the women coped through the support received from their spouses, some cope through drawing on their religious faith as well as through the support received from their religious leaders, and others revealed that they got support from friends, caregivers and relatives. Majority of the women avoided situations that reminded them of their infertility problem and the situations that made them uncomfortable, others tried to learn more about their problem and sought solution to their infertility problem.

It was therefore recommended that supportive programmes should be organized for these women in this category.

Family, gender, and alternatives to (biological) parenthood: advice on unresolved infertility in Britain before the era of assisted reproductive technologies

*Yuliya Hilevych,
(University of Cambridge)*

Sharing one's experience of infertility is emotionally charged, and many decide to present their childlessness as a choice rather than a set of circumstances. This positioning of one's reproductive identity is not only linked to that the boundaries between infertility and childlessness have blurred in the era of assisted reproduction, but also to that being voluntary childless is a legitimate answer in many Western societies today. To understand this present-day dialectic between infertility and childlessness, we do not only need to consider the complexities of present infertilities, but it is also a fundamental question to understand how 'alternatives' to parenthood were discussed and constructed before 'hope technologies' as IVF existed.

This paper theoretically develops a concept of alternatives to (biological) parenthood by studying the content of advice to unresolved infertility that was available to infertile couples in Britain before the invention of IVF (1978). It analyses 24 handbooks for childless couples and family doctors, and 106 articles published in professional journals for family doctors, i.e. Family Planning, the Practitioners, between 1950 and 1980. This study illustrates that nuclear family's desire for biological parenthood was nurtured through encouraging women to be active in seeking advice. This desire was further embraced in artificial insemination and hormones as the first tangible alternatives to unresolved infertility. However, as hopes were high yet technologies not always worked or accepted, childlessness became quickly appropriated to the needs of a nuclear family and seen as the main alternative to (biological) parenthood just before IVF was invented.

Families & Relationships B

W727

Disclosure to disconnection: the role of social media in the coping practices of new fathers with mental health difficulties

*Paul Hodkinson, Ranjana Das
(University of Surrey)*

This paper considers the role of social media in new fathers' attempts to cope with mental health difficulties. It does so amidst cultures of silencing and limited support with respect to fathers and mental health (Mayers 2018; Galanski 2013), alongside indications of positive well-being outcomes when fathers engage with online spaces (Salzmann-Eriksson & Erikson, 2013; Fletcher & St George, 2011). We draw on interviews with fifteen fathers who had

experienced mental health struggles after having a baby in highlighting varied social media experiences. Many fathers had learned more about their symptoms online and several emphasised the value of engaging with the accounts of other sufferers. Few had found it easy to communicate about their own difficulties, though some had devised coded attempts to reach out digitally. For others, the use of social media had contrasting broader roles – as a means to escape from their struggles or as a contributor to them. In the case of the latter, moments of disconnection were afforded much significance. Consistent with recent research on positive and negative aspects of internet use in relation to maternal wellbeing (Das, 2018), we conclude that social media offer clear potential as positive outlets for fathers suffering mental health issues, but that, in practice, their role is varied. In avoiding deterministic celebratory or pessimistic understandings, our findings echo existing bodies of research on the complex implications of social media for wellbeing (Baym, 2015; Livingstone & Third, 2018) while highlighting underlying barriers to male mental health communication (Mayers 2018).

Intimate life in a postemotional age: Exploring the emotionality of Tinder users

Jenny van Hooff, Andrew Kirton
(Manchester Metropolitan University)

This paper contributes to an understanding of contemporary intimate life via an engagement with the concept of 'postemotionalism' (Meštrovic, 1997). The postemotional age is one in which emotionality has become increasingly mechanised and routinized, where in the face of phenomena people understand as deserving of particular emotional responses, we see a rise in the cynical performance of emotion and concomitant reproduction of certain established emotional regimes/paradigms. In this paper we consider the ways in which uses of 'dating apps' might represent the postemotionalisation of intimate relationships. We draw on data from a qualitative study of heterosexual men's use of Tinder, and focus in particular on how the men interviewed seemingly understand and experience emotion in relation to their uses of this app as part of their intimate lives. We argue that participants demonstrate attempts to reconcile the accelerated 'hyperintimacy' that these technologies afford with established ideas about how they and the people they meet might 'feel' in this context. The accounts that these men offer indicate a deferral to and reproduction of certain heteronormative and highly gendered understandings of emotion and intimacy. We conclude that the concept of postemotionalism is of analytical value in helping draw attention to emotionality in this particular context, and that in turn, the use of dating apps as part of people's intimate lives is illustrative of those shifts that the postemotional society seeks to draw attention to.

"I think a lot of people will judge me" The classification of women's reproductive decision making

Kristina Saunders
(University of Glasgow)

Despite a social and political backdrop of apparent increased choice and the insignificance of social categories, there is an expectation that all women will reproduce in line with traditional conceptions of femininity, exacerbated by the postfeminist requirement to 'have it all' (McRobbie, 2007). However, this expectation also exists alongside differential value that is attached to women's decisions about having and raising children, with some constructed as choosing 'incorrectly'.

Using interview data with 23 women and service providers in Scotland, I will draw attention to the persistence of class that is said to be displaced, shown through the hierarchy of worth assigned to women's reproductive decisions, and by women's ability to use resources to invest in their children. Tyler's (2015:507) theorizing of classification, where class is viewed as a "description of a given place in a social hierarchy and as a name for political struggles against the effects of classification", allows for an analysis of class which considers how inequalities in social relations are sustained, but also highlights the way in which value is assigned to certain women and their decisions, and how women can be regulated or restricted by classification. The intersection of neoliberal and postfeminist norms with middle-class values will be shown to construct a valued reproductive subject who is self-investing and future oriented. However, I will also argue that different material conditions produce different orientations to having and raising children which are not lacking in value, but are alternatives to the neoliberal, postfeminist, and middle-class norm.

'Am I being unreasonable to feel undervalued?' Navigating inequality in domestic settings on the UK parenting site Mumsnet

Yvonne Ehrstein,
(City, University of London)

The question of how to combine paid work with parenthood is a pressing one, at least for western women. While women are now fully immersed in the labour market and gender equality has arguably been achieved, feminist research continues to show that caring and domestic responsibilities are still unequally distributed between the genders, and women remain primary caregivers. Thus, the balancing of private and public realms of life emerges as a key site where persistent gender inequalities are played out.

Taking the UK's most popular parenting website Mumsnet as a case study, the data comprise ethnographic observations of online forum interactions and in-depth interviews with website users (n=30) aged 29-48. The paper seeks to show how this large and influential British parenting community constructs and navigates the multiple and conflicting everyday labours involved in heterosexual family and work life. A particular focus pertains to patterned emotions such as complaint, suffering, anger and irritation that mothers articulate when discussing felt inequalities in the distribution of reproductive labours, both on- and offline.

Preliminary findings indicate that i) Mumsnet operates as an outlet for feelings that are deemed inappropriate in a neoliberal climate that celebrates the successful reconciliation of maternal and working identities; ii) the banal routine of sharing and posting is an entertaining yet also performative act allowing to express dissension and resistance towards gendered norms and expectations to combine working and parenting in the UK context that goes at least beyond private utterances of frustration.

Frontiers **W007**

Applied Sociology in the Undergraduate Curriculum: a Workshop

Nick Fox,

(Sociologists outside Academia Group)

This event is aimed at those involved in the teaching and/or development of undergraduate sociology curricula. It builds on the launch of the BSA-SoA curriculum in applied sociology in April 2018.

The aims of the event are:

- To explore how applied sociology may be delivered within the undergraduate sociology curriculum.
- To assess the impact of an applied sociology component on employability and career planning by students and graduates.
- To consider how sociology programmes can support students and graduates into careers as applied sociologists
- To examine how an applied sociology component can supply evidence on employability for subject-level TEF.

The format is an interactive workshop for conference attendees, which will enable them to find out more about the BSA Applied Sociology curriculum; discuss their own programme and how it includes or might include an applied sociology component; and produce a story board for an applied sociology component in their undergraduate degree.

Workshop content:

1. An introduction to the BSA-SoA applied sociology curriculum.
2. Case studies of applied sociology in action, in the UK and globally.
3. Models for applied sociology components in undergraduate programme curricula.
4. Interactive discussion among event participants on how applied sociology is being implemented, or might be incorporated into their programmes.
5. Activity to story-board an applied sociology component in their own degree programme.
6. Discussion and conclusions.

Methodological Innovations **W009**

Writing and Exhibiting a 'Live' and Convivial Sociology: dissemination, impact and the future of Sociology.

Magali Peyrefitte,

(Middlesex University)

The paper reflects on the experience of organising a portrait exhibition as part of an ethnographic study into suburban home-making with a group of women who reside in Toulouse (France). In being publicly exhibited, the portraits

conferred the societal importance of the women's stories and offered a trope into women's agentic trajectories into suburbs of lower-middle and middle income. The portrait exhibition is also recognised for its relevance as a social event where dissemination happens through conviviality. Defining the idea of a convivial sociology, the paper contributes to the discussion on 'live' sociology and the role of a public sociology, one that is not simply determined by an audit culture of impact measures, but one that considers impact as an affective and intellectual response challenging power-relations in the research process and the dissemination of knowledge.

The First Encounter with Quantitative Research Methods: Top Tips for Teaching Numbers

Charlotte Brookfield, Tina Haux (University of Kent) and Rima Saini (City, University of London) (Cardiff University)

This paper draws on the outcomes of a recent Postgraduate and Early Career Academics' retreat at the University of Kent that explored possible ways of engaging social science undergraduate students in the UK with quantitative research methods. It has previously been documented that social science, and particularly sociology, students do not anticipate having to study numbers as part of their degree programme (Williams 2008; Chamberlain et al. 2015). Moreover, previous research has highlighted that almost 20 per cent of sociology students chose to study the discipline at degree level due to the fact that they hold an antipathy towards mathematics and wanted to avoid dealing with numbers altogether (Williams et al. 2008; Falkingham and McGowan 2011; Nuffield 2012). Therefore, introductory quantitative research methods modules can be daunting for both sociology students as well as those teaching. How do we enable students to understand the role of number in their discipline, and how do we improve their confidence to utilise such techniques through pedagogy? This paper discusses the various approaches taken in different Q-Step centres across the UK and evaluates how successful these have been. We conclude by sharing our 'top tips' for teaching quantitative research methods.

Making Things Up? On creative writing as a research methodology

Philippa Thomas, (University of Glasgow)

This paper will examine the potential of creating fiction as a social research method through reflecting on the sociological 'crime fiction' I have produced as part of my practice-based research. Following the ontological premise that our research methods produce rather than represent our objects of investigation, I will discuss on the process, ethics, and rationale for writing fiction as a method of social research. My doctoral project in visual sociology (Thomas, 2017) explored and critiqued the dominant imaginary of crime through undertaking experimental empirical research with ex-prisoners, a policeman, a private investigator and criminologists who produced differing and conflicting versions of crime. Sensitive to the 'enforced narratives' (Steedman, 2000) of criminalised people, I drew on approaches from Science and Technology Studies to 'translate' my empirical data into new forms including fiction and film, in order to explore the politics of showing and telling about crime. I am interested in how we might use creative methods to do research that performs the partiality and provisionality of all knowledge claims, whilst working sensitively and collaboratively with people who are socially marginalised and often over-researched. How might we work with ideas of partial truths while engaging ethically with people who are used to being treated as liars?

Race, Ethnicity & Migration A W011

The catastrophic everyday: Asylum seeker welfare in the postcolonial present

Lucy Mayblin, (University of Warwick (from Nov 2018: University of Sheffield))

The everyday has long been a key concern of the disciplines of sociology and anthropology, and recent years have seen a renewed interest in the quotidian in these disciplines and beyond. Much of this work is interested in making the everyday extra-ordinary in order to see it with fresh eyes. And yet how are we to address the banal everyday lives of people whose everyday lives are exceptional, whose marginalisation does not demand further othering and exoticising which risks casting them as irredeemably other? For some asylum seekers, the everyday at this point in their lives is not 'normal' but exceptional, not banal but catastrophic. This paper reports on interviews with asylum seekers living on Section 95 'asylum support' in a city in the North of England. Interviews focussed on the fabric and routines of their everyday lives. This qualitative research data is then discussed in relation to Mbembe's work on necropolitics. The paper thus makes three contributions: first, it presents new empirical data on the systematic impoverishment of asylum seekers in the UK. Second, it develops an operationalisable theory of the everyday for use in postcolonial studies; and third, it contributes to debates in the sociology of the everyday by introducing the concept of the 'catastrophic everyday'.

'Here to play': Music-making and forced migrants' embodied practices of diasporic belonging in Bristol

*Nicola De Martini Ugolotti,
(Bournemouth University)*

Amid a resurgence of xenophobic narratives surrounding migration and an overarching 'hostile environment' framework regulating asylum in Britain, this paper explores music-making as an embodied lens highlighting the (in)visible negotiations of place, belonging and uncertainty enacted by about 50 forced migrants through the co-creation of weekly music sessions in Bristol. In advancing this perspective, the paper addresses forced migrants' bodies as highly political sites where established scripts and 'truths' of asylum (e.g. victimization, passivity, gratefulness) are recurrently inscribed by the State and humanitarian actors through institutionalized practices, relations and moral representations. At the same time, this paper explores how the participants temporarily disrupted these embodied power relations by addressing their bodily, affective and collective engagement with music-making, as a practice enabling them to negotiate pleasure, expression and community in contexts of marginality, destitution and uncertainty. Consequently, the discussion addresses the participants' weekly music sessions as practices of diasporic belonging: relationalities arising from multiple and shared forms of exile, marginalization and precariousness that enabled momentary, but productive spaces of belonging beyond ethnic, national and religious lines. In discussing the stakes, challenges and implications of the participants' engagement with music-making, the study thus highlights the relevance of the multiple and (in)visible forms of sociality that forced migrants enact beside the discursive and institutional frames and hierarchies of State and humanitarian intervention/regulation.

Resettlement Policy and Practice: The lived experiences of Syrian refugee families

*Hannah Haycox,
(The University of Manchester)*

The Vulnerable Persons Resettlement Programme (VPRP) constitutes the UK government's unilateral response to forced migration as a result of the Syrian civil war. Distinct from the mainstream asylum dispersal model, the VPRP aims to resettle 20,000 Syrian refugees between 2015 and 2020, with a primary focus on maintaining family units. The positioning of resettled families as the inherently vulnerable, 'deserving' victims of the Syrian war is accompanied by the immediate granting of temporary protection, permission to work and recourse to public funds. However, the historical continuum of racialised and exclusionary immigration and asylum policy, the cultivation of Islamophobic sentiment in a post-Brexit UK and the exacerbation of existing inequalities due to continuing austerity measures represent crucial elements of the UK's social, political and economic landscape into which refugees are resettled.

This paper draws on research with refugee families resettled as part of the VPRP. It explores their experiences of the resettlement programme within the context of historically entrenched policy responses to refugees and asylum seekers. Drawing on two geographical locations in the North West, the paper explores the impact and experiences of two different local approaches to refugee resettlement.

Race, Ethnicity & Migration B W324

Why are some migrants white but not fully white? Critical race studies and the continued currency of race in signification of minorities in education.

*Aneta Hayes
(Keele University)*

Drawing on critical race studies in education (e.g. Warmington et al, 2017; Gillborn, 2018; Shain, 2012; 2013), the presentation will focus on the continued currency of race in the process of signification of Eastern European pupils in education; a topic which is gaining specific urgency in the context of Brexit. The presentation will explore ways in which the biological meaning of race may afford Eastern European pupils the same privileges as the white British majority. The presentation will also explore how, on the other hand, the social aspects of race of Eastern Europeans (such as their immigrant status, 'low' social class in the receiving country and speaking English 'with an accent') may disadvantage them in ways that point to the same patterns in which non-white minorities experience educational inequalities and discrimination. The presentation will also discuss Eastern European migrants' narratives of earned citizenship and deservedness in the context of the UK's EU referendum and how they contrast with ways in which they are excluded in education through racialized frames of 'class' and 'numbers' (Van Dijk, 2000).

Theorising race and gender: blind spots in equality agendas for sport coaching

*AJ Rankin-Wright, Professor Kevin Hylton, Dr Leanne Norman
(Durham University)*

Sociological work on the 'race'-sport nexus is vital to better understand broader debates around intersectionality, discrimination and inequalities, and to inform 'race' and gender equality initiatives in all sectors of British society. This paper applies the concept of 'blind spots' to describe the partial approaches to 'race' and gender equality agendas in sport coaching in the United Kingdom (UK). Critical sociological scholarship that examines intersecting gendered and racialised structural and relational experiences that facilitate, as well as constrain, sport coaches' progression is sparse. The qualitative approach employed for this research is underpinned by Critical Race Theory and draws on Black feminism and intersectionality scholarship to develop new insights in the analysis of organisational approaches to equality work in the context of sport coaching. It draws on semi-structured, in-depth interviews with Equality and Coach Education Leaders to explore how sport organisations and national governing bodies in the UK approach 'race' and gender equality. The three key themes identified and discussed are: The absence of 'race' in the equalities agenda; Patterns of invisibility; and Whitening Equality. The institutional 'blind spots' around 'race' and racialised gendered issues in the sport context, often regarded as meritocratic and equal for all, powerfully highlights and forefronts the complexity of contemporary racisms and their connection with gender, and other oppressions (Carrington 2012). Intersectional analysis of organisational approaches to equality agendas is imperative to examine the complexities of inclusion and exclusion and the different levels in which social divisions are constructed and interconnected.

Rights, Violence & Crime

W004

Abortion: Crisis, Regulation and Nation-building in the UK and Ireland

Gillian Love,
(University of Sussex)

The UK and Ireland are in crisis. Both nations are weathering the effects of the global financial crisis, austerity measures, the refugee crisis in Europe, and the uncertainty of Brexit. Simultaneously, abortion debates have re-emerged in the national discourse in both countries. Whilst abortion is traditionally understood to be a medical rather than political issue in the UK, abortion has nevertheless repeatedly erupted into the public, political domain in recent years in ways that suggest it is much closer to the surface of our national politics than we once thought. This paper will argue that these recent debates are symptomatic of a broader political struggle to constitute 'the nation' in times of crisis.

To explore this, the paper will provide a contemporary history of abortion politics in the UK and Ireland, focusing on three significant moments of political rupture: the cluster of amendments to British abortion law and practice were proposed by Conservative MPs in 2012; the 2015 sex-selective abortion debate; and the Irish abortion referendum of 2018. Critical abortion scholarship is urgently needed to examine the Irish referendum outcome and the wide-ranging changes it will precipitate. However, abortion in England, Scotland and Wales cannot be dismissed as 'safe' or immune from political upheaval. This paper will argue these three moments can be seen as moments of moral regulation of gender and nation, and through these case studies will reflect on the future of abortion rights in a time of global crisis.

Getting out or Getting in? Young women's criminalisation for those labelled as 'at risk'

Deborah Jump, Susan O Shea
(Manchester Metropolitan University)

This paper examines the potential relationships and boundaries

between criminalisation and social marginalisation. Drawing on data from a 3 year international research project, it considers the structural disadvantages that young women at risk of gang membership and CSE are facing. It illustrates how well-meaning funders and practitioners can (in)advertently expand criminalisation. Indeed, by targeting deprived and excluded young people,

projects that focus on 'at risk' youths can compound the issues rather than rectify

them. This paper will therefore explore the potential issues and unpack the ways in which helping young people 'get out' of gangs can potentially funnel them into targeted services that may overlook the underlying inequalities.

Science, Technology & Digital Studies

W003

Performing Expertise: An Ethnography of Terrorism Conferences

Tom Mills, David Miller, Narzanin Massoumi
(Aston University)

This paper presents some of the findings from an empirical examination of the world of terrorism expertise. Rather than working backwards from a normative and theoretical model of expertise, as in Collins and Evans (2002, 2008) for example, this research focuses on the practical role of terrorism expertise and terrorism experts in society. It uses a variety of methods including social network analysis and investigative research, but in this paper we focus on ethnography, which we consider an indispensable tool for researching social networks in action and actuality. It describes a variety of terrorism conferences attended during the course of the research, detailing the different locations and settings, the organisers and attendees, including their apparent rationales for involvement, the interactions and networking, the presentations, discussions, and the levels of ideological congruity and contestation. It argues that what we observed at these conferences was not so much the transmission of substantive knowledge about 'terrorism' amongst experts, or from experts to policy makers, but rather the construction and consolidation of the social networks of which a core of policy orientated terrorism experts are part. These networks, we argue, cohere not around a core of knowledge producers, as assumed in the Studies of Expertise and Experience (SEE) approach, but rather a set of state and private institutions, the strategic and ideological imperatives of which shape the knowledge produced and circulated by this network. This, we argue, has the effect of militating against evidence based understandings of political violence.

'More business than we could shake a stick at': Challenges in the application of digital forensics in crime examination

Dana Wilson-Kovacs,
(University of Exeter)

The use of digital data in the examination of different types of crime has increased rapidly in recent years, signalling key changes to the ways in which evidence is obtained and analysed. This paper argues that as forensic expertise expands to the digital domain, there is urgent need to capture the development of this field and understand the obstacles it faces. Despite an enduring sociological, social policy and practitioner interest in the contribution of forensics to the investigation of crime, efforts to examine its role and value in a digital context have been rather modest to date. It is argued that aside of the many, mostly fictional, accounts of crime scene investigation that centre largely on the use of forensic genetics, interactions and exchanges pertaining to the forensic field have been rendered invisible and rarely scrutinized in their routine undertaking. While usually subsumed to police work, they are neither self-evident, nor should they be taken for granted. Drawing on fieldwork in progress, which focuses on the application of digital forensics in four police forces in England, the argument explores the uptake and integration of digital forensic practices within existing knowledge structures and organisational arrangements, charting hierarchies of authority and expertise through the perspectives of digital forensic practitioners, computer and mobile phone examiners and police users.

Health Networked Communities as Resilient Issue Publics

Stefania Vicari
(The University of Sheffield)

Social science research has shed light on the potential of mainstream social media platforms for the emergence of experiential health knowledge on the basis of which individuals join networked communities to share information on specific health issues. This research is providing in-depth explorations of the emergence of non-traditional forms of storytelling, where visual content -for instance -plays a key role in sharing personal experiences of health and illness. However, research aimed at thoroughly assessing the potentially different types of information produced and shared on mainstream social media platforms in general and Twitter in particular is still underdeveloped. In other words, is storytelling - textual, visual or multi-format - the only element used by lay actors to learn and share information about health on mainstream social media platforms? Do lay actors only rely on their experiential knowledge to talk about health and illness? These questions – centred on the nature of the discursive work produced on social media platforms - lead us to approach health networked communities as resilient publics forming around issues that have to do with the everyday experience and understanding of health and illness. By employing a digital methods approach to BRCA-focused Twitter data, this paper questions the notion of 'lay expertise' in the production of knowledge around hereditary cancer conditions and sheds light on the need to explore inter-group power dynamics in health information sharing on social media platforms.

Social Divisions / Social Identities A

W110

Everyday inequalities and working-class habituses in Russian industrial neighbourhoods

Alexandrina Vanke,
(University of Manchester)

Various kinds of inequalities structure individuals' everyday lives (Bottero 2019; Irwin 2018), which are space-based and territorially differentiated (Pilkington 2012, 2013). Social markers of class, gender, age and race/ethnicity contribute to framing everyday inequalities, producing unequal power relations and placing individuals in specific locations in social hierarchies (Bottero, Irwin 2003). These social hierarchies, objectified in geographical space (Bourdieu 1985), order everyday experiences and produce specific classed, gendered, aged and raced habituses (Bourdieu 2005; Bourdieu, Wacquant 1992). In the paper, I consider the role of everyday inequalities in the process of production of working-class habituses in two industrial neighbourhoods located in two Russian cities. The research is based on 140 pages of field notes and 48 in-depth ethnographic interviews conducted in 2018. The paper seeks to address the following questions. What kind of everyday inequalities are there in Russian industrial neighbourhoods? How do these inequalities contribute to production of working-class habituses? How do working-class people perceive inequalities inside and outside the neighbourhoods?

An estate revisited: Narratives on 'Tatty houses and Posh streets'

Lyndsey Kramer
(University of York)

This study is work in progress. It formulates ideas around Social Capital, Cultural Capital and migration to an old council estate on the edge of Bradford. The estate is described by Athwal et al (2011:7) in their comparison of three areas of poverty in Bradford, as a 'traditionally white estate'. Since 2015 there has been a flourish of new builds on the estate, many built for private purchase and are owner-occupied or privately rented. Those living in the new builds therefore have different current socioeconomic status to the traditional residents; many also have different ethnic backgrounds as they have come from 2004 EU accession states.

The contention is that the regeneration is in effect an embourgeoisement of certain streets. Employing the theoretical underpinning of Bourdieu's (1984) concept of Cultural Capital, Social Capital and Habitus, the aim is to analyse migrant networks on the estate.

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Drowning by numbers – critical issues in quantitative knowledge production on social exclusion

Sanna Aaltonen, Sakari Karvonen
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In this paper we discuss the classificatory forms of power in producing and reporting quantitative knowledge on young adults on the margins in the Finnish context. Our starting point is a critical reading of recent research reports based on extensive register data gathered by national organizations for administrative and statistical purposes. The register data is increasingly used not only for mapping and tracking the 'socially excluded' youth – almost on a real time basis – but for developing criteria for risk assessments to be conducted among children and young people. Additionally, the online publications tend to use highly elusive graphics to illustrate the state of young adults and the structural divisions between those who fulfill the life-course specific expectations and those who appear to be failing in this task. The latter ones are defined often with an acronym only (NEET) and through negation (not in education, employment or training). Drawing upon a Bourdieusian notion on reflexive sociology we argue that the increasingly sophisticated use of register data and the confidence in quantitative analysis may amount overlooking the unspecificities, uncertainties and unsensitivities of the statistical procedures behind this praxis. Further, we argue that focusing increasingly on visual manifestation may rather contribute to the stigma and the societal problem of exclusion than to alleviate the social conditions of the individuals suffering from it.

Emotional orientations to problems of living in anxiety self-help books

Valérie de Courville Nicol

(Concordia University)

I present elements of my work on anxiety, middle-class identity and self-help books in the United States context (1970-2000). I use an approach I call embodied in/capacity theory to analyze the emotional orientations produced by self-help authors that are popular with readers. I argue that these orientations position readers in a moral understanding of their suffering within a problem/solution complex (i.e. an emotional in/capacity). I outline six forms of in/capacity (e.g. unworthiness/belonging), six types of anxiety (e.g. status anxiety), the agential deficits with which they are associated (e.g. lack of self-esteem), and the strategies for self-transformation (e.g. interdependence, compassion, inclusion). I show how each emotional orientation is grounded in middle-class struggles at navigating significant social transformations in the post-1960s period, for instance the equalization of social relations and the denaturalization of individual value.

Social Divisions / Social Identities B

W828

Living Gender in Diverse Times: Enduring Inequalities and Emerging Possibilities for Young People in the UK

Sally Hines

(University of Leeds)

Following a dramatic rise in the cultural visibility of people who identify across, between or beyond, the categories of male and female, significant cultural commentary has been given to the wider ramifications of gender diversity on young people. For example, media reports in the UK and US regularly declare that the millennial generation – or generation Y - are rejecting traditional gender labels and norms and endorsements of non-binary gendered identity by celebrities are presented as emblematic of this shift. While this suggests that traditional gender identities and expressions are being less rigidly experienced by young people in contemporary society, there is also an important body of research that has long demonstrated how young people's ways of 'doing gender' are constrained by power relations and the circulation of gendered norms. Alongside the continued prevalence of transphobia, this suggests that celebratory declarations of a shift in how young people understand and practice gender demands caution and further exploration.

Drawing on initial findings from an ESRC funded project exploring young people's understandings and practices of gender in the UK, this paper, considers the ways in which gender is understood and practiced by young people from different demographic groups in the UK. In conclusion, the paper foregrounds the concept of intersectionality as key to understanding both enduring inequalities and emerging possibilities of gender in the contemporary UK.

From Gender Egalitarianism to Gender Essentialism: The New Generation of Working Class in Post-Reform China

Anita Koo,

(Hong Kong Polytechnic University)

The Chinese revolution promised women equality with men in all spheres of life. In the course of socialist transformation, China's women have entered a new age, enjoying 'liberation' in the sense of education, high employment rate, and improved social status in society. However, since the market reform, the declining influence of socialist discourse of gender equity has led to the emergence of neoliberal labour market values of human resources that have reshaped the gender division of labour and enhanced gender inequalities. During the same period, a liberalized discourse on gender is prevalent in urban China to an extent that it challenges traditional patriarchal ideology and state discourse on feminism. Today despite their class circumstances, the young generation of Chinese women may feel that they have more power, more freedom and more agency than the previous generation in resisting reified gender roles and making more choices in education and labour market. Even girls from disadvantaged families or with rural background now have chances to receive vocational training before employment. Based on my ethnographic data in Chinese vocational schools, I critically examine the gendering process in schooling to disclose the myth of gender liberation through the coupling effects of individualistic discourse and education. This paper explores how the essentialized gender discourses, the market value of gendered subjects and gendered employment shape the learning and training of the working-class youth. It challenges the liberalized gender discourse which tends to essentialize women's roles in labour market instead of disrupting them, and opening them.

The contemporary gender agenda: transgender and gender fluidity

Shaminder Takhar,

(London South Bank University)

The aim of this paper is to contribute to the discussion about gender politics which focusses on women's oppression and trans liberation. Transgender and gender fluidity is nothing new and the paper looks at how concepts such as cis, transgender, gender fluidity, non-binary and gender dysphoria have emerged in our vocabulary. The second part of the paper concerns Judith Butler's work *Gender Trouble* which uses concepts such as performativity, and examines whether they are useful in an analysis of gender / transgender issues. Despite the controversy surrounding trans exclusionary radical feminist thought, the paper discusses how some feminist thinkers have commented on the fact that there are many ways of being female and male, with trans people widening the spectrum of gender expression. In 2103, 700 feminists issued a statement for trans-inclusive feminism and inclusion in women's spaces, which is a step forward and highlights the question asked by Angela Davis: who are we talking about when we say women? This referred to the exclusivity of the feminist movement which poses an interesting question about the oppression faced by black trans women. It exposes the normalisation of gender and how it can be contested, therefore, the paper asks whether it is possible to go beyond the gender binary which allows for a full expression of identity.

Between class and precarity. Subjective views on inequalities.

Vera Trappmann

(Leeds University Business School)

Inequalities are evolving along different lines. While class still plays a crucial role in the distribution of resources and life chances, explaining the widening gap between rich and poor (Savage et al. 2015, Umney 2018, Lessenich 2017), new axes show their effects as well. Precarization is creating new objective as well as subjectively perceived insecurities even in stable segments of societies. On a global scale, the increase of precarisation is expected to give rise to new forms of collective identity and class consciousness, establishing a precariat (e.g. Standing 2011; critical: Hardy 2015; Wright 2016).

Our contribution therefore inquires the perception of social order and hierarchies among young people in precarious working and living conditions. We ask how they make sense of the inequalities they experience and encounter in their everyday life as well as social structures and social divisions on an abstract level. Based on the analysis of biographical narrative interviews with young people aged 18-35 in the UK and Germany we are able to give insights into the interpretations and legitimisations that make it difficult for young people to translate observations of inequalities into structural and abstract categories as class or precarity.

Sociology of Education A W823

Initial Teacher Education Policy Reforms: Conflict or Collaboration? A Bourdieusian Analysis of the Current Policy Context of Initial Teacher Education in England

Sarah Worton,

(UCL Institute of Education)

The teacher shortage in England has resulted in policy reforms to deregulate the sector and introduce increasing market mechanisms in an effort to recruit more teachers. As I have previously argued (Worton, 2018) neoliberal policies have sought to deal with the recruitment crisis by reworking the public sector to mimic aspects of the private sector. This can be seen through the deregulation of routes into teaching, incentivising and marketing particular training programmes, outsourcing aspects of training to the private sector and structuring recruitment for teachers in ways which sets providers in competition with one another. The aim of the research is to use a critical policy approach to analyse how current policy is affecting power relations in the field and privileging some providers over others. Leaders in Initial Teacher Education (ITE), from both schools and universities, were interviewed to understand their experiences of working in this policy context. This paper will explore their responses in terms of the emerging hierarchy as a result of certain providers possessing more valued capital than others in the field. The research uses Bourdieu's (1992) theoretical and methodological frame to make sense of the current field of ITE and conceptualises the providers as 'agents' working in the field who use different forms of capital to improve their position in the market. Teacher recruitment remains in crisis, and findings suggest that current reforms, rather than solving recruitment problems, are creating complex and unequal playing fields for both providers and applicants, which may be contributing to the continued crisis.

The impact of competing capitals on the sociology of education

Julia Everitt,

(University of Derby)

Education can be viewed as the solitary responsibility of schools, delivered behind closed doors within institutions that operate as silos. However, policies encourage external visitors such as voluntary organisations, employers and post-

16 education providers in to schools to respond to social issues and change including the fragmentation of society. This is seen as a good thing, but the views of those invited are rarely taken into account. The paper presents the perceptions of school staff and external visitors from four case study schools collected through a pro-forma, semi-structured interviews and documentary analysis. The findings indicated the prevalence of different forms of capital e.g. social, cultural and economic (Bourdieu, 1997, Becker, 1964) which were competing. Whilst value may be attributed to the cultural capital of an external visitor, this was often due to the offer of a free activity. Austerity measures forced some schools to use the social capital they built with an external visitor to ask for a free activity even if they lacked qualifications. Some teachers valued the cultural capital of an agent for their specialisms or experience to support young people holistically; whilst others did not as they preferred teachers. Agents used their economic capital to enter schools but some were clearly interested in the marketing aspect of their involvement. However, this was also perceived as beneficial for schools. Access schools was tightly controlled by the school staff which included the types of agents that could enter and the messages they could give out.

An understanding of business engagement in schools in Wales

*Hannah Blake,
(Cardiff University)*

The private sector has always played a role in the educational system, however with the increase in businesses wishing to discharge their corporate social responsibilities in schools, their presence is growing. The form of civil engagement that is employee volunteering is performed by businesses both large and small, although the extent of their action differs accordingly, especially regarding educational involvement. This paper will discuss the findings from research which has been undertaken with schools and businesses in Wales as a means of understanding the types of involvement between businesses and schools and the explanations behind these partnerships. The research is formed from a series of interviews with businesses known to have a CSR policy as well as with schools and pupils who 'benefit' from the involvement of the businesses within the schools. The aim of the research was to understand the justification of businesses and schools who form these partnerships whilst also looking to discover the extent to which schools and their pupils benefit from the engagement with businesses.

Inadequacy of a digital academic

*Francesca Coin,
(Ca' Foscari University)*

Academic research has been one of the first areas to be exposed to the digital revolution. The reform that has marked the passage of academic governance from the Humboldtian university system to the neoliberal university in managerial and business terms, made use of a series of mechanisms aimed at monitoring and evaluating individual performance on an ongoing basis, tracing every interaction taking place in the academic environment and in the outside world. Drawing inspiration from the work of Deborah Lupton, Inger Mewburn and Pat Thomson, *The Digital Academic: Critical Perspectives on Digital Technologies in Higher Education* (2017), this paper looks at the digital self of contemporary academics. Using digital platforms such as Academia.edu, LinkedIn, Google Scholar, University e-repositories, SlideShare, Content aggregator tools, digital academics can increase their daily interactions and the impact of their research. More than being interaction tools, these tools transform the academics into digital individuals whose performance is constantly monitored until they find themselves prisoner of a growing 'dataveillance' (Lupton, Mewburn and Thomson, 2017). In this context, the question concerns not only the impact of digital technologies on the quality of contemporary research, but also the impact of digital surveillance on the living and working conditions of contemporary academics, at a time where the tensions, conflicts and malaise that inhabit the neoliberal university have become ever more manifest.

Sociology of Education B W002

Working-Class Students as Imposters in Elite Higher Education? Racism, Classism and the Politics of Belonging

*Carli Rowell , n/a
(University of Glasgow)*

'I've never seen a black girl'

'Speak the queens English [...] you fucking common scum'

'Oh my god were you like poor?'

'You're at the university, are you sure?'

A growing body of work illuminates the pressures and pulls of everyday academic life within and the effects upon the self. Feelings of imposterism, fraudulence, inauthenticity and non-belonging emerge in response to the 'toxic impossibilities' (Pereira 2016) of neoliberal-academia. However, much of this work derives largely from the reflections of academics, aspiring, established or otherwise (Breeze 2018; Gill and Donaghue 2016; Loveday 2018; Pereira 2016). Drawing upon an ethnography of working-class students at an elite university this paper contributes to the collective endeavour of casting light upon and challenging contemporary university life. It explores the ways in which the neoliberal-university and neoliberalism per se plays out in the lives of and compounds participants experiences of studying at an elite university and draws attention to the ways in which the working-class, first generation students were made to feel like imposters as a result of their seemingly mundane pedagogical and socio-cultural interactions.

In doing so, this paper asks: What are the effect of being accused of lying about one's student status in order to romantically impress others; of having your academic grades called into question as a result of your status as a recipient of social security? Of recognising a photo of your locale in a lecture that heavily perpetuates racialized serotypes; of being told your fucking common scum and that you don't belong?

Evaluating the fairness of admissions to UK higher education

*Vikki Boliver, Stephen Gorard and Pallavi Banerjee
(Durham University)*

An essential ingredient of fair access to higher education is fair admission, commonly defined as equal chances of admission for equally well qualified applicants regardless of social background. At present, the evidence regarding the fairness of university admissions in the UK according to this definition is mixed. Previous studies have found that applicants from lower socioeconomic backgrounds, state schools, and ethnic minority groups are less likely to be offered university places than applicants from more advantaged backgrounds, even when they have studied the same subjects and achieved the same grades in A-level and equivalent qualifications (Zimdars, Sullivan and Heath 2009; Boliver 2013; Noden, Shiner and Modood 2014; Boliver 2015 and 2016). However, contrary evidence published by UCAS (2015, 2017), using different variables, different modelling techniques, and more recent data, suggests that university offer rates by socioeconomic background and ethnicity are within expected margins of error once predicted A-level grades and specific degree programme applied to have been taken into account. UCAS data has been inaccessible to academic researchers and policy-makers for the past six years. This paper makes use of newly-released UCAS data for recent cohorts of applicants to explore the question of fair admissions in definitive detail.

Can private providers be expected to improve higher education inclusion, choice and quality in the UK?

*Stephen Hunt, Vikki Boliver
(UCL: Institute of Education)*

The UK government is keen to grow the private provision of higher education as a means of promoting greater choice and quality for students and of facilitating faster progress on widening access to higher education.

We assess these much-mooted benefits of private provision drawing on unique data from a comprehensive a 2017 UK web-based survey of private providers carried out as part of our work within the Centre for Global Higher Education.

We mapped their geographical distribution. Our findings indicate they are poorly placed to contribute to widening access, being concentrated in the South-east, particularly London, and underrepresented in low HE participation neighbourhoods.

With regard to greater choice for students, our findings suggest that private providers offer a much narrower range of disciplinary specialisms than public providers, and often offer courses at sub-degree or postgraduate level rather than at traditional bachelors level. With regard to quality, although many private providers are validated by a public provider or public body, only a minority have had any kind of external quality inspection. Moreover, an estimated 30 percent of private providers ceased to operate between 2014 and 2017, which is suggestive of quality issues including the adverse effects of sudden 'provider exit' on students.

We conclude that private providers are unlikely to be the answer to the UK government's higher education ambitions as the sector is currently structured.

Theory W323

Decolonizing Theory II: Race, Postcolonialism, and the Decolonial

Nasar Meer,

(University of Edinburgh)

Calls to decolonise universities have become more insistent in recent months. This has included both a growing concern with the Eurocentric nature of the curriculum and the ways in which disciplines are implicated in this. This session - alongside the one on Decolonising Theory: Race, Postcolonialism, and the Decolonial - asks what it would mean to decolonise theory. How could we do theory differently and what sort of different theory would we need to participate effectively in the conversations around decolonising knowledge. This session orients around issues of culture and epistemological justice.

Race in the Decolonial

*Nasar Meer,
(Edinburgh University)*

What role is the category of race playing in decolonial theory? Specifically, are clusters of scholarship on macro and micro racialization (e.g., CRT and racial formation, and everyday racism and the study of micro-aggressions) retaining their distinctive explanatory power, or being folded into a more diffuse decolonial critique. In this paper, it is argued that paying attention to a distinction between these traditions, and then trying to get them not only in the “right order”, but also on their own terms, is conceptually fruitful – however messy the outcome may be. This exercise also includes opening up the relationship between the decolonial and the postcolonial. What is advocated is an approach in which traditions of critical race scholarship, postcolonialism and the decolonial are not subsumed into one another, but retain distinctive and explanatory power.

Teaching anti-racist materialisms

*Angela Last
(University of Leicester)*

This paper asks what it means to teach an anti-racist materialism. The paper will look at both historical/dialectical materialism and new materialism. Due to its ‘levelling’ movement, materialism is generally associated with anti-elitism and anti-anthropocentrism. However, materialist history is also entangled with racist scientific and even occult histories, as, for instance, authors such as Donna V. Jones have argued. In this paper, I would like to take a closer look at the materialist histories that do not tend to get taught, and how not teaching them leaves many of our supposedly progressive theorisations with tacit racist elements. The paper argues that, instead of singling out racist theorists such as Heidegger etc and distancing us from them, we should look at all theory as having a racist heritage that still remains underexamined.

The Racial Conditions of Homo Economicus

*James Trafford,
(University for the Creative Arts)*

This paper addresses a structural lacuna at the heart of approaches to neoliberalism by both liberal advocates and Marxian critics. According to the widely accepted accounts of Wendy Brown, Will Davies, and Wolfgang Streeck, neoliberalism reaches beyond economic policies of deregulation, privatisation, and welfare roll-back, to shape all human activity according to market principles. This does away with substantive differences between us, and reconstructs us as market actors in the image of homo economicus. However, this universalising narrative fails to account for the ways in which this economisation of culture is fundamentally shaped by, and gives shape to, racial stratifications. The idea that the technical rationality of economics has overcome liberal cultural and political realms reproduces the separation of cultural phenomena like race from economic phenomena like markets made by liberal advocates of neoliberalism. Resultantly, neither approach can explain why the racialization of society has gotten worse not better, and they force the unconvincing argument that neoliberalism is coming to an end through the revenge of politics. By analysing the ways that Foucault’s critique of homo economicus was used to analyse the 2008 financial crisis, I show that this interpretation has obscured and legitimated the increasing coloniality internal to metropolitan centres. Race emerges as a structuring principle for these approaches, with entrenched raciality productive of the subject proper of neoliberal economics and politics; required even for homo economicus to function.

Work, Employment & Economic Life A

HANGING LANTERN ROOM

Varieties of precarity in Europe: An empirical analysis of different types of precarity in comparative perspective

Christiana Ierodiakonou, Ioulia Bessa
(University of Cyprus)

The paper focuses on the concept of precarity, whose prevalence has massively proliferated the past years in academic and public policy debates. Yet, the term remains theoretically fragmented (Della Porta et al., 2015) and empirically under-investigated (Standing, 2011, 2014). Consistent with Puar (2012) and Nielsen and Rossiter (2015), we argue that precarity transcends the financial and contractual vulnerability that extant research tends to focus on (Rubery et al, 2018; Moore and Newsome, 2018). We thus propose a multi-dimensional conceptualisation of precarity that is theoretically informed and empirically tested, including four broad facets. In addition to the typical employment and financial facets, we suggest that precarity also relates to household and social aspects, arguing that varieties of precarity in Europe go beyond employment (Alberti et al, 2018)

Drawing on data from the 2015 European Working Conditions Survey (EWCS) from 17 countries, we first used factors analysis to create different factors that measure the multiple elements of the different precarity facets. Then, we conducted latent class analysis to create clusters that identify homogeneous groups of individuals with similar characteristics considering these four precarity aspects. In what is next, we will explore the profiles of clusters to understand who is most affected by each type of precarity and 'map' the clusters to identify how varieties of precarity are distributed in Europe. Finally, we will use the EWCS 2005 data in order to compare and explore whether and how the economic crisis has had significant effects on the aspects, extent or distribution of precarity.

Un/Associated: Accounting for Gender Difference and Farmer Heterogeneity Among Peruvian Sierra Potato Small Farmers

Anouk Patel-Campillo, Anouk Patel Campillo
(London School of Economics and Political Science)

Recognizing the challenges faced by small farmers, international institutions have encouraged national governments to foster the collective organization of small farmers and farmer membership through policy interventions that target rural populations, and more specifically 'women' and 'marginalized farmers'. Yet, access to membership continues to elude the most disadvantaged small farmers. Based on Peru's 2012 National Agricultural Census, we conduct cross-group (women versus men) and intra-group (among women and among men) comparisons to tease out markers of social difference that account for exclusion. We argue that considering women and marginalized farmers as homogeneous and residual populations obscures the social markers that differentiate small farmers. It points to gender-based inequality as well as other forms of inequality that influence the membership status. Regionally, our analysis points to gendered spatial inequalities exemplified a large number of districts without the presence of associated women potato farmers. At the national level, we also find that the gender asset gap in land ownership favours men but we find differences in the magnitude of the gender asset gap regionally and mixed patterns of land ownership by women and men at the district level. Our analysis of household composition points to the feminization of women farmer households due to the absence of male partners and a large presence of elderly women in comparison to men farmer households. Overall, our analysis shows that while gender-based inequality persists, there are other cross-cutting markers of social differentiation among women and men that influence farmer membership status.

Masculinity, precarity and the moral economies of post-socialism: working-class men in contemporary Russia

Charlie Walker,
(University of Southampton)

A defining feature of social hierarchies and inequalities across Western neoliberal economies has been the material and symbolic impoverishment of working-class men that has resulted from the replacement of stable, blue collar jobs with forms of precarious employment, and, in turn, has been said to underpin the recent surge in right-wing populist movements. This paper draws on ethnographic research with working-class men in Russia, who, like their western counterparts, are pathologised as abject losers lacking the qualities of responsibility, flexibility and self-improvement demanded by the new economy. The paper explores how, in contrast to the racist value hierarchies of Lamont's (2002) American workers, or the white victimhood of Hochschild's (2016), manual labourers in the cities of Moscow and Ulyanovsk adopt positions of value in a moral economy constructed on the imaginaries of state socialism, prioritising notions of collectivism over individualism, use value over profit, and honesty over corruption. These psychic landscapes of class (Reay 2011), as well as drawing on the Soviet past, stem both from the men's failed attempts at self-reinvention through education and employment in the new service sector, and from efforts to mobilise their cultural, social and bodily capital to bridge the gap between low and insecure income and familial expectations of them as providers. The paper thus emphasizes that, although in material terms men's responses to marginalisation – predominantly excessive working practices that undermine physical wellbeing – are familiar and limited, their political responses are not confined to the reactionary cultural politics identified in existing accounts.

Theorising precariousness, precarity and vulnerability in the context of UK austerity

Stefanie Petschick,
(Nottingham Trent University)

Vulnerability and 'precarious life' have emerged as concepts within feminist philosophy and have been powerful in challenging discursive and political framings of violence and conflict. They have been used to develop critical ethical responses to the normalisation of violence and have been involved in developing new perspectives on political agency and ways to theorise forms of resistance (Butler, Gambett, Sabsay, 2016). This paper explores the ways in which this body of theory can be mobilised in researching and theorising precarious work and precarity in the context of UK austerity. The paper therefore brings together these two areas of research and theory development, investigating their existing intersections and developing new ways of understanding and articulating precarious work. Approaching precarity as a politically induced condition that exposes different populations to unequal levels of risk, this paper suggests understanding austerity as a form of violence, raising ethical questions for researchers in the field.

Work, Employment & Economic Life B

W001

Apprenticeship training as equalizer? – Social origin, individual decisions, institutional arrangements and the stratification process

Hans Dietrich, Oliver Wölfel

(Institute for Employment Research (IAB))

This paper studies transitions from general education into apprenticeship training and from apprenticeship training into a first employment position in Germany. Employing linked survey data from the ALWA-study and register-based data (IEB), the authors extend the standard model of status attainment by introducing the firm as independent actor. Sequential logit and simulation models are performed. In line with the status attainment theory our empirical findings confirm social background effects (parental education and labour market participation) on descendants' decisions for apprenticeship training and the labour market decision after graduation from apprenticeship training. These findings are in line with empirical results from models in the context of school based educational decisions. Additionally, we identify an own-standing effect of the training firm on individuals' decisions regarding transition from general education into apprenticeship training or higher education and from apprenticeship training into higher education or the labour market. As the available set of observable characteristics typically is limited to analyse individuals' and firms' behaviour, the authors take unobserved heterogeneity into account. Simulation models allow unobserved heterogeneity both to vary in size and to interact with explanatory or confounding variables. These simulation models indicate interaction effects of unobserved heterogeneity with confounding variables which may affect not only the size of coefficients but also their direction.

Care crises and policy: how social hierarchies and inequality play out in landscapes of care

Andrew Fletcher, Linda McKie

(Durham University)

The UK's ageing population, combined with issues around austerity and changing employment practices, increase the complexities of care provision across the lifespan. This has become an ongoing 'care crisis' (Dilnot, 2011), which is experienced in different ways by different groups according to gender, social class, and spatial and temporal dimensions.

The issues of care and workplace care policies are emerging as points of intersectional inequality within rapidly changing employment and demographic contexts. These are perpetuated in a large part by the care policy structures that simultaneously alienate women and trap them within low-paid work roles. We recently described how low-paid female employees avoid using workplace care policies, which are inadequate or irrelevant to their needs (Fletcher and McKie, 2018). We now focus on identifying and enabling policy-based solutions, including: sociological approaches that give policymakers the frameworks to understand policy users' needs; international examples that exploit cultural characteristics such as concepts of reciprocity and time banking ideas; and strategies for approaching policy overhaul that ask: how can we use this knowledge to inform workplace policy structures and increase 'enabling flexibility' for women?

This is most pressing for low-paid women workers who cannot afford to buy in care solutions, yet provide or script the majority of activity in their care-worlds. They are discriminated against by care policies that are supposed to help them. By exploring solutions to this multifaceted structural problem, we can go some way to addressing it.

The field of graduate recruitment: leading financial and consultancy firms and elite class formation

Sol Gamsu, Michael Donnelly

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In a crowded graduate labour market, the symbolic value of transitioning to a high status multinational employer likely represents an important marker of distinction. For the first time, a unique Destinations of Leavers in Higher Education (DLHE) data-set is used here to model entry to elite multinational employers in finance, accountancy and consultancy sectors among graduates of different social origins, universities, degree subjects and with different degree classifications. From a sample of 11,755 graduates working across these three sectors, we examine what predicts entry to 33 leading firms and then examine pay hierarchies amongst the 3,260 graduates working for these companies using random-effects models. At first glance, significantly, we find that elite recruits come from a much broader range of universities than might be imagined. However, a closer look at the highest paid graduates within these firms reveals more familiar patterns of social and institutional stratification. We argue that these patterns likely reflect the nature of work undertaken by graduates in these elite firms, with institutional and social origins of graduates differing according to the particular track taken in what are likely to be highly differentiated graduate recruitment schemes.

Thursday 25/04/2019 at 15:30 - 17:00
Paper Session 6

Cities, Mobilities, Place & Space A
W622

Reconstructing Mapuche-ness through Ethnic Place Production: Ruralising the Urban Context Together.

Dana Brablec-Sklenar,
(University of Cambridge)

Cities have rapidly become the main residential site for indigenous peoples worldwide; this represents one of the most important challenges faced by modern indigenous societies making them vulnerable to a range of socio-political and economic inequalities. The Mapuche are a good example of this situation, with 35% of their population concentrated in Santiago alone. The article provides an examination of the ways in which the Mapuche collectively negotiate the use of space with local-municipality authorities for the development of ethnic-based activities such as workshops and ceremonies in Santiago de Chile. When successful, Mapuche associations have been able to materially appropriate a space under a loan concession. Nevertheless, even when negotiations with the public sector failed, the collective action of individuals, framed by Mapuche associational margins, has still allowed the Mapuche to appropriate space by symbolically gaining it as their own ethnic place. The article engages in the debates for the creation of an updated urban indigenous policy that tackles the increasing cultural, political and economic demands of this population.

From burden to reciprocal advantage: the Utrecht Refugee Launchpad as an experiment in local consent

Caroline Oliver, Rianne Dekker and Karin Geuijen
(University of Roehampton)

'Socius young people and refugees live here together' proclaimed the banner tied to the railings outside the Plan Einstein asylum seeker complex in the wijk (neighbourhood) of Overvecht in Utrecht. This was the public face of the Utrecht Refugee Launchpad, an initiative that was developed in the face of the sudden arrival of asylum seekers following the refugee 'crisis' in 2015-2016. This paper will present findings from two years research into the project, an urban innovation led by the city council to develop a more dynamic, socially inclusive and 'future-free integration process' for asylum seekers and refugees. Opening Plan Einstein in this marginal neighbourhood was risky however; therefore in response to anti-immigrant hostility, local residents were offered 'something back'. This included access to local housing provision on the same site and entry to the same entrepreneurship programmes, English language classes and social activities as asylum seekers. Situated in sociological and geographical work on social contact and everyday multiculturalism, the paper will explore the nature of encounter within these designed spaces. Using mixed methods research among stakeholders, local youth living in the centre, neighbourhood residents (some of whom participated in activities) and asylum seekers, it will critically examine the potential and reality of whether shared 'presence' through 'living and learning together' disrupts binaries of 'host' and 'guest' communities. In particular, we expose how the material infrastructure of the centre – and ultimately debates about locks, keys and kitchens - shaped relations, ultimately influencing possibilities for more intimate knowledge of the other.

The plight of cultural co-existence among migratory groups in Algerian marginal urban environments

kelthoum Bibimoune, Aouar Dallel
(University of Batna1)

Abstract : In the light of the changes that have taken place in the world during the last decay, the phenomenon of illegal immigration to neighboring countries, in particular, has widely spread. The belief that the receiving countries would provide, in addition to peace, the appropriate social, economic and sanitary atmospheres that migrants have long dreamed of and lacked in their own countries are the main objectives behind emigration. However, the shocking reality emigrants face once they land on the receiving soils may be even more severe than what they left behind them in their own original countries. The present work is mainly a descriptive case study of the immigrant communities' daily life for the duration of their presence in the city of Batna - Algeria . More precisely we aim to portray those immigrants' reality under the cultural practices and the linguistic fusion in the marginal urban environments of the city of Batna. Questions like: what forms of cultural coexistence are being pursued by immigrant minorities with the local culture ? How can they achieve their endeavors in the light of the disadvantaged marginal urban environment of the host area?

How can the weak structures of those areas reflect on the forms of cultural coexistence, and affect the possibility of culturally accepting or rejecting the other?; form the sum of the issues which we aim to elucidate in the present research.

Cities, Mobilities, Place & Space B

W610

Public libraries, austerity and homelessness

Emma Davidson

(Centre for Research on Families and Relationships)

Public libraries do far more than lend books. They are one of the remaining freely accessible civil society institutions and, in their local form, provide a public sphere for civil engagement; from social arena, to providing opportunities for participation. However, austerity measures have cut public library budgets, resulting in limited opening hours, depleted stocks, reduced staff and a growing reliance on volunteers. Other services are fighting, or have succumb to, closure.

While cuts to public libraries affect us all, the consequences are unequal and reflect a widening gulf between rich and poor. Those who are excluded, less able or disenfranchised disproportionately rely on public libraries, not only as a source of information, but as a space of inclusion. To illustrate, this paper draws on ongoing research on the impact of austerity on public libraries. It presents the accounts of homeless people and their everyday encounters with their local library. On one hand the public library was relied on for access to information services necessary for navigating welfare reform, for informal education and books for enjoyment. On the other, it cultivated homeless users' sense of belonging, providing a space of safety, peace and sanctuary. The paper demonstrates the vital contribution that public libraries make to supporting community well-being and social justice – but only when given proper investment and priority. A stark rendering of what will be lost should statutory public library services continue to be cut, this paper demonstrates how austerity is creating the conditions for widening social divisions.

Mothering, norms and urban resource access: organizing resources as symbolic economy?

Talja Blokland, Hannah Schilling

(Humboldt Universitaet Berlin)

This paper connects emerging new perspectives in global urban studies on the fluidity and invisible forms of urban life (Simone 2010; Nutall&Mbembe 2008) to more mainstream understandings of structured forms of durable inequalities, by elaborating on the concept of symbolic capital (Bourdieu 2000; 1977, Skeggs 2004; 2011). We show that the ability to economize on and to invest in norms of benevolence, reciprocity, honor and kinship matters for the organization of resources. The paper draws on empirical work in Berlin and Abidjan on the livelihood of single mothers and young adults living in lower-middleclass and poor neighborhoods. The interviewees in Abidjan stress the importance of investing in reputation building, gifting and reciprocating services, in fleeting encounters and temporary associations. This is acknowledged as important form of ensuring livelihoods in postcolonial settings (Vuarin 2000; Simone 2010). Starting from there, we juxtapose Abidjan's realities with the practices of single mothers in Berlin. To them, making use of symbolic resources matters, too. Through the comparison, we show how symbolic capital is used for organizing livelihood at the juncture of different fields: the domestic, the institutional and the market (see Wood & Gough 2006 on welfare regimes). This way, we draw attention to economies invisible in analytical frameworks focusing on income and official stocks of capital. In other words, the constraints that come with lone parenthood in late capitalism and its current forms of (re)commodification, are entangled with a renewed importance of symbolic capital that analyses on inequalities have to take into consideration.

The mobility of exclusion through time and place: 'lesser' citizens in public space

Nicola Helps,

(Monash University)

For populations perceived to be, and treated as less than full citizens, experiences of social exclusion are 'normal', 'everyday', 'ongoing', and 'enduring.' Contrastingly, experiences of social inclusion are constructed as the exception, existing only in isolated moments, and often attached to specific places, events or initiatives. This paper examines the way in which experiences of social inclusion and social exclusion are reflected in and reinforced through practices and processes of governing public spaces within Victoria, Australia. In doing so, this paper seeks to advance our conceptual understanding of spatiotemporal governance and social exclusion.

Drawing on move-on directions, as well as crime prevention through environmental design initiatives (CPTED) as case examples this paper argues that exclusion both dominates particular spatiotemporal contexts and is able to move with the 'lesser' citizen through time and place. This leads to the contention that it is necessary to conceptualise exclusion as not exclusively attached to specific places or mechanisms but as attached to individual, stigmatized, 'lesser' bodies.

The implication of this conceptualisation is that in order to disrupt the narrative of exclusion, we must not only interrogate individual mechanisms of governance (which operate in specific spatiotemporalities). Rather, we must also disrupt the broader social, cultural, political and legal narrative which is characterised by stigma and exclusion.

Towards a Visual Grammar of Benefits Stigma: Representations of Space and Place in Factual Welfare Programming

*Lisa Taylor, Dr Katherine Harrison, Professor Jayne Raisborough
(Leeds Beckett University)*

This paper presents the initial findings of an analysis of representations of space and place in a current example of Factual Welfare Programming (FWP): Channel 5's *On Benefits*. Spatial segregation is a key feature of new forms and experiences of urban poverty. Precarity, economic exploitation and government spending cuts effectively herd marginalised and vulnerable individuals into areas that are 'abandoned' as the State retreats through its neoliberal austerity policies. Poor people have little choice about their place of residence yet are defined by and held accountable for it. Yet, while scholarly work has rightly criticised media constructions of 'undeserving' benefits claimants themselves, the role of space and place in FWP has not been explored and, consequently, we lack an understanding of the ideological work performed by representations of impoverished urban and domestic scenes in the creation of benefits stigma. This paper addresses this gap through a visual grammar analysis of *On Benefits*. The paper analyses: (i) the representation of cities, streets and domestic interiors in *On Benefits*; (ii) cinematographic strategies that draw attention to recurring streetscapes, roomscales and incongruous domestic objects; (iii) the composition of spatial imagery into an overall narrative generative of stigma. In so doing, the paper aims to expose the cultural mechanisms used in FWP to generate disgust around space and place and to attach stigma to benefit claimants based on locales and residences not necessarily of their choosing or within their control.

Culture, Media, Sport & Food W308

There was no golden age: social mobility into cultural and creative occupations

*Orian Brook, Orian Brook, Dave O'Brien, Mark Taylor
(University of Edinburgh)*

Cultural and creative industries are currently narrated in policy and by key public figures as one of the greatest forces for openness and social mobility in Britain (Hancock 2016). However, there is scarce evidence to support this position. Recent research suggests creative and cultural occupations are dominated by those from professional and managerial backgrounds, with cultural theorists arguing this reflects declining rates of social mobility over time. This paper provides the first empirical assessment of claims made by policy and cultural theory concerning changing patterns of social mobility into cultural and creative occupations. We use the ONS Longitudinal Study to offer the first analysis of changes in social mobility into creative occupations over time. We demonstrate that: creative occupations have always been characterised by overrepresentations of those from privileged social origins, with little evidence of a classless meritocracy; absolute social mobility is declining in these occupations, contradicting policymakers' faith in a 'meritocracy' for talented individuals aiming to work in artistic and cultural jobs; this is in contrast to stability in relative social mobility, indicating there was no 'golden age' for social mobility into cultural occupations. These three points underline the importance of occupational perspectives on creative industries and the value of sociological analysis for public policy questions in this area. In particular, the lack of social fluidity in the occupations producing culture is a key issue for future public policy intervention.

Bureaucratic control and gendered discrimination in the cultural industries

*Gavin Maclean, Katherine Sang, Diljeet Bhachu
(Edinburgh Napier University)*

With the increased attention to disparities between men and women within the cultural industries in light of the BBC pay review and the rise of the #MeToo movement, this paper examines the sources of underrepresentation of and inequalities experienced by women within the cultural industries. Following researchers who have called for research to link inequalities to the production and consumption of culture (Oakley and O'Brien, 2016), this paper draws on a cultural labour studies perspective to examine how 'bureaucratic' forms of control in production (Ryan, 1992; Hesmondhalgh, 2013) perpetuate inequalities within cultural work. This paper draws on qualitative data from interviews with 41 women working within a number of cultural industries - including actors, screen and theatre writers, classical, folk and 'indie' musicians and dancers. This paper demonstrates how strategies to reduce risk within the industries, such as the use of genres and commissioning decisions based on consumption, gender the resulting

production process. 'Bureaucratic' controls within productions – such as casting calls and auditions – ultimately work to exclude women further.

Hierarchies and divisions in the subfield of Italian gallery owners.

*Anna Uboldi,
(University of Milan)*

This work examines the occupation of the gallery owner from a Bourdieusian perspective, open to some interactionist suggestions (Becker 2004, Goffman 2002). This study takes place in Italian art galleries in Milan. It is a qualitative research based on in-depth interviews with gallery owners and participant observations during openings and art fairs. The analysis explores some characteristics of this occupational culture (Hughes 2010). The field of gallery owners is a case of economy of symbolic goods, characterized by a double loyalty to both artistic and economic values (Bourdieu, 2005). This ambivalence takes shape in the definition of gallerist in opposition to the idea of art dealer. It acts within practices and discourses and it structures internal divisions in the art gallery field. The moral claim of the label of 'gallerist' (Bourdieu 2001) allows interpreting some dimensions of this creative microcosm. First, I propose a classification of gallery owners' profiles, through the heuristic lens of the field of cultural production (Bourdieu, 2005) and in terms of different positions-taking. Secondly, art fairs are interpreted as ceremonial events and amoral representations (Goffman 2002). They are social occasions where this community affirms, through interactional practices, its occupational identity. To summarize, the analysis reveals some clashes of classification and hierarchies in the art gallery field. In this way, I can define this microcosm of work as an occupation between humility and pride (Hughes, 2010).

Families & Relationships

W727

Children's Privacy in Families in Turkey: Power, Control and Surveillance over 'Minors'

*Hamide Elif Üzümcü,
(University of Padova, Italy)*

Children are often considered at the bottom of the social hierarchy in many cultures. They are often addressed as vulnerable minors and dependants in dichotomy with adulthood. In contemporary Turkey as well, children's social position tends to be defined through the power relations with adults. This research deals with children's physical, emotional and intellectual spaces, in other words, children's privacy within the unequal relations between family components in Turkey.

The new sociology of childhood approach challenges societal positioning of children as passive recipients of family socialization and recognizes children as social actors with agency who influence the social conditions as well as being influenced by them. Employing this approach, the research aims to understand how family members consider children's privacy at home. In order to comprehend how children's privacy is constructed around their daily life practices, two everyday domestic life spheres are observed: Children's media uses and their uses of domestic spaces.

In this qualitative research, in-depth interviews are conducted with 24 families with 11-12-year-old children in Eskisehir, Turkey. Interviews with children are made individually while with parents as a couple. Each interview data is supported with extensive ethnographic notes. Participatory action techniques are adapted throughout interviews with children, such as playing online games together, looking at posts from their favourite Instagram/YouTube accounts. In this paper, preliminary findings of the ongoing fieldwork will be presented. Novelty of the research is that the delicate social matter of privacy will be analysed through children's voices in Turkey where privacy has Islamic connotations.

Gender inequalities at home: time allocations among UK mothers and fathers and associations with parental wellbeing

*Svetlana Speight, Allison Dunatchik, Robert Wishart
(National Centre for Social Research)*

The UK has seen some convergence in how parents divide paid work and care, with a growth in dual full-time earner households, increased working hours of mothers in part-time employment (Connolly et al., 2016; ONS, 2018), growing expectations around 'a participative father' (Adler and Lenz, 2016, O'Brien, 2013) and continuing shifts towards more egalitarian views on division of labour within the household (Taylor and Scott, 2018). However, mothers still spend substantially more time on housework and childcare than fathers (Altintas and Sullivan, 2016; Wishart et al., 2018).

The paper uses data from the UK Time Use Survey 2014-15 to examine the relationship between parental time-use patterns and their levels of wellbeing. We examine wellbeing across a range of outcomes (including evaluative,

eudemonic and hedonic measures) and aim to assess to what extent within-household gender inequalities in time use contribute to how parents experience and evaluate their life.

Previous research suggests that levels of wellbeing among parents in the UK and many other countries are substantially lower than those among non-parents (Glass et al., 2016). It has also been found (at least, for the US) that parents do not always enjoy childcare activities (Roeters and Gracia, 2016). The dataset we are using contains time-use and wellbeing measures for both mother and father in the same household and therefore allows us to examine gender inequalities in within-household time allocations and how these may affect parental wellbeing.

The study is funded by the Economic and Social Research Council.

Marital disruption, remarriage and child wellbeing in China

*Yang Hu,
(Lancaster University)*

Demographic and family changes in contemporary China are characterized by a dual increase in marital disruption and remarriage. In this research, I analyze data from the 2015 China Education Panel Survey (N = 8,933) to profile and explain well-being disparities between children from intact, disrupted and remarried families. The results show that children fare less well in disrupted than in intact families. Remarriage, particularly that of both parents, is associated with additional damages to children's well-being, over and above marital disruption. There is also considerable gender asymmetry in father's and mother's remarriage. While the former is associated with children's mental distress, the latter is also associated with impaired educational wellbeing and cognitive development. Social selection, economic and non-pecuniary resources played little role in explaining the poorer wellbeing experienced by children in disrupted families and stepfamilies, compared with intact families. While family structure mediates wellbeing disparities between children from disrupted and intact families, it does not explain why children fare less well in stepfamilies than in intact biological families. Variations in child well-being with parents' marital status are most consistently explained by poor parent-child relationship and parental conflicts. Comparative assessment of marital disruption and remarriage demonstrates that remarriage is not just another 'marital transition' for children. Rather, the two are qualitatively distinct. Reflecting critically on the theories of selectivity, resource deprivation and structural instability, the findings highlight the need to consider China's distinctive sociocultural and institutional settings in configuring the gendered relationship between marital instability and child well-being.

Race, Ethnicity & Migration A W011

Writing Justice/ Performing Injustice: Publicity and the Birmingham Trojan Horse Affair

*Lucy Mayblin, John Holmwood, Therese O'Toole, Helen Monks, Khadijah Elshayyal
(University of Warwick
from Nov 2018 Change to University of Sheffield)*

The session has 3 main elements. It will in part be an 'author meets critics' event focussing on John Holmwood and Therese O'Toole's recent book 'Countering Extremism in British Schools? The Truth about the Birmingham Trojan Horse Affair.' However, it will move beyond a simple focus on the book and explore the public sociology which the authors have been engaged in as part of the 'Trojan Horse' case. This involved Holmwood participating as an expert witness in the legal case associated with the Trojan Horse affair, and also acting as consultant on a theatre production which explores it. The director of the theatre production (which was performed in London and at Edinburgh Festival in 2018) will present at the session, reflecting on the process of producing this play in dialogue with sociologists and others. Finally, Khadijah Elshayyal will act as discussant, drawing linkages between the two presentations and reflecting on the theme of writing justice, performing injustice.

This special session focuses on the Birmingham Trojan Horse affair in which school teachers and governors were (falsely) accused of a 'plot' to Islamise schools. Reflecting on their recent book *Countering Extremism in British Schools? The Truth about the Birmingham Trojan Horse Affair*, John Holmwood and Therese O'Toole will discuss the book as well as the process of acting as an expert witness for the defence in the Trojan Horse affair. Their reflections will be framed in relation to doing public sociology in the context of populism and the criticism of experts. Here, the idea of an 'expert witness' offers a viable and positive account of 'publicity' but there are challenges in writing for justice against the backdrop of Islamophobia and secular criticism of religion. The case is similar to that of Hillsborough, where the truth about the affair has been suppressed and those seeking to uncover it, in both sociological writing and theatrical performance, have been accused of facilitating 'extremism'. In dialogue with these reflections, the director of a play based upon the Birmingham Trojan Horse affair (which won the 2018 Amnesty International Freedom of Expression award) will discuss the process of researching, writing and performing within a challenging political climate. Holmwood acted as expert consultant to this play, in this sense extending the scope of

his public sociology in relation to this case. Finally, Khadijah Elshayyal will act as discussant, drawing linkages between the two presentations and reflecting on the theme of researching justice, performing injustice.

The role of sociology as witness for the defence: a model for public sociology?

John Holmwood, T. O' Toole
(University of Nottingham)

This presentation will discuss Holmwood and O'Toole's recent book 'Countering Extremism in British Schools? The Truth about the Birmingham Trojan Horse Affair' (Polity Press, 2018). The presenters will also offer reflection on the process of acting as expert witness for the defence in the Birmingham Trojan Horse affair, in the light of discussions of public sociology in the context of populism and criticism of experts. Paradoxically, it will argue that the idea of an 'expert witness' offers a viable and positive account of 'publicity'. The obligation is to the court, considered as a locus of the staging of arguments and clarification of fact. The expert witness facilitates decision-making by those who are constituted to make that decision as representatives of the public. It will also discuss the problems of writing for justice in the context of widespread Islamophobia and secular criticism of religion, including in the self-understanding of sociologists and reflect upon the controversial effect on debate of changes to the Prevent agenda (counter extremism) that arose from the Government's peremptory and, arguably, authoritarian response to the affair.

Performing injustice: the role and responsibility of verbatim theatre

Helen Monks
(Lung Theatre)

This presentation offers reflections on the process of researching, writing and performing a play based upon the Birmingham Trojan Horse affair. It will consider how dramatic effect operates in the context of verbatim theatre and the dramatic role of 'balance', both in terms of characters selected for portrayal, and selection of topics. The presentation will also address the broader social and political context in which the play, and the response to the play, must be understood. The play, Trojan Horse, was critically acclaimed and won the Amnesty International Freedom of Expression award. See attached document on reception.

Medicine, Health & Illness B

W009

The role of workplace accommodations in explaining the UK disability employment gap

Tarani Chandola, Patrick Rouxel
(University of Manchester)

The UK Government is aiming to halve the disability employment gap. Reducing the disability employment gap is not simply a matter of getting currently unemployed disabled people into work, but also stemming the flow of people from work into unemployment and economic inactivity due to ill-health and the onset of impairments. Workplace accommodations (such as modified tasks, duties, hours, equipment and services) have been proposed as one of the key interventions to enable disabled workers to remain in work. Systematic reviews of Randomised Control Trials (RCTs) suggest workplace accommodations enable workers with musculoskeletal conditions to return to work. However, the evidence is weak in relation to workers with mental health condition. Moreover, evidence from Randomised Control Trials is problematic as in real life, social and power dynamics between the disabled worker and their manager can make the negotiation of workplace accommodations fraught and stressful.

We analysed longitudinal data from the UK Life Opportunities Study, following up 37,412 workers aged 16 and over with and without a range of impairments in terms of their workplace accommodations. We found strong evidence that workplace accommodations appear to enable workers with impairments to remain in work and economically active. This was true for a range of impairments, particularly for workers with impairments related to their mental health. Disabled workers need access to formal and impartial organizational procedures for implementing workplace adjustments if the government is serious about reducing the disability employment gap.

Reclaiming 'dependency': developing a sociology of relations and systems for responding to urban exclusion

Andrew Guise, Dr Andrew Guise
(King's College London)

State reform in the UK and many other settings, most recently under austerity, has limited the resources available for the socially excluded. Governing and public discourses in turn increasingly emphasize work over support, and that responsibility for poverty and exclusion resides with individuals. Experiences of poverty and inequality reveal there

being no 'legitimate dependency'; this 'denial of dependency' (Peacock et al, 2014) a result of emerging forms of citizenship and linked stigma and discrimination.

These processes of denying dependency come in the context of potential need for it, especially within the experiences of vulnerable urban populations. Talking about dependency is though limited, and these experiences remain under-theorized within social science. In this paper I will explore what a sociology of relations of 'dependency' in the context of urban exclusion could look like, and how this could add to current theory of caring and empowerment, and so support health and wellbeing.

In particular, I will explore literature on caring and empowerment as it relates to relationships within health and social support services. Further, I will build on study of stigmatized identities and state led processes of reproducing these inequalities to explore how conceptualization of dependency could be used to critique governing discourses, and help shape health, social and care support systems. Lastly, I will consider in what ways could dependency be supportive of health and welfare? In what ways and contexts could it not?

Empowerment and agency through social prescribing: Perspectives of Community Navigators in Scotland

*Anna Terje, Dr Sarah-Anne Munoz, Prof Sandra MacRury
(University of the Highlands and Islands)*

Social determinants of health and wellbeing include intersecting inequalities of social exclusion, deprivation, and (geographical) isolation. With a drive in the UK public health agenda to move towards community-based solutions and preventative approaches to ill health, social prescribing has been thought to support individual and community resilience in this context.

The medicalisation critique posits that autonomy and capacity of individuals to manage their health is restricted by viewing social and societal problems through the scientific lens. This in particular affects disempowered groups, drawing attention away from the social inequalities that are at the root of reduced agency (Lupton, 1997). Critics of the medicalisation narrative have advocated for empowerment of patients through engaging in preventative social and physical measures, thus 'taking control' of their health.

mPower is an INTERREG VA funded cross-border initiative, addressing demands on health and social care in seven partnerships across Scotland, Ireland and Northern Ireland. It provides its beneficiaries (aged 65 and over, with one or more long-term condition) with a social prescribing service, with co-produced personalised Wellbeing Plans, as well as eHealth interventions enabling self-management.

This paper presents initial findings from the mPower evaluation, drawing on qualitative interviews with Community Navigators in Scotland. Looking at processes of empowerment through narratives of front line staff connecting patients to local resources, this paper will focus on the themes of connectedness, community and agency. We will explore the role of mPower in beneficiaries' engagement in practices of the self that enhance wellbeing, thus enabling increased control over their health.

Inequalities in dementia diagnosis in the UK. A narrative literature review of factors contributing to variations in timing of diagnosis.

*Josie Henley, Dr Alex Hillman & Prof Ian Rees Jones
(WISERD)*

This paper reports on the findings of a narrative review of existing literature, with the aim of exploring evidence for underdiagnosis as a function of structural socioeconomic factors. The sociology of diagnosis is embedded in social constructionism with a question of whether diagnosis matters (Brossard & Carpentier, 2017). However, a key point in health inequity is that diagnosis grants access to services.

Early diagnosis of dementia is associated with improved outcomes: (Robinson, Tang & Taylor, 2015). Yet, while rates of diagnosis are improving, a third of those with dementia potentially remain undiagnosed (Aldus et al., 2017; Mason et al., 2018).

Despite a general improvement in diagnostic rates, a diagnostic gap clearly exists. Further, there is international evidence for a negative association between socioeconomic status and rates of dementia diagnosis (Sczufca et al., 2008), with some evidence that socioeconomic status is more important than other markers of inequality (Yaffe et al., 2013).

Aldus et al. identified participant factors correlated with undiagnosed dementia (e.g. living alone, a lower severity of impairment), while Rimmer et al. (2005) cited access to care services, cost and stigma as contributory factors to underdiagnosis and undertreatment of Alzheimer's disease. Reduced access to medical care is a function of socioeconomic status.

Situating dementia diagnosis as an effect of structural inequality is essential to address the inequity of this underdiagnosis. As a first step, this review of existing literature identifies trends and findings in underdiagnosis in order to locate the key factors resulting in socioeconomic status affecting dementia diagnoses.

Rights, Violence & Crime

W004

Historical changes in criminalising of lootings in the Northeast region of Brazil

Guilherme Benzaquen, Guilherme Benzaquen
(Universidade Federal de Pernambuco)

Looting is a consensually criminal practice, that is to say, there are a social consensus about those cases being a disrespect of the law. But, as Machado says, when we are dealing with crimes, there are two legitimate orders that overlap: an institutional-juridical order and a quotidian order. What means that looters know that are committing a crime but, even so, they can mobilise quotidian legitimations for their acts. In this work, I will analyse the history of lootings in Brazilian Northeast with the main goal of discuss the way that changed its criminalization. I intend to present the changes in both legitimate orders: the institutional-juridical – the way lootings are framed by the State – and the quotidian – the discourses of non-state actors. For this purpose, I will use data from the specialized historiography and from a field work I've been doing.

The analysis shows a double historical change in criminalising. In the order institutional-juridical, the category that frames the looters changed: nowadays is uncommon that they are interpreted as a multitudinous crime and more common that they are interpreted as theft. In other respects, in the quotidian order there is a weakening of a legitimate discourse based in the argument of looting necessity due to the hunger issue. These changes indicate a tendency of depoliticization and individualization of the criminalising of lootings in Brazil.

A sociology of the penal voluntary sector: fluidity, plurality, neutralisation and reflexivity

Philippa Tomczak, Dr Gillian Buck, the University of Chester
(CRIMVOL)

The penal voluntary sector (PVS) is an important, complex, under-theorised area. Its non-profit, non-statutory organisations are ill-understood, yet highly significant in the operation of punishment and the structural inequalities bound up therein around the world. Burgeoning scholarship has begun to examine specific parts of the sector, particularly individualised service delivery. This focus on voluntary organisations committed to delivering public services, which at best engage in advocacy around narrow policy questions, is doing society a disservice. Voluntary organisations, as part of broader civil society, have played important roles in challenging inequalities ranging from domestic violence to same sex rights. Despite increasing Government attempts to curtail campaigning (such as the 2014 'Lobbying Act' in England and Wales), these organisations continue to campaign using a variety of strategies and they continue to affect social marginalisation and rights. Nevertheless, (too) many voluntary organisations and practitioners self-censor. We offer a five paradigm framework which conceptualises the PVS more fully. Our plural framework applies and extends Burrell and Morgan's (1979) influential four paradigm model of social theory, which maps the theoretical diversity underpinning organisational activity. Our framework i) provides sensitising concepts which open up the fluidity and plurality of PVS programmes and practices, and ii) highlights the (potential) roles of brokers in (re)directing activity, (de)neutralising protest and encouraging reflexivity.

Adventures in Criminalized Identities: towards a viscous understanding of culture

Finola Farrant,
(University of Roehampton)

Not only have those in contact with the criminal justice system caught the popular imagination; concerns with crime, justice and punishment have long been a staple of popular cultural entertainment.

Drawing on an array of discourses about imprisonment, including empirical data from interviews with ex-prisoners, this paper argues that analysis of popular culture and individual narratives allows us to move beyond the false binaries of society/individual, subject/object and fact/fiction. Popular culture, which may appear mundane, innocuous and everyday, offers provocative and telling cultural and ideological information about society.

The concept of viscous culture is used to explore the sticky connections between the various systems of power exercised through social, political and economic structures, individual identities and wider cultural understandings of

criminal justice. In this analysis, the viscous contamination between the stories we are told, the stories we tell, and the stories that we listen to is recognised.

The aim of this is to theorize critical concepts in a manner that demonstrates, in a concrete, as well as theoretical way, the mimetic function of all texts that contribute to the production, coproduction and reproduction of shifting and contested understandings of crime, punishment and justice. From tragedy to comedy, such adventures into criminalized identities reveal the viscous and porous nature of the relationship between popular culture and real-life action.

Social Divisions / Social Identities A

W110

Culture and Subjective Well-Being: Evidence from European Regions

*Anneli Kaasa,
(University of Tartu)*

It is well-known that happiness varies across countries and regions. Cultural background has been often discussed as one possible determinant of happiness and subjective well-being. It is quite reasonable to assume that how people feel about their lives might be influenced by the cultural environment and values and attitudes prevailing in the society. However, the literature on this topic remains rather theoretical: there are just a few studies that have tested the relationship between culture and subjective well-being empirically. The aim of this study is to investigate the possible relationship of different cultural dimensions with subjective well-being across European regions. The data describing subjective well-being come from the ESS and EVS – both enable the analysis at the regional level as well. Regarding the cultural background, there are many different possibilities for measuring culture, the most popular being the Hofstede's original approach that captures cultural differences into four cultural dimensions: power distance, uncertainty avoidance, masculinity and individualism. In order to describe cultural dimensions in Europe at the regional level, data created by author and colleagues based on the ESS and EVS are used. Correlation, regression and graphical analysis are applied. The results of the correlation analysis show that power distance, masculinity and uncertainty avoidance are negatively and individualism positively related to subjective well-being. However, including all four into the regression analysis with control variables shows a more interesting and complicated picture. This study contributes to understanding cross-cultural differences in subjective well-being.

The Everyday Hauntings of Romantic Love: Symbolic Interactionism, Homosexualities, and Singlehood

*Dr Aliraza Javaid,
(University of East London)*

Symbolic Interactionism has often evaded the social, cultural and historical formations of love. Here, I propose some ways that this long-standing theoretical framework can contribute to the subject matter of love. To theorize love, I argue that love is situationally constructed in the midst of everyday romantic discourses, story telling, and subjectivities. I demonstrate this argument in 3 ways: first, the ideology of romantic love serves to position men, notably heterosexual men, in hierarchical superior positions whilst women and non-heterosexual men in subordinate ones, producing unequal sexual relations; second, adopting a Symbolic Interactionist perspective, I show how constructs of love, romance and intimacy emerge from everyday interaction and to which social actors become progressively committed; third, the 'in the closet' notion is critically examined to argue that it is a form of social control that hinders the public confession of gay love.

One Small Step For Man: Examining Change and Continuity in Young Australian Masculinities

*Brittany Ralph, Dr Steven Roberts
(Monash University)*

Current theorising of 'inclusive masculinities' cites the renewed emphasis on intimacy evident in platonic relationships between men in Western societies as evidence of the disintegration of a hegemonic gender order. Given the expansion of online movements like the MRAs and incels, this at first might suggest a binary formation of contemporary young masculinities. Reflecting on this online phenomenon alongside findings from a study of young Australian men's understanding and experience of homosocial intimacy, I point to the nuanced ways gender power continues to inform men's lives, including those who engage more openly in homosocial intimacy. Using qualitative data from focus groups with twenty-two men from five different subcultural peer groups and eight follow-up individual interviews, I illustrate that exaggerated intimate behaviours are not considered authentic displays of affection. Rather, they have been adopted into the repertoire of ways men can perform masculinity and therefore do not meaningfully challenge gendered power structures. However, this hybridity is neither a means of reconfiguring male power, nor evidence of entirely inclusive masculinities, but instead constitutes an initial step toward inclusivity; a transitory phase that is fragile and at times contradictory, but should be neither overstated or dismissed. I therefore highlight the need

for intergenerational research methodologies that examine the drivers of change and continuity in masculinities and explore how men navigate the pursuit of a masculine identity amid social shifts toward gender equality.

Social Exclusion Inside a Village and the Role of Guanxi and Renqing: Case Studies of Social Stratification in Two Chinese Villages

Ju Ruan

(Hanshan Normal University)

This paper is based on two case studies of social exclusion in two Chinese villages against the background of social stratification. Five types of social exclusion of the poor --housing , marriage , renqing , ritual and gossip exclusion are identified, which shrink the guanxi networks held by the poor, weakening their social and ritual capital, leading to reproduction of inequality. This research finds that the concept of in-group and out-group separation, superior and inferior separation, symmetrical exchange, and absence of ideas of modern social welfare, combine to result in social exclusion of the poor. The exclusive and hierarchical nature of guanxi exacerbate social exclusion and further widen social stratification inside a village. This process is underpinned by traditional Confucian li, in which ideas of modern social welfare, equality and universalism lack purchase.

Social Divisions / Social Identities B W828

Who counts as a mother, and what counts as a baby? Challenging discourses around Second Trimester pregnancy loss in England.

Aimee Middlemiss,

(University of Exeter)

In England, live birth produces a full person, with a claim to citizenship through birth registration. This person's parents can make claims on the state, such as for Child Benefit, through their relationship with the baby. Stillbirth, after 24 weeks' gestation, produces a different type of person, registered separately, but whose mother may claim her parenthood through paid state maternity leave. By contrast, pregnancies which end without a recognised live birth before 24 weeks are not legally defined as having produced a person, nor is there any form of legal recognition of motherhood. The legal definitions dovetail with medical discourses in the context of abortion law, in which pre-24 week fetuses are non-viable. This study in South West England draws on ethnographic interviews and fieldwork with women who have experienced Second Trimester pregnancy loss involving labour and birth between 13 and 24 weeks' gestation, and whose interpretations of the event conflict with the legal and medical discourses. It investigates how some women challenge legal and medical definitions of their pregnancy experiences by making claims about the personhood of their dead foetus/baby and their own status as mothers. Through practices associated with the birth of persons, such as interactions with the body of the baby, and the death of persons, such as funerals, these women challenge established hierarchies of newborn being, claim their motherhood, and challenge state, medical and lay definitions of pregnancy and the kinship it produces.

'Not you, you're OK': Gender, 'Race' & Oppositionality in Yorkshire Post-Punk Identity.

Rio Goldhammer,

(Leeds Beckett University)

Yorkshire was, and in many ways still is, a cultural melting pot, prime for the oppositional culture that emerged in the 1970s and 80s. As an auto-ethnographer of Yorkshire post-punk, I have been interviewing key participants of the scene alongside amassing field notes from the last 12-months of my own participation as a singer in a post-punk band. Questions of 'race', masculinity and place have emerged as significant themes in my fieldwork. O'Brien (2012) described Yorkshire during the post-punk era as a 'paranoid atmosphere of gender warfare that played itself out in 'ripper territory'.' She specifically noted groups such as Gang of Four and Delta 5 as exponents of a post-punk feminism that emerged in this period. For O'Brien, '[t]here was a feeling that the macho male society, which spawned Peter Sutcliffe, tacitly condoned his activities' (2012, p.35). Fletcher (2012) considered Yorkshireness to assume a 'mixed breed of white masculinity', while Clavane (2016) suggests an innate anti-establishmentism. My fieldwork has identified a triad of place, identity, and opposition in Yorkshire post-punk; this paper offers a case study of one participant, Aki, a post-punk musician and first-generation British-Pakistani from Bradford. For him, post-punk represented a rejection of two contrasting cultures, but also a new 'tribe' that offered protection from more hostile groups. Was post-punk a safe haven from aggression in the 1970s and 80s? Was Bradford? Or was it just a case of 'not you, you're OK' within a local music scene?

Women Asylum Seekers and Refugees in Higher Education in the UK: A Gendered Gaze to Borders

*Rumana Hashem, N/A
(University of Warwick, UK.)*

Recent study on education suggests that women are more advanced than men in educational achievement in the UK (Finding, 2013). Despite sexist bias in higher education (HE) and career opportunities, women are achieving more successes if/when provided with access to HE (Yvette et al. 2018). But how many women in asylum have access to HE in Britain? If provided with access, can all women obtain HE? This paper is concerned with how everyday borders and institutional racism affect right to education for women in asylum. I broaden the discussion on 'border' and 'racism' to boundaries, gender and ethnicity of asylum seekers and refugees to identify the different forms of 'borders' which women from different ethnic background encounter whilst trying to access higher education.

Drawing on case studies and first-hand accounts of women refugees seeking HE, the paper intends to address above questions and more, such as: what are the forms of borders that women asylum seekers and refugees experience in universities in the UK? What other discrepancies in terms of gender and sexuality do refugees face and how do these differences affect their career chances in the host country? By way of illustration, I argue that the differential achievements of women in asylum are related to harm done by gendered borders, partially formed by institutional racism and partly by their ethnicity and gender identities. I utilise data from a civic engagement project and my experience in teaching and learning with asylum-seekers and refugees in an Open Learning Initiative programme.

Social Divisions / Social Identities C **W525**

RECALIBRATING CLASS: MAPPING, RESISTANCES AND THE EVERYDAY

What spaces are left to talk about class in the 21st century? This session considers the various ways in which class analysis can, and should be recalibrated. 'Recalibrating class' here has multiple meaning and purpose, but at its core it is a call to revise and go beyond prevailing analytical frames and conceptual lenses in current class research. The panel will engage in critical consideration of existing theoretical paradigms in class research, to open a dialogue about new class based, analytic epistemologies.

The Bourdieusian paradigm has come to dominate class analysis. While vital in responding to intellectual and material conditions (the 'cultural turn', 'individualism', neoliberalism etc) and emerging at necessary moment to salvage class analysis; this 'new class paradigm', this session attests, has served its purpose. Its hegemonic dominance has been said to marginalise a politics of class and produce de-historicised (or flat) analyses. It has also tended towards a sociology of class without adequate depth, complexity or feeling. This session asks: 1) What lies beyond these existing frames, and what is missed using conventional conceptual tools? 2) What new inequities does the de and re-composition of class bring about but also what makes class 'liveable'? That is, what are the new injuries and new rewards in everyday classed lives?

To do this the session explores class through alternative analytical lenses which critique pre-existing theories of 'the everyday' and 'naturalisation', mapping out nuanced and subtle modes of class-based reproduction and resistance and thinking through radical potentials and possibilities

Class and Everyday Life

*Kirsteen Paton
(University of Liverpool)*

This paper attempts to re-navigate contemporary class analysis by operationalizing the everyday as a key analytical lens. This reimagines classic but outmoded everyday life theory to explore, as Berlant puts it, the conditions and crises of contemporary capitalism which 'disorganises the ordinary'. This paper sets out four key ways in which the everyday lens can be used to recalibrate class analysis. First, the everyday is a vital analytical scale which offers a classed view of the knot between the agential and structural, and lets us plot the connections between them, confronting the point at which class is made and remade. Second, the everyday offers a vital mode of critique. It helps challenge the existing Bourdieusian stronghold by providing a more encompassing analytical frame to demonstrate the ways in which class is reproduced in the everyday, at multiple levels, and the new injuries and new rewards that this brings. Third, the everyday is also profoundly political. The everyday lens situates the present as a moment of emergence which encompasses historical conjunctures of crisis as moments of reconstruction of economic life but also moral, cultural, and intellectual realms. The everyday lens allows us to see power and politics in an expansive rather than narrow way. Finally, the everyday lens has salient methodological purchase. It has an immersive, ordinary quality which poses interesting and fortuitous questions which force us think more imaginatively about ways of seeing, attentiveness and the everyday resources we have at our disposal in our sociological practice.

Radical Cartographies of Class

Kirsty Morrin

(University of Liverpool)

'Being classified' is a modality of inequality. It is experienced through 'raced' and gendered being, it is inscribed in, through and on bodies, it is material, and it is expressed through devaluation and struggle. This paper draws on Brah's notion of 'cartographies of diaspora' to consider a 'class' epistemology (or epistemology of classification) that is at its foundation, critical, spatial and socio-historical. Thinking with cartographies as metaphor, but also a processual, technical and aesthetic tool for analysis, the purpose of this presentation is to map out, or redrawing the boundaries of class analysis to more encompassing ends. Thinking radically, this paper goes beyond traditional 'measures' of cartographies, to consider a notion of counter, alternative or tactical cartographies that are importantly and necessarily set on a fuzzy and changeable foundation. Here claims are made that there is a need for an epistemology of a radical cartographies of class, which are overtly political in that they are looking to find the potential, and possibilities for equitable and just change.

Rethinking Naturalisation

Wendy Bottero

(University of Manchester)

Pioneering theorists of mundane non-compliance and everyday resistance attack theories which suggest that power and inequality are 'naturalised' so that people no longer feel that resistance is possible or necessary. Accounts of mundane or everyday resistance argue that beneath the surface of people's compliance we can see widespread discontent, expressed through recalcitrance, insubordination and misbehaviour, which shows that inequality is far from 'naturalised'. However, critics express caution about seeing non-conforming or non-compliant behaviour as representing dissent to wider social arrangements, or as opposition to power and authority, beyond very local and immediate concerns. The argument here is that much of what has been labelled as 'resistance' is in fact simply a form of survival, self-help or corner-cutting strategy. Indeed, much rule-breaking behaviour in organisations is not undertaken as non-compliance but rather is about a flexible interpretation of how to apply rules in the light of larger organizational priorities. However, it is also clear that 'encroachments', 'everyday modifications' and 'evasions' have the potential to substantially transform wider social arrangements, and more generally indicate that there are limits to the control of the powerful or of the dominant order. If we are interested in the practical possibilities of social transformation and the limits to social control or regulation then it seems we need to look more broadly at non-conforming and non-compliant social practices. In doing so, however, it may be that what we need to focus on are not just the constraints of power relations but the collective steering of social relations more generally.

Sociology of Education

W823

Producing new diasporic identities through alternative education: Black and mixed-race families experiences of schooling, Saturday Schools and home education

Martin Myers, Kalwant Bhopal

(University of Portsmouth)

This paper draws on research (Bhopal and Myers 2018) with Black and mixed-race families living in urban areas who adopted a range of alternative education strategies for their children. These included decisions to home educate and to use Saturday schools. Although different reasons for choosing such strategies were discussed, many families related their decision to experiences of racism within mainstream schools. In addition to countering such racism the research also found alternative education routes were an effective means of bolstering their own fluid family histories. Many families did not fit easily into readily recognisable demographic categories. Instead they often recounted complex narratives e.g. diasporic journeys traversing three continents; parents and step-parents with multiple and diverse histories; families who had encountered tragedies and loss; and, families reconciling the accounts of their grand-parents' diaspora with the different realities of their own lives. One apparent success story of alternative educational provision was its seeming potential to reinforce very diverse family identities and provide a space in which such diversity became more readily understandable. In this way, the local work of families and the communities in which they live, appeared an effective means of challenging some of the inequalities they faced in their daily lives. The paper will explore alternative education as a means by which cosmopolitan identities (Beck 2018) find security within a fluid, changing world.

Beck, U. (2006). *Cosmopolitan vision*. Polity.

Bhopal, K. & Myers, M. (2018) *Home Schooling and Home Education: Race class and inequality*. Abingdon: Routledge.

An Indian account of urban life, 'labour' and education: developing sociological understandings of 'the (poor) 'child''

Reva Yunus,
(Azim Premji University, India)

The modernist Eurocentric notion of childhood exported to former colonies (Malkki and Martin 2003) has historically shaped realities of educational exclusion (Balagopalan 2014) and contemporary educational discourses in 'developing' countries like India (Nieuwenhuys 2009). Further, the 'abstract universalism of the 'poor child' encoded in global developmental discourses obscures the specificity of the 'ideal child' (Sriprakash 2016). The notion of 'multiple childhoods' that emerged in response to such discourses has often failed to locate these childhoods in historically specific cultural, national and economic contexts (Hopkins and Sriprakash 2016). Thus, there is need for sociological engagements with contemporary 'childhood' that capture a range of cultural experiences; this paper offers such an engagement in the specific case of India and seeks to challenge the normative notion of childhood that underpins educational policy and practice and has developed in a complex interaction with Eurocentric notions (Sriprakash 2016).

While 'the poor child' has emerged as the object of educational reform her lived realities remain farthest from Indian educational discourses. Drawing upon ethnographic data generated through my doctoral work at the university of Warwick I present gendered and classed accounts of working class students' experiences of internal migration and their 'labour' in/outside the home in terms of their access to and participation in schooling; and how students make sense of the significance of schooling. I locate these experiences within larger (inter)national social and economic logics as well as India's deeply stratified school system thus offering an analysis that can inform approaches to education policy and practice.

Generation 9/11: British Muslim girls talk about their past, present and future lives.

Farzana Shain,
(Keele University)

Media and policy attention surrounding Muslim girls and young women in Britain has been heavily dominated since 9/11, by a focus on 'extremism' and 'security' at the expense of other factors that may shape their lives. The literature on the perceived radicalisation of young Muslims (Field, 2011, ISD, 2015) has grown exponentially in the last decade, as has critical terrorism research (Brown, 2008, Spalek and Lambert 2008, McGhee, 2008, Jackson 2009, Lynch 2013). Yet, there are many and varied issues facing young British Muslims from questions of cultural belonging to schooling and employment/unemployment. For example, despite high rates of participation in further and higher education, 71% of Muslim women are not in employment and according to the British Social Mobility Commission (2016), Muslim Pakistani and Bangladeshi women who do work, earn less than their counterparts from other ethnic minority groups. This paper reports the findings of Leverhulme Trust funded research (2017-2019) exploring British Muslim girls' accounts of growing up and being educated in the shadow of 9/11. Drawing empirically on in-depth interviews and focus groups and theoretically on feminist and postcolonial approaches (Brah and Phoenix 2004, Mirza 2012), the paper explores the strategies that the young women draw on to navigate a range of competing pressures. The analysis offers insights into the cultural, political and economic factors that underpin the interaction of gender/race/religion/class and education in the era in which Muslims are identified primarily through the lens of the 'war on terror'. ?

Corruption and trust in South African Education: Perceptions of teachers and school boards.

Jacqueline Baxter, Melanie Ehren, Andrew Patterson
(The Open University UK)

South Africa has a long history of oppression and apartheid that has led to great inequalities. Despite its classification as an upper-middle income country, learning outcomes are generally poor. Only the top 16% of South African Grade 3 children are performing at an appropriate Grade 3 level (Spaull and Kotze, 2015). Almost three decades after the fall of apartheid, resources and capital are distributed unevenly across schools: large performance gaps related to wealth, socio-economic status, geographic location and language of students are endemic. Corruption has been identified as one of the reasons for systemic failure to improve (Chisholm et al., 2005). According to research carried out by Corruption Watch in March 2017 complaints showed principals and school governing body (SGB) members were involved in corrupt activities. Research into causes of corruption adopts either an economic perspective or a normative and cognitive approach (Misangyi, Weaver, & Elms, 2008), the latter proving more effective at tackling the root causes of corruption. This paper uses qualitative interviews from 8 primary schools, with teachers, head teachers and school

governors to examine their normative perceptions of corruption and examines how these perceptions work to undermine trust in educational processes and practices in South African education, in examining: a) Which factors colour normative perceptions of corruption in education b) To what extent these perceptions undermine trust in the education system. The paper concludes with an exploration of how responses to both questions and can be used to improve trust within the system.

Theory W323

Was Durkheim White? Anti-Semitism and the Dangers of Binary Racialised Readings of Theorists

*Matt Dawson,
(University of Glasgow)*

Recently, increased attention has been given to a critique of the canon for its biases and omissions. There is much to be welcomed in this critique however it has, at times, been guilty of imposing simplistic binary racialised readings of writers onto the past. This paper will explore this through the case of Émile Durkheim. It will suggest that claiming Durkheim as a 'white' theorist is a problematic claim. Instead, I will trace the instances in which Durkheim was racialised during his lifetime as part of the anti-Semitism found in Fin de Secile France. I will conclude by arguing that this reading of Durkheim does not somehow make his writings free of critique, but should encourage us to be more careful when reading patterns of racialisation into the canon.

Can the Subaltern Contribute to Sociology? Challenging hierarchies and inequalities in the production of the sociological imagination through subaltern theoretical directions

*Piermarco Piu,
(University of Warwick)*

Given a renewed focus on hierarchy and inequality, many scholars have argued that sociology must tackle the challenge of an expanded sociological imagination constructed by different subjects – social scientists, non-academic researchers, activists, etc. Global and Postcolonial sociologies, specifically, respond to this issue by negotiating hegemonic and subaltern sociological knowledges, thus potentially challenging geographical and epistemological hierarchies and inequalities in knowledge production. In this respect, Global and Postcolonial sociologies emphasize the contributions of subaltern perspectives for expanding their sociological imagination. These sociologies therefore learn from subaltern perspectives, while simultaneously legitimizing subaltern locations as sites of knowledge production.

Nevertheless, these debates promote an epistemological agenda that considers subaltern perspectives as contributions to theories of sociological knowledge, yet overlooks the practical-political implications of the 'subaltern question' for the sociological imagination.

This paper will address these issues by questioning the professional stratifications (cultural hierarchies) within the cooperative construction of knowledge/sociological imagination (co-theorization) through the possibility of subaltern theoretical directions. In this respect, the Italian *conricerca* (co-research) provides a radical analytical framework that focuses on the subalterns' theoretical and political contributions, dismantling the tensions between co-theorization and cultural hierarchies by foregrounding the collective political direction of the research.

Outlining the problem in this way will ground my discussion about the conditions for subaltern theoretical directions in Global and Postcolonial sociologies. This paper will thus relate 'co-theorization' along 'professional stratification' to the political question of research organisation, thus presenting the 'negotiations' of hegemonic and subaltern sociological imaginations as a matter of 'direct democracy'.

Decolonising Nostalgia in the Sociological Canon

*Meghan Tinsley,
(University of Manchester)*

Nostalgia pervades the sociological canon that emerged from Germany and France in the first decades of the twentieth century. From Durkheim's division of labour to Weber's iron cage, sociology's great theorists conceptualise modernity as a spatial and temporal departure from an 'authentic' reality. Nostalgia, in turn, is bound up with, and projected onto, the twentieth-century imperial project. The preponderance of nostalgia in early twentieth-century Europe should affect our reading of the canon as the product of imperial space and time. Taking the situatedness of the canon as my starting point, I ask whether a decolonial nostalgia is conceivable, and what form it might take. I argue that a decolonial nostalgia derives from an irreversible experience of loss in the past, coupled with the imagining of a new reality in the future. As a case study, I trace the emergence of decolonial nostalgia in the work of Frantz Fanon. I find that Fanon's romanticisation of Africa in *Black Skin, White Masks* replicates the imperial nostalgia of the European canon. Yet Fanon's later writings on the Algerian Revolution—including *The Wretched of the Earth*, *A Dying Colonialism*, and various political writings recently published as *Alienation and Freedom*—use nostalgia to make

sense of the destruction of precolonial reality in both the colonising process and the anti-colonial struggle. Acknowledging this loss, in turn, forms the basis of a new, decolonial society.

Can Criminology be decolonised?

*J M Moore,
(Newman University)*

Criminology emerged as a discipline at the same time as Europe was engaged in colonising much of the world. Theories of 'crime' have been developed without recognition of the intimate links between colonialism and criminology (Agozino, 2003). Early criminological texts demonstrate the racism present at the birth of criminology (Bonger, 1943; Forero, 2017), a presence that remains largely unacknowledged in criminological literature.

A process of decolonising criminology would involve exploring this history, the discipline's complicity in colonialism, its adoption and deployment of racism, its fixation on individuals and its failure to address structural harms or the major crimes against humanity perpetrated by Euro-America: colonialism, genocide, and slavery.

Such a process would be not risk free. To acknowledge criminology's history we run the risk that: 'Things fall apart; the centre cannot hold; Mere anarchy is loosed upon the world' (Yates, 1920). But would that be a bad thing?

Work, Employment & Economic Life A HANGING LANTERN ROOM

Hierarchies and inequalities in the gendered organisation: LGB employees negotiating heteroprofessionalism

*Christiana Ierodiakonou, Andria Christofidou
(University of Cyprus)*

This paper draws on Acker's (1996; 1990) seminal work on gendered organisations and explores the experiences of Lesbian, Gay and Bisexual (LGB) individuals at work in Cyprus (Drydakis, 2014). In traditional professional contexts, the 'heterosexual matrix' (Butler, 1999) tends to be sustained and reproduced, entrapping individuals into a dualism of masculinity and femininity that becomes a source of inequality for those who deviate from heteronormative imageries of the professional employee.

We rely on 20 in-depth interviews with highly-educated LGB employees to examine whether their experiences reflect practices of gendered organisations, as well as the strategies used in negotiating their non-heterosexual identities in organisations that habitually value heteroprofessionalism (Mizzi, 2013). We find that, in this context, the main factors that influence LGB employees' coping mechanisms are their perceptions of organisational climate and the patriarchal and religious values of their families. The identified coping strategies map onto Griffin's (1992; 1991) typology of strategies (i.e. passing, covering, implicitly and explicitly out), but in our case are highly fluid and dynamic. Within each strategy, LGB employees find ways to exercise agency and (re)negotiate prevailing notions around gender and (hetero)sexuality. We provide thus an analysis of matters of structure and agency in heteronormative organization cultures, the (re)negotiation of gender and sexuality norms, and (the limits of) transgression. By doing so, we contribute to the growing body of literature on LGB people in the workplace by drawing attention to the interplay among gender, sexuality, organisational structures and the invisible hierarchies that marginalise LGB employees.

Embarrassment, Regulation and Professionals

*Clare Butler,
(Newcastle University)*

Embarrassment is multifarious and fascinating: it is generally considered to arise from our failure to observe a valued social norm (Goffman, 1956, 1963). Yet, it might also follow our witnessing the failure of others. As such, embarrassment can be used as a tool of management through its reciprocal disciplinary gaze (Foucault, 1963, 1975). Here, embarrassment is often individualising and divisive. However, all is not lost, displays of embarrassment signal a concern with social order, which can build sociality and togetherness (Goffman, 1956). Nevertheless, that I might embarrass myself, you and you me, and the potential for ensuing discomfort, means that embarrassment is at the heart of many regulatory systems.

Being a member of a profession adds another layer of complexity to the notion of what is embarrassing when considering the diverse audiences to the work of professionals i.e. 'the profession', employing organisations, fellow professionals, students, patients etc. However, little is known about the nature, role, experience or impact of embarrassment in regulating professionals' work.

Drawing on interviews with speech and language therapists, the paper finds that embarrassment stimulates (for good and bad), but also impairs (also for good and bad); it disempowers (intentionally and seemingly unintentionally) and yet also sometimes empowers. The paper closes much as it started by highlighting that embarrassment is multifarious and fascinating. Yet, not quite as it started because it argues for the importance of hierarchy within and without of professional groups; and the inequalities engrained in the practices of knowledge production, which can enliven embarrassment.

Evolving as a widening participation practitioner, the role of experience in becoming transgressive

*Jon Rainford,
(Staffordshire University)*

Individuals that work within widening participation bring with them a wealth of both personal and employment experiences. The role of the Widening participation practitioner is however under-researched (Burke 2012). This paper contributes to the understandings of this growing workforce. Emerging from a wider study into the differences between widening participation policy and practices, this paper draws on sixteen in-depth semi-structured interviews with practitioners in seven universities that explored their personal and professional histories and their experiences of practice.

I argue that there are distinct types of practitioner that appear to emerge from the data. Drawing on the work of Margaret Archer (2007), I will demonstrate the importance of understanding how individuals' positions mediate objective structural and cultural powers. Through the discussion of four emergent types of practitioner, I argue that both personal and professional experience causes practitioners to work either in the interests of the institution or the individuals they work with. This can be done in compliance with institutional policy, or adopt a more transgressive stance. This also will allow for discussion of the importance of understanding what makes practitioners fit into each type and the impact this understanding can have on creating the conditions for practitioners to work in ways that best meet the needs of the individuals they work with opposed to being driven by institutional agendas.

Work, Employment & Economic Life B W001

Age, gender and race in the workplace: discrimination in recruitment

*Anna Paraskevopoulou, Anna Paraskevopoulou; Nick Drydakis; Katerina Sidiropoulou
(School of Business and Law, Anglia Ruskin University)*

Despite the growing participation of older workers in the labour market, age discrimination prevails and many employers are prejudiced against older workers (Bowman et al 2017). Several studies have shown that age often intersects with other characteristics such as gender, contributing to 'double' or multiple discrimination.

Using quantitative research and qualitative interviews, our study focused on the topic of discrimination in the UK at the recruitment stage. The experiment was conducted during 2017 whilst the qualitative research is on going. Findings suggest that there is evidence of discrimination based on the characteristics of age, gender and race/ethnicity: older women are more likely to be excluded from job interviews; Black older women experience further difficulties in gaining an interview. Moreover, those selected tend to be shortlisted for lower status jobs.

The paper will engage with theories of intersectionality, as well as 'hard' and 'soft' types of discrimination, in order to explore notions of the 'ideal worker'. There are several implications in the findings. Here we will focus on three main challenges: first, of legislation which does not fully cover 'triple discrimination'; second, for trade unions in dealing with cases of multiple discrimination; and third for policy makers who despite the government encouragement, witness older workers in the labour market excluded during the process of recruitment. The research has been conducted during a period of uncertainty around Brexit and the paper will take this factor into consideration.

Economic democracy as a 'cure' for workplace health inequalities.

*Chris Yuill
(Robert Gordon University)*

The case for economic democracy and greater worker control as a 'cure' for workplace health inequalities will be put forward in this paper. It will draw on primary empirical research and previous theoretical research. The current neoliberal workplace will be sketched out as one of hierarchies that erode the control and autonomy of workers. As the wider research and my own research on work, alienation and wellbeing indicate a lack of control coupled with work

that lacks purpose and wellbeing damages health and wellbeing. Conventional approaches to health in the workplace focus on various neoliberal technologies that responsabilise workers. In effect, workers are blamed for not being able to manage their stress. Such approaches are ineffectual at producing any real difference and can further erode wellbeing

I will argue here that deeper structural changes are required in the workplace. Change that involves allowing workers greater economic democratic control over their work. Doing so would require a shift in the balance of power in the workplace enabled through the flattening of hierarchies. Power here will be envisioned as working at two levels. The ability to influence and inform local working conditions and the strategic direction of a company. Historical and international examples will be drawn on to illustrate how workplaces could be organised that will allow for greater worker control and thereby improving health.

Friday 26/04/2019 at 09:00 - 10:30
Paper Session 7

Cities, Mobilities, Place & Space A
W622

Pokémon Go and Parental Play: Emerging forms of Joint media engagement

Michael Saker, Leighton Evans
(City, University of London)

Pokémon Go is an enormously popular hybrid reality game (HRG) that allows players to occupy a space that is both physical and digital. Since its release in late 2016, it has become a global phenomenon. It has been downloaded over 750 million times to date, and it is still played by roughly 5 million players on a daily basis. This paper reports on an original research project that was designed to examine the impact of Pokémon Go on spatiality and sociability. The study was conducted between May 2017 and July 2017, using an online survey that received 375 responses from Pokémon Go players geographically spread across the globe. Significantly, a number of these respondents did not begin playing Pokémon Go because they were interested in it themselves, but rather because of their children's desire to play this locative game. Accordingly, for these parents, Pokémon Go facilitated a form of joint media engagement (JME) that enabled them to extend and develop their familial relationships. Markedly, our research also found that the game mechanics of this HRG implicitly challenged family hierarchies, as parents were often required to continue playing Pokémon Go at times when their children were unable to join them. In these instances, children effectively outsourced their digital labour to parents who were willing to work in return for extended periods of sociability. This paper will explore these issues in the context of HRG, paying particular attention to new parental challenges that emerging forms of JME might present.

The (Digitally Augmented) World of Harry Potter in Edinburgh: Methodological Considerations for Studying Mediated Popular Culture Tourism in the Age of the Geoweb

Kath Bassett,
(The University of Edinburgh)

Existing scholarship on 'literary' (Herbert 2001), 'media' (Reijnder 2011), 'pop-culture' (Lundberg and Lexhagen 2013) and 'fandom-generated' (Linden and Lindin 2017) tourism make a number of important contributions to understanding these phenomena. Most notably, this research highlights the intricate relationship between fictional imaginary worlds, emotions, and concepts of place. While various media forms and cultures are acknowledged in these studies, few unpick the part that digital technologies play in mediating and shaping these encounters with place, nor contextualize these phenomena within work theorizing the increasingly 'informed city' (Amin and Thrift 2002). My ethnographic research on Harry Potter Tourism in Edinburgh contributes to the scholarship by centering the internet and digital technologies. In this way, I conceptualize popular culture tourism as a vehicle for unpicking the relationship between atmosphere, emotions and affect; the consumption and production of digital spatial information; interactions with space and place; and the ways that these forces assemble together and have both material and immaterial implications for the localities they weave together. By discussing some of my preliminary findings related to how these forces impact those who own and/or manage these related businesses, this presentation will explore the methodological challenges and opportunities of studying locality as something which is 'material', 'inter-subjective', as well as 'digital'. More specifically, I will discuss how a focus on digital practices and labour, as well as on emotions and affect may enhance explorations of how social and locative media shape 'life on the ground' in the age of the geoweb.

Virtual Cities, Real Possibilities: Considering place and space in digital media

Emma Fraser,
(University of Leeds)

Conceptualisations of place and space are often broadly applied to social and material space, and the co-construction of place (Lefebvre (1991), Massey (2005)). However, as everyday life becomes increasingly digital, and social practices are impacted by emerging technologies and activities embedded in 'virtual' sites, what of the non-physical, non-'real' cyber or digital spaces that heavily influence our social and cultural worlds?

With reference to digital video games and hybrid reality (including user generated examples of urban spaces in the online world of Roblox, and the ongoing development of VR and AR software for city design, including participatory planning), this paper will outline theoretical and methodological approaches to the study of place and space in digital media.

Using an interdisciplinary approach that combines digital and urban sociology with media studies and geography, the discussion will reflect specifically on the representation and experience of urban space and place in digital, 3D worlds. This approach particularly problematises understandings of virtuality and the visual through the work of Walter Benjamin on image spaces; Svetlana Boym on Cyber space; and Gillian Rose's work on visual methods and digital place atmospheres,

The paper will conclude by addressing the fact that digital technology industries are compromised as highly profitable commodities, but also by inequalities (particularly of race and gender). In this context, can an understanding of digital media phenomena in terms of the visual and virtual reveal a redemptive politics, particularly through collaboratively constructed digital places and spaces?

Space Invaders: How New Technologies Are Challenging Conceptions of Urban Spaces

*Philip Wane,
(Nottingham Trent University)*

Space Invaders: How New Technologies Are Challenging Conceptions of Urban Spaces

Augmented Reality (AR) and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), better known as drones, are just two of a range of new technologies challenging our traditional conceptions of urban space. This paper will offer some insights into the impact that AR and drones are having on current conceptions of urban space and how these technologies may alert us to wider threats to the transformation of public spaces including the privatisation of former public spaces or the insertion of surveillance technologies. AR and drones offer challenges as to how cities are visualised offering as they do new vistas and multi-sensory mediations of cityscapes. AR offers a hybrid reality in which digital information is overlaid onto physical structures and drones offer a new perspective on cityscapes, quite literally a bird eye view, and in doing so they shift the emphasis from traditional horizontal physical and social stratifications to a new verticalized volumetric vector on urbanism. Through a focus on AR and drones this paper will offer a brief but illuminating insight into some of the social challenges posed by the propagation of new technologies into cities. What are the implications of internet connected, sensor rich, devices, also known as the Internet of Things (IOT)? Are urban populations participating in an (un)planned panoptical programme? If so how can sociologists contribute to a critique of surveillance and spatial rights in contemporary cities?

Cities, Mobilities, Place & Space B W610

Navigating the Implicitly 'Masculine' Space of 'The Gym': Structural Inequalities, and Women's Strategies for 'Getting By'

*Luke Turnock, Maria Moxey
(University of Winchester)*

'Gym space' is supposed to be accessible to all, however numerous factors in construction, provision and atmosphere generate an environment where inequality is pervasive. Whilst women are welcomed in the 'cardio section' of many commercial gyms, there is an intimidatory atmosphere in the 'weights section' bred by young men 'showing off' to one another for status, in an implicit 'masculine hierarchy'. Gym construction encourages these behaviours through their use of space, and features such as mirrored walls and stark downlighting, which give the impression one is always on 'stage'. On top of this, much supposedly 'shared' equipment is de facto male-only: for example a boxing bag where the only gloves provided by the gym are size 'large', and will therefore fit only men.

This paper seeks to explore women's perceptions of the 'masculine' space of the gym, and features they would like to see changed, or at least given consideration. Following its exploration of space, place and atmosphere, the paper shall then move on to discuss strategies for navigating this 'intimidatory' space, identified by women interviewed in the course of research. These include training only at specific times to avoid the rush of young men in early evenings, training only with a personal trainer to act as a 'shield' against judging male gaze, and wearing specific 'gym clothing' to give the impression of 'belonging'. It will then offer solutions on practical changes that gyms and their clients can make to address the identified issues further, and become more inclusive.

Examining Gender Equality in Urban Leisure Spaces of Turkey: The Case of Millet Kiraathanesi (Public Reading Space)

*Gokben Demirbas,
(University of Glasgow)*

In this paper, I aim to investigate the gender dynamics in the use of the newly opened millet kiraathanesi (public reading cafe) in Turkey, which is a top-down, national project announced by the current president as a political promise during the 2018 general and presidential elections. The idea is to provide citizens a leisure space where they can find books, magazines and newspapers to read as well as have their tea and cake. I will analyse this promise as part of the broader project of the ruling party to dominate in the socio-cultural field. In May 2017, the current President stated 'As you know politically ruling is one thing. Socially and culturally ruling is entirely different. We have been in power since 14 years. But we still have problems in ruling the social and cultural field' (Hürriyet, 29.05.2017). The rapid allocation of significant buildings in many cities of Turkey and explicit support of Turkish Directorate of Religious Affairs to the promotion of such leisure spaces lead one to question the extent to which gendered codes of respectability will play a role in the use of millet kiraathanesi. Drawing on my PhD project, I claim that a strengthening of the honour code in the public sphere in its new forms emerged after the Justice and Development Party (JDP) came to power in 2002. In order to examine the role of honour code in the use of millet kiraathanesi, I will conduct a qualitative pilot research in three cities of Turkey.

Breaking down boundaries? Exploring shared art-making in an open studio mental health setting

Lydia Lewis, Dr Helen Spandler

(University of Wolverhampton)

Research suggests that community arts projects can help promote well-being and mental health recovery. It has also been suggested that opportunities for mutuality – connectedness to others and different kinds of sharing and reciprocity between people - in community settings promote support well-being and recovery. Yet research into arts projects targeted for mental health has not tended to focus on shared creative practice mutual creativity - between participants/members and practitioners. In the context of an arts and mental health organization that employed a therapeutic community and open studio approach in which art therapists made art alongside members, this article explores the possibilities for, and tensions associated with, generating mutuality between studio managers and members through this approach. Presenting qualitative findings from participant observation and interviews, it explores how shared art-making may work to affect relational asymmetries, acting as a social leveller while also working to obscure, reinforce or (re)construct social distinctions and hierarchies. It also shows how the shared practice worked to produce mutual acceptance between those involved, although this principle had limits when it came to tolerating disturbance in the studio, and sometimes enabled participants to challenge personal, creative and therapeutic boundaries. Taking a critical sociological perspective that takes account of the wider social context and power inequities, the discussion encompasses an analytical focus on gender. It also relates the findings to conceptions of wellbeing and social recovery and highlights implications for art therapy practice.

Culture, Media, Sport & Food - Roundtable

W308

Researching nutritional outcomes of families attending holiday food programmes- methodological issues and power relationships.

Karolina Klimczak,

(Birmingham City University)

The aim of this PhD research is to describe and analyse the nutritional outcomes of English holiday food programmes for children.

This mixed-methods study of programmes in West Midlands also aims to:

- Explore the differences in programme delivery of holiday food programmes in one local authority in England
- Explore the perceptions, views, and reported practices of relevant stakeholders

For families who rely on Free School Meals during term time, it might be necessary to seek other forms of support during school holidays. This 'holiday gap' is suggested to have a negative impact on the mental and physical health of children and adults. In response, 428 organisations across the United Kingdom provide meals during the holidays (Forsey, 2017).

I have used three qualitative methods that were deemed non-intrusive and suitable for research with children and vulnerable participants (Liamputtong, 2007). These methods allowed me to explore the nutritional outcomes through direct observations of participants' experiences.

The programme is designed by stakeholders with higher socio-economic status for families from deprived backgrounds and also by adults for children. Therefore, I gained an insight into the power relationships and taste

hierarchies that are enacted through food and impact the outcomes. I would like to discuss the initial findings of the study and the research methods that were practical and useful in capturing the data.

Forsey, A. (2017) *Hungry Holidays: A report on hunger amongst children during school holidays*. Available at: <http://www.frankfield.com/upload/docs/Hungry%20Holidays.pdf>

Liamputtong, P. (2007) *Researching the Vulnerable: A Guide to Sensitive Research Methods*. London: Sage.

Food after children: Dynamics of class and gender in the transition to eating as a 'family'.

*Irmak Karademir Hazir,
(Oxford Brookes University)*

Children's diet is a topic of great concern for policy makers, families and social scientists in the UK. Existing research on child-feeding tends to identify parental styles of feeding, to help eliminate the 'unhealthy' eating habits. In addition to creating a responsabilising discourse, this literature tends to disassociate feedwork from foodwork. Research on this topic also treats feeding practices as if they emerge in a vacuum, failing to contextualise them into family routines. This paper aims to fill this gap and explore the interaction between these two mutually constitutive domains. How do adults' established food habits influence the process whereby babies are introduced to solid foods? How do the foodwork habits and practices change in couples after they have children? How do families with diverse class positions and gender division of labour experience this transition? These questions will be addressed by drawing on a BA funded longitudinal research on pre-school children's feeding practices in the southern UK. This project uses a technique of 'go along interviews', where daily practices -including shopping, cooking, feeding and eating- are shared with parents in the home and beyond. To unpack the dynamics of transition to eating with children, discussions will draw on theories of practice (Warde 2005, Halkier et.al 2011), class (Bourdieu 1984), and parenthood (Miller 2005, 2010). In addition to contributing to the sociological literature on this topic, the findings will inform policy makers on the conditions under which feeding and eating routines are established and changed in modern family settings.

What difference does money make to young people's experiences of school meals?

*Laura Hamilton
(UCL Institute of Education)*

Outside the home, school is where young people spend the majority of their lives, consuming a third of their food and drink during the school day (Nelson 2004) and school meals have long been understood as an important nutritional intervention. Yet research on school food policy and practice suggests there are tensions between the child constructed as a 'consumer' versus the child as a 'citizen' (Morgan & Sonnino, 2006). Whilst the money that is available to children as food 'consumers' at school is likely to influence their food and eating practices, few studies examine how children's food and eating at school are mediated by income, or compares the experiences of young people from lower and higher-income households. This paper addresses this gap by analysing thirty-five in depth qualitative cases of young people from lower and higher-income households in an inner London borough. The cases, based on semi structured interviews and visual methods with children and their parents, are drawn from a larger doctoral study that is linked to a mixed methods study of 'Families and Food in Hard Times' (ERC grant agreement n° 337977). Findings suggest that low-incomes and free school meals constrain how much, when and what food young people can buy in school, at times leading to hunger and shame. This is in contrast to the autonomy and choice experienced by young people from higher-income families, suggesting that whilst school meals offer potential opportunities for fostering a sense of shared community they can also perpetuate social inequalities.

Families & Relationships A W709

Love, marriage and intimate relationships in later life of China

*Kun Li, Kun Li
(The university of York)*

In the context of globalization and the emergence of China's modernising society, China is experiencing a rapidly expanding ageing population. This demographic transformation has led to the rise of issues associated with loneliness and social care, family and interpersonal relationships (Qi, 2014; Yeh et al, 2013; Huang, 2011; Wong, 2005; Wang, 2015). Yet in the dramatic social transition period, it is likely the values and experience of intimacy of older people are also changing, however, the existing research has seldom focused on older people's private intimacy, love and values. The aim of this paper is to explore understandings of love and attitudes towards remarriage or cohabitation of men and women in later life in China. The presentation reports on data generated in four Chinese urban cities, 45 semi-structured interviews with both men and women who are single or in long lasting marriage, and

who are aged between late fifties and nineties. The interviews were conducted in Mandarin and explored the participants understanding of the meaning of love and marriage, their attitudes towards 'twilight love' in old age; and how they negotiate their family relationships. In particular the presentation will focus on how romantic and individual choices are influenced by the process of modernity; how romantic issues embody social-historical and political changes; and how individuals' reflexivity towards love and marriage life during the Chinese transformation period.

Leaving an inheritance: A sociological exploration of bequest giving

Rhian Powell,
(Cardiff University)

This paper will draw on my ESRC funded PhD research, which aims to explore how people thinking of making a will balance their perceived obligations towards the family, the state and civil society. The aim of this research is to understand how the family, charities and wealth are regarded by exploring the ways that people aim to make a difference after death. Inheritance planning can tell us a great deal about what people value and what they want the world to look like after they have passed away.

Data has been collected through semi-structured interviews with third-sector organisations and people willing to discuss their experiences of leaving an inheritance. This paper will begin to explore what inheritance practises can tell us about modern family relationships and how the family is positioned in relation to civil society. The key focus of this paper will be on the ways that people seek to perform family through their inheritance decision-making. I will consider the complex relationship between family and charities and discuss the ways in which family can both help and hinder charitable bequest giving.

Continuities and changes in marriage and family life

Shuang Qiu,
(University of York)

Today, in our liquid and mobile lives people are confronted by a complex array of choices, catalysing individuals to construct a mobile nature of the self (Beck and Beck-Gernsheim, 2002). Marriage is arranged on the orders of the parents by the words of the matchmakers, which used to be a common regulative principle of mate selection in traditional China. Although literatures show a significant ongoing decline in arranged marriage accompanying with a decreasing influence of parental involvement in children's marriage decision in all areas of China in the past decades, it does not mean that people are keen to know prospect partners by themselves to the exclusion of others' introductions. China's distinct cultural and historical context provides a novel setting in which to explore to what extent these changes have reshaped family practices and intimacy in China.

Drawing on in-depth interviews with 39 Chinese heterosexual people with varied social backgrounds aged between 23 and 57, this paper, looking in particular at the changes in finding potential marital partner and family living arrangements, argues that people's gendered experiences of marriage, and family life are undergoing transformation, in which modern trends coexist with powerful traditional patterns. In addition, the geographical effects on mate selection practices were also found in this research which adds another dimension to understand status hypergamy in Chinese marriage culture.

Hierarchal Subscriptions of Un/Partnered Womanhood

Amy Andrada,
(University of Edinburgh)

The #MeToo movement spurred collective responses from women in the U.S. and globally, arguably demonstrating their unity. Elsewhere, debates have highlighted women are not a homogeneous group. In 2016, 53% of white women voted in favor of Presidential nominee Donald Trump, despite sexual assault accusations framing him as a sexual predator. More recently, polls indicated 43% of white women believed Brett Kavanaugh's, U.S. Supreme Court nominee, testimony when denying claims of sexual assault. In these cases, research found women aligned their values with that of their partners providing an explanation for anti-feminist narratives on a macro-political level. Patterns of alignment, based on partnered status, in the public sphere parallel that in the private sphere whereby women maintain values supported by familial ideals.

In the Western world, social constructions of 'woman' are derived from ideals based on femininity. Used interchangeably and intrinsically linked, the roles of 'partner' and 'mother', in part, largely define femininity. Feminist research informs that the social realities of women are varied in these contexts, despite normative ideals perpetuating the need to fulfill these roles according to traditional standards. Performances enacted outside normative subscriptions are often perceived and responded to as othered. This creates divisions which in turn perpetuates ingroup and outgroup formations; these formations are then assigned unequal status and therefore produce hierarchies of mother/womanhood. The research examines the varied performances of 'mother' and 'partner', illuminating group formations and their contentions in maintaining ideals of identity in the private sphere.

Families & Relationships B

W727

Familial agency and power structures: educational and social mobility in Pakistan, Singapore and China

M. Arif Naveed

(University of Cambridge)

Families are creative, reflexive agents, embedded in webs of power relations that structure opportunities and constraints their members encounter, in pursuing inter-generational education and social mobility (Weber 1921). Our focus on families reveals how life chances of individuals are shaped by power relations – within, between and beyond families (including the community, the nation-state and the global economy). This panel explores families' classed and gendered aspirations for, and understandings of, educational and social mobility in the Global South, and contributes towards developing a sociological sensibility in understanding parents' pedagogic work in negotiating the future of younger generations. Families not only shape the dispositions, values and aspirations of their members (Bourdieu 1977), they also re-interpret, resist and re-contextualise policy agendas (Bernstein, 1990) and prevalent gender norms and social hierarchies (Murphy 1986) – and in so doing, reproduce or transform power relations.

This panel draws on four contributions, grounded in qualitative data collected through innovative research designs to capture cross-gender and cross-generational dynamics, in Pakistan, Singapore and China. Each paper contributes to an understanding of how families' voices can shed light on, or critique, dominant political and power structures. They illustrate the cultural construction of 'intergenerational (educational, social and international) mobility' and the differentiated capacities, strategies and capabilities of families and their members, within and across generations, to realise these aspirations (Sen 1999; Appadurai 2004; Hart 2016). Panel members will each present their work, then invite questions and discussion with the audience around themes of families' agencies in relation to schooling, politics and power.

Social closure, schooling and the strategies for intergenerational social mobility in rural Pakistan

M. Arif Naveed

(University of Cambridge)

This paper investigate the complex ways in which rural social structure in Pakistan mediates the life chances of individual, *in* and *through* schooling. It draws upon an intergenerational, familial research design involving semi-structured interviews with members of the eight families in a rural community. I emphasise on the cultural specificity of the rural Global South characterised by the agrarian modes of production, a lack of welfare state, and an acute dependence on dense local social networks. I argue that the social mobility research in such contexts requires situating schooling in the thick of social life (Espin-Anderson 1999; Wood 2003) characterised with cooperation, competition and contestation over scarce resources and opportunities.

Taking family as the unit of analysis, I draw on Max Weber's (1921) idea of social closure to examine the ways in which the privileged families tend to achieve social closure by monopolizing resources and opportunities (Murphy 1986). Such an approach reveals the role that power plays in shaping the strategies for social mobility, and hence in restructuring of the rural social order. Seeing families as the main sites for mobilising and channelizing power in the given social hierarchy also helps examine the strategies of the underprivileged 'to escape subjection, disesteem, and dispossession', and to secure better futures for their children (*ibid.*). The transformative potential of schooling, I argue, is heavily mediated by such power relations at the community level – a fact that is often overlooked in the international development and educational agendas.

Meritocracy and Inequality in the lives of socio-economically disadvantaged families in Singapore

Charleen Chiong,

(University of Cambridge)

Meritocratic logics are often present in the philosophical underpinnings of social and education policy across many developed economies, including the U.S. and the U.K. In Singapore, the term 'meritocracy' is explicitly touted by the state as a key lever for upward social mobility. At the core of the 'meritocratic' framework is the assumption that regardless of socio-economic background, a successful future might be attained through individual effort and talent. The promise of equity-through-meritocracy, however, has been challenged as it favours those who already have capital (Koh 2014).

This paper explores how the views and voices of families on the socio-economic margins of Singapore society can offer unique insight into how equitable dominant policy logics are, such as 'meritocracy'. Drawing on semi-structured and focus group interviews with twelve low-income, ethnic minority group families, I argue that analysing the dialectics of state-parent-young people's agencies highlights two main tensions in Singaporean meritocracy. First, my analysis

of families' perspectives reveals how they experience tensions between state welfare and individual responsibility, in Singaporean meritocracy. Second, it highlights tensions between past and present – between how parents and young people's experiences of different phases of Singapore's political-economic development influences their construction of aspirations for mobility in a 'meritocratic' state. Thus, I argue that families' perspectives – particularly when situated in their socio-political, historical and generational contexts – can offer insights into the logics of Singaporean meritocracy, and its equity implications.

Making history speak: An intergenerational investigation of contemporary Chinese middle-class families pursuing overseas educational choice strategies

Juan Chen,

(University of Cambridge)

This article studies Chinese middle-class subjectivity through the lens of overseas educational strategies. It analyses the experiences of education and social mobility of three generations of contemporary Chinese middle-class families—grandparents, parents and children. The article aims to capture an intimate and 'up-close' picture of the ways in which the different generations understand, conceptualize and respond to increasing pressures for the younger members to undertake higher education overseas. It discusses how the family members struggle with and resist socio-cultural forces specific to their generational identity and personal history, their individual experiences of education, and the extent of the individual members' mobility within the Chinese context. I discuss the overseas education choices faced by the younger family members, the intergenerational and interpersonal negotiations involved, the global capitalist economy, and neoliberal subject formation in Chinese society. I argue that the undertaking of overseas higher education fulfils key middle-class Chinese desires, making the subject central to the understanding of middle-class intersubjectivity in contemporary Chinese society.

'I am, because I can': Mothers as they shape their daughters' education in Pakistan

Aliya Khalid,

(University of Cambridge)

As the focus of global development shifts to reaching the unreachable, in Pakistan, girls' education has taken centre-stage. Using quantitative methodologies these global debates take a functionalist view of mothers by focusing on mothers' attributes including education and empowerment and finding its relationship with daughters' education. This view reduces a mothers' role by bringing these 'attributes' to the fore, while ignoring mothers as actors who face social inequalities as they attempt to influence educational decisions in families. Consequently, within policies the important pathways that lead mothers to achieve agency are usually muted. In this study, I explore these pathways that help mothers feel 'capable' and 'free' to influence their daughters' education.

I address questions of mothers' influence by viewing their lives through the lens of the Capabilities Approach and the household model of cooperative-conflict. The two approaches provide a framework to evaluate relational freedom and social factors that force women to self-censor their preferences.

I analyse 30 individual interviews with mothers and other family members, conducted in a rural community in Punjab to gain in-depth understanding of mothers' as agents of change in the wider society. For this paper, detailed analysis of two mothers suggests that a mother takes a stance of 'I can' when she has support in the shape of family or friends. This paper challenges the normative assumptions of mothers as mere instruments for their daughters' education and invites a careful reimagining of mothers as actors of social change carefully rooted within an arrangement of relationships

Lifecourse

W003

'Hitler's gift' to British sociology – a benefit and a lost opportunity?

Christopher Husbands,
(London School of Economics and Political Science)

This paper covers two phases of 'Hitler's gift' (Medawar and Pyke, 2001), but specifically as applied to British sociology. The phases incorporate:

- those who came to the UK during the 1930s to escape persecution or after having been dismissed by the Nazi regime's Aryanization laws; and
- those who came to the UK during or after the War, who, but for the dislocations occasioned by it, might have remained in their native countries.

It is well-known that some famous academic refugees from Hitler's Germany came to the UK during the 1930s. What is less known is that there were other less famous academic sociology refugees who came to the UK, mostly ending up at LSE. They usually pursued graduate research for a doctorate, though some already had a foreign doctorate. The lost opportunity is that, with jobs in sociology being available in the 1930s almost exclusively only at LSE, these academic refugees had to pursue their later careers abroad. After the War a number of graduate students with European backgrounds also came to this country, and, but for the War, they are likely to have stayed in their home countries.

This paper will identify those from both phases and will trace their known later career trajectories. It will offer biographical detail not only about those who are known from their appearance in existing literature (e.g., Turner, in Holmwood and Scott, 2014), but also on others who have slipped under the radar of the history of UK sociology.

Dying alone: inequality in life and death

Glenys Caswell,
(University of Nottingham)

Social divisions which lead to inequality do not only impact people's lives, but also their deaths. Inequalities experienced may include funeral poverty, unequal access to appropriate health care including palliative care as well as a lack of choice with regard to the manner of dying. Inequality can also be experienced by those who make decisions about their deaths which are not socially approved.

This paper focuses on one such group of deaths which appear to transgress socially acceptable limits. These are lone deaths, which occur when an individual who lives alone dies alone at home and their body is undiscovered for a long period of time. Such a death may be the result of a decision to die alone, or it may be the unintended consequence of another decision, such as not seeking support from health and social care services.

Lone deaths provoke strong negative reactions. They are often reported in the media, usually locally but sometimes also nationally, and they are described in terms reflecting blame and opprobrium on the person who has died, their local community and the wider society of which they were part.

Drawing on ongoing research this paper argues that those who undergo a lone death experience inequality both in their dying and its aftermath. Their deaths also present a challenge to social order, which requires the damage they inflict to be repaired through a re-categorisation of their deaths in an effort to bring them back within the bounds of social acceptability.

Methodological Innovations

W009

Time-travelling (feminist) ethics

Niamh Moore, Rachel Thomson, Sharon Webb
(University of Edinburgh)

In this paper we reflect on the experience of negotiating ethical issues raised in archiving and reanimating a feminist sociological study conducted 30 years ago, drawing on the early stages of an ESRC-funded Transformative Research project, 'Reanimating data: experiments with people, places and data'. Bringing 1988 and 2018 into conversation is

productive: revealing how ideas concerning ethical research have changed over time, particularly given new preoccupations with intellectual property. UK research has been at the forefront internationally of moves towards data archiving. It also has a well-developed tradition of feminist methodology involving an expanded lexicon of ethical labour that does not align neatly with the contractual focus on consent and risk management associated with institutional ethics review. In this project we take up a dataset generated before various data protection acts came into being (yet deeply engaged with questions of power in the research process and the ethical violence of interpretation). Through bringing the dataset into conversation with a feminist community archive, we explore how a feminist orientation to ethics enables us to negotiate contemporary framings of 'ethical governance', exposing lacunae in the past where important issues were neither named nor recognised. We retrieve lines of ethical enquiry that deserve to be expanded in a data landscape where access, ownership and coproduction are understood as transformed by the affordances of the digital. As our methods, data, epistemological and political concerns transform, we argue for an 'inventive ethics', responsive to changing times, changing contexts and the complex affordances of digital technologies.

Being uncomfortable is important: Reflections on power and privilege when conducting research in a foreign country and a second language

Ashely Rogers

(University of Abertay Dundee)

While positionality and language are central to the practices, processes and ethics of knowledge production, this is especially the case with foreign researchers in other countries. As two UK researchers, we both learned a second language (Portuguese and Spanish) in order to conduct ethnographic fieldwork in urban sociology in Brazil and Bolivia. Learning and working in an additional language is often an integral aspect of ethnographic work, with proficiency and competencies affecting everyday life in the field, as well as analysis and writing of data. Our positions as minority world researchers in the majority world, and our feelings of deep unease about this that emerged prior to, during, and after our respective projects, cannot be separated out from these (in)competencies.

This paper therefore reflects on aspects of power, inequality and privilege that filtered through our research processes. We reflect on these in terms of our own personal and ethical challenges in the field, as well as writing about it. It has stemmed from the numerous conversations we have had with regards to our reflections on positionality, imperialism, representation and knowledge. While these are all large and highly loaded concepts, what we hope to do is initiate further thought and discussion in an academic context where we are under increased pressure to conduct research in, with, and on other countries. Rarely explored in depth, due to exposure and vulnerability, we emphasise the importance of addressing the uncomfortable feelings we have in doing the work we do.

Democratising Research Methods as a Form of Scholar-Activism: An Experiment with Collaborative Focus Group Analysis

Sui-Ting Kong, Petula Sik-Ying Ho; Stevi Jackson

*(Department of Sociology
Durham University)*

Political divisions persist in the Post-Umbrella Movement context in Hong Kong. They have created rifts in the intimate lives of Hong Kongers when intimate partners, families and friends see each other as essentially either 'yellow ribbon' (pro-democracy camp) or 'blue ribbon' (pro-China camp). In exploring the movement's personal impact on participants, bystanders and opponents, we developed a new methodology - collaborative focus group analysis (CFGAs), with the aim to create safe space for communicating political differences. The methodology also breaks down the distinction between researchers and researched and engages the latter as co-researchers through the design of coupling a focus group with a reflecting team. By analysing the processes of our first application of CFGAs, we have found that listening and responding to others' personal stories of being participants, non-participants or bystanders in the Umbrella Movement not only created a strong sense of solidarity among them, but also enabled sharp exchanges without creating antagonism. This form of solidarity is situated, and it relies on an empathetic understanding of others' pain, suffering, hopes, fears and pleasures, shared understanding of living with familial hierarchical harmony as a father, husband, wife, daughter or son, and the common experience of living under the authoritarian rule of 'Grandpa China'. This paper further argues for the need to democratise everyday research practices as a form of scholar-activism for promoting democracy and reducing political antagonism in politically turbulent times.

Children's Neighbourhoods Scotland and the Capabilities Approach

Maureen McBride, Sarah Ward

(University of Glasgow)

In Scotland, one in four children live in poverty and this has a profound impact on their life chances. In this paper, we report on early findings from a place based approach in the East End of Glasgow which aims to improve wellbeing for

young people living in disadvantaged areas. In developing our evaluation framework for this project, we have drawn heavily on the capabilities approach.

Developed by Amartya Sen the Capabilities Approach (CA) is a framework which accommodates social, economic and political analysis and which holds that the wellbeing of a person should be assessed in the space of capabilities. Capabilities are the freedoms and opportunities that individuals or communities have to achieve what Sen calls functionings, what people or communities are able to do or what they are. CA highlights that people differ in their ability to convert income or commodities into valuable achievements with resources central to social justice. In this paper, we will draw on qualitative data from children and use CA to evaluate both the appropriateness of place as a site for poverty reduction and reflect on Scotland's poverty reduction strategy. We argue that through its focus on democratic deliberation not only are we able to place children's voices at the centre of the evaluation framework but we are also able to identify the barriers and facilitators that the young people face as they try to be what they want to be and achieve all they can.

Race, Ethnicity & Migration A W011

Here, there, everywhere? Mapping EU nationals in the UK.

Laurence Lessard-Phillips, Nando Sigona
(University of Birmingham)

As of June 2017, there were close to 3.4 million nationals from the European Union residing in the United Kingdom, representing approximately 5.3% of the total UK population and more than a threefold increase in numbers since the early 1990s, especially from the mid-2000s (ONS 2017; Vargas-Silva and Markaki 2017). Before, during, and following the EU referendum, issues with regard to these numbers, the free movement of EU nationals, and 'controlling EU immigration' permeated political, media, and popular discourses in the UK. Yet, a clear and detailed picture of the current and historical geographical distribution and the living conditions of EU nationals in the UK is lacking (see Sabater 2015 for an exception). It is important to understand the demographic circumstances of an understudied population, who is growing in demographic importance in the UK and for whom the UK exiting the European Union is most likely going to have an impact.

In this paper, we use various administrative data sources to map and profile EU nationals in the UK, focussing on their historical geographical distribution in the past 35 years, with a special focus on the changes since the Maastricht Treaty and 2004 enlargement, and contrasting this with the situation at the time of the Referendum. We use Census data and official immigration estimates to examine their circumstances. This historical perspective will allow us to capture EU heritage across generations in contemporary Britain.

Costa del Brexit: The Good Life in Jeopardy?

Joel Busher,
(Coventry University)

Conservative estimates put the number of British citizens living in other EU countries at around 1.2 million, of whom a little over 300,000 live in Spain. The figures are however likely to be considerably higher due to the large numbers of British citizens living in Spain and the rest of the EU while still registered as resident in Britain, and the even larger numbers of British citizens who live just part of the year outside Britain. This paper explores the Brexit journeys of a small number of the British who live in Spain. Based on repeat narrative interviews over a period of two years with approximately 30-35 people – of whom some were in favour of and some staunchly opposed to Brexit – as well as auto-ethnography, it traces how the unfolding Brexit process has shaped their everyday lives, their sense of belonging and their hopes and visions of the future.

To 'become or not to become British': naturalisation and (dis)integration for EU citizens in post-Brexit Britain

Nando Sigona, Marie Godin
(University of Birmingham)

In many European countries, there has been a restrictive turn in nationality laws establishing 'regimes of difference' (Ahmed, 1998) that allow States to cherry pick who can become 'new citizens' while at the same time creating 'new denizens' (Morrice, 2017). In the UK context, the academic focus has often been on changes made over time in the design of British citizenship (Tyler, 2009). However, a new range of studies are looking at the lived experience of what it means to go through the process of 'becoming a citizen' examining migrant's agencies at acting as negotiators of this interpellation of what it is to 'be British' (Bassel et al., 2018). Building on this literature, this paper aims to look at aspirations and motivations behind choosing to become or not to become British for EU citizens in a post-Brexit context. The topic of naturalisation for EU nationals resident in another EUMS is to date largely unexplored. With the share of citizenship granted to EU nationals that has increased from 5% in 2007 to 26% in 2017 (ONS, 2018) this

paper casts light on the range of motivations informing decisions to becoming or not British and relate them to the varying positions of interviews in British society.

Talking Brexit with British People of Colour living in the EU-27

Michaela Benson, Chantelle Lewis
(Goldsmiths)

This paper calls for an understanding of Brexit as unexceptional, as business as usual. Presenting original empirical research with British People of Colour who have made their homes and lives in the EU-27, we argue for an alternative to prominent narratives about Brexit that depict Britain as newly racist and xenophobic. Specifically, we make a methodological, empirical and conceptual intervention into an emerging body of social science scholarship to respond to recent calls for research on Brexit to move beyond methodological nationalism and whiteness (see for example Bhabra 2017a). As we argue, focussing on the testimonies of British People of Colour living in the EU-27 offers a unique lens into how Brexit is caught up in personal experiences of racialisation and racial violence, and longer histories of structural and institutional racism. Importantly, these experiences precede and succeed Brexit, taking place in both Britain and other European Union countries.

The Brexit vote and the dynamic contemporary conditions of belonging

Hannah May Fletcher,
(University of Sheffield)

The vote to leave the European Union in the 2016 referendum represented an important moment in bringing divisions surrounding belonging and social identity to the forefront of public attention. The split between Leave and Remain revealed mixed and uneven political geographies, signalling entrenched splits between different groups in society. This presentation will explore the initial findings of a PhD project looking at the Brexit vote's implications for dimensions of belonging. The research is concerned with the views of British-born white residents in a working-class neighbourhood in Northern England. Its focus on one neighbourhood enables the project to better understand the role of space and place in discussions surrounding the contemporary divisions between groups positioned differently within the social hierarchy. This presentation will make an important contribution to emerging analyses of Brexit by considering the interplay of race and class. Whilst the vote for Brexit arguably saw race and class coalesce, work on the referendum has problematically tended to treat these as separate. Most commentators have focused on the class-based cleavages of the EU referendum vote at the expense of considering the role of race. This PhD's focus on understanding the Brexit vote through the lens of race and class in a white working-class community will also enable the presentation to offer some critical reflections on the 'left behind' thesis and the purported link between the white working class, xenophobia and the Leave vote.

Race, Ethnicity & Migration B **W525**

Rethinking 'home' and belonging among LGBT migrants in Scotland

Francesca Stella,
()

This paper draws on the findings of an ESRC-funded project (2015-17), and explores the cognitive and emotional aspects LGBT migrants ascribe to the notion of 'home'.

The project focussed on LGBT migrants from Central Eastern Europe and the Former Soviet Union living in Scotland, and used qualitative methods to explore migration trajectories, experiences of migration and settlement, and migrants' sense of belonging.

The paper draws on interviews and visual data from a subset of 18 migrants; all of them took part in a biographical interview and submitted a collection of personal photographs on the theme of 'home', whose meanings were further elaborated on in a follow-up interview. 'Home' was variously understood as a process of 'home-making', a physical space, a location where meaningful social relations are formed or maintained, and a place of memory.

In unpacking meanings of home, the paper brings into conversation insights from migration and sexuality studies. In migration studies, 'home' is often a heuristic device providing a window into migrants' identity and belonging by exploring attachments to multiple places across national borders (Bocccagni 2017). While migration is often posited as estrangement from an original home, and its positive associations with familiarity, authenticity and security, Brah (1996) has pointed out that migrants' 'homing desire' is not necessarily a 'desire for the homeland', but rather a process of 'home-making'. Meanwhile, queer migration is often posited as 'homecoming', a journey from homophobic or heteronormative domesticity to another site to be called home, embodying queer authenticity and belonging (Fortier 2001).

Queer, National and Transnational Belongings of Polish LGBTQs in the UK

*Lukasz Szulc,
(University of Sheffield)*

Mid-2010s have brought some crucial political changes in Europe with rather depressive prospects for Polish LGBTQs in the UK. In Poland, Law and Justice (PiS) party secured the majority of seats in the Parliament in the 2015 elections. In the UK, British voters decided to leave the European Union in the 2016 Brexit referendum. While PiS has reenergized a queer-free vision of Polish national identity, Brexit has reinvigorated British anti-immigrant sentiments, especially targeting recent East European immigrants. These broader political changes and their accompanying discourses translate into everyday instances of homophobia and xenophobia as well as feed into the negotiations of multiple belongings. Drawing on more than 600 survey responses and in-depth face-to-face interviews with Polish LGBTQs in the UK, I will discuss how they navigate their gender and sexual identifications through national and transnational spaces. I will show how the rise of PiS in Poland has weakened the feelings of Polish national identity and how Brexit has reinvigorated the Polishness, or alternatively Europeaness, for some of my interviewees. I will also discuss how some interviewees explain their support for Brexit, reevaluating their primary national belongings which oscillate between 'British-Polish' and 'Polish-British'. Altogether, I will draw on stories of Polish LGBTQs in the UK to map complex trajectories of their multiple belongings; their views, plans and attachments to multiple spatial and cultural scales, intertwined with their gender and sexual identifications.

The primacy of language to the ethnicization and avoidance strategies of Polish migrant's identity's

*William Shankley,
(University of Manchester)*

Language is routinely considered a prominent marker of ethnicity and boundary marking particularly for white migrants in Britain where language functions to distinguish them from White British people. It has been fifteen years since the EU expansion in 2004 led to large-scale migration of Polish people to Britain and given changes to racism post-Brexit, it is vital we understand the sociological processes that relate to the ethnicization of Polish whiteness. Furthermore, this understanding can contribute to how we consider Polish migrants as social actors in the strategies they deploy to mitigate and/or avoid any harm. The paper uses data from 41 interviews conducted with Polish respondents living in a large urban area in the north west of England and collected between November 2015 and February 2016. This paper finds that language (language proficiency and accent) is the most significant cultural marker of Polish ethnicity and therefore salient in processes of ethnicization. The prominence of language also features prominently in the strategies that Polish migrants deploy to limit the stigma attached to these identities. However, these strategies cannot be deployed equally among all Polish migrants. The strategies that draw of semantics or language elocution function as forms of misrecognition but are confined to elite or middle-class migrants or those who migrated at a young age. Low-income Polish migrants are unable to deploy the same linguistic strategies as a consequence of structural disadvantages within the labour market that restrict their ability to improve their English language skills.

Science, Technology & Digital Studies

W007

Image-ing Tragedy: An Iconological Approach to Mobilizing Morality in Human Disaster

*Sam Han,
(The University of Western Australia)*

This paper aims to explore the dynamics of morality and feeling amid increasingly normalized human tragedy around the globe. In particular, it aims to conceptualize 'tragedy,' and 'the tragic,' not simply in terms of genre but as 'mood,' which frames and mobilizes collective feelings through the circulation of images and video on social media. Drawing on recent developments in affect theory, new cultural approaches to tragedy and visual studies, I aim to provide an account of tragedy that takes mediatization seriously, and weighs the significance of images in providing social categories of understanding 'the tragic.' Using the iconological method pioneered by WJT Mitchell, it will analyze two 'image-events'—the photograph of the washed-up body of young Syrian refugee Alan Kurdi and that of the Facebook live video of Philando Castile, a school cafeteria worker in St. Paul, Minnesota in the US, shot and killed by a police officer in 2017.

Post-scarce online informational resources, equal development? The role of using the internet for learning in mitigating unequal career mobilities between rural migrant and urban resident workers in urban China

*Chong Zhang,
(Durham University)*

In China's urban labour market, compared to urban resident workers (URW), rural migrant workers (RMW) are found to have a less promising prospect on their career progressions. Whilst an emerging 'post-scarcity' feature of online informational resources could be seen and skill-development is considered as a helpful means to help career mobility, it remains relatively unknown that whether through using the internet for learning (UIL), the RMW-URW career progression disparity can be mitigated. To address this issue, a mixed-methods study has been carried out to study three aspects of this issue (How is UIL related to occupational mobility? Is there a digital divide in UIL between RMW and URW? And, does UIL appear to be equally helpful for their career mobilities?). The quantitative result shows that whilst in general UIL is associated with positive career mobilities, the association appears to be stronger among RMW, however, RMW are also found to be less likely to be engaged in UIL. The subsequent qualitative inquiry also found that 1) white collar workers tend to narrate UIL as a necessary but not sufficient means for their career progression/ a means to prevent downward mobility, 2) the formation of UIL disposition needs the accumulation of relevant embodied cultural capitals (e.g. acquired professional knowledge), which are conditioned by one's position, and 3) URW indeed have more diverse non-skill-related resources (e.g. social capital, direct inheritance) to help their career progressions, which might help to explain why the UIL-mobility association is stronger among RMW.

FEMINIST STUDY LOOKING INTO THE BENEFITS OF USING WHATSAPP FOR FAMILY SOCIAL CAPITAL

Camilla Ndukwe, Prof Garry Crawford
(University of Salford)

FEMINIST STUDY ON THE BENEFITS OF USING WHATSAPP FOR FAMILY SOCIAL CAPITAL

This paper is part of an ongoing PhD research which aims to identify how women have adopted and integrated mobile phones into their daily living. The research adopts a feminist approach to gain a first-hand understanding of women's experiences. The study which is qualitative in nature draws on 24 in-depth interviews to gather data on women's experiences of using mobile phones. The study sought to explore the various ways in which women used their phones, the reasons for their choices, the factors that influence their choices and the benefits or demerits of using a mobile phone. The participants are all Nigerian women. This paper will be focusing on one of the study's key themes- the social benefits of owning and using mobile phones.

Many studies have explored the benefits of social media and messaging application especially to students and young adults. Finding from previous studies confirm that these platforms are useful for educating women, however, there is almost no study that have specifically explored how women use WhatsApp to build or maintain social capital. Therefore, this paper will focus on the role WhatsApp plays in enabling the women to maintain relationships with their maternal families, friends from their home towns or the families they grew up with. The paper will also be exploring why the women have chosen WhatsApp as their chosen platform for communication and eventually the consequences on social capital.

Boundary work and practices of exclusion in a local community Facebook group

Nick Foard,
(Nottingham Trent University)

Boundary work plays an important role in the cultural performance of community in urban neighbourhoods, sustaining collective identities which can serve to include and exclude individuals and groups (Blokland, 2017). As more and more neighbourhood communities are establishing online spaces in the form of locally-focused social media groups, the question arises of whether neighbourhood boundary work is merely reproduced in these corresponding online spaces, or whether they might offer a potential arena in which exclusionary practices can be more readily revealed and challenged. In this paper I discuss early findings from a digital ethnographic study of a large local community Facebook group, based upon analysis of posts and comments over several months. Specifically, I consider: the ways in which references to offline activities, interactions and experiences are used to carry over and perform boundary work in the online group; ways in which online interactions are used to challenge and re-examine cultural norms found offline; and the role of the administrators in moderating the group as a further extension of boundary work. In addressing these issues, the research enables a better understanding of the interactions between the networks of online spaces and hierarchies of neighbourhood communities.

Social Divisions / Social Identities A

W110

Unequal youth migrations: exploring the synch between class and age among post-crisis European migrants

Simone Varriale,
(School of Social and Political Science, University of Lincoln)

This presentation explores how symbolic boundaries between youth and adulthood shape experiences of upward and downward social mobility among EU migrants. Drawing on 56 biographical interviews with Italians who moved to

England after the 2008 economic crisis, and focusing on three individual case studies, the paper reveals that normative understandings of adulthood emerge as a central concern from participants' biographical accounts, and that they mobilise unequal forms of cultural, economic and social capital to maintain a feeling of synchrony between social ageing and social mobility. Drawing on Bourdieu and the sociology of adulthood, the article proposes the concept of 'synch' to explore how tensions in the relationship between social ageing and social mobility shape experiences of migration. This allows for an innovative theoretical bridge between cultural class analysis, adulthood studies and migration studies, and for a better understanding of how intersections of class and age shape intra-European migrations.

Social Media and Oppositional Coordination of the Russian Ethnic Minorities

Guzel Yusupova
(Durham University)

The paper examines the social movement of Russian ethnic minorities in defence of the second state languages in the context of politics of fear, paying special attention to the developments in Tatarstan. Analysis is positioned on the intersection of complexity theory in nationalism studies that explains how small actions of ordinary people could lead to a national movement and the theory of connective action from the literature on social movements which explains how digitally mediated political engagement leads to a social change. This theoretical fusion provides a nuanced explanation of spontaneously organized resistance to the demotion of minority languages by the central government.

Interviews with activists, participant observation and qualitative content analysis of social networking sites (SNS) reveal that despite the covert restrictions of offline social mobilization, the resistance has been transformed to the vivid online connective action advancing grass-roots activities and inter-ethnic solidarity. This has resulted in establishing weak ties between representatives of the single ethnic group and among different ethnic groups and in making ethnic minority issues more salient in public discourse. Connective action in SNS has led to the awareness that many people share the same political positions and has resulted in feelings of togetherness that helped to promote united actions in the restricted political space to oppose the decisions of the federal government.

A New Research Agenda for Comparative Colonialisms in Queer Analysis: Comparing British and Portuguese Colonial Histories and Legacies in Kenya and Mozambique

Matthew Waites, Gustavo Gomes da Costa Santos
(University of Glasgow)

Comparative analysis of colonialisms is of critical importance, and hence this paper proposes and instigates such systematic comparative research with respect to same-sex sexualities and gender diversity. We offer a historical sociological comparison of the Portuguese and British empires analysing relevant regulation, in relation to two African contexts: Mozambique and Kenya. Through a comparative methodology, we illuminate important differences in the regulation of same-sex sexualities and gender diversity, that have contemporary legacies: a) the difference in timing of criminalisation of same-sex acts and its impacts in the emergence of homosexuality as an issue of governmental repression; b) the more interventionist approach of Portuguese colonialism relative to British "indirect rule"; and c) the difference in racialised perceptions of homosexuality as a mainly European desire (in Portuguese colonialism) or as potentially occurring universally (in British colonialism). Identifying such differences can assist those aligned with queer politics to understand and engage coloniality in the present. The paper thus initiates a new research agenda at the conjuncture of the new global historical sociology's transboundary analyses, and comparative colonialisms, with the analytical agendas of gender and sexuality studies and queer politics.

Social Divisions / Social Identities B

W828

The monetary origins of Stigma

Francesca Coin,
(Ca' Foscari University)

'How could the predatory targeting of economically dispossessed communities and the subsequent bailout of the nation's largest investment banks [...] be recast as a problem caused by the racial other', asked Chakravarty and Bonilla Silva after the subprime crisis (2012: 364)? This paper draws on (i.) the sociological analysis of money and (ii.) Tyler's definition of stigma to explain the production of the racial other as a social parasite. Its thesis is that stigma - the political attempt to 'channel hostility against the most vulnerable groups' and to define them as 'a parasitical drain upon scarce resources' (Tyler, 2013:211) is a form of neoliberal governance intended to protect the free market from a crisis of legitimacy. In order to do so, this paper focuses specifically on the nature of money as theorised by Geoffrey Ingham and addresses the discrepancy between monetary theory and practice. Tracing the representation of money

in the media using NVivo coding and text mining techniques and (2) using ethnographic research in Greece to document the escalating representation of women and migrants as outcasts and the introduction of punitive policies against the poor (Wacquant), this paper considers stigma as a political weapon mobilised to conceal the predatory nature of money and protect market legitimacy; a governance tool intended to recast the causes of the financial crisis as effects of the 'parasitical' conduct of welfare recipients.

Shame and resentment: Emotion, class relations, and mothers' poverty at times of means-tested welfare

Orly Benjamin, Orly Benjamin
(Bar Ilan University)

Scholars interested in the emotions triggered by welfare policies, primarily examined shame, an emotion that assumes belonging. The possibility that welfare policies and multiple citizenship positions may give rise to additional emotions, was not examined. This has hampered research from arriving at a perspective of class relations that recognizes the refusal to succumb to the hegemonic feeling structure. Focusing on resentment, I propose a class relations perspective, one recognizing the politics of belonging as a struggle over entitlement to support. This perspective emerged from the analysis of structured interviews conducted in Israel with 90 mothers, of seven ethno-national categories, living in poverty. I raise two research questions: First, against which circles of belonging do mothers who live in poverty speak of experiencing shame? The assumption here is that shame is contingent upon belonging and shared values – when belonging and shared values converge, shame may be painful. Second, when mothers' talk indicates resentment, what do they resent? The assumption is that the explicit naming of resentment cannot be expected when cultural feeling rules are reinforced by the need to maintain an appearance of cooperation and obedience. For theoretical purposes, I also raise a third question concerning the possibility that value judgement may reveal the current multiplicity in citizenship. My findings enable a conceptualization of 'managed' resentment that is associated with experiences of indifference, direct deprivation and non-rationality of welfare representatives. Resentment feelings in the negotiation of non-belonging and the refusal to accept welfare bureaucrats' value judgement, are discussed.

As cold as charity? Using Mass Observation panel writing to compare public views on the role of voluntary action in welfare provision in the 1940s and the 2010s

Rose Lindsey, Brewis G; Ellis Paine A; Hardill I; Macmillan R
(University of Southampton)

This paper presents findings from an interdisciplinary study which has been examining differing discourses and narratives of the role of voluntary action in welfare provision across two distinct timeframes in the UK - the 1940s and the 2010s.

These two time-points represent potential 'bookends' for the British welfare state as we currently know it. The timing of the publication of the Beveridge Report in 1942 (during WW2), and its recommendation for comprehensive changes to welfare services in the UK to tackle the 'five evils' - idleness, squalor, want, ignorance and disease - was referred to by Beveridge as 'a revolutionary moment' (1942:6). This same term has been used to describe the impact of the programme of austerity in the 2010s with welfare services being dismantled in England (Brindle et al, 2014). A key focus of this study is on these two transformational moments, and their impact on people's views of the respective roles and responsibilities of the state and voluntary action in the provision of welfare services.

This paper looks specifically at 'public' discourses and narratives from the 1940s and 2010s, drawing on Mass Observation (MO) writing from both periods. It provides a brief introduction to the methods used in this study. It then compares the discourses of MO writers across these two timeframes (where possible comparing the views of writers with different socio-economic/political identities). It examines similarities and differences in perceptions of beneficiaries of charitable and state-provided welfare services, inequality, and who should be responsible for welfare service provision.

Exploring the place of stigma in the lives of women who claim social security benefits: structural constraints and agential responses

Nancy Evans,
(University of Liverpool)

In the context of unprecedented welfare reform, alongside media depictions and policy narratives which continually demonise benefit recipients, examining the lived experiences of those at the receiving end of such interventions is particularly pertinent. Exploring the voices and experiences of women in this context is necessary, not least because women's position within the welfare state, and the gendered relationship between welfare, paid work and care have traditionally been overlooked within social policy analyses, and some of the recent welfare policy shifts have been found to disproportionately affect women. Moreover, stigmatising media depictions of those who rely on social security benefits are gendered, with ideals of 'femininity', 'respectability' and deservingness increasingly attached to labour market participation. My research draws on Goffman's (1963) micro-level focus on agential responses to stigmatisation, as well as contemporary critiques, which place far more emphasis on structural power relations which

create and reinforce stigma (Tyler and Slater, 2018; Scambler, 2018). Qualitative research exploring the lived experiences of marginalised groups continues to successfully challenge dominant narratives, however there is a shortage of empirical work specifically examining gendered experiences of and responses to stigma. My research explores this using 26 Free Association Narrative Interviews with 13 women in Merseyside, who were purposively recruited via a women's organisation. The Free Association Narrative Interview (FANI) method draws on a psychosocial approach and uses repeat, in-depth interviews to produce rich data. The conference paper will discuss my methodological and ethical considerations, and some emergent findings of my data collection.

Sociology of Education A W823

Career-Related Perceptions and Aspirations of Diverse Group of Biomedical Science PhD Students in the United States: A Mixed-Methods, Longitudinal Study.

*Simon Williams, Remi Jones; Richard McGea
(Aston University)*

In the United States, improving the proportion of underrepresented racial and ethnic minorities (URMs) in academic science careers is a priority (National Institutes of Health, 2012). Evidence suggests that a significant proportion of students, particularly URMs, are deterred from persisting towards academic careers during the PhD (Gibbs, McGready & Griffin 2015).

In this paper, we explore the varied ways in which a diverse group of PhD students construct their career-related aspirations during (and beyond) the PhD and how they interpret the academic job market. We pay particular attention to the ways in which URM students understand their identity, and try to position themselves as a 'minority' in science.

We draw on quantitative and qualitative data, collected annually over a five-year period (2011-2016) to explore, and follow the evolution of, the students' (n=400) career-related perceptions and aspirations. The paper is informed by a relational approach to sociology in the Bourdieusian tradition, drawing heavily on the concepts of field, capital and habitus. We argue, amongst other things, that the PhD science field can be particularly difficult for URM students to navigate due to a lack of relevant cultural capital. This study has been supported by the following National Institutes of Health (NIH) grants: DP4 GM096807 (ARRA); R01 GM085385, R01 GM085385-02S1 (ARRA), R01 NR011987, R01 GM107701, and 1R35GM118184-01.

Dancing to a Different Tune: tracing employment pathways of performing arts graduates

*Ciaran Burke
(University of Derby)*

Stemming from the rapid de-industrialisation of the 1970s and 1980s and the emergence and firm development of the knowledge economy, higher education has moved from a peripheral institution to one of central economic significance. The expansion of U.K. higher education, and echoed globally, has witnessed participation levels rising to nearly 50% of young people. However, increased levels of higher education participation have not been met with equal opportunities for graduate employment.

While levels of graduate under-employment are prevalent across a range of degree pathways, some are more susceptible than others. Successive research from the Warwick Institute of Employment Research (Elias, et al., 1999, Purcell and Elias, 2004) has identified creative industry graduates as experiencing particularly prolonged levels of underemployment and at times taking longer than their 'traditional' counterparts to secure and build a graduate career. Based on empirical research charting the short-term and long-term employment trajectories of graduates from performing arts degree courses, this paper will examine the classed nature of portfolio careers. In particular it will illustrate the central role that a priori capitals, identified by Bourdieu, play in navigating a fluid and volatile labour market.

Social mobility as a snake eating its own tail: The problematic politics of social mobility research into elite higher education and elite employers – how do we go forward?

*Sol Gamsu,
(University of Bath)*

Through a review of research undertaken under the remit of the Social Mobility Commission (SMC), I examine the political implications for sociologists of policy-oriented research around social mobility in the form of access to elite universities and employers. I draw on criticisms by the Centre for Contemporary Cultural Studies of early post-war sociologists of education (Finn et al. 1978; Baron et al. 1981), who they argued were too focussed on researching

issues of access to selective forms of education with the result that broader structural issues of inequality were not examined. With rising educational participation, there are now similar dilemmas facing sociologists researching access to graduate employers and elite universities. Whilst the SMC has fostered research examining access to elite universities, it has largely ignored the persistent inequalities between universities (Boliver, 2015). Similarly within the SMC's analyses of entry to elite employers, the focus has been on equitable recruitment and employment practices within large corporate firms, not on the actual economic activity of the firms themselves. Taking the Big Four accountancy firms as an example, I explore how these firms have been involved in privatisation, job losses and erosion of employment conditions. The working-class and ethnic-minority graduates these firms wish to recruit are likely to come from communities that have been affected by the damaging economic activity that these firms are fostering. This paper seeks to open a discussion about how we go forward with access oriented research whilst at the same time acknowledging the need for broader structural change.

Sociology of Education B W002

CHALLENGING EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY IN MARGINALIZED URBAN SETTINGS: THE POTENTIAL OF PLACE-BASED REFORMS

*LORNA ERWIN,
(YORK UNIVERSITY)*

This paper argues that challenging racial and class-based disparities in schooling requires research that looks at the dynamic interaction between individuals and the surroundings in which they find themselves and that situates their narratives within a larger political, economic and symbolic context.

Based on a longitudinal case study of a youth-centered initiative—Success Beyond Limits (SBL)—undertaken in a racialized, low-income neighborhood in Toronto, the analyses draws on focus-group testimony and interviews with students, mentors, and teachers. The findings, which focus on the long-term processes of school reform, have crucial implications for policy and practice, as well as research agendas.

The paper explores how different components of SBL, a unique, integrated full-year program, within a public school setting, have profoundly influenced student aspirations and trajectories. What emerges as central to SBL's effectiveness is its multidimensional approach, which, involving as it does a hyper-local, place-based focus, supports close adult-youth relationships. It has also sustained a range of resources and interventions that address a variety of student academic and social needs, with an emphasis on collective empowerment.

Research utilizing place-consciousness has been mostly carried out in rural settings—settings where community survival and ecological issues figure prominently. By contrast, this paper argues for a place-based emphasis on urban inequality that foregrounds students as subjects rather than objects of educational practice. More specifically, by tying the realities of place to pedagogy, such approaches inculcate a sense of collective responsibility. In effect, improving educational outcomes becomes part of a broader agenda of empowering communities.

'Schools don't teach you how to cope with life.' The school experiences of NEETs in London

*Magdolna Lorinc,
(University of Sheffield)*

Periods of being NEET (not in education, employment or training) can have long-term consequences for individuals' future job opportunities, earnings, psycho-social wellbeing and health – all with high societal costs (Bell & Blanchflower, 2011; Coles et al., 2010). Therefore interventions are sought by policy-makers to successfully reduce NEET numbers (Hutchison et al., 2016; Mawn et al., 2017; Thurlby-Campbell & Bell, 2017). It is well established in the academic literature that negative school experiences and educational underachievement are among the main risk factors for becoming NEET (Archambault et al., 2009; Duffy & Elwood, 2013; Furlong, 2006; Janmaat et al., 2015). Drawing on a longitudinal qualitative study in London, this paper explores the processes and mechanisms in schools that contribute to young people becoming NEET after leaving education.

In line with previous research (Rumberger, 2011), our findings indicate that turbulent labour market transitions are often preceded by disengagement from school, resulting in low/no qualifications. Levels of engagement, in turn, depend on the complex interaction of personal, socio-economic and environmental circumstances (Görlich & Katznelson, 2015; Heath et al., 2017; Holland et al., 2007).

Through analysis of NEETs' accounts of their school experiences, we explore how unfulfilled support needs contribute to becoming NEET. Participants felt that the education system did not prepare them for 'real life'. According to them, an excessive focus on academic achievement, a lack of adequate career advice and guidance, and limited work

experience provision in schools all contributed to dead-end post-compulsory education and training choices, dropping-out and, ultimately, becoming NEET.

Schooling Youth Cultures in East Asian Education: the Case of Taiwan

Chi-Chung Wang,

(Institute of Sociology, Academia Sinica)

In sociological research on youth (sub)cultures, there has been a theoretical absence concerning the active role of the educational system in shaping young people's cultural life. Based on a school ethnography conducted with student members of high school rock clubs in Taiwan, this article begins to fill this gap. I analyse how certain schooling structure and institutions – such as academic ranking and exams – frame the way students engage in their rock activities, and how this facilitates the popularity of heavy metal rock and the replication of exam culture in students' rock subculture. Extending Shildrick and Macdonald's use of the term 'leisure career', I suggest that an in-depth analysis of the interplay between young people's 'educational career' and their focused leisure activities can be useful in understanding how specific patterns of decision making shapes young students' everyday culture and contributes to the distinctiveness of their subcultural participation.

Theory A

W323

Rethinking Foucault's Analysis of Disciplines through Representation as Intervention

Dean Curran,

(University of Calgary)

In *Discipline and Punish*, Foucault argues that disciplines that study areas of social life produce rather than discover the body of knowledge that forms the discipline. Foucault's insight has led to a vast amount of research that identifies how social science knowledge and its associated devices and apparatuses engage in 'making up people' and social life as a whole. While this research paradigm has been incredibly fruitful this dilemma of science as either discovering pre-existing features or producing these features fails to adequately integrate both the representational and the interventional quality of social sciences. This paper proposes the approach representation as intervention to reconcile the representative dimensions of science – the fact that science aims to represent, admittedly always in a one-sided way, its objects of study – with the fact that it also always potentially has impacts on the phenomena it aims to analyse. In fact, as is shown in this paper, it is only through the representational dimension of science – that a body of claims is about a set of phenomena in the world – that the interventional dimension of social science can be made intelligible. This approach and the necessity of the representational dimension for intervention is then shown through a critical analysis of the performativity thesis regarding the impacts of social science on social life.

Oxymoronic Social Policy- Managing the 'Troubled' Family

Rebecca Carter Dillon,

(University of Plymouth)

The Troubled Families (TF) Programme in England (2012-2020) is the latest in a long line of social policy interventions in the lives of families with complex needs; it is a continuation of a policy tradition of blaming materially disadvantaged families for their poverty, without acknowledging the significance of the wider socio-economic context. The TF Programme takes an oxymoronic position, prescribing that families be controlled- 'Local Authorities must appoint a keyworker for each family who will manage the family and their problems' (DCLG, 2016), whilst at the same time expecting them to take responsibility for making positive, sustained changes to their 'troubled' lives.

My PhD research, which comprised interviews with 34 professionals from different services involved in the TF Programme, and six families receiving support in a local authority in the SW of England, looked at the issues of power and powerlessness that the Programme reinforces. I took a Feminist Standpoint Theory (FST) approach to studying power (Rolin, 2009); this approach prioritised first the voice of families 'done to' by the TF Programme and, second, that of the professionals working closely with them. FST provided a framework for critical consideration of families' experiences of receiving support from the Programme in a context of poverty and inequality, and I explored professionals' attempts to provide empowering support within a disempowering context. I have critiqued the underlying assumptions and economic and ideological arguments that underpin the TF Programme, and demonstrate that it does little to address the real issues impacting on 'troubled' families.

The Evolution of the Hostile Environment: A Darwinian Social Evolutionary Perspective

William Kerr,

(The University of Birmingham)

The hostile environment policy of the UK government emerged out of a process of increasing hostility towards immigrants, seen by both major parties as a necessary strategy to win votes. But it is only a 'successful' strategy because it works within a particular cultural environment, one that seemingly accepts hostility towards the other as being 'normal'. In this paper I look at the ways in which cultural environments evolve, and how this can perpetuate inequalities, with a specific reference to the hostile environment policy. I argue that Darwinian social evolution, using the concepts of variation, inheritance and selection within a local environment, can understand how particular cultural environments evolve and consequently place constraints that make certain strategies more successful than others. I first outline the Darwinian social evolutionary perspective, distinguishing it both from social Darwinism and sociobiology, and then elucidate Clarissa Rile Hayward's concept of 'de-faced' power, which focuses on boundaries that constrain agents' actions. Following this, I combine these concepts in an examination of the cultural environment of the UK and how this made the hostile environment policy not only possible, but also acceptable. I argue that by understanding how these boundaries evolve and shape actions, we are better able to make changes in more positive directions.

Charity Inequalities: Who Can Take Advantage of Charity's Symbolic Power?

Jon Dean,

(Sheffield Hallam University)

This presentation will offer a sociology of charity, an often forgotten field for sociological analysis. Charities, and the act of charity itself, are imbued with an immediate social authority. Doing something for charity, or being charitable, is usually seen as a 'good thing': socially worthy, a signifier of moral value, an exhibition of an individual's inherent altruism and kindness. As a result of this inherent goodness, charitable organisations, which act as funnels to collect and distribute altruism in a strategic manner, have public influence in their ability to encourage the general public in appeals for donations, and in lobbying for policy change. Yet like any other sector of society, charity is beset by inequalities, in terms of participation, power, and representation. Focusing on how certain elite individuals - from Donald Trump's Foundation to Bill Gates' philanthrocapitalism - are able to utilise the symbolic power of charity for their own means, this paper will critically examine how in certain circumstances charity becomes a tool for reproducing inequality rather than tackling it. Drawing on original empirical studies of charity leadership, and the presentation of 'good' selves through social media, and the theories of Weber and Bourdieu and recent critical studies of giving by McGeoy and Krause, this examination will show how sociological critiques of social hierarchies and inequalities that ignore the role of charity and gifts are incomplete.

Theory B W001

Incompatible Perspectives or a Match Made in Heaven? Examining the Implications of Applying both Insider and Outsider Viewpoints in Community Research.

Su Jones, Nathan Kerrigan

(Aston University)

The current ethnographic approach in community studies has been one drawn of a binary between being an insider researcher or outsider researcher. Such an approach has facilitated a tension between these two positions in relation to the confirmability and trustworthiness of data collected. While insider researchers claim legitimacy as they conduct research with populations of which they share a cultural base; thus enabling a greater level of openness and trust, outsider researchers contest such position arguing that they have greater claim to legitimacy not having a cultural bias which an insider perspective might bring. But are these positions incompatible? The following paper will explore the implications of applying both an insider and outsider perspective in a research project. Based on proposed research within a community in a Midlands city, this paper examines the process of insider and outsider perspectives of 'sense and place making' within a community under-going change as a response to proposed new development. Community dynamics will be explored to highlight how residents are enacting strategies of control towards each other as a result of s106 funding being made available to conduct new developments identified from the community, causing tension between different community groups of conflicting vested interests.

Reflections on self-reflection: Useful distinctions and the possibility of a common conceptual ground

Christoforos Bouzanis

(University of Glasgow)

Influential developments of the idea of the dialogical self in social theory (Wiley, 1994; Archer, 2003) have related the concept of inner speech with the concept of reflexivity which designates agential powers of monitoring, evaluating and questioning one's own beliefs, values and ultimate concerns, as well as of objectifying and assessing institutional settings and structural forms. In most recent analyses, the key debate revolves around the possibility of theoretically combining reflexivity and habitual action. This paper aims at introducing key distinctions that can trigger

interdisciplinary communication among sociologists, philosophers, psychologists and other specialists in the social sciences, that participate in the discussion about the dialogical self. I start the analysis by explaining (a) why we need to distinguish among habitual action, routine and tacit knowledge, while excluding habitual action from the theorizing of institutional and structural reproduction – a fallacy which is a remnant of Bourdieu's influence in social theory. Then, I argue for (b) the idea that the presupposition of dialogical self does not necessarily entail the possibility of self-reflection, (c) the idea that the assumption of self-reflection does not necessarily entail the possibility of collective or individual effect on the transformation of social forms, and (d) the idea that the assumption of collective/individual (causal) effects on social forms does not necessarily imply intentional reflective political praxis. These four remarks can, I think, constitute a common ground among critical realists, social constructionists and anti-realists in their debates upon the constitution of social realities and the discursive construction of identity.

Communal Synchronicity

Aksel Tjora,

(Norwegian University of Science and Technology)

While it may certainly be argued that various aspects of society (innovation, technologies, communication etc.) are being accelerated (i.e. Hartmut Rosa), there are tendencies of diverging levels of synchronicity. On basis of various studies of community development within online and offline settings, this paper suggests a typology of asynchronous, semi-synchronous, and synchronous communal forms to address the connection between time/space dimensions and social development. A major question is raised in the paper about the maintenance, development, and transformation of critical public spheres, and how participatory hierarchies and inequalities may result from lost time/space synchronicity. Especially, the economic-technological management of online public spheres (by membership, algorithms, etc.) and the growing domination of such online spheres may significantly challenge democratic processes' impact on societal development. The paper concludes with a call to sociology to independently and critically develop studies of fragmentation and de-synchronisation of potentially empowering communal platforms.

Advocating a contemplation of 'identity leisure'; a challenge to the metaphysics of presence essential to 'identity work'

Sarah Burton, Ricky Gee

(Nottingham Trent University)

From the latter stages of the 20th century onwards there has been a rise in identity politics and the concept of 'identity' has become increasingly more important to study. Leading theorists in this field have studied macro and micro identity politics (Goffman, 1959, 1963; Lawler, 2013; Hall, 1996; hooks, 1982) but few research studies attempt to combine the two standpoints of the macro and the micro in order to explore the relationship between the structural forces at play with identity formation and levels of social agency. Snow and Anderson's (1987) seminal work coined the term 'identity work' to illustrate how homeless people actively engage in varying identity performances to preserve their self-dignity. This paper will deconstruct the notion of 'work' in this context and challenge not only its latent etymological and epistemological position, but also its conflation with action; succumbing to the guardrails of the metaphysics of presence (Derrida, 1984). Drawing on post-structuralist theories we argue that 'identity work' as a concept is overly focused on that which is present to the individual rather than what is absent. Such a vantage point does little to consider the ethical implications of a conceptual over use of 'work', at the expense of 'leisure', therefore lacking a nuanced account of identities that do not have to 'work' hard to save face (Goffman, 1963). Using vignettes from two different studies we conclude that identity 'leisure', with its challenge to identity 'work' provides an important addition and conceptual tension within the field of identity discourse.

Work, Employment & Economic Life

HANGING LANTERN ROOM

What is gamification doing to work and why does it matter?

Lynne Pettinger,

(University of Warwick)

Gamification brings both 'fun' and competition into workplaces and is one of many ways that software affordances have changed managerial practices and transformed occupations. It is now present in military, manufacturing, and service sectors. This paper brings together software studies and the sociology of work to understand the problematic 'solutionism' (Morozov, 2013) present in gamification. It discusses how gamification promises solutions to managerial problems of work motivation and productivity through twin appeals to the health and wellbeing agenda promoted by 'psy' disciplines and adopted by HR departments, and to the mythic power of technological change to be always a force for good. It also unpacks assumptions made by gamification developers and salespeople about the translatability of tacit and explicit work skills into gamified software practices and hence considers the unspoken but important transformations of work embedded in gamifying practices.

Skills formation and skills matching in online platform work

*Laura Larke, Sian Brooke, Huw Davies, Anoush Margaryan, and Vili Lehdonvirta
(University of Oxford)*

A growing proportion of the world's population earn part or all of their income from work mediated through online platforms, in what is variously known as crowdwork, platform-based work, online gig work, and online freelancing. Emerging research suggests that such work is an increasingly important form of employment that allows skilled workers to access opportunities to earn income outside of their local labour market (Katz & Krueger 2016, Huws & Joyce 2016, Kässi & Lehdonvirta 2018). Work mediated by online platforms is a continuation of broader shifts in the global economy, representing a form of flexible, market-based, and oftentimes sporadic employment, where individual responsibility over career trajectory and skills development is emphasized by both workers and clients. The digital transformation of labour markets is demanding workers become responsible for their up-skilling or re-skilling in order to remain competitive. Against this backdrop, our study investigates: how individuals using digital platforms to access work have acquired and developed both their saleable and socio-professional skills; what learning activities and strategies they undertake to self-regulate their learning; how they match their skills to market demand; and how platform design and public policy influences their learning practices and skills matching. Utilising data from qualitative, semi-structured interviews with 80 EU-based crowdworkers who are currently using one of four large online freelancing platforms, this study fills a significant gap in the existing literature by addressing digital workplace learning practices.

The results of this study have implications for how we understand new labour markets to function and how workers participating in these markets behave. We will examine how notions of power and responsibility present themselves in online platform-based work compared to more traditional ways of working, and look at how existing forms of capital (technical, economic, cultural, and social) impact online freelancers' ability to learn and develop professionally so that they may engage successfully with employers. This study also has implications for our understanding of workplace learning (Margaryan, 2018) and vocational training, and how those needs might be met in a shifting economic landscape.

Exploring the influence of time pressure on routines and food practices of adults in employment

*Lucy Sam, David Watts, Jennie Macdiarmid
(University of Aberdeen)
Tony Craig
(The James Hutton Institute, Aberdeen)*

Issues pertaining to a lack of time, time constraints and perceived time pressure have been identified as barriers to healthy eating. In particular, time constraints imposed by employment may heighten the perception of time pressure and limit the amount of time available for food shopping, preparation and eating. This in turn may be associated with increased consumption of convenience foods which could negatively impact diet quality. Adults with both employment and childcare responsibilities may experience additional time constraints and pressures compared to those without children. However, evidence on the influence of time barriers on routine food practices among UK adults in employment is limited.

This paper explores perceptions and experiences of time pressure in relation to routines and food practices (shopping, cooking and eating) of adults in employment, living with or without children. In-depth, face-to-face semi-structured interviews were conducted with 30 participants including men and women aged over 18 years in paid employment, working at least 15 hours per week. The focus will be on the emergent themes of: understanding perceived time pressure; the construction of routines and food practices; the mediating role of healthy eating ideals and household composition.

Friday 26/04/2019 at 11:00 - 12:30
Paper Session 8

Cities, Mobilities, Place & Space A
W622

The organisation of Manchester's electricity system(s)

Torik Holmes,
(Lancaster University)

In this paper, I consider and describe the multi-scalar organisation and management of the electricity system. I explain how the system's multi-scalar organisation has real consequences, with infrastructural changes and developments configured and framed in relation to different organisational values, objectives and spatial boundaries. As a consequence of describing the multi-scalar organisation of the electricity system, I move beyond a focus on the urban-infrastructure nexus. The dynamics of this nexus have become a prevalent theme and interest within literature concerning the development and management of different infrastructural arrangements. In contrast, I focus on the dynamics of the space-infrastructure nexus, describing how 'urban', 'regional' and 'international' versions of the electricity system are crafted and configured through the work of particular organisations and organisational relationships. I describe how the production of each version of the electricity system sees infrastructural changes and extensions positioned in relation to particular logics. Indeed, the multiplicity discussed suggests that the electricity system is an ongoing outcome of different and intersecting ontological frames. In this regard, I suggest that the system is not exclusively an 'urban', 'regional' or 'international' assemblage. Instead, the system can be usefully conceptualised as an ongoing outcome of organisational practices and relationships between organisations, which produce, work with and act in relation to different spatial scales. I further suggest that developing and working with this conceptualisation of the space-infrastructure nexus has consequences for how other infrastructures are approached and researched. Such consequences will be outlined.

Reflecting vying interests? Exploring the 'domestication' of hydraulic fracturing in the UK elite journalism

Julian Matthews,
(University of Leicester)

The process of hydraulic fracturing has become one of the latest environmental concerns to be reported in the national (UK) news media. This controversy shares likenesses with others (e.g. previous issues with road building) where journalists are required to report in a context of governmental consent for a potentially environmentally damaging activity and amidst protests from environmental groups and local communities. Against this context, it is important to assess the efforts of journalists to 'domesticate' the issue according to these vying UK interests. As such, this paper explores the domestication of fracking in national (UK) journalism according to the following question: to what extent does UK press reflect different arguments, rebuttals and concessions on fracking? Explored over time is the presence of story framing and speaking opportunities of different stakeholders. The paper finds that reporting includes marked story frames (benefit vs risk) that are found commonly elsewhere (e.g. USA, Ireland, Canada and Poland – see Matthews and Hansen 2018). The observed levels of the optimism and pessimism associated with this framing nonetheless, reflect the specific politicization of the issue within the UK, where elite discussion rather than local protests predominate. Additionally, we see slight variations in use of frames and voices among newspapers according to their political positioning, with the Times, positioned to the right, focusing on economic benefits and the Guardian, positioned to the left, more concerned with risk. Although largely absent from national reporting at present, increased local protest will likely challenge these reporting configurations.

Understanding the shared transportation services in Latin-American cities: the impacts of ridehailing in Mexico City

Thalia Hernandez Amezcua,
(Institute for Transport Studies)

The adoption of shared mobility services challenges transportation researchers, policymakers, and planners. Given the long-range business, policy, and planning decisions that are required to support transportation infrastructure towards to a sustainable development, planners and decision-makers needs more information to decide how to allocate scarce resources, integrate shared modes into transportation management plans and, provide incentives to encourage greater use of shared-use mobility services.

Ridehailing systems are promoted in developed countries as an antidote to car-dependency. However, the effects of this services can be completely different in Latin-American cities; the adoption of 'private shared transport systems' can perpetuate car culture and increase the car dependency. Besides, the play of the informal market and unemployment rates can have an important impact on ridehailing services (Clausen and Velázquez García, 2017) as well as inequality. Also, it is possible to hypothesise that the social structure can replicate old patterns of privileged access for some and denial for others. All those topics remain unknown; ridehailing' impacts and its consequences are important, but understudied, the cause of concern in Latin-American cities.

The central question in this dissertation asks is how the factors which affect the use of ridehailing systems in Mexico City, considering the social stratification and the experience of users and drivers (partners of the platform) affects the travel behaviour and, as a consequence of this, the carbon emissions.

An introduction to my masters dissertation project “Reading the signals: The meanings of pedestrian crossings in uncertain times”

Martin Greenwood,
(University of Manchester)

I'm a current PhD candidate at the University of Manchester's Department of Sociology. I returned to education to study MA Sociology 16 years after completing my undergraduate degree in Comparative Religion. I am interested in the ways public services and public space condition people's ideas about the future and in the sociological utility of the concept of utopia.

This paper discusses how current pedestrian crossing practice in the UK might reflect a weakening of the public domain after decades of neoliberalism. The paper notes the historical specificities that underlie pedestrian crossing practice in the UK, where individual judgement is often used as a basis for the decision to cross at a crossing regardless of what the signals advise. Ethnographic observations are reported which indicate that the consequences of this concession to individual judgement are often experiences of confusion, awkwardness, hazard, and opprobrium. Drawing on Katharena Manderscheid's use of Foucault's 'Dispositif' in mobilities research, together with Andrew Sayer's elucidation of 'Lay Morality', the paper posits that pedestrians' evaluations of theirs and others' practices could provide a resource from which to draw links between experiences and behaviours at the crossings and broader processes of social and political change. The paper describes how participants were sought who made regular walking journeys through Manchester that included significant interruption by pedestrian crossings. They were asked to wear a GoPro camera to record their journey from their perspective, as the researcher followed, also wearing a GoPro, to record a contextualising view. The footage was edited such that both perspectives could be viewed simultaneously and used as a means of elicitation of participants' thoughts about their journey. Findings are presented which suggest that pedestrians' reflections on theirs and others' practices reveal contradictory notions of how people should conduct themselves at the infrastructure, perhaps reflecting the recontextualising of this public good in the neoliberal era. It concludes with a speculation upon the implications of this for future urban pedestrianism.

Cities, Mobilities, Place & Space B W610

Beyond empowerment and exploitation: Gendered aspects of migration of Nepali care workers in the UK

Sanjaya Aryal
(University of Essex)

Based on ethnographic case studies of Nepali care workers in the UK, this paper by looking through the gender lens investigates the migration decision making process and changing household roles among these transnational migrants. Gender and migration literature and the evolving concept of 'global care chain' are good resources while looking at the gendered impact of migration as these literature are not only addressing the invisibility of women in migration studies until the 1970s but also analysing the global link of care, gender and mobility with special focus on the impact of migration on the migrants and their family members. From the case studies of both male and female care workers, it is found that though every individual in one way or other follow different process in making a decision to migrate based on their gendered power relationships and context, the migration decision making process for women is much more complicated and difficult than for men which are further exacerbated by the gendered ideologies and expectations based on patriarchal value system. At the same time, this paper found the diverse impacts of migration on gender relations which fit beyond the existing binary debate of empowerment or exploitation. Hence, it argues that the impacts of migration on gender relations should be analysed not only limiting to the individual migrants but by broadening it at the family and societal level which are spread at different locations transnationally.

Culture, Media, Sport & Food A W308

Accessibility and the concert hall: can buildings fight elitism in classical music?

*Neil Smith,
(Maastricht University)*

It has long been established that the nineteenth-century concert hall was the manifestation of a particular understanding of music and its relationship with society. The space was dedicated to the autonomous work of art, which, as religion faded as a fundamental orientation, was elevated to a quasi-religious sanctity – a vision of classical music that is still very much part of how it is appreciated, branded and consumed today. Yet orchestras are increasingly being asked to fight 'elitist' tags through increased involvement with the community, with social interventions and education projects now the norm. They must somehow break out of the concert hall.

Questions of the concert hall's position in society have primarily been posed when looking back into the past. This paper asks what can be learned by asking these questions of the present: how do today's new concert spaces reflect the new educative and accessible mission of the modern orchestra? This paper presents initial findings from an ethnographic study involving concert spaces throughout Europe (Porto, Hamburg, London, Paris, Berlin) and a more detailed study of the concert 'ecosystem' in Scotland. It will be argued that these examples, while informative, do not go nearly far enough in addressing the challenges that 'crossing the threshold' poses for some socioeconomic groups.

Circus art: a challenger and a preserver of social hierarchies and inequalities

*Olga Lucia Sorzano,
(City, University of London)*

This presentation explores the case of circus, an undervalued artform that is successfully breaking down social hierarchies and inequalities around the world. However, in the formalisation and recognition process of the practice, renewed hierarchies and internal peripheries emerge. That is the case of the so-called 'social circus', a movement that is increasingly dividing circus practitioners according to their socio-economic background. The term 'social circus' was initially used in Latin America to denominate an alternative movement that emerged in the encounter of circus artists and youngsters who had been excluded by society. Inspired by their attitude and energy, these young professionals found a new way of practicing their artform. The result is a consolidation of horizontal professional training programs involving those traditionally labelled as deprived youth that also breaks down cultural and sociopolitical barriers. Today, 'social circus' is recongised as a programme initiated by Cirque du Monde, the humanitarian arm of Canada's Cirque du Soleil. It is broadly understood as a program operating outside the professional and performance circus worlds that uses circus skills as a tool for 'assisting' vulnerable populations. The analysis investigates the various forces behind the translation of the initial meaning of 'social circus' to find modern division between artistic, political, and social spheres, the hybridisation of the Latin American approach with similar programs in the global North, and the consolidation of Cirque du Monde as Cirque du Soleil's corporate responsibility platform. The result is an ambivalent category that combines and perpetuates traditional global structures of power.

Culture, Media, Sport & Food B - Special Event W001

Social mobility and inequality in cultural and creative work: research and knowledge for policy as a social practice.

*Susan Oman, Abid Hussain, Mark Taylor
(University of Manchester, Arts Council England, University of Sheffield)*

The creative and cultural industries are reportedly becoming less equal. Alongside this, work is underway to measure class across public sector workers. Macro-level trends in the social origins of the population measure parental occupation when growing up as a proxy to understand this aspect of inequality.

This panel builds on recent academic and policy projects that attempt to address how to measure and manage who gets to get in, get by and get on in the arts.

Taylor will present new analysis from Panic!: how senior arts managers adopt the discourse of diversity, despite the prevalence of inequality at this level. Oman will describe research designed to understand the contexts in which workforce data are collected and measured, a project undertaken to help Arts Council England (ACE) introduce social mobility to its diversity reporting. It will critically reflect on tensions between the ideal question for sociologically robust

analysis, and the methodological, practical and ethical issues of asking people to collect and share these intimate data.

Hussain, as Diversity Director of ACE, will reflect on its commitment to improve access and progress in the sector and how research influences this work.

Each presenter will reflexively account for an aspect of gathering, analysing and using data to address inequality in context. This special event is a space in which to discuss how current practices rooted in Sociology, but working across other associated disciplines, can not only challenge social hierarchies and inequalities, but through close partnership with a policy sector, can influence change.

Social mobility and inequality in cultural and creative work: how do inequality metrics 'work' in cultural organisations

Susan Oman

(University of Manchester)

This paper presents findings from a research fellowship embedded in Arts Council England offices and a number of their funded organisations. Specifically, it reflects on the three levels at which the fellowship operated: interviews with key member of staff with responsibility for data and diversity practices and policies; focus groups across the workforce in these organisations; working in a non-departmental government body, to advise their future work and practices. It brings into context the experience of asking and answering uncomfortable questions about social background, whilst also reflecting on the appetite to address inequality and measurement cross the sector and the role of knowledge and evidence in this. A presentation of responses to parental occupation questions will demonstrate how people working in the cultural sector see their life-course in relation to that which is assumed 'norm' by social mobility proxy questions. A subsequent discussion will outline how this issue was dealt with methodologically in a policy sector that must meet demands for robust quantitative recording of social mobility, while reassuring those in the professions that these measures might reflect the qualitative experience of their personal life narratives and lead to social change.

This empirical presentation will lead into a reflexive discussion on the realities of making an intervention in a policy sector as an academic. Speakers will touch on the labour involved in the conversations behind the scenes: working with many partners across the sector and in policy-making contexts and other public engagement for research to become a worthwhile social practice.

Social mobility and inequality in cultural and creative work: diversity talk from the top

Mark Taylor

(University of Sheffield)

Cultural production is crucial in shaping society. Recent scholarship has drawn attention to the way that the occupations involved with cultural production, brought together under the banner of cultural and creative industries (CCIs), do not reflect the demographics of British society, particularly with respect to gender, race and ethnicity, and class. This paper seeks to understand how these inequalities are maintained by looking at a comparatively under-researched group: senior men in positions of power making decisions in CCIs. The paper presents data from 32 interviews with senior men across a range of CCI occupations. The analysis shows that misrecognition and outright rejection of inequalities is now unusual; that 'inequality talk' and the recognition of structural barriers for marginalised groups is a dominant mode for senior CCI men; that gentlemanly tropes and the idea of luck, rather than structural advantages, were used by senior men to explain their own success and separate and distance them as individuals from the inequalities they described; and that men felt they had limited capacity to effect genuine change in the context of a set of occupations they understood as fairer than other professions. Overall, the analysis shows how 'inequality talk' and the awareness of structural issues differs significantly from senior CCI men's own accounts of their career success. This difference, and the distance between the discourse of career luck and 'inequality talk' helps to explain the persistence of exclusions from the workforce for those who are not white, middle class origin, men.

Environment & Society

W525

'Tax me!' Young flyers' perceptions of carbon offsetting, carbon taxes, and responsibility for mitigating aviation emissions

Roger Tyers, Roger Tyers

(University of Southampton)

The contribution of aviation to global carbon emissions is an increasing cause for concern. As other sectors decarbonise, flying is projected to expand whilst using vast amounts of fossil fuels, at least for the foreseeable future. Flying is increasingly embedded in many social practices and has become a normalised activity in the global North,

and increasingly in the South too. One potential policy solution is voluntary carbon offsetting, where flyers pay an optional additional fee to mitigate the emissions caused by their flight – a voluntary, consumer-led response. This paper uses focus group data to examine how a sample of 60 UK-based students of different nationalities understand and evaluate carbon offset schemes.

The findings suggest three key barriers to carbon offsetting: general scepticism; economic rationalism; and institutional dependency. Scepticism reflects the perception of offsetting as an unfamiliar concept that might not deliver its supposed benefits; economic rationalism focuses on consumers prioritising value for money over ethical concerns; and institutional dependency refers to the belief that it is the responsibility of institutions such as government – not individuals – to mitigate aviation emissions.

Interestingly, participants responded positively to the notion of a mandatory carbon offset or carbon tax added to flight costs, suggesting that greater education of the need to reduce or mitigate aviation emissions could generate greater support for an aviation carbon tax. It also suggests that consumers themselves recognise the weakness of individualised responses, and may expect producers and governments to lead in mitigating the effects of unsustainable consumption.

Fine young 'scepticals': climate scepticism in longitudinal perspective

Bruce Tranter, Jonathan Smith
(University of Tasmania)

Citizens who reject the scientific consensus on anthropogenic climate change form a small, but often highly vocal minority in many advanced industrialised countries. Our longitudinal survey data show that young people living in the Australian state of Queensland, are among the most likely of all young Australians to be climate change sceptics. In Australia, despite prevarication over climate policy among both the conservative and (allegedly) progressive major parties, the proportion of climate sceptics has declined, both nationally, and among our sample of young Queenslanders. However, our findings indicate that political party identification is very strongly associated with climate scepticism. Parental political socialisation appears to play an important role in climate scepticism, with conservative political party identifying parents, far more likely than other parents to have climate sceptic children. The implications of these findings will be discussed.

Discontinuities, socialisation and the many beginnings of sustainable consumption practices

Seonaidh McDonald, Caroline J. Oates
(Robert Gordon University, Aberdeen, UK)

Within the marketing and social psychology literatures there has been an emphasis on understanding the motivations of decontextualized individuals towards single sustainable behaviours. This study moves away from a conceptualisation of individual behaviour as independent, rational, coherent and acontextual to a view of sustainable consumption set within norms and performed through relational practices. Building on work that highlighted strategies that are being used to advance, integrate and make sense of sustainable consumption practices, this study is centred on how specific sustainable consumption practices become part of individual performative repertoires, households, and relationships. We conducted 45 in-depth interviews that produced narratives that addressed multiple sustainable consumption practices in each household represented. Interviews were between 60 and 90 minutes and conducted in Scotland, England and the Republic of Ireland. These were transcribed verbatim and analysed inductively.

Our data show that there is a wide range of different kinds of beginnings. We found that each participant described multiple kinds of beginnings. The beginnings fell into two broad groups: discontinuities and socialisation. Discontinuities that led to new sustainable practices could be produced by: new and old media; infrastructural changes; role models; travel; leisure commitments; and life stage transitions. We discovered evidence of multiple forms of socialisation including through inter-generational influence; intra-generational influence; reverse socialisation; institutions; and place. We also uncovered narratives of (un)beginnings where there was resistance to practices that signal unpalatable social norms.

Energy vulnerabilities, poverty, and governance

Catherine Butler, Karen Parkhill, Paulina Luzecka
(University of Exeter)

Fuel poverty is recognized as a distinct social justice problem in the UK. However, the ways in which it is framed and addressed by government policy have recently come under increasing academic scrutiny. In particular, some have asserted that its narrow framing as a technical issue of energy efficiency, distinct from poverty itself, obfuscates other structural causes of the problem, thus excluding alternative solutions (Middlemiss, 2016). While others have highlighted the ways that dominant policy discourses have tended to frame fuel poverty as a lack of adequate space heating, thus omitting other energy uses, which are essential for people's wellbeing and capacities for social participation (Simcock et al, 2016). This has led to calls for greater understanding of the complex underlying causes of people's vulnerabilities to energy poverty, and, in particular, for insights into how non-energy policies and processes of

governance may have an indirect impacts on people's energy use, access, and affordability. This paper responds by examining welfare and employment policies in the UK and showing their influence on people's energy needs, their ability to meet those needs, and their quality of life and well-being. The research involved in-depth semi-structured interviews with people working in energy and welfare governance roles at national and regional levels, and with members of the public directly affected by welfare and employment policies. The paper uses this data to examine the interrelations between energy vulnerability and poverty, and reflect on the implications for governance processes and policy.

Families & Relationships A **W709**

Reproductive Hierarchies and Inequalities? Having or not having children in Italy, Spain and the UK

Lynn Jamieson

(University of Edinburgh)

This paper revisits discussions about inequalities in reproduction and reproduction of inequalities reflecting on the accounts of women and men aged 30-35 in established couple relationships about having children. We talked with both childless couples and those with one child about imagined future children and their childhoods. The small samples (40 in each country, Italy, Spain and the UK) are structured between those in insecure and secure employment and by higher versus basic level education. As well as attending to economic security and family support we were also interested in how more general threats to the future including climate change are dealt with in people's accounts of their responsibility and possibilities with respect to having children.

Inequality in ageing: Exploring the influence of gender and socioeconomically level in the personal life of elderly in Chile

FRANCISCA ORTIZ,

(The University of Manchester)

We live in a world where social relations are crossed with diverse inequalities, which manifest themselves over time. In this presentation, it will be explored two of the most critical disparities in contemporary social divisions: gender and socioeconomically level. One of the hypotheses is that these two categories are accumulative disadvantages with the years; therefore, it comes quickly to make visible in the elderly. In particular, it is proposed that one methodological tool that in social sciences needs to capture them and to support challenges to them, could be the reconstruction of the history of life from this people. Making visible their histories with all the narrative and the support network, it will be possible to play a role in public debate and social practice to challenge the particular problem of the crisis of care. In instances, it will be used the case of Chile, to illuminates these ideas. Given the rapid growth of the elderly population in this country, the rising inequalities embedded in a neoliberal pension system, and no enough answer from the government to this realities, are making Chile an excellent case of studying this problematic.

Families and food poverty in a Portuguese rural context

Vasco Ramos, Mónica Truninger; Sónia Goulart Cardoso; Fábio Rafael Augusto;

(ICS-UL)

In contemporary Portugal, several representations of rurality and the 'countryside' coexist. These range from idyllic depictions of a place of beauty and wellbeing to anti idyllic portrayals of emptiness and loneliness. However, there are persistent associations between rurality and the existence of social structures that uphold practices of communal solidarity, especially about localities closer to urban areas, where economic and social infrastructures allow framing everyday life in quasi-urban conditions. Such contexts are assumed to have denser informal social support networks, which would help in alleviating or preventing poverty and social exclusion, even when institutional support fails. These assertions are often coupled with expectations about the role of extended kinship, ownership of small plots of land and proximity to areas where food is produced, circumstances that would reduce the incidence and intensity of poverty.

In this presentation, our aim is to analyse how living in a rural area shapes the experience of food poverty for families. Drawing on qualitative data from the Families and Food Poverty research project, we will address cases of low-income families living in a predominantly rural context in Portugal, specifically an area located in the outskirts of the Greater Lisbon Area. Special attention will be given to the specificities of this socio-spatial context, including the availability of formal support networks. Furthermore, we will investigate to what extent personal/familial resources and informal support networks alleviate food poverty for these families. Our discussion will add to the scientific debate on food poverty and inform Portuguese welfare policies and programs.

Families & Relationships B

W727

Talking Politics: Emotions, Brexit and Everyday Family Relationships

*Katherine Davies,
(The University of Sheffield)*

This paper explores how the UK's 2016 referendum on the European Union has been experienced within family relationships, drawing upon qualitative interviews to consider the ways in which people 'talk politics' with their family. The paper outlines different motives for and practices of discussing politics in families; from a wish to avoid political debate to a feeling of wanting to explain and defend one's position to a motive of educating others. The paper explores the ways in which these practices are bound up within the emotional landscapes of existing intergenerational relationships, personal biographies and wider political atmospheres and discourses. Drawing upon Smart's (2007) emphasis on the tenacity of family ties as well as Hochschild's work on emotional labour (1993) and politics and emotion (2016), the paper will argue that, contrary to media portrayals of a 'divided' nation characterised by generational conflict, people expend great effort and skill in avoiding conflict with family members, developing tacit understandings of if and when to talk politics and with whom.

Studying the 'in-between' – new theoretical directions for a sociology of family and personal life

*Vanessa May,
(University of Manchester)*

This paper explores the significance of studying 'in-between spaces', 'space' here denoting both physical space and more abstract relational space. Inspired by Jennifer Mason's concept 'socio-atmospherics' (Affinities, 2018) and Susie Scott's work on 'nothingness', I argue for a transformation of how these in-between spaces are conceptualised. Instead of constituting a background hum that does not merit sociological attention, the in-between can be conceived of as connective spaces or fields of tension – of repulsion and attraction – that are filled with action, forces and energies. I explore two examples of how the in-between can be brought to life sociologically. First, theorising the in-between from the perspective of belonging reveals efforts to make connections, to form bonds and to relate – as well as to draw distinctions and boundaries in order to create distance. Second, what happens in these in-between spaces is not so much characterised by 'big events', such as when a person decides to divorce their spouse, for example. They are instead filled with the minutiae of how people lead their day-to-day lives such as doing the washing up, leaving the house to go to work and driving the kids to school. This paper explores a range of empirical studies on family and personal life with the aim of illuminating how a focus on the in-between can open up new avenues of exploration, new questions, but also new understanding of the character of personal life.

'It almost politicised you, even as a little kid': emotion, politics and childhood in memories of the 1984/85 miners' strike

*Carly Guest,
(Middlesex University)*

This paper draws on interviews with people from striking families who remember the 1984-85 UK miners' strike as children. It explores how the strike is remembered as a time of intense emotion; fear, excitement, hope and disappointment. Many of the participants describe how the everyday activities, relationships and places experienced during the strike were part of a process of politicisation. The emotional force of this process is apparent across the interviews, demonstrating how memories and experiences of social inequalities and hierarchies are shaped by the personal, relational and emotional.

Frontiers

W007

Technoscientific imaginaries, precarious relationalities and sustainable futures: Positioning psychosocial research to make a difference

*Karen Henwood, Alice Dal Gobbo
(Cardiff University)*

[Submitted to the Psychosocial Study Group]

Psychosocial work has been discussed as a way of fostering engagement by sociologists with grand challenges posed by climate change, sustainable energy transitions, and transforming futures. Methodological issues have been raised as part of substantive, psychosocially-focussed research to sharpen questions about what can be productive

about linking investigative social science, socio- technical interventions, and environmental and sustainable energy policy. This presentation will build on the recognition that has been given to psychosocial inquiries for offering insights into ways of increasing public engagement with social interventions (e.g. 'carbon conversations') by environmental social action groups. Already these inquiries have established ways of exploring both affective dynamics and everyday sense making, and enabled social scientific reflections upon lived lives involving affect, with a focus in the emotional burdens of affective sense making (<http://www.energybiographies.org>). The current presentation will open up further questions about the science/public interface in terms of 'precarious relationalities'. It will ask if scientific imaginaries and practices 'pro-duce' (energy system change) in such a way that they are both founded on, and re-iterating of, a model of precarious relationalities whereby a certain fluidity, uncertainty and undecidability are not so much seen as problematic but rather as opportunities for mastering and controlling innovation. In this context, what role do affective meaning-making practices and unconscious investments play? What kind of socio-political implications do they have? How can developing psychosocial research strategies make a difference?

Feeling 'out of place'– A psychosocial exploration of cultural (dis)orientation as an immigrant worker

*Nini Fang,
(University of Edinburgh)*

What is it like to be an immigrant worker in a 'hostile environment' in the UK? How does the form of discursive environment, which produces immigration as an issue of social epidemic, impact on an immigrant worker's psychological experiencing of their cultural (dis)localities and subjectivity? In this presentation, I draw on my personal, psychoanalytically-informed voice to explore into these questions, by foregrounding the materiality of the hosting environment as the place in which the present relational matrix takes place, in which the internal dynamics of object relationships are lived in the present sense, and idiosyncratic expression of selfhood assumes forms.

The materialised reality of the place matters not least because it is drenched in power relations but also as it is where an immigrant worker seeks dwelling. The hostile host, in this sense, not only produces immigrants as its guests (Derrida & Dufourmantelle, 2000), but also as unwelcome yet persistent guests to be yoked to their place of otherness and inferiority. By presenting vignettes of my encounters with the Home Office, I call into questions the existential conditions of the immigrant worker and the potentiality for object-relatedness on relational grounds problematically punctuated by hostile rhetoric. Could an immigrant's sense of locality ever be anything but, evoking Said (2013[1999]), 'out of place'? To address this, I will explore into 'out of place' as not simply an emotional, lived experience, but also a state of being that is embodied, psychically worked on, and strategically evoked in resisting power of the hostile host.

From the distant Crusades to 'local' 'Islamic terrorism' – from the European civilizing processes to the contemporary Western de-civilizing process?

*Lars Bo Kaspersen
(Copenhagen Business School)*

This paper takes its point of departure in a number of wars fought far away from most of the European survival units (states) in the 8th century at the Iberian Peninsula and in the 11th and 12th centuries more specifically in the Middle East and Eastern Europe/Baltic countries. The claim is that the distant wars at the frontiers of 'Europe' in the 8th, and especially in the 11th, and 12th centuries were crucial to the European civilizing processes, including the Christian dimension and this was reinforced by the Ottoman conquest of Konstantinoble 1453, the defeat of the Ottomans in the battle of Lepanto 1571 and the two sieges of Vienna in 1529 and 1683.

The external 'islamic' threat contributed to a European civilizing process in which Christianity became an important aspect. The Islamic 'signifier' functioned as a common enemy (hostis) for most European survival units with some continuity from the 7th and 8th centuries to the 11th, 12th, and 13th centuries. It continues in the 16th and 17th and it returns in the 21st century. During this long period of time war against 'Islam' moves from being a distant war in the Middle East in the 11th century to become a 'civil' war ('War against terrorism') in the big cities in Europe. The 'islamic fundamentalists are recruited from European citizens. 'The enemy is an inherent part of the civilizing process. Finally, the paper discusses the implications of these developments for the civilizing processes.

Medicine, Health & Illness

W002

Rhetorical and regulatory boundary-work: The case of medical cannabis policy-making in Israel

*Dana Zarhin, Maya Negev, Simon Vulfsons, Sharon Sznitman
(University of Haifa)*

Recent studies have explored how professionals draw boundaries to reach workable solutions in conflictual and contested areas. Yet they neglected to explore the relationships and dynamics between how boundaries are

demarcated in rhetoric and in policy. This article examines these relationships empirically through the case of medical cannabis (MC) policy-making in Israel. Drawing on interviews with key stakeholders in the MC policy field, formal policy documents, and observations of MC conferences, this article sheds light on the dynamics between rhetorical boundary-work and what we term regulatory boundary-work, namely setting rules and regulations to demarcate boundaries in actual practice. Results show how certain definitions of and rationales for a discursive separation between "medical" and "recreational" cannabis and between cannabis "medicalization" and "legalization" prevailed and were translated into formal policy, as well as how stakeholders' reactions to this boundary-work produced policy changes and the shifting of boundaries. Both rhetorical and regulatory boundary-works emerge as ongoing contested processes of negotiation, which are linked in a pattern of reciprocal influence. These processes are dominated by certain actors who have greater power to determine how and why specific boundaries should be drawn instead of others.

Caring in cold blood: Empathy and ambivalence in the experience of laboratory animal technicians who care for fish in contemporary biomedical research settings

Reuben Message, Beth Greenhough; Emma Roe
(University of Oxford)

Human capacity to sense and respond to the suffering of non-human animals is key to animal care and welfare in practice. While shaped by scientific, moral and culture hierarchies, systems and histories, we sense intuitively these modes of relating are easiest with familiar, terrestrial and appropriately-sized, 'warm-blooded' mammals whose moods and faces humans attempt to read as we would those of another human, and with whom some corporeal intimacy is possible. By contrast, empathy with 'cold-blooded' aquatic animals like fish has been considered 'beyond human capacity' (Driessen et al 2013) and fish outside the 'moral circle' (Lund et al 2007). However, in the context of biomedical research in the UK, fish are legally sentient animals, and those who care for them are expected to provide them with a level of care appropriate to their regulatory and ethical status, and equal to that of other protected species, such as rats. This results in tensions between the public roles and duties of professional animal care givers, and the private difficulties they face in sensing and responding to 'alien' fishy needs. Drawing on ethnographic notes and interviews, this paper argues that the experiences of laboratory animal technicians as they try (sometimes unsuccessfully) to learn to be affected by and care for the 'cold-blooded' are ambivalent and contradictory. While reproducing conventional species hierarchies, inequalities and ideas about inter-species relations, they simultaneously hold the potential for new modes of relating to animal difference.

'You don't really know what a good life is until you've not got one': Reflecting on disciplinary boundaries within multidisciplinary research

Sharon Greenwood,
(University of Glasgow)

Multidisciplinary research is on the increase within health and social care (Green & Thorogood, 2018) – frequently between healthcare professionals, and academics working within sociology and social policy. These projects are typically fast-paced, collaborative encounters, driven by the need to produce 'meaningful outputs' within a pre-set time frame. This push for 'fast' research means that it can be more difficult to negotiate and reflect upon the normative, 'taken-for-granted' assumptions made along disciplinary lines.

This paper shares experiences from recently completed, multidisciplinary project, which sought to develop a Quality of Life (QoL) measurement tool, specific to patients with kidney failure. Working alongside doctors, nurses, and patients, this research gathered accounts of the lived experience of being on dialysis. Previous QoL models in this area have been predominantly developed by physicians and focused on the physical impact of being on dialysis, at the expense of excluding the emotional and social effects of being a 'dialysis patient'.

From an early stage, it became clear that different parties held varied perspectives of what a 'good' quality of life involves. Understandings were typically influenced by class, gender, and ethnicity – thus subject to pre-existing hierarchies of power and inequality. Consequently, those with the most marginalised voices – in this case, patients – typically went unheard within the development of previous models. The model derived from this research synthesised both academic, practitioner, and patient perspectives to produce a more meaningful and responsive method to evaluate the quality of life of patients with kidney failure.

The legitimacy of biomedicine among the indigenous peoples: a Case Study of Dourados Reservation.

Maria Beldi Alcantara,
(Medical Faculty-University of Sao Paulo)

This study aims to present the cultural dialogue between the actions implemented by the Unified Health System - SUS and the indigenous peoples (Guarani and Aruak) of the Dourados Reserve.

The Dourados reserve has always relied on resources from abroad to survive and with all the demands of the Guarani and Terena with the problems generated by the coexistence with the surrounding society, in this case, the city of Dourados.

About health, the SUS implemented in 1999 the indigenous health with a biomedical view. What we want to highlight is the fact that the demand created by SUS, about mental health. It imposes psychologists and psychiatrists who attend to the problems of the indigenous population. Now in August 2018 the imposition of the Center for Psychosocial Attention-CAPS.

All these measures are implemented without prior, free and informed consultation to indigenous peoples and, also, are carried out without previous training of the biomedical teams, necessary to work with such a specific population as to the ontologically related classifications of well being and illness religion.

What we perceive is the creation of problems and demands that this type of attitude causes, increasing discomfort and stigma, due to the lack of dialogue that occurs when these measures are implemented.

This work aims to present this malaise that grows among the indigenous population with the implementation of these measures.

Methodological Innovations

W009

Developing coaching programmes for young people

Tina Salter,
(YMCA George Williams College)

Mentoring and coaching have been cited as effective tools in supporting individuals through significant transitional life stages (Lancer et al, 2016). However, the dominant one-to-one support mechanism for young people transitioning into adulthood is mentoring (Salter, 2014). Many youth mentoring programmes are based on a deficit model (Philip, 2008) and could inadvertently form a barrier to successful youth transition into adulthood. Examples of programmes targeting young people labelled at risk of 'emotional and behavioural difficulties' (Caldarella et al, 2009) or 'not in education, employment or training' (Colley, 2006) are plentiful. Whilst the mentors themselves work professionally and may not even be aware of the underlying deficit model, the agenda for these programmes often is to re-socialise those young people.

Theoretical constructs which address coaching for young people are underrepresented in the literature, but can be evidenced in practice. Whilst coaching models can also be based on deficit constructs, there is evidence to suggest coaching offers greater flexibility towards a strengths-based approach. To coach rather than mentor a young person would necessitate the coach facilitating self-directed learning (Knowles & Knowles, 1955). This is collaborative in approach and encourages the young person to identify what it is they would like to work on (rather than serve the agenda of the referrer) and support them to take responsibility for any change or new ways of thinking and self-management.

This paper draws on case study research capturing practice-based examples of coaching for young people and compares findings to well-documented examples of youth mentoring.

Researching Ambiguity: Understanding Gender Expressions through Indirect Interview Techniques and the Reflexivity of Discomfort

Eva Cheuk-Yin Li,
(King's College London)

Ambiguity is a realm of social experience which continually presents challenges to sociological researchers. It includes the discursive use of ambiguity, uncertainty in decision-making that shapes one's identity and practice, and indeterminacy that influences an agent's relations with social structures. Researchers who work with empirical data often struggle between deriving operationalisable concepts and allowing openness and flexibility.

This paper draws on my reflections on researching the lived experience of zhongxing ('middle gender/sex'), a mainstreamed form of non-normative gender expression in Chinese-speaking societies. It is less of a sexual orientation but configurations of gender practices that resist identitarian language. Since existing research either focused on textual representations or (masculine) lesbians, I employ an interactionist and transnational queer feminist framework to understand the use of ambiguity in the construction of gendered selfhood among women of different sexual orientations, including those who 'felt ambivalently'.

In order to capture a broader range of data and minimise the risk of imposing preconceived definitions, I employ an indirect method of qualitative interview informed by grounded theory (Charmaz, 2006, 2008) and queer methods

(Browne and Nash 2010). In specific, I will focus on the 'reflexivity of discomfort' during interviews as a practice of confounding disruptions (Pillow, 2003) to delineate and make sense of ambiguous meanings, ephemeral practices, and conditions that make life livable (Brim and Ghaziani, 2016). In this way, ambiguity yields critical epistemological and methodological implications to 'queer' sociological knowledge production and (re)imagine the possibility of resistance.

'How does one evaluate equality?': A critical appraisal of Athena SWAN within Social Sciences

*Evangeline Tsao,
(University of York)*

An increasing number of HE institutions and departments are now submitting to the Athena SWAN Charter, demonstrating a commitment to promoting gender equality in the sector. While some research shows that quantitative data has been effective within STEM subjects to evidence and encourage changes, particular challenges emerge when this approach is applied to Social Sciences and Humanities disciplines which are considered 'feminized' and tend to have a stronger presence of women. Gender disparity in this context should, arguably, be considered as indicative of existing cultural bias rather than a result of institutional discrimination. However, action plans formulated to 'recruit more men' have been suggested, and thus should be carefully examined as they could have a detrimental effect of disadvantaging already marginalized and diverse groups of women. Additionally, the data collected and used in applications are mostly based upon the gender binary, rendering non-binary or other identities invisible. These issues, accompanied by the current critique that Athena SWAN is effective for advancing equality agenda more for white women, raise the question of how equality and diversity could be otherwise evaluated, and what methods may be more effective to generate actual change for different groups. Adopting qualitative methods with focus on intersectionality, this paper aims to critically appraise Athena SWAN, exploring whether and how, participatory methodologies may contribute to a more heterogeneous understanding of equality, and can potentially open up a discussion of the complexity of assessing equality – and thus any subsequent action plans.

Sketching Trust Stories: A practical examination of how a multimodal method can inform the conceptualisation and operationalisation of a process approach to trust

*Rachel Ayrton
(University of Southampton)*

Creative, visual and multi-modal research methods are commonly used in data collection, presentation, and dissemination of research findings; however, they are rarely applied to the research practices of conceptualisation and research design. Responding to Pierre Bourdieu's call for the construction of the object to be rigorously undertaken in every moment of research (Bourdieu & Wacquant 1992), I explore how such methods can be employed by the researcher to understand, communicate, build on and operationalise an abstract concept - trust - as a precursor to empirical investigation.

Trust is a phenomenon which is commonly invoked both in everyday life and in academic discourse; however, its familiarity obscures the lack of conceptual clarity surrounding the term, which has deep implications for how it can be approached methodologically. In light of dominant constructions of trust as an attitude or a behaviour, I argue that trust is better conceived of as a process (Möllering 2001, 2006, 2013; Dietz 2011). I exemplify and advance this approach using a creative research method - storyboarding. Based on three imagined trust dilemmas developed with the involvement of a visual artist, I demonstrate how a visual creative process can safeguard the interconnection between theory and method through encouraging consistent attention to the construction of the research object. It also speculatively reveals new facets of phenomena under investigation, and supports reflexive attention to the researcher's relation to the object of research, thus enhancing reflexivity and rigor in empirical research.

Race, Ethnicity & Migration A - Special Event W011

Exploring patterns of ethnic inequality in British institutions

*Karis Campion, Dr Karis Campion, Dr Roaa Ali, Neema Begum, Dr William Shankley
(University of Manchester)*

This special event will present four inter-linked papers from colleagues at CoDE (the Centre on Dynamics of Ethnicity) at the University of Manchester. The papers explore how ethnic inequality manifests and is reproduced and maintained within British institutions using a variety of qualitative and quantitative methods. By examining how dominant modes of thinking can value particular agendas, outlooks and strategies, two of the papers explore how these processes can work to exclude people of colour from entering into and being equally represented in the cultural sector (Ali), and higher education sector (Campion), resulting in substantial ethnic inequalities. Through an

examination of the experience of ethnic minority people in local and national politics, the panel will also consider how race inequalities persist in political structures at the national and local level and how the experiences of ethnic minority people in these systems are further shaped by the variables of gender, class and religion. The final paper draws across all of the themes and presents the preliminary findings from the forthcoming book *State of the Nation*. The book is the fruits of a joint project between CoDE and the Runnymede Trust. Using media content, interviews and statistical data, it provides a snapshot view of the contemporary national context, to map out some of the spaces where barriers to participation and representation for ethnic minority people are particularly acute and how these might be effectively dismantled going forward. The panel, therefore, presents a thoroughly researched overview on the present state of ethnic minority engagement, representation, and experiences in the cultural, educational and political sectors. By doing so, the panel examines how ethnic inequalities persist and get reproduced socially and institutionally in the UK, and explores the ways in which this can be addressed moving forward.

Just another tick-box? Exploring in-depth institutional insights into the priorities, processes and purposes of the Race Equality Charter

Karis Champion,

(University of Manchester)

The Race Equality Charter (REC) was introduced in 2014 as a new race equality initiative in Higher Education. Its presence signified a demand for institutions to properly account for disparities in the outcomes and progression of both students and academics of colour (Bhopal 2018, Boliver 2016, Runnymede 2015, Rollock 2019). Despite the good will of the Race Relation Amendment Act 2000 which required universities to develop race equality policies, it has been argued in the past that these often materialised in an 'equal opportunities' approach and the promotion of 'diversity' agendas which have sanitised the real issues at stake which are 'anti-racism' and social justice (Ahmed & Swan 2006, Pilkington 2018). The REC suggests a more targeted approach, in that it summons institutions to apply for its REC award by highlighting areas of ethnic inequality through in-depth self-analysis of quantitative and qualitative data and then develop action plans and solutions in response (Loke 2018).

Adding to the very small body of work on initial institutional responses to the REC (Bhopal 2018), this paper utilises in-depth interviews with senior staff directly responsible for REC applications at an institution that has an award. This case-study approach highlights how they perceive it as comparing to other (race) equality initiatives, questions whether action plans are communicated effectively through the institution and considers key challenges to race equality practice within the university and across the sector.

Changing the narrative on Ethnic Diversity in the cultural sector from desirability to essentiality

Roaa Ali

(University of Manchester)

Cultural and creative industries represent a growing aspect of the economy, and the significance of cultural work on promoting social understanding and engagement has often been highlighted and celebrated nationally. There have been several recent calls, such as the Arts Council Creative Case for Diversity 2016, that advocate for ethnic diversity within the sector and emphasise the social, and sometimes artistic benefit for the desired practice of inclusion. Ethnic inequalities have been and continue to be a problem within the cultural sector (Oakley and O'Brien 2016; The Warwick Commission 2015; Ofcom 2017). One of the contributing factors to the slow progress in addressing ethnic inequalities is the discourse around diversity in the sector. This paper explores the necessity of changing the current narrative around inclusion from that of tokenism and social responsibility to economic productivity and arts progression, arguing that it is not only ethical and socially conscious to advocate diversity, but it is also economically and artistically essential for the health of the sector.

This paper presents this as part of the preliminary findings of the "Cultural production and consumption" work-package, part of the ESRC funded Centre on Dynamics of Ethnicity (CoDE). The project explores the nature of ethnic minority experience in key organisations in the UK cultural sector, particularly the Museum, theatre and TV production fields. The research has aimed to investigate those questions utilising institutional ethnography and qualitative interviewing. The paper will summarise and evaluate these methods, present the initial findings of the research and introduce recommendations.

Local politics, representation and ethnic minorities

Neema Begum,

"While there have been relatively rapid improvements in the representation of ethnic minority groups in Westminster, ethnic minority people continue to be under-represented in parliament in relation to the general population. The picture at the local level fares worse with the most recent census (2013) showing a much lower representation of ethnic minority groups in local government (3%) as compared to parliament (8%), with particularly low levels for ethnic minority women.

This paper will present preliminary findings from the "Politics

How far have we progressed? A synoptic review of the challenges ethnic minorities face in arts and media, state education and political institutions in Britain

*William Shankley,
(University of Manchester)*

This paper is a synoptic review of three collaborative chapters written as part of a book project entitled 'State of the Nation'. The three chapters this talk focuses on are the patterns and developments in the arts, media and cultural industries, state education system and political institutions. The chapter uses an array of empirical data that includes official statistics, interviews and media content and will present the implication of the analysis of these across the three areas to draw together the broader work of CoDE. The paper finds that white privilege persists in the three dimensions and this is evident in the outcomes of the White British group compared to the black and ethnic minority groups. Moreover, ethnic minorities (staff, students and audiences) face barriers that limit their progression, full participation or engagement with these institutions or are not represented in a manner that truly reflects their everyday experiences in Britain. Specifically, in the cultural policy that has been rolled out to increase ethnic minorities participation in the cultural industries and representation in media content, the success of the policies has been limited by their definition of diversity, including the linking of diversity with representation and a commitment to ethnic minority access and career development. The paper also finds that across the three areas, ethnic minority employment and representation has increased. However, there continue to be barriers to their involvement and participation in senior leadership and decision-making processes.

Race, Ethnicity & Migration B

W324

Life inimical to life – a biopolitical appraisal of Donald Trump's travel ban

*Svetoslav Nenov,
(Coventry University)*

Donald Trump's travel ban, which was upheld by the Supreme Court in a 5-4 decision on June 26th 2018, is considered to be his most substantial legal victory since he stepped into office. The travel ban effectively and indefinitely bans entry to the United States from seven Muslim-majority countries and is largely seen as an implementation of Donald Trump's pre-election promise to enact a 'Muslim-ban'. This paper aims at providing a legal biopolitical analysis of the travel ban in view of establishing its significance vis-à-vis the Western neo-liberal order. Biopolitics, in strictly Foucaultian terms, is understood to be a governmental technology of power which takes the population as its referent object, and is committed to the circulation, promotion, protection and propagation of life through the use of a large array of administrative mechanisms. It also undertakes the task of securitisation of life through state racism, or the disallowal of life that is inimical to life. The paper will suggest that the travel ban acts as a biopolitically framed, juridically legitimised expression of the sovereign prerogative, which at the same time goes against the circulatory dynamic of global political economy. The paper will provide a legal analysis of the three executive orders through which the travel ban was conceptualised and will also consider the Supreme Court case that allowed for the travel ban's implementation. It will conclude that the US legal system is a-moral and discursive in character, leaving the door open for the implementation of further biopolitically informed legal decisions.

Rights, Violence & Crime

W004

'Bad apples' and 'legitimate targets': Intergroup perceptions of victimhood and violence in Northern Ireland

*Sarah Jankowitz, Sarah Jankowitz
(University of Liverpool)*

Northern Ireland's conflict and peace process has attracted boundless scholarly attention, however, twenty years after the peace agreement was signed the process of addressing the legacy of the conflict is an unfinished project. At the heart of contention surrounding the conflict is the reality that many groups are both responsible for violence and have suffered a massive human toll. As in many other societies emerging from intergroup conflict, groups tend to view themselves as the primary or 'real' victims and thus the acknowledgement of victims and prosecution of wrongdoers which are rooted in international norms are rife with contention. Drawing in scholarship on critical victimology and intergroup relations, this paper examines the perceptual and intergroup dimensions of victimhood through the rhetoric of 'bad apples' and 'legitimate targets' in Northern Ireland. This offers an analysis on the ways in which group-serving

narratives of violence frame their own actions as just and moral. Violence committed by one's own group is justifiable and moral if directed against those who can be framed as 'legitimate targets', whereas and those whose actions threaten groups' moral self-image are portrayed as deviants or 'bad apples'.

Deradicalization: towards a sociology of an experience

Kevin McDonald, Kevin McDonald
(Middlesex University)

This paper presents research-in-progress being undertaken with the support of a British Academy small grant, that sets out to explore experiences of disengagement from radicalisation pathways. This project builds on an earlier study (McDonald 2018) of pathways into jihadist radicalisation that highlighted three clusters of experience. The first centres on 'us', constructed around the axes of us/them, inclusion/exclusion, order/disorder, purity/impurity, with affective states organised around anxiety and the social construction of disgust. The second centres on 'you', built around an affirmation of power, with significant debt to imaginaries of gaming, an experiential structure of the hidden and the revealed, the visible and invisible, winners and losers. A third focuses on experiences of 'I', where we encounter practices of individuation such as purification of the self, sacrifice of the self, and experiences of the sublime where a heightened sense of awe and enormity gives rise to experiences of displacement, in some cases developing into experiences of the uncanny, danger or dread. These pathways underline the extent that radicalisation is an active social process, embodied and communicative, where actors produce and are sustained by an 'affective fabric' increasingly associated with mediated experience. The current study focuses on disengagement from these pathways, with a particular focus on affect disclosed in atmospheres, fragments and traces, the challenge to think with and through dis/continuity, dis/orienting experience, and entanglements of here and there, now and then (Blackman 2015). Within this, the focus of this paper is the changing relationship to experiences and imaginaries of violence.

The ethics of researching terrorism: academia and the security state

Narzanin Massoumi, Tom Mills, David Miller
(University of Exeter)

This paper discusses the relationship between academic researchers and the security state focusing in particular on the extent to which secrecy, deception and coercion – significant issues in contemporary security and conflict research – violate key ethical standards and professional norms. Using data from an ESRC project on terrorism expertise, the paper highlights three key ways in which ethical and professional standards in social scientific research on political violence are compromised: 1. Undermining the evidence base (through lack of transparency on data and conflicts of interest); 2. Collaborating on research supporting deception by the state that undermines the ability of citizens to participate in democratic processes; and 3. Collaborating on research that helps to legitimate human rights abuses and the coercive powers of the state. These issues are widespread but neglected across: research on 'terrorism' and political violence; literature on research ethics; and, ethical practices and safeguards within research institutions.

In order to address these issues more effectively, we propose a sociological model for the assessment of research ethics that, unlike most discussions of ethics in research on political violence, considers the broader ethical and professional obligations of social scientists. Our approach takes account of the ethical challenges and dilemmas of researching conflict and 'terrorism'. This moves beyond the rather narrow, procedural approaches that currently dominate; seeking to broaden ethical considerations to include questions of social power, academic freedom and the politics of knowledge production.

Social Divisions / Social Identities A

W110

A 'Touchy' Subject: Investigating Sexual Harassment in Singapore's Universities

Rachel Kuo,
(University of Cambridge)

Following the development of feminism and the modern feminist movement, much interest has been directed to comprehending women's experiences of victimisation and violence through consciousness-raising attempts. As a form of violence against women, sexual harassment has been extensively documented and analysed in multiple contexts, such as the universities, the military and the workplace. Recently, the 'MeToo' movement has seen many individuals explicating their experiences with sexual harassment online and spurred even greater condemnation of violence against women. Most academic studies on sexual harassment have, however, focused on examining harassment as it occurs in the context of formal power relationships. Furthermore, literature on sexual harassment in Singapore is sparse, indicating a booming silence on this topic. This thesis is thus an exploratory study on sexual harassment of university students. I aim to find out the prevalence of sexual harassment in Singapore's universities, students'

attitudes towards and understandings of sexual harassment and most importantly, what their interpretations and experiences reveal about gender and power dynamics. Through an examination of my empirical data, I argue that peer sexual harassment in Singapore's universities is a gendered exercise of power underscored by students' subscriptions to particular assumptions of femininity and masculinity and reiterated through social practices of the objectification of women and sexual coercion. Ultimately, peer sexual harassment cannot be divorced from the broader macro-societal gender inequality fundamental to Singapore society.

Exploring sexual violence prevention work on university campus

Helen Bovill, Helen Bovill

(University of the West of England)

In 2018 three focus groups were carried out (Bovill, Waller and McCartan) with 15 first year students. These focus groups lasted up to three hours producing data contributing to UWE SpeakUp Campaign. Focus groups identified five prevalent social norms: unwanted touching, consent, inappropriate use of social media, domestic abuse and initiation and humiliation ceremonies. Five short films regarding these social norms were developed. In September 2018 these films were used as part of an induction talk to more than 5000 Freshers at UWE, from the student inclusivity team.

Continuing with the research, Bovill sent out closed questionnaires to all first year students (September 2018) using evidence based measures: 'readiness to help', 'bystander efficacy', and 'bystander behaviour' scales (Prevention Innovations Research, 2015) to explore the landscape of first year student's knowledge of sexual violence and bystander action, receiving 560 responses. Bovill repeated this to all first years (February 2019), replicating the original questionnaire and additionally asking whether students received SpeakUp or bystander interventions, receiving 605 responses.

Additionally, colleagues from E&C and HAS, piloted a two-hour bystander programme re-developed by (Bovill, McCartan and Waller 2018) from the original eight-hour intervention developed at UWE by (Fenton et. al. 2014). 130 first year students received this programme (September 2018-January 2019). Bovill evaluated this via closed questionnaire, receiving 89 responses.

This talk will present early thoughts from this research exploring sexual violence on university campus.

Behind Closed Doors: Hegemonic Masculinities, Romantic Love, and Sexual Violence in Gay Relationships

Dr Aliraza Javaid,

(University of East London)

In this paper, I seek to unravel the relationship between hegemonic, non-hegemonic, and dominant/dominating masculinities in gay relationships, using the issue of sexual violence as my core focus. I critically examine the ways in which gay men in gay relationships navigate through these different masculinities at different times, places, and contexts. The intersection between masculinities, romantic love, and sexual violence in gay relationships will be explored, theorized, and understood. I examine these links, with the support of the conceptual lens of hegemonic masculinity. Uncovering sexual violence in gay relationships is important because it is often hidden from sight and placed on the borderlines of significance. Bringing this focus to the fore will help us to make sense of the ways wherein sexual violence in gay relationships manifest. I aim to examine how masculinities are hierarchically structured in gay relationships, with the view of understanding how gay men move through or are positioned in different masculinities at differing times. I make links between the ideology of love and sexual violence, arguing that practices of love, such as saying 'I love you', act to secure male rape victims in violent/abusive relationships and often positioning them in subordinate masculinities. I argue that male rape legitimates an unequal relationship between men by constructing the perpetrator as masculine and the victim as feminine in gay relationships.

Social Divisions / Social Identities B W828

Class, spatial segregation and social cohesion in Chile

Gabriel Otero,

(University of Amsterdam)

This study examines the relationship between social cohesion and class-based stratification. In contrast with most of the evidence reported thus far for developed Western countries, we focus on an emerging and highly unequal context: Chile. For this purpose, we use a variety of measures that directly captures the core of social cohesion, such as social interactions, social trust, civic participation, place attachment and solidarity. Theoretically, we agree on a definition of social cohesion as a descriptive, multifaceted and gradual phenomenon attributed to a collective, indicating the quality

of collective togetherness. We hypothesize that profound dissimilarities of the way in which the cohesion and unity of social life are built, depending on the distribution of material and symbolic resources managed by people (e.g. income, networks). This study uses data from ELSOC, a nationally representative survey of the Chilean urban population aged 18–75 years (2,984). To identify social classes in Chile we intersect measures of occupational class, educational level, household income, and social capital. To measure spatial resources, we merge the survey data with georeferenced data within a 300-meter radius from each interviewee's home, including relevant measures such as population density, and socioeconomic segregation. Our methodology combines multiple correspondence analyses and hierarchical clustering techniques. Preliminary results show that the socio-spatial resources of stratification, namely being a high-level manager or professional, having higher economic and cultural capital, and living in an affluent segregated neighbourhood, and especially holding a higher education degree, are very important in explaining the perceived social cohesion.

Poverty patterns during childhood – Characteristics, determinants and impacts on social participation

Claudia Wenzig, Torsten Lietzmann
(Institute for Employment Research (IAB))

In Germany – like in most European countries – children and adolescents are still a social group at higher risk of poverty and welfare benefit receipt. However, most official statistics as well as a number of research findings depend on cross-sectional data. Using longitudinal data instead enhances the perspective on poverty trajectories during childhood. As a result, questions of how poverty patterns are characterised and determined arise. Against this background, we examine poverty patterns of children in Germany in a longitudinal perspective as well as their determinants and impacts on social participation.

We employ the nine waves of the German panel study 'Labour Market and Social Security' (PASS), which is an annual household panel survey. In order to gain a more precise picture of low-income households, we distinguish between five different household income situations: 'secured income position', 'intermediate income position', 'at risk of poverty', 'receipt of basic social security' and 'at risk of poverty and receipt of basic social security'. In order to identify typical poverty patterns, we use sequence analysis in combination with cluster analysis. The results show five differing clusters in terms of changing income situations and the length of poverty. As determinants of poverty cluster affiliation, we identify household and parental characteristics. The results of impacts on child development show that growing up in a low-income family, especially in permanent poverty, restricts children's opportunities to participate in social activities and interact with peers.

Geography Matters : Social Exclusion/ Poverty and Intersectionalities in Rural Contexts

Philomena De Lima,
(University of the Highlands & Islands- Inverness College)

Research on understanding the specific dynamics and processes of social exclusion/poverty in rural areas has tended to lag behind the urban, despite the fact that 90 per cent of the European Union territory is rural and more than half of the total population lives in rural areas. Growing research has challenged this urban 'gaze' by exposing the invisible nature of social exclusion and the experiences of many 'hidden others' in rural communities. Although urban and rural areas share similarities, research suggests that the drivers, dynamics and experiences of poverty/social exclusion are contingent on the specific dynamics of place and spatial contexts in which they are located. Research on rural poverty and social exclusion has identified the complex and multidimensional aspects of social exclusion, related to 'access' (both in relation to public, private and third sector services and mobility) interacting with other structural and social factors as critical to experiences of social exclusion and poverty in rural contexts. The presentation will draw on two research studies involving migrants, 'local communities' and policy makers in rural communities in the UK and Spain to illustrate the importance of developing more nuanced conceptual and empirical approaches to social exclusion by taking into account the diversity of rural areas and the ways in which rurality intersects with other social identities and structural issues to shape particular experiences of social exclusion and poverty.

Sociology of Education A - Special Event

W823

Constructing the higher education student across Europe

Rachel Brooks, Rachel Brooks, Jessie Abrahams, Anu Lainio, Predrag Lažetic
(University of Surrey)

It is often assumed within much of the academic literature, and by many of those working in higher education, that universities across Europe are homogenising, converging around an Anglo-American model as a result of neo-liberal pressures and the aim of creating a single European Higher Education Area. Moreover, European policies and

marketing materials commonly suppose that higher education students can move unproblematically across national borders – as part of the Erasmus mobility scheme, for example. In this symposium we bring some of these assumptions under critical scrutiny, and consider the extent to which higher education students across Europe are, in practice, understood in the same way within and across particular nations. We draw on five data sources (university websites, newspaper articles, student focus groups, policy documents and interviews with policymakers) from six countries (Denmark, England, Germany, Ireland, Poland and Spain) to examine dominant constructions of the student.

The four papers each have a different focus considering: (i) national and institutional variation in online constructions of students (drawing on analysis of university websites in all six countries); (ii) how students understand their own role, and the purpose of higher education more broadly (drawing on student focus groups in Denmark, England and Ireland); (iii) the extent to which students should be conceptualised as consumers (drawing on newspaper articles and student focus groups in Denmark and England); (iv) how policymakers discuss diversity within the student body (drawing on interviews with policymakers and policy documents in all six countries).

Diversity and the European higher education student: policy influencers' narratives of difference

Rachel Brooks,

(University of Surrey)

Comparative studies of European social policy have pointed to significant differences with respect to the way in which diversity is valued and understood, contrasting nations that have adopted strongly compulsory and integrationist policies with others that have pursued more voluntary and pluralistic approaches. Within the higher education sector specifically, although there have been numerous European-level initiatives to encourage national governments to take action to widen access to university, we know relatively little about how key policy actors conceptualise diversity with respect to the student population, and the extent to which such understandings are shared across national borders. Drawing on in-depth interviews with a range of 'policy influencers' in six European countries and an analysis of relevant policy documents, this article suggests that dimensions of difference are not always valued equally and that, despite policy imperatives promoting higher education homogenisation across the continent, some significant differences between nation-states endure.

Images and constructions of higher education students on university websites in Europe

Lažetic Predrag,

(University of Bath)

battlegrounds on which discourses about students and higher education are articulated through a combination of visual images and texts (Rose, 2001). Previous gender-centred discourse analysis of a sample of university websites in English speaking countries (Leathwood and Read, 2009) pointed at the prevalence of a "good" feminised student within the "masculinised tradition" of the university. This paper extends this research in a much wider comparative perspective by analysing 36 university websites in 6 European countries.

Analysis indicates a divergence in the portrayal of students on university websites in different countries and across types of institutions - rather than convergence towards the image of a "good", typically female student who enjoys a "total experience" at university, which dominates English and Irish websites but also websites of highly ranked universities across the other four countries. This (in its roots Anglo-Saxon) focus on student experience can be seen as the institutional middle-ground discursive position between the construction of students as consumers and dependent instrumental learners, and the historical enlightenment view of students as people committed to personal development. On the other hand, analysis indicates that in some countries (Spain, Germany and Poland) student images and texts are more commonly absent. Students in these countries tend to be constructed as recipients of public service, mostly as independent learners and are expected to independently manage administrative steps and navigate their studies and student life.

Students; Being and Becoming Consumers of Higher Education?

Anu Lainio, Jessie Abrahams

(University of Surrey)

Within an increasingly marketised higher education (HE) environment, there is a growing tendency to construct students as being and becoming consumers of HE. In this paper we scrutinise this notion by exploring the discursive practices of 'the student consumer' in Denmark and England. These two countries pose an interesting point of comparison as they have very distinct welfare regimes and HE funding systems. Traditionally 'a consumer' is understood as an economic construct (Clarke et al. 2017) and is established in economic relationships; exchanging money for commodified good and services. This definition implies that it is the economic exchange which renders the transaction as one of a consumeristic nature. Interestingly, the consumerist discourse is still apparent in contexts in which tuition fees are not paid. One could ask whether, through being provided with a free education alongside a maintenance grant, some sort of economic relationship and an expectation of a consumerist behaviour is still

established. To what extent is this something that can be related to Williams' (1983, 79) notion of consumer as a "more abstract figure in a more abstract market"? We draw upon empirical data collected in the two countries from focus groups with university students and analysis of national newspapers. We raise a question of what it actually means to consider students as 'being or becoming' consumers of their education and we seek to begin an exploration at a conceptual and theoretical level around 'the student consumer'.

Theory W323

Socialist Nationalism Redux

*Marek Szopski, none
(Warsaw University)*

In the countries of the Soviet block, which were the offspring of the 4 empires: the Russian, the Austrian-Hungarian, the Prussian and the Ottoman ones, a way of social thinking was associated with the ideas of national liberation, and modernisation, but not in the spirit of liberal democracy of the Western type, but rather an illusory sense of community tied with the common threads of custom, language and religion. Contrary to many views, the Soviet model was based on brutal enforcement of what was perceived as the progressive way of constructing society along Western lines. The radical decoupling of the political and religious spheres in the cultural project resulted in the reluctant adoption of the solutions in the social sphere that were more of a postulate than reality in the Western societies of the time. The 2 World Wars made some of those postulates reality; such as women lib, welfare state, minority rights, including LGBTQ not as an extreme left agenda but a mainstream liberal democratic dogma. It is in the form of a 'backlash', to use Susan Faludi's term, that the countries of the former 'fascist' orientation, Italy, Austria-Hungary, Polish National Democracy, Romanian Iron Guard etc. find its postmodern existence plausible in the EU. The reconstruction of the Central and Eastern European projects will require a very thorough redefinition of their cultural self-identity mythology. Otherwise they will find themselves much more akin to the authoritarian or semi-totalitarian regimes of the Russian, Turkish or Central Asian kind.

Rethinking global power: the space of states

*William Atkinson, Will Atkinson
(University of Bristol)*

This paper proposes a novel sociological framework for understanding international relations. The starting point is Pierre Bourdieu's notion of field, denoting a system of domination and struggle in relation to a relatively autonomous principle of misrecognition, or capital. While originally deployed to understand national-level struggles among, for example, artists and state bureaucrats, some scholars (e.g. Gisele Sapiro, Frederic Lebaron, George Steinmetz, Julian Go) have since begun identifying transnational or even global fields. Building on some of these ideas, the paper makes the case that there is a field, or space, of states in which state actors, controlling state resources (especially economic capital, military capital and cultural capital) are positioned. There are dominant and dominated states, and states with different compositions of capital, and state actors' feel for the game underpin so many global strategies, from trade deals and embargoes to war. This conception, for which there is some tentative empirical support, has the potential to overcome many of the limitations of existing theories of international relations and global power – from realism and constructivism to world-systems theory – while integrating some of their major insights.

Cosmopolitanism and Memory Wars in Dark Times

*Larry Ray, Laurence Ray
(University of Kent)*

Europe is a site of culture wars, exemplified by the rise of the far right (of which Brexit is one manifestation), nativist politics and nationalist romances that recall Arendt's 'dark times'. One aspect of this is disputes over traumatic memories of war, occupation and the Holocaust in European history. This paper begins by reconsidering Sznajder and Levy's claim that Holocaust commemoration is a point of reference for future-oriented European cosmopolitan ethics in the Second Modernity. This is questioned with reference to the shift from 'memory laws' to 'memory wars' (Koposov) that pitch the protection of national narratives against encroachment by cosmopolitan ones. The argument refers to Habermas's later concept of 'Juridification' highlighting the potential conflict between law (norms) and culture (values) and the problems of securing legitimacy in post-national formations. An example of this conflict, and of the emergence of culture wars more generally, is taken from the recent Polish 'anti-defamation law' prohibiting claims that 'the Polish Nation' was responsible or co-responsible for Nazi crimes. The law asserts extra-territoriality and 'applies throughout the world, regardless of local laws.' Holocaust memory then becomes not a universalistic foundation of future-oriented cosmopolitan ethics but a guardian of sacred symbols of particular communities. This turn is in part embedded in post-communist memory politics and overlaying of multiple traumatic pasts. But also illustrates how binary ideological

constructions (such as national vs cosmopolitan) and hierarchies of suffering exploit past events as resources for the transformation of identity.

Proposing Ochamalienwu Theory of Community Policing for Nigeria

Aminu Musa Audu

(Independent Researcher)

This paper discusses my recently published monograph (Aminu Musa Audu, 2018) which proposes Ochamalienwu Theory of Community Policing. This theory offers evident-based explanations on the nature, dynamics, risk factors and suggestions to solve crime problem. There is perception of increasing rate of crime problem such as armed robbery, kidnapping, insurgency, corruption and terrorism Nigeria and 'police and public divide' resulting to the public not willing to cooperate with the police by giving useful information, posing threat to the police's ability to perform. Consequently, there are various efforts made towards finding solution to the crime problem. Community policing took its root in the US and UK in the 1970s, however the policy is transferred to other countries to address global security concerns such as the UK-DFID's overseen community policing initiative in 2002/2003. However, the policy implementation was not yielding the desired result because of trust and communication issues between the police and public. Given the dearth of literature to address this concern, this paper aims to establish whether there is trust gap between the police and the public, focussed to examine the relationship patterns between these stakeholders as co-producers of security and community safety. Adopting interpretative framework with interviews and focus groups discussions, key findings of these empirical data have indicated that the desired positive impact of the implementation of community policing policy has not been fulfilled. In the context of the empirical findings, this paper proposes Ochamalienwu Theory of Community Policing for effective security programming in Nigeria.

Sociology of Religion

W003

A Patriarchal Church within 21st Century Scotland. How women navigate between church and social spaces.

Yvonne Bennett,

(Canterbury Christ Church University)

Female equality is legislated in Scottish society yet some conservative Presbyterian churches are patriarchal in dogma, with a male-only hierarchy. This paper looks at the ways in which women, from three generations, navigate between their church community and their social community. It examines the different views held on female equality and the role and position of women when it comes to decision making within the church and society as a whole. The women interviewed are 19 years, 36 years and 75 years old, all belonging to The Free Church of Scotland. All are heavily involved in the church community, yet none can hold a position of authority within the church.

Conversion, Commitment and Community: Exploring the Role of Women, Marriage, and Family in Chinese Migrant Christian Communities in Britain

Xinan Li,

(Loughborough University)

This presentation draws insights from a doctoral research project on Christian conversion of Chinese migrants in Britain. In the research, I have proposed a thesis of 'believing through belonging', highlighting the importance of commitment in the understanding of Chinese migrants' Christian conversion in Britain. The commitment of Chinese migrant Christians in Britain, characterised by two key components, religious belonging and communal belonging, explains how Chinese migrant Christian converts live their religion and build various communities in Britain. In this presentation, I expect to probe gender issues, which was not a focus in my doctoral research, with data from my original research and follow-up interviews with some married Chinese migrant Christian couples, as well as (female) clergies. I argue that although conventional views and values on gender-related issues are highly appreciated in contemporary Chinese migrant Christian communities in Britain; in practice, I observe that in the building of various Chinese Christian communities, mainline Chinese Christian institutions have attempted to challenge the conventional patriarchal understanding of Christianity through women ordination. At the same time, the promulgation of the traditional institution of marriage and family, a point where traditional Chinese culture and Christian values can overlap, has greatly contributed to the building of Chinese migrant Christian communities in Britain.

The tainted and the polluted: Is the Church of England a hostile environment for women priests?

Sharon Jagger,

(University of York)

Women priests in the Church of England have attracted researchers since they entered the Church hierarchy in 1994. Yet much of this research has left the relationship between gender constructions and the Christian symbol system unchallenged. From a feminist perspective, I explore how women priests are kept in liminality (Turner, 1969) by a dual structure forming women-free zones. I am attempting to understand the complex relationship between symbolism and hierarchically and how inequality is perceived and constructed in religious terms. An equal-but-different trope haunts the woman priest as she attempts to understand how femininity, femaleness and the priesthood interrelate. As the Church struggles to deal with swiftly changing understandings of social relations, I ask how women priests negotiate structural differentiation based on theologies that generate gender hierarchy and inequality. Women priests find themselves the source of symbolic taint, are perceived by some to deconsecrate the altar and are subject to limiting and silencing discourses within the Church. This paper will explore how women priests subvert and collude with, and protest and forgive, gender inequality that is embedded in the structure of the Church, focusing on their relationships with male clergy who do not recognise women's priesthood – these relationships are surprising on many levels. I have discovered women priests can be tricksters (Hyde, 1998) in the way they cross boundaries and, in Sara Ahmed's words, 'she might pass as willing in order to be willful' (Ahmed, 2018, p. 83).

Distinctive or professionalised? Understanding the postsecular in faith-based anti-trafficking responses in the UK

*Hannah Lewis, Gwyneth Lonergan, Emma Tomalin, Louise Waite
(University of Sheffield)*

Responding to a perceived rise in the activity of faith-based organisations in the field of anti-trafficking in the UK, this paper examines the intersection of religion and the current 'fight against modern slavery'. We argue that the intersection of faith and human trafficking is an important dimension in understanding the contemporary modern slavery complex, which has not yet been explored in academic research beyond the United States of America. A mapping of UK anti-trafficking organisations demonstrates that FBOs are more likely to be single-issue groups specialising in services for trafficked persons, and are occupying the traditional position of 'filling the gaps' in mainstream provision. While FBOs are clearly prominent in the anti-trafficking domain, we question whether this is really evidence of postsecularism since faith actors are secularising aspects of their work as they professionalise. Examining the multitudinous roles of faith based organisations and actors in the UK anti-trafficking field demonstrates not only the diversity of faith action in this field, but also indicates the emergence of a dual register where FBOs can secularise in some public facing activities but also retain religious distinctiveness in being able to access certain groups and funding streams, and to connect with people in terms of their faith identity.

Work, Employment & Economic Life A

HANGING LANTERN ROOM

Contestation of the social order depending on political orientation and party preference: evidence from a survey of public opinion in Switzerland

*Aurélien Abrassart, Stefan C. Wolter
(Centre for Research in Economics of Education, University of Bern)*

The foundations of the social order in contemporary societies have been shown to rest on nature and reason, whereby institutional arrangements influence the perception of the prestige of occupations through the legitimization of their role in the 'natural' order of things. Because of an important consistency in prestige ratings from respondents across various social groups, countries and over time, 'deviant' perceptions of the social order have attracted little attention. Yet structural changes in modern economies, brought by rapid globalization and technological change, might have significantly affected the view of the social world in the last decades. In particular, resistance to these transformations at the political level could lead to a growing contestation of the social order.

We contribute to this important question by analyzing a unique data set in Switzerland based on a survey of adults' perception of the social prestige of occupations. As our results indicate, party preference does not significantly influence one's view of the social world. However, the closer the political belief system of respondents to either extreme of the political spectrum, the less likely they are to assign social prestige to occupations according to their educational requirements. Moreover, occupations more salient in autonomy are less valued among respondents at the far left of the political spectrum. The increasing complexity of modern societies and labour markets in knowledge economies might therefore have triggered a strong reaction from the losers and potential losers of these developments who, in turn, adopted radicalized belief systems to cope with these changes.

Police Officers, Mental (ill-) Health and Spoiled Identity

Jon Garland,

(University of Surrey)

This paper considers the processes through which some police officers with mental ill-health experience stigmatization in police organizations. Situated in the sociological framework of Goffman and in modified labelling theory, it draws on the findings of a qualitative study and examines the sources of stigma embedded in police work, the consequences of stigma for the labelled officer, the nature of any resistance to the application of the label and approaches to challenging stigma within the policing context. It suggests that in order to tackle these negative attitudes constabularies must do more to address the processes of stigmatization associated with mental ill-health at the individual and institutional levels.

Encountering the invisible 'B' in LGBT: Identity work processes and producing bisexual identities in the workplace

*Michelle O'Toole,
(University of Edinburgh)*

Bisexuality is under-represented within the wider LGBT umbrella of gendered and sexualised identities as a distinctive phenomenon, being marginalised both academically and organisationally. This paper draws on the responses of 11 bisexual workers from a variety of industries and investigates experiences of bisexual identity work in terms of: the relative (in) visibility of the sexual orientation to co-workers; the contested, momentary decisions about whether and how to disclose bisexual selves in interaction; and how organisational settings, practices and norms affect the performance of bisexual work identities. Our preliminary findings suggest that societal misconceptions - rooted in heteronormative and gay-centric assumptions about bisexuality - filter into workplace interactions. Binary attitudes towards sexuality and the contested legitimacy of bisexuality challenge bisexual employees to make sense of their identity work across various relational, interpersonal and ambivalent encounters, encompassing humour, shock, alliances and forms of emotional labour. Implications for further research and practice that can raise awareness and recognition of bisexual workplace identities are discussed.

Finding Purpose after leaving the Armed Forces – Meaningful Work in the Third Sector

*Silke Roth,
(University of Southampton)*

Each year, about 16.000 men and women leave the UK Armed Forces and according to the Office of National Statistics, about 2.6 mio Veterans and 35.000 reservists lived in Britain in 2015. The vast majority of veterans successfully transition to civilian work and life. Nevertheless, the experience of leaving the military is associated with the 'unmaking' of militarized identities. Leaving the armed forces can be understood as a 'cultural transition' or even culture shock which is associated with the loss of military structure, status and camaraderie. Especially, when the military and the civilian sphere are understood as quite distinct, the question arises whether and how social, cultural and symbolic capital can be transferred from one sphere to the other. Service leavers do not necessarily make use of existing support offered by the military and a variety of charities. The disaster relief organisation Team Rubicon (TR) UK recruits former military personnel and those without a military background as staff, interns and volunteers. Team Rubicon provides a context in which former service men and women can draw on their skills and provide as well as receive peer-support. Volunteering is associated with well-being. My research suggests that the organisation represents a bridging organisation between military and civilian spheres and offers opportunities to find purpose, community and self-worth. My paper contributes to analyses of meaningful work in the third sector. Based on fieldwork and qualitative interviews with staff, interns and volunteers, I analyse how those involved in Team Rubicon understand their work as meaningful.

Friday 26/04/2019 at 15:15 - 16:45
Paper Session 9

Cities, Mobilities, Place & Space A
W622

Coal, prisons, and disadvantage: evidence of continued inequality in former coal-mining areas

Phil Jones, Dr. Emily Gray; Prof. Steve Farrall
(University of Derby)

Nearly twenty years after the miners' strike the number of prisons in coal mining areas outstripped the number of prisons in non-coal mining areas, after accounting for population. We argue this is evidence of yet another detrimental outcome faced by these communities in the 1980s as workers and their families had their source of income, identity, and purpose abruptly removed.

We identify former coal mining areas based on the methodology previously used by Beatty and Fothergill (1996). We adapt this methodology to classify 1974-1996 county geographies (as these were the contemporary geographies as the majority of the mines closed) to select coal and non-coal counties.

Our hypothesis was that there were more prisons in former coal mining areas than non-coal mining areas per capita. Using Poisson regression we identified that coal mining counties are 90% more likely (95% confidence interval: 27% -- 184%) to have a prison than non-coal mining counties in 2001.

In comparison, a similar Poisson regression of the number of prisons in 1961 is not statistically significant, suggesting prisons were built and expanded in areas of economic change during the 1970s and 1980s.

Even decades after the closure of the majority of UK coal mines, we find evidence of continued social inequality and division between the 'north' and 'south', with important implications for the recovery of these and similar areas in light of contemporary austerity.

The public, policies and decision-making – a comparative perspective on city governance in Nottingham and Stuttgart

Hannah Keding,
(University of Nottingham)

This paper focuses on the relationship between civil society and those developing policies in two cities, Nottingham (UK) and Stuttgart (Germany). Urban and welfare state governance are examined and compared focusing on the question of how urban policies aiming for social and intergenerational justice are devised. Drawing on interviews with key stakeholders in both cities and on documentary sources, different power dynamics emerge. Whereas measures aiming to enhance social and intergenerational justice in Nottingham often originated from its City Council, dominated by the progressive and electorally successful Labour Party, Stuttgart's diverse municipal council composition of 10 parties and groups has in some instances been driven by a partly very active civil society. These contrasting tendencies correspond to differently pronounced inequalities between the public and decision-makers in each city – in terms of a realisation of basic social and economic rights, allocation of economic and educational resources and engagement with public issues. Implications for civil societies and for conceptualising urban governance will be discussed. The public relevance of these issues is underlined by the ongoing and very controversial debate about revisions to local authority boundaries in Nottinghamshire.

From mining towns to Merseyside: Labour's changing heartlands

Jamie Furlong,
(University of Southampton)

There is a well-established narrative in the geographical understanding of British elections: 'left behind', white working class places are gradually moving to the Conservatives as Labour dominate in urban, ethnically diverse 'cosmopolitan' areas. Using merged constituency-level census data with election results to run linear regression models at each general election in from 1979 to 2017, this research presents clear evidence of this process in England and Wales. However, spatial analysis shows that though Labour once consistently performed above model expectations in the coalfields of South Yorkshire, the Midlands and Wales, this has gradually shifted to Merseyside. Labour's heartlands have moved from largely white, working class mining communities to largely white, working class Merseyside. Through elite interviews with local politicians, this paper then explores the unique place-based factors associated with Labour's increasing dominance in Merseyside - an area that is bucking the national trend. It illuminates the importance of: geographical factors, such as the increasingly positive perception of Liverpool and an increasing connectedness

between the city and its outer suburbs; cultural factors such as the influence of football club identification, the Hillsborough disaster and the self-referential myth of Liverpool's 'otherness'; and political factors such as a widespread anti-Conservatism that has defined the region since Thatcher's time as prime minister.

Cities, Mobilities, Place & Space B

W610

A Night at the Carnival: Rural Identity, Spaces of Resistance & Social Change

Nathan Kerrigan
(*Birmingham City University*)

Carnivals are not simply single event celebrations. They are diverse spaces which involve complex processes of place-making and identity construction. They are also spaces where resistances are fought and the affirmation of identities are maintained and protected. Despite this, sociological and geographical enquiry has given very little attention to the examination of carnivals as spaces of resistance and maintenance of identity. Based on ethnographic data (semi-structured interviews and direct and participant observations) collected for a larger project, the following talk aims to explore the impact of localised social change occurring in a small, but developing rural town in the south of England. Themes of social and spatial organisation of identity and power are explored by focussing on the carnival in the local area in which some residents (those with middle class status and longer-standing in the town) used to maintain their specific rural identity against the backdrop of social change. Findings highlight the symbolic imagery of the procession reinforced the rural and picturesque nature of the place. However, this was contingent on longer-term residents with the greatest material and emotional investment in the area who constructed such imagery during the procession. The talk demonstrates a need for sociological and geographical appreciation of social and spatialised understandings of protecting/maintaining rural identities by denoting the use of carnival space as a place of social reactionism that attempt to bound rural space whilst simultaneously resisting against unwarranted change.

Line dancing, cultural feelings and other leisure spaces in Stoke

Mark Ball,
(*University of Leeds*)

This paper follows a period of participatory fieldwork with a line dancing group in Stoke-on-Trent. Drawing on literature around conviviality, the potential of leisure and cultural value, this paper will suggest that understanding the values of, and a taste for line dancing is a productive exercise. Here the joyful feelings of formation dancing, the lack of discipline in a disciplined dance, and a sense of ageing together all factor into this discussion. Useful here is Ben Highmore's recent book *Cultural Feelings*, particularly in unpacking the line dancing mood. The paper will conclude with reflections on leisure spaces in cities, and the difficult task of valuing more informal cultural/leisure practices. Here the working club setting will be paid close attention, and the variety of activities taking place on a given weekday night. 'It may look like an ordinary pub, but it feels anything but ordinary on a Tuesday night'.

'Take me to Church'- Developing translocal music worlds through the creative peripheral placemaking and programming of Other Voices

Susan O'Shea,
(*Manchester Metropolitan University*)

Other Voices has been building alternative music worlds and embedding peripheral music making and performance into its programming since 2002. From Dingle to Derry, Ballina to Berlin, Other Voices disrupts popular perceptions about Irish music highlighting the emerging creative diversity of the country. The small church stage, at one end of the Wild Atlantic Way tourist trail, provides opportunities to introduce performers to new audiences. Making a significant contribution to local economies it promotes an Ireland far removed from the stereotypes of folk music and forced migration in less affluent times. By harnessing the soft power of the Irish diaspora, and looking beyond the metropolitan giants of music from Dublin and Belfast, Other Voices builds links between rural Irish towns and global music cities, embracing new technologies of performance, participation and distribution. In a volatile funding environment, despite attempting to foster translocal partnerships for artists, their part-funded 'exposure' model has been criticised as making music mobilities difficult for some where material inequalities still persist.

Using social network analysis, I map how Other Voices developed to promote regional place-based music, new artists and translocal connections. Applying 'core/periphery' and 'strength of weak ties' network theories, I examine performer networks and the role 'playing with' other more well-known musicians might have on the careers of emerging musicians. This is supplemented by a narrative review of online discourses around the parity of performance opportunities. This paper makes a contribution to the literature on music worlds and a social network approach to understanding social capital.

Cities, Mobilities, Place & Space C

W727

National Identity Figures In Australia and Britain

Jed Donoghue, Jed Donoghue & Bruce Tranter
(University of Tasmania)

National identity is claimed to be founded upon the myths and legends of a 'golden age', personified through heroes, saints or sage. Using national survey data from Australia and the United Kingdom, we asked who are the most important Australians and British, living or dead. Australian and British citizens were expected to identify with romantic, anti-authority outlaws, sports people or disciplined and successful military figures, such as Ned Kelly, Bradman or General Sir John Monash in Australia, or Robin Hood, Bobby Moore or Lord Nelson and the Duke of Wellington in the UK.

However, Australians selected former prime ministers, surgeons and a saint in their top 10 important people. Australian responses were far more evenly distributed among several important figures than in the UK. By far the most frequently selected figures in the UK were a very popular Royal and a former Prime Minister. The most important people identified in both countries tend not to be heroes from a distant 'golden age', but more contemporary leaders, from the twentieth century who have had a direct influence upon the stability and prestige of their nation. In America George Washington and Abraham Lincoln have stood the test of time as important national figures but our findings suggest that national heroes in Australia and the UK may be limited to a shorter term of worship unless they can be adapted to citizens' contemporary concerns.

Culture, Media, Sport & Food

W308

THE CULTURE OF RUSSIAN NEW WORKING-CLASS YOUTH: REPRESENTATION IN BIOGRAPHICAL NARRATIVES

Tatiana Gavrilyuk,
(Industrial University of Tyumen)

The subject domain of the research is the cultural subjectivity and the lifestyle of the working class youth in contemporary Russia. The notion of the 'new working class' and the criteria for its definition have been proposed and substantiated. Applying the categories of the intersectional theory, the emphasis has been made on the micro-politics of differences within the working class youth, the translation and implementation of class normative patterns and values through family socialization, subcultural identities of young workers and their attitude to other social groups. The cultural landscape of Russian working-class youth has been described including such practices as traditional and new media consumption, tastes in art and popular culture, creativity, leisure practices, and health care. Cultural barriers for the upward social mobility of working-class youth has been regarded in the macrosocial context of the structural opportunities and constraints of a society characterized by the extremely high degree of social inequalities and the precariousness of youth labor. The empirical basis of the research is presented by the combination of the biographical method (30 in-depth interviews) and quantitative survey (the poll of 1500 respondents). Using the main analytical method of reflexive analysis, based on the categorical field of phenomenology, the intentionality of utterances, non-reflexive knowledge, structuring of the vital world, the logic of building links between the events in one's own biography have been revealed. This report was supported by the Russian Science Foundation grant ? '17-78-20062 Life strategies of young people of the new working class in modern Russia.'

'I would like to have definitive information about what we'll have to do when this Brexit will start': Hierarchies of media literacies among Italian migrants in Brexit times

Giuliana Tiripelli

This paper investigates how a specific group of EU migrants engages with mediated information to adjust life plans during Brexit, and it points to new hierarchies in media literacy within apparently uniform communities of migration. Firstly, the paper discusses the results of the pilot questionnaire circulated on the official Facebook page of the Italians living in Nottingham in summer 2018. The questionnaire asked participants about the impact of Brexit in their life planning, their uses of mediated information, and general socio-economic data. The pilot aimed to explore how different approaches to mediated information could relate to different attitudes towards life-planning and different socio-economic factors during Brexit. Secondly, the paper explains how this pilot informs a wider project investigating EU migrants' approaches to mediated information in 2019, based on additional unexpected findings in the pilot. The

questionnaire also revealed the existence of a polarised variety of media literacy skills within this local community, and the absence of institutions effectively serving as official providers of authoritative information for these migrants. Instead, the questionnaire triggered many unsolicited, direct requests to the researcher – also a member of the community - for 'definitive' information about steps to take in view of Brexit implementation. These unexpected results points to interesting issues of positionality and impact in this area of research. They call for research that is shaped around the expressed needs of the community, and which adopts deeply sociological approaches to the study of media power to support communication strategies that can fill these needs.

Trolling the everyday: the shifting norms of public discourse

Catherine Happer, Andrew Hoskins
(University of Glasgow)

Trolling is constructed in public and often academic discourse as an individual pathology, a rare and extremist form of behaviour. This paper challenges this conceptualisation and instead interrogates trolling as a logical if not inevitable consequence of recent shifts in technological, media and political culture.

The continuity of privately held political and cultural opinions is disrupted by their relocation to the public space of social media. In this same space, extremist opinions and ideas are promoted; likes, retweets, posts, grab attention and signal importance. Continuity is maintained through elite speakers setting the cultural tone with politicians such as Trump and Farage using trolling as a form of political strategizing, and journalists such as Owen Jones using trolling as a form of censorship. But change is manifested in the weight of the support of the voluminous collectives who follow them. Trolling here is mass behaviour.

Despite this, there is a lack of empirical research investigating the motivations for these types of online interactions, how actors make sense of or justify their own behaviours and where the lines in respect of normal and acceptable are drawn in different contexts and through different collectives. In this paper, we draw on our focus group data on public understandings, experiences and motivations in relation to trolling, how trolling becomes morally sanctioned and in some contexts seen as perfectly rational. We also explore the wider impacts of these cultural shifts in respect of cultural and political change.

Smears, scandals, silences: understanding the news media's portrayal of deaths in custody

Elizabeth Barkas,
(University of Glasgow)

The context for this paper is the thousands of deaths in custodial settings in England, Wales and Scotland since 1995, which have raised issues about the treatment of vulnerable people and the use of force by state agents, as well as institutional racism and the difficulties for family members navigating the inquest process. Some cases have sparked important campaigns led by family members and other supporting organisations, and provoked considerable public debate, but most do not become major news. This paper presents on the basis of a doctoral research project examining news media representations of deaths in custody in Great Britain. The research as a whole examines news about a sample of contentious deaths occurring between 1995-2015, including content analysis and a case study approach including interviews with the key actors involved in making the news. This research explores the ways in which the legitimacy of state institutions is challenged and defended via contestation over news about these incidents. Crucially, this research also illuminates the silences that are created when news coverage is muted or non-existent. This paper presents preliminary findings from the first stage of the research, which analysed news coverage of a sample of 200 deaths. It examines how the deceased were portrayed, which sources were most prevalent, how official narratives were put forward and to what extent these were challenged, within an overall assessment of the key causal factors shaping news coverage.

Environment & Society

W525

'There is no food waste in Somalia': Immigrant perspectives on household sustainability in a global North city

Tally Katz-Gerro, Catherine Walker, Sherilyn MacGregor
(University of Manchester)

Research on the intersection between environmental change and international migration has tended to focus on climate change as a driver of migration from the developing South to the industrialised North. Significantly less attention has been given to the cultural dimensions of adapting to climate change and environmental degradation at a time when many 'first world' cities are becoming more heterogeneous. This means that little is known about how culturally-specific notions of sustainability, premised on reducing the impacts of Western over-consumption, are understood by immigrants to global North cities.

In this presentation we discuss the findings of mixed-methods research that explored the environmentally significant household practices of 60 Somali immigrants living in Moss Side, Manchester, with equal participation from men and women. Discussions of practices focused on food provisioning, use of water and energy and following council-regulated waste and recycling systems. Set against ambitious local government plans for cleaning and greening the city, we discuss the way participants understand sustainability, how ideas around sustainability correspond to their past and present experiences of household resource use (i.e., in Somalia and the UK), how culture and religious norms shape household practices, and gendered and generational differences in participants' responses to policy messages about household sustainability.

Our conclusions make a timely contribution to academic and policy discussions of household sustainability. We contend that the perspectives and practices of immigrants - a population traditionally overlooked in household sustainability research - can make important contributions to more inclusive sustainability governance.

Maintaining fresh air: a practice approach to home ventilation

*Jenny Brierley,
(University of Sheffield)*

The critical need to reduce carbon emissions, to mitigate climate change, demands a high level of airtightness to minimise energy use for heating in new homes. This requires effective planned ventilation, to avoid negative consequences for indoor air quality, health, comfort, and the building itself. Shortcomings in maintenance and unintended day-to-day actions by residents are commonplace, however, which undermine the ventilation strategies in low-energy homes. Why does this happen?

Taking a socio-technical approach, rather than the commonly adopted technical, behavioural or legalistic approach to the problem, this research employs a case study method, using a survey, focus group and interviews to explore this question. The experience of housing associations, their professional maintenance practitioners and their residents is examined, focusing on five social rent low-energy housing developments across England. Practice Theory is used as the framework for analysis. I seek to understand what creates and sustains those practices relevant to effectively maintaining fresh air in energy efficient homes, through the interrelationship between these parties.

This paper presents initial findings, in terms of identifying key practices and a comparative analysis. I also critically reflect on how useful Practice Theory is in answering the research question methodologically. I conclude by considering what further opportunities this theory offers for addressing the problems identified through changing practices.

Lost property: exploring the sustainability of lost objects

*Helen Holmes, Ulrike Ehgartner
(University of Manchester)*

This paper presents the initial findings from a pilot project exploring lost property and its potential connections to issues of sustainability and social change. Abstract notions of absence, nothing and loss are becoming increasingly intriguing phenomena for sociologists interested in the everyday (Scott, 2018). However, whilst their theoretical connotations are being progressively discussed, empirical investigation into these phenomena remains absent. This project seeks to translate the abstract notion of loss into an empirical and material focused study. Involving qualitative interviews with: lost property offices; households; museums and repair cafes/re-use networks in Manchester, it explores how lost property connects to broader issues of waste and sustainable resource use. This research addresses both the sacred and the profane, paying attention to lost items of significant symbolic value (e.g jewellery), as well as those of a more ordinary nature (e.g umbrellas, gloves). In particular, it is interested in understanding how lost objects are replaced or substituted with other objects. Likewise, the project examines the broader issues of lost objects and their connections to practices of re-use and repair; this is through both a focus on consumer purchasing decisions but also what happens to lost objects which are never claimed. Broadly, the project contributes to debates on the sociology of the everyday, developing an agenda which explores people's relationships to objects and the relevance of this for sustainable practice and social change.

Is climate change policy fit for purpose? Analysis of four environmental policy-assemblages

*Nick Fox, Pam Alldred
(University of Huddersfield)*

National and international policy-makers have been addressing climate change and associated environmental degradations for 30 years. However, it is questionable whether current policy is socially, politically, economically and scientifically capable of adequately resolving the threats that climate changes poses to the planet and to living organisms. In this paper we interrogate critically four policy perspectives on sustainability and climate change: 'liberal environmentalism'; the United Nations policy statements on sustainable development; 'green capitalism' (also known as 'climate capitalism') and finally 'no-growth economics'. Our analysis is founded in a 'posthuman' ontology, which

aims to de-privilege human interests in relation to those of other animate and inanimate matter, while not denying continuing human involvement in the Earth's ecosystem. Humans, from this perspective, are part of the environment, not separate from or in opposition to it, and possess unique capacities essential for environment sustainability. We analyse the four policy positions micropolitically, treating each as a 'policy assemblage' comprising a range of human and non-human elements that establish what the policy can do, what it ignores or omits, and consequently how it might impact on environmental sustainability and climate change. None, we conclude, is adequate or appropriate to address climate change successfully. However, our analysis also supplies the starting point from which to establish a socially, scientifically and politically adequate posthuman climate change policy. We offer suggestions for some of the constituent elements of such a policy.

Families & Relationships - Special Event

W709

New Directions in the Sociology of Suicide and Self-Harm

Amy Chandler,
(University of Edinburgh)

Suicide rates are characterised by significant inequalities, with individuals and communities living with marginalisation and/or socioeconomic disadvantage experiencing a greater burden of self-completed death. Given that the incidence and meanings associated with suicide are socially patterned, sociological perspectives are vital. However, while sociology has a well-known history of research addressing suicide, in contemporary suicide research sociology is notably marginal. In this session we draw together researchers who are contributing cutting edge sociological insights to understanding suicide across the UK. Speakers will address gaps in existing sociological work on suicide and discuss new research which speaks to these. Notably, all presentations draw upon qualitative approaches which are rarely used in 'mainstream' suicide research.

Papers enrol diverse qualitative methodological approaches (from interviews to arts-based methods) and theoretical tools to critically interrogate the meanings associated with suicide among diverse groups. These include women who have lost a male partner to suicide (Mallon), multidisciplinary professional teams responding to looked after young people's self-harm (Evans), and refugees living in Scotland (Wright). Through four presentations, the panel will attend to the complex ways in which socio-cultural factors shape understandings of suicide, and how sociological insights can contribute. Papers emphasise the role of relationships (Owens) in shaping the contexts and aftermath of suicides. We argue that sociological approaches, particularly drawing on microsociology and the sociology of emotions, are vital in understanding suicides. The panel will reflect on the challenges facing sociology in engaging effectively with mainstream (largely psychological/psychiatric and quantitative) suicide research and suicide prevention efforts.

Survival, signalling and safety: foster carers and residential carers' interpretation of self-harm among care-experienced children and young people

Rhiannon Evans,
(Cardiff University)

Narratives of self-harm and suicide continue to receive scant theoretical and empirical attention. Indeed, (dis)continuities both within and across accounts remain largely overlooked. Uncovering meaning and tensions in narratives is imperative to understanding the complexity of causes, but also to comprehending motivations for responses, particularly the reactions of professionals. To date, research on 'professional narratives' have privileged the clinician and the clinic, with the repertoires of interpretations held by other professionals being underexamined. This presentation aims to remedy such an oversight through the presentation of interview data from thirty social care professionals, comprising foster carers and residential carers. It will explore the symbolic meaning that these professionals ascribe to self-harm and suicide among the children and young people they care for. Three repertoires of interpretation will be presented: survival, which conceives self-harm as a mechanism for negotiating and navigating the structurally disadvantaged position of "looked-after child"; signalling, which understands self-harm as a communicative tool for expressing emotional distress; and security, which sees self-harming practices as testing the authenticity and safety of the caring relationship. These registers of meaning are squarely located within a socio-cultural framework, with carers centralising the relational aspect of both causes and treatment. The presentation will consider how elicitation of these repertoires provides insight into the oft documented challenges of inter-professionals' interactions. Carers' juxtaposition of socio-cultural explanations with the bio-medical discourses they believe to be espoused by clinicians creates distance but also discord, particularly in regard to notion of expert identity and expertise.

Understanding suicide and self-harm through arts-based methods: critical reflections

Sarah Jeavons Wright

(University of Edinburgh)

Research addressing the meanings of suicide and self-harm has tended to draw on standard qualitative approaches such as semi-structured interviews and focus groups. In this paper we discuss the challenges and opportunities of using arts-based methods to explore meanings of self-harm and suicide among different groups. Drawing on a recently completed study with people who had self-harmed, and practitioners working with those who had self-harmed, and an ongoing study adapting arts-based approaches for exploration of views of suicide among refugee groups, we reflect on the way in which methods used to research suicide and self-harm work to produce meaning. In particular, our paper grapples with the tensions inherent in research which might serve to 'fix' meanings that are unstable, culturally and socially variable. By contrasting findings, and emerging findings, from studies with groups who bring very different cultural understandings of suicide, we illuminate some of the wider challenges facing qualitatively inclined sociologists researching suicide and self-harm.

Emotionally, materially and socially. A qualitative study of the experiences of women bereaved by the suicide of an intimate partner.

Sharon Mallon,

(Open University)

suicide, are based on studies that assemble those who experience these losses into a collective group, regardless of their relationship to the deceased. Furthermore, research has tended to focus on the psychological aspects of the death, without considering the social implications.

This paper explores the experiences of individuals who had a particular type of relationship with the deceased, analyzing data collected during interviews with 19 women whose intimate partner died by suicide. Drawing on sociological theories, we explore several of the prominent and interrelated themes that emerged from participants' accounts: destruction, disempowerment and dishonour. Gender theories will be used to critically examine experiences in relation to the destruction of domestic, emotional and material security. While work on stigma will be used to provide insight into the ways in which these deaths acted as a stain on their character, disempowering and discrediting these women within their communities. Finally, we provide examples of the ways in which the observed, and in some cases 'infamous' nature of death by suicide, can in the long term lead these women to experience a new and 'marked' identity as a 'woman bereaved by suicide'.

Our findings demonstrate some of the ways in which aspects of suicide bereavement are uniquely gendered and the impact this has for the bereaved. We conclude by arguing this is worthy of greater attention if the practical and emotional consequences of suicide are to be fully appreciated

Towards a microsociology of suicide and its prevention: Understanding suicidal crises in context

Christabel Owens,

" My research focuses on the prevention of suicide at the micro-social level. I take this term from Scheff's Microsociology (1994), defined as "the detailed study of the thoughts

Frontiers W007

'Good Mothers, Breastfeeding and Class: A psychosocial analysis of the implication of class in the mobilisation of the symbolic capital of breastfeeding'

Sharon Tugwell,

(Birkbeck College, University of London)

In contemporary discourses around maternity and health, breastfeeding is positioned as the most superior method of infant feeding, offering unparalleled physiological and psychological benefits to both mother and child. Yet Britain continues to have some of the lowest breastfeeding rates in Europe with current statistics suggesting that it is young mothers, who left school before the age of 18, that are least likely to breastfeed; whereas mothers aged over 30, who left school after the age of 18, are the group most likely to initiate and continue breastfeeding. Breastfeeding is therefore subject to structural influences which extend far beyond mother-child relations. This paper considers the ways in which the symbolic capital of breastfeeding is understood and mobilised by two very different women. The first is a single mother of two children with different fathers, who left school at age 16 and is currently unemployed, reliant on state benefits. The second is a married, university lecturer with two children. At the time of interview, they were both breastfeeding their youngest children, both aged two. The paper seeks to explore the relationship between different forms of inequality and hierarchy by considering the impact of structural factors on the women's lives, and how these factors intersect with the ways in which the symbolic capital of breastfeeding can be mobilised and appropriated. The symbolic capital of breastfeeding becomes a crucial component in the different ways that each

woman takes up and embodies a maternal subject position, with remarkably different psychosocial implications for both.

Interdisciplinarity and Visual Research Practice and Sociology teaching

*Sheila Quaid,
(University of Sunderland)*

As a lecturer I introduced visits to art galleries, use of TV, movies and music in theory modules. This led to co-creation in assessment where students chose their own sources that were meaningful to their identities. The importance of enabling them to find ways to connect personally to sources without necessarily having to make personal or ideological disclosures proved effective. Most chose to work with visual sources over and above all others and the impact was considerable. When teaching post structural theorists, I connected theory with their own chosen movies. Their work became deeply interpretive, theoretical, and critical. They skilfully theorised race, gender, class, nationality and sexuality. This teaching approach created a learning environment where the most intensely personal aspects of identity were analysed. This experience led to my professional collaboration with community arts and creation of interdisciplinary sociological and participatory arts conferences. This innovation also led to interdisciplinary conference on Visual Methods on learning and Teaching and then further community engagement with ESRC Festivals of Social Science interdisciplinary conferences entitled Parenting: Nature Nurture Future which brought together environmentalists, artists, sociologists' film theorists and historians. This interdisciplinary community engagement was held in collaboration with a local arts project called Thought-Foundation. The event achieved considerable reach out and was featured on a Participatory Arts radio. The feedback has been from wide ranging practitioners, for example in Child and Language development, environmentalists, artists and educators lead me to seek further discussion with sociologists about power of the visual.

Tracking the psy-curriculum within 'Asia's world city': The provision of school-based support services in three Hong Kong secondary schools

*Andrew Pau Hoang,
(The University of Hong Kong)*

The Hong Kong Special Administrative Region (HKSAR) government has aimed to establish the region as 'Asia's world city'. This aim often neglects how social and economic development through internationalisation is structured by Hong Kong's historically entrenched inequalities. English hegemony conditions the stratification between fluent English-speaking elites and the 'newly ghetto-ised locals'. Structural racism and ineffective language policies impede social mobility for ethno-racially minoritized South Asians. Pressures to reinforce national education incite fear over the possible 'death' of Hong Kong Chinese culture and language.

This study examines the institutionalisation of these social and economic inequalities in Hong Kong's diverse secondary educational sector. Multi-sited ethnographic fieldwork was conducted in three secondary schools between December 2017-April 2018, representing distinct student populations, school cultures, international-local and private-public education systems. Through non-/participant observation, interviews, document and policy analysis, I tracked the provision of school-based support services (social work, counseling, pastoral guidance and discipline) as interprofessional, affective technologies of care, intervention, psychosocial discipline and social reproduction.

I theorize connections among social inequality, care and governance in education through conceptualisation of these services as 'psy-curriculum'—distinct from the hidden curriculum. Leveraging psyche/affect at the interstice of social welfare and education, the psy-curriculum delimits and separates processes of subjectification through the creation of 'non-/ideal students'. Through intersectionality, I show how the psy-curriculum is entwined with local, global and placeless imaginaries, divided along class, ethno-racial and linguistic lines. I reexamine Hong Kong's colonial past and internationalisation ambitions as conditions of possibility for the psy-curriculum's continued operation and future transformations.

Medicine, Health & Illness

W002

Agency, identity and equality: Understanding socially orientated approaches to recovery for African and Caribbean men

*Kris Southby,
(Leeds Beckett University)*

This symposium will consider the significance of ethnicity, gender, culture, identity, and agency to mental health recovery. It will include two papers, a service-user led theatrical performance, and a group discussion. The focus is on

the experiences of African and Caribbean men. The session will interrogate the value of socially-constructed approaches to recovery that challenge traditional service hierarchies.

Despite several initiatives, notably the 'Delivering Race Equality' national policy, designed to reduce persistent racial disparities in mental health services, people from Black, Asian, and Minority Ethnic (BAME) communities continue to have poorer experiences and outcomes. This disparity is most significant for African and Caribbean men. Recent approaches to supporting individuals with mental health difficulties centre on the notion of recovery. African and Caribbean men, however, can often become stuck in a 'stalled cycle of recovery' if the services and support they receive are not tailored to their unique needs as both people of African and Caribbean heritage and as men.

This symposium will draw together findings from a National Institute of Health Research, School for Social Care Research Project that was conducted in Leeds and London by Royal Holloway University and by Leeds Beckett University between 2016 and 2018 (Principal Investigator: Prof. Frank Keating). The project explored the extent to which a socially-orientated approach to recovery might better support the mental health of African and Caribbean men and what this support might look like.

The first presentation, led by Dr. Kris Southby, will explore how recovery is conceptualised by service users and their supporters. The second presentation, led by Dr. Pamela Fisher, will identify the factors that promote social recovery for African and Caribbean men. A key finding is that hierarchical service delivery often entrenches experiences of exclusion and inequalities related to ethnicity, gender, and social disadvantage. In contrast, providing care that recognises men's life experiences is central to the processes associated with social recovery.

The powerlessness often experienced by African and Caribbean men in traditional service delivery will be portrayed in a short-film, 'Take Control', written and performed by Devon Marston. Devon is a founding member of the Sound Minds music and theatre group, an expert-by-experience, and advisor to the research project. The film illuminates the issues discussed in the papers and acts as a powerful catalyst for reflection and discussion.

The symposium will be chaired by Prof. Frank Keating (PI), with Dr Stephen Joseph as discussant.

The meaning of recovery at the intersection of ethnicity and gender for African and Caribbean men in England

*Kris Southby,
(Leeds Beckett University)*

'Recovery' is a contested concept within mental health. This is to the detriment of patients' progression. The aim of this paper is to consider the meaning of recovery for African and Caribbean men with mental health experience in England.

A qualitative design using a phenomenological approach captured the dynamics of recovery processes and outcomes for African and Caribbean men across the two study sites (Leeds and London). Fifty-nine in-depth semi-structured interviews were conducted with African and Caribbean men with mental health experience (n=30), supporters/family carers (n=15), and service providers (n=14). Data were analysed using Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA). At two co-creation events, service users co-analysed the data.

Findings suggest that recovery for African and Caribbean men is a complex, dynamic concept. A number of interconnected and often overlapping aspects collectively represent and contribute to recovery. These include recovery as a healing journey, leading a 'normal' life, autonomy and control, aspirations for the future, identity, and being free from health services.

Whilst previous research similarly highlights issues of autonomy, social inclusion, personalisation, and identity as fundamental to recovery for all service users, this paper argues that recovery for African and Caribbean men is flavoured by their lived-experience at the intersections of ethnicity and gender. Service providers should acknowledge the men's personal and collective understanding of recovery based on their unique life histories.

Enablers of social recovery for African and Caribbean men: towards co-production

*Pamela Fisher,
(Leeds Beckett University)*

Traditional service delivery is often hierarchical and impersonal, and this can inhibit the potential for African and Caribbean men to gain or re-gain a sense of agency, understood as the ability to take control of their lives.

A qualitative design using a phenomenological approach captured the dynamics of recovery processes and outcomes for African and Caribbean men across the two study sites (Leeds and London). Fifty-nine in-depth semi-structured interviews were conducted with African and Caribbean men with mental health experience (n=30), supporters/family carers (n=15), and service providers (n=14). Data were analysed using Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA). At two co-creation events, service users co-analysed the data.

The discovery or recovery of agency was identified by the participants as possibly the most significant dimension of recovery. A further key finding was that social recovery is significantly facilitated by creating 'safe spaces', that is spaces in which men develop authentic relationships of interdependence based on mutual trust and shared life experiences. The 'care' provided within safe spaces was often compared, by the participants, to their experiences of traditional mental health services that were often characterised by impersonal 'power over' approaches. Within safe spaces African and Caribbean men were able to develop relationships of equality that enabled them to develop the constructive personal and collective identities needed to acquire a sense of individual agency that is central to recovery.

Take Control

*Devon Marston,
(Sound Minds)*

'Take Control' is a play about people from Black, Asian, and Minority Ethnic (BAME) communities' unsatisfactory experiences of hierarchies, coercion, and control in the mental health system in England. It portrays a service user's interaction with their social worker; they want to have greater control in their recovery journey, but continue to be disempowered by coercive and depersonalised professional practice.

We will be screening a film of the 'Take Control' play. It will be a useful stimulus for discussion on mental health issues. The play has been performed at numerous mental health events. Excerpts were included in a BBC2 Newsnight piece about racism in the mental health system, prompting an Early Day Motion in the House of Commons.

The play is written and performed by Devon Marston from the Sound Minds music and theatre group. Devon is an expert by experience and co-founder of Sound Minds. Sound Minds is a user-led charity and social enterprise transforming the lives of people in south west London experiencing mental ill health through participation in arts activities since 1992.

Methodological Innovations

W009

Prompting or checking? Repurposing Facebook Activity Logs and Search Histories in interview settings

*Justine Gangneux,
(The University of Glasgow)*

In the aftermath of Cambridge Analytica, this paper discusses the methodological opportunities and challenges of repurposing social media platforms as a source of data and a tool for research. Drawing on empirical data from my doctoral research, this paper examines the re-purposing of Facebook Activity Logs and Search History as 'digital prompts' in interviews settings. I will focus on the practical and methodological challenges I faced which were generated by the continuous interferences of a third-party platform designed to encourage connections between users while capturing and mining large volumes of data. The challenges common to this kind of research largely ensue from the asymmetries of power between social media corporations and researchers - often working on their own. In this paper, I argue that, as researchers working with social media platforms, we are dependent on tools and data not originally designed for research and need to critically and collectively reflect on the complex ways in which this affects our research and knowledge production.

'Thank you for asking me': ethical judgements in blogging research

*Jenni Brooks
(Sheffield Hallam University)*

This paper explores in detail how ethical challenges were navigated in a research project exploring blogs written by people living with dementia.

Blogging about health conditions has been shown to lead to improvements in wellbeing and an increase in social support (Rains and Keating, 2015). Accessing this writing can give researchers insight into unsolicited, longitudinal accounts of people's lived experiences which may be unobtainable by other methods, allowing voices previously neglected in research to be heard.

However, there is debate about whether blogs constitute 'textual artefacts', and are therefore available for researchers to use without permission; or whether bloggers should be counted as 'human subjects', meaning informed consent should be obtained before using their words for research (Lomborg, 2012). Seeking permission risks being ignored or rejected - frustrating if material is freely available online. But bloggers do not often write with researchers as their intended audience - so are we prying if we use their work without permission? If we anonymise, are we denying authorship?

Ethical guidelines suggest taking a reflexive approach to each project, and considering the expectations of both researchers and bloggers when making ethical decisions. In this project, bloggers were asked for permission to include their work, and were credited with authorship. This paper explores the positives and pitfalls of this approach, and argues that fulfilling the aims of inclusion of unheard voices in research does not justify 'exploitative' methods of including work without permission.

The Iraq War, Green Corn Rebellion and Me: Dialogical Critical Autoethnography

Derek Morris,
(University of Edinburgh)

The paper which I will present utilises the 'Documents of Life' (DoL) approach developed by Ken Plummer as a framework; a socio-cultural exploration inspired by *The Polish Peasant in Europe and America* (Plummer, 2001; Stanley, 2013; Thomas and Znaniecki (TandZ), 1958). My entry point will be examining my MPhil thesis as a DoL, the telling of: the learning and unlearning of race, being raised on a ranch, and the experiences of being soldier in the Iraq War, then moving to Turkey. I am inspired by how TandZ studied the Polish immigrant (Wladek) sociologically, noting that 'personal life-records, as complete as possible, constitute the perfect type of sociological material' (TandZ, 1958: 1832). The autoethnography will be dialogical with its augmentation of numerous DoL materials, similar to TandZ. My research now is in developing a new form of 'critical autoethnography,' a more dialogical one, including TandZ's notion of the 'narratable self,' conceived as a 'relational and dialogical approach to thinking about self in society, in which series and temporality are important to understanding the processes of personal and social becoming' (Reed-Danahay, 2017; Stanley, 2010: 146-147). My autoethnography will be in dialogue with the DoLs associated with the mostly forgotten Green Corn Rebellion, comparing and contrasting them with my own story in order to analyse why farmers/soldiers chose to fight. I will examine the narratives developed on a micro-level and how this relates to the macro-level, exploring the reasons people are compelled to join a fight in either the military or a movement.

Oral history and the creativity of memory

Laura Fenton
(University of Manchester)

Remembering and narrating the past are creative practices: they draw on and weave together embodied, sensory experience, and can have a strong lyrical or poetic quality; they generate something new from existing materials. This paper explores the creativity of memory as it emerged in an oral history project conducted in partnership with a professional curator and Manchester Art Gallery for the exhibition "Shirley Baker: Women and Children; and Loitering Men". Former residents of 'inner city' areas of Manchester and Salford photographed by Shirley Baker in the 1960s and 1970s were interviewed about their recollections of the places represented in the photographs. Excerpts from interviews were then selected and edited for an audio guide that accompanied the photographs in the exhibition. Most interviewees were children or young people when Baker was photographing their areas. Drawing on the lyrical turn in sociology and literary approaches to oral history, we argue that Baker's photographs provided visual material for the creative appropriation and narrative reimaging of childhood and adolescence. We consider how the construction of character and the use of metaphor emerged as two potent sites of creative production in the accounts. The paper concludes by exploring how 'found' - as opposed to elicited or generated - photographs can offer productive resources for oral history and qualitative interviewing.

Race, Ethnicity & Migration A W011

Mixed people and families and generational change

Miri Song,
(University of Kent)

Since 'mixed' was first offered as an option in the ethnicity question in the 2001 England and Wales Census, Britain's recognition of, and interest in, mixed (or 'multiracial') people and families has not abated. Recent studies have focused

primarily upon how mixed people identify themselves, or how parents racially identify their multiracial children. But Britain now has a population of multiracial individuals who are themselves parents, about whom we know very little. What are the particular concerns for multiracial individuals who are parents? Do multiracial people (who are parents) want to steer their children toward a particular kind of upbringing, and if so, toward what (and why)? Furthermore, as the children of mixed people grow up and constitute a 'second generation' mixed population, how what are the implications of using the category 'mixed' in the decennial census? This presentation will emphasize the importance of generational change in our examination of mixed people and families.

Centring Place in the Analyses of Black Mixed Race Identity

Karis Champion,

(University of Manchester)

When the function of place is referenced in the study of mixed race, it is often evoked through the topics of heritage, lineage, family trees and racial ancestry (Gaskins 1999, Sims 2016) and other discussions of place have focused upon national contextual effects on the formation of mixed race identities (Caballero 2005; Joseph-Salisbury 2016; Mitchell 2013; King-O'Riain et al 2014). In some analyses, place is even treated as a mere backdrop which fails to recognise how it functions as a major point of reference for ethnic identifications. Drawing on 37 interviews with Black mixed race people in Birmingham, this paper argues that the field needs to better explore the ways in which mixed race identities intersect with immediate localities. It shows how attachments to the local and departures from it were particularly transformative for their racial selves and suggests that neighbourhoods were the blueprint which they worked from to negotiate their ethnic identities. Lessons regarding race in the home were made legible, when they were contextualised in the broader spaces beyond that boundary which were loaded with racial symbols and histories (Keith 2005; Amin 2002). Despite the tendency in studies on mixed race to privilege racial identity as a defining feature of the mixed race experience, this paper argues that mixed race identity becomes knowable through places inhabited and moved through. It will demonstrate the agency and power that place has in organising social life and identities and warns against its continued absence in the analyses of mixed race identity.

Race, Ethnicity & Migration B

W324

The microdynamics of power and performance in focus group discussions with the South Sudanese diaspora in the UK

Rachel Ayrton,

(University of Southampton)

Diasporic communities affected by intra-state conflict face unique challenges by virtue of their geographical dislocation from the 'home' with which they identify and that confers their political rights. The experience of conflict has the potential to disrupt solidarities fostered by the shared experience of migration and minority status in countries of settlement. As a result, issues of power loom large. I argue that the micro-dynamics of power in focus group discussions have relevance to the relations of power in the population group from which participants are purposively sampled and, consequently, their observation enriches research findings.

In recent years there has been an increasing recognition in methodological literature that both the content of focus group discussions and the interaction that takes place form indivisible facets of focus group data. Interaction, however, is not a neutral activity but one that is infused with the dynamics of power in wider society and in the immediate context of the discussion. I use Bourdieu's notion of fields of power to analyse focus group discussions on national identity with South Sudanese diaspora in the UK.

The story thieves: the ethics of conducting research with refugees and asylum seekers

Edanur Yazici,

(University of Sheffield)

The plight of refugees is never too far from popular discourse, whether it's harrowing tales of people losing their lives in the Mediterranean or of people living in squalor in order to escape persecution. This, coupled with the language of the refugee crisis, has led to a proliferation of research on refugees and asylum seekers. This paper will explore the issues that surround the ethics of research with over-researched and othered communities. The paper will ask whether all research relationships are essentially exploitative and extractive with researchers stealing stories and using their positions of power in order to amplify their own voices. Following this, the paper will explore ways that these dynamics of power can be mitigated in the research process with a focus on positionality and reflexivity. The paper will present the experiences of refugees and asylum seekers as a case study through a discussion of how people are expected to tell their stories to different audiences – be it government officials, lawyers or researchers. The paper will conclude with ways that people can reclaim their own stories and how they can be used as a mode of resistance.

"Sometimes, you feel less than a person': media use, liminality and the UK asylum experience'

*Siobhan Holohan, Natalie Soleiman
(Keele University)*

This paper examines some of the conceptual and methodological issues to emerge from a project that sought to gain insight into how people in the British asylum system might use different forms of media to negotiate their non-citizenship status. Our focus was on both the possible impacts of media narratives on feelings of belonging and isolation, and how users might counter the possible effects of such narratives using alternative media forms. The qualitative interview data revealed a population that are highly engaged with current social, cultural and political developments, particularly in relation to immigration and asylum, but that also have a complex and somewhat abstracted relationship with different media forms dependent on their biographical context. In line with contemporary theories about diasporic media audiences, participants largely avoided mainstream media, preferring instead to access 'information' and entertainment that reflected and supported their personal stories (Georgiou 2017; Tsagarousianou 2012). However, unlike other diasporic audiences, our participants did not often go on to engage in media practices that sought to maintain links with their homeland. Instead, many described a situation where their asylum status has led to the development of a psychic barrier between them and both home and host country, a liminal space that echoes their non-citizenship status (Hynes 2011). Consequently, this paper will reflect on how the asylum seekers in our study use media to negotiate their precarious status within a hostile public sphere context.

Jews, 'Gypsies,' and Kawaramono (Burakumin) in Pre-modern Times : racialized hierarchies and inequality across vast geographical distances

*Yasuko Takezawa,
(Kyoto University)*

The vast majority of studies of social hierarchies and inequality involving the axes of racialization focus on patterns of stratification either within national contexts or across nations that share an Atlantic trajectory, a Mediterranean (or Southern

European) trajectory or a Pacific trajectory. However, there are few studies that compare social hierarchies in the Atlantic as compared with both Southern Europe and the Pacific. In this paper I compare Jews in Spain, Gypsies in Romania and Kawaramono (most of whom were later called Burakumin) in Japan in the medieval period. Despite the geographical distance between these locations and despite the clear differences in their histories, I argue that such a comparison enables us to bring forth many of the common underlying patterns of social hierarchies that prevail, no matter the context. I highlight evidence of comparable patterns of racialization of all three social categories with an emphasis on: a discourse surrounding their origins; a perception of the groups as polluted and the prohibition of intermarriage; a history as non-sedentary or late comers in predominantly agrarian societies; 'monopolization' of economic activities due to social exclusion; an ambiguous relationship with the ruling class in each of the contexts, and the discourses of 'privileges.' I suggest that a comparison of this kind can open up the door to other comparisons across these vast areas, in ways that facilitate a more truly global analysis of social hierarchies.

Race, Ethnicity & Migration C W001

Living together in the context of Brexit: Negotiating uncertainty in the East End of Glasgow

*Anna Gawlewicz,
(University of Glasgow)*

While there is evidence of a profound impact of Brexit on diverse communities in the UK, empirical material for existing research was mostly collected in the run-up to or straight after the EU referendum. Furthermore, this research has tended to selectively focus either on migrant or the long-settled population, and to explore their stories in isolation. How do these stories intertwine? How do diverse communities make sense of uncertainty 'after a while' when (at least some) emotions have settled and people have to 'keep calm and carry on'? This paper addresses these questions by looking at Polish and the long-settled residents in the East End of Glasgow, Scotland, and how they negotiate Brexit one-two years after the vote. In doing so, it provides empirical insights into convivial encounters and engages with wider work on everyday multiculturalism and community relations. The East End of Glasgow has been experiencing a dramatic change recently and is becoming increasingly diverse. While it has a history of poverty and deprivation, it has been attracting new populations, including migrants, because of growing investment and vast regeneration agenda. Polish nationals constitute the largest migrant population in the area and have been significantly contributing to local economies, transformation and communities. Methodologically, the paper is based on 40 interviews with Polish and the long-settled participants conducted as part of the study 'Living together in the context of Brexit: Migrant-'host'

encounters in the East End of Glasgow' funded by the Urban Studies Foundation (Mar 2017- Dec 2019, www.livingtogetherandbrexit.com).

Walking, Talking and Sensing Urban Multiculture: Understanding Narratives of Community and Conviviality in the Materialities of Place and Difference

Dillon Newton,
(University of Salford)

With the publication of the Casey Review in 2016, a political discourse was regurgitated fixated with the purported development of ethnic 'segregation' and cultural withdrawal in urban places with long histories of migration. Rooted in the 2001 'race riots' in the north of England, the re-emergence of this anxious discourse concerning the failures of state 'multiculturalism' ran contrary, however, to a strong body of informed sociological and policy research. Encouraged by evidence-based findings that had presented a significant challenge to the notion inner-city communities lived 'parallel lives', this theoretically-informed sociological research has provided an important counter-narrative on how multiculture is lived, understood and achieved in the everyday in an uncertain time.

Situated in this context, this presentation draws on work-in-progress PhD research that developed a narrative methodology to explore accounts of community life in a transient urban setting underpinned by material conditions shaping power relations and narratives of place. At the core of this project was a walking interview that encouraged participants with differing roots in the locality to link the here-and-now with feelings of cultural difference and memories of place. Reflecting on the ways walking and talking has a certain embodied and relational attribute, this presentation seeks to contribute to enlightened research exploring the complicated, fractured and messy realities of how cultural difference is lived in the everyday. It will critique of an anxious policy discourse rooted in an age of anti-migrant populists and new nationalisms, whilst contributing to ways forward in an intellectual context somewhat adrift.

Conviviality under threat? The case of Polish migrants in Manchester in the context of Brexit

Alina Rzepnikowska
(University of Manchester)

On 23 June 2016, the UK voted to leave the EU by 52 to 48 per cent. Leave won the majority of votes in England and Wales. The EU referendum choices were strongly linked to views about immigration in the UK. An IPSOS Mori (June 16, 2016) poll showed that immigration was the top issue for British people voting in the EU referendum. The wave of post-Brexit vote hostility revealed the extent of racism and xenophobia which affected migrants and settled ethnic minorities, including British citizens (Burnett, 2017; Komaromi and Singh, 2016; Rzepnikowska, 2018). By drawing on qualitative longitudinal research on Polish migrants in Manchester, this paper explores the influence of Brexit on everyday lived experiences of migrants, and it asks whether conviviality can endure despite exclusionary anti-immigration rhetoric. This paper illustrates the importance of the interplay between the media and political discourses, race and ethnicity, class and spatio-temporal dynamics in shaping relations between recent migrants and the local population. While some accounts revealed co-existence of conviviality, tensions and racism, reflecting a fragile and highly dynamic character of conviviality; other narratives showed examples of a sustained neighbourly convivial culture resisting racism and xenophobia. This convivial culture is characterised by low-key interaction between neighbours, interdependence, cooperation, trust and acts of care and kindness, showing the possibility of maintaining social connections and belonging in the context of Brexit.

Faith, migration and business: the role of Pentecostalism in migrant entrepreneurial practices in London and Birmingham

Maria Villares-Varela, Olivian Sheringham, Queen Mary University London
(University of Southampton)

This paper analyses the role of Pentecostalism in migrant entrepreneurial practices. Whilst the link between religion and enterprise is at the core of foundational sociological essays – including Weber's discussion of the relation between religion and the emergence of capitalism - the connection between religious faith and business practices has remained, until recently, notably under-explored. A growing body of work is emerging which examines the connection of religiosity and workplace practices and enterprise. Elsewhere, and within a wider body of work examining the 'post-secular' landscape of many European cities, scholars have explored the role of Faith-Based Organisations (FBOS) in welfare provision, outlining the ways in which the boundaries between the work of faith-motivated and secular organisations are becoming increasingly blurred. Yet less attention has been paid to entrepreneurship, both in terms of churches themselves as entrepreneurial actors and generators of particular norms and values about entrepreneurship, and the wider entrepreneurial aspirations of believers. Our focus on Pentecostalism emerges from its importance amongst new Christian migrant communities in the UK and its emphasis on the promise of prosperity, its success among the poor and its role in career aspirations. Drawing on qualitative interviews with Pentecostal migrants in London and Birmingham, in this paper we critically examine: i) the role of Pentecostal churches in

supporting entrepreneurial activities among migrant communities; and ii) the ways in which Pentecostal beliefs and values influence the aspirations and practices of migrant entrepreneurs.

Rights, Violence & Crime

W004

Rights and Intersecting Inequalities in Prison Culture: Transdisciplinary International Perspectives

Sally Haw,
(University of Stirling)

There are over 10 million prisoners worldwide. The majority come from the poorest, most vulnerable and deprived groups in society. Many follow similar trajectories, with higher rates of unemployment, lack of satisfactory education and a risk of involvement with gangs as well as drugs. These socio-economic inequalities, strongly related to class, race and gender, limit the life chances of marginalised groups, often leading to many periods of imprisonment in overcrowded, violent institutions with inadequate health provisions. Structural inequalities of prisoners and their rights are additionally hampered by strong emphasis on crime, deviance and violence in public and media discourse, commonly subjecting offenders to casual dehumanisation, off-hand denunciations and slanders, and serving as a strong framework for policy debates.

As a part of MRC-AHRC funded project Right to Health in Prison, this international panel brings together a diverse team of researchers from media, communications, sociology, law, human rights, criminology and public health to explore transdisciplinary conceptual, theoretical and methodological frameworks and innovations to reflect on rights and intersecting inequalities in prisons and prison culture; from philosophical and legal perspectives on human rights to healthcare, media and social narratives of criminalised youth, prisons and prisoners to methodological aspects of the precarious world of prison research. It importantly shows that the advance of democratic values and human rights depends not only on policies and practices, but also on a symbolic battle that takes place at the level of individual, collective and institutional narratives, in which media and communications play a central role.

Intersectionality and structural inequalities in media framing of prisons, prisoners and their right to health in Brazil and Scotland

Alenka Jelen-Sanchez,
(University of Stirling)

Media representations of prisoners importantly influence cultural, political and public attitudes and bear significant implications on their right to health. This study focuses on examining media reporting in Brazil with one of the highest rates of imprisonment in the world and in Scotland with one of the highest in Europe. While the prison population in the two contexts differs (the majority of prisoners in Brazil have an African background, while in Scotland the majority are indigenous Scots), inmates in both systems mostly come from the poorest, most deprived and stigmatised communities. To explore how prisons, prisoners and their right to health are represented in the media and how these representations reflect and/or reinforce intersectional inequalities in society, we conducted framing analysis of prison news published in most read daily newspapers in Brazil (O Globo and Estadão) and Scotland (The Herald and the Scotsman) between July 2017 and July 2018. Following Entman's (1993) conceptualisation of framing, the study explores inclusion and exclusion of different themes in the news as well as their definitions, causal interpretations, moral evaluations, and treatment recommendations. The preliminary results indicate that framing in Brazilian newspapers strongly depends on race, class and gender with derogative frames for non-white male offenders from favelas, whereas reporting in Scotland is more 'politically correct' with strong inclinations to stigmatise offenders from disprivileged communities in pathological frames, particularly women. These frames importantly align with the broader policy discussions on right and actual access to health in prisons.

Shadowy prowler or reflexive scholar? The precarious world of international prison researcher

Laura Piacentini,
(University of Strathclyde)

Criminology's recent theoretical turn towards disrupting the dominance of global north scholarship through new critical work coming from 'the global south' is gathering apace. Yet, absent from these debates is theoretical and empirical understandings of world penal development, beyond the global north and south, and this has significant impact on methodological approaches to the study of world penal systems, not least researcher positionality, self-reflexivity, ethical ambiguities, sample sizes and so on. This paper seeks to both develop and disrupt conventional methodological frameworks for exploring the author's research in world penal systems by providing a critical, methodological account of new social media approaches to prison research, using a case of Russia. Part one of the paper explores how prison researchers must navigate and interrogate multiple selves in the penal field. Part two of the

paper draws down findings from a UK Leverhulme study into the sociology of rights consciousness amongst Russian prisoners who are engaging in online prisoner blogging using illicit communication devices. The paper will examine how the researcher exercises power by emphasising the ontological awareness of knowledge production: what a researcher finds is determined by who she or he is (race, class, cultural background, and gender). The paper will also interrogate concerns about prisoners as 'research subjects'.

Social Divisions / Social Identities A W110

We Are Our Media: producing alternatives for the North East of England?

*Susan Lewis,
(Durham University)*

A growing, diverse group of people in the North East of England has recently published the second edition of *The Eclipse*, an 'alternative tabloid' by and for the people of the region. Born out of dissatisfaction with mainstream media influence in the Brexit debate (Seaton, 2016), members have also cited inequality and a sense of powerlessness, the impact of austerity and welfare reform, and lack of trust in the press, politics and politicians as reasons for involvement in the project.

The newspaper is just one aspect of the We Are Our Media (WAOM) project. By committing to a print version and distributing many of the 20,000 copies face-to-face, the group seeks to engage directly with local people – including the disadvantaged and electronically disenfranchised – to hear their stories. The aim is to make 'spaces for conversation, [to] understand common issues and be empowered to do something about those issues' (<https://www.weareourmedia.com/>).

Drawing on ethnographic research conducted with WAOM, and interviews with the project's originators, we explore the origins, objectives and hoped-for outcomes of this project. Grassroots journalism is nothing new (Gillmor, 2006) but, we suggest, there is more at the heart of this socially innovative project than the need to fill a local news gap. 'The process of [people] hating politics tends to feed on itself,' Stoker (2009) argues, especially when driven by a mainstream media feedback loop. Can do-it-ourselves journalism and news by and for people hope to change the conversation and thus the dynamics of democratic (dis)engagement?

The regression of common dreams – on making sense of right-wing political shifts

*Tim Winzler, Tim Winzler
(Glasgow University)*

In this paper I will go back in history to make sense of the present rise of right-wing political thought. Using a historical example of worker's resistance that might seem to be unlikely for contemporary sociological eyes, I wish to disrupt the rather uniform views of 'resistance' that prevails in the discipline, as something that 'obviously' challenges the status quo, and in an unambiguously progressive way. I show that there are furthermore – although often neglected or relegated to structuralist or moralist explanations or condemnations – forms of resistance that might be called 'integrated' – integrated into the norms and limitations of the existing structures, times and places.

I will use this critical reflection and expansion of the concept of resistance to then make sense of eastern European rightwing populist shifts. What economic anthropologists like Don Kalb or Chris Hann have been arguing for a while – that the people in these countries have been morally dispossessed- can be complemented and rounded out by sociological arguing that attempts to identify more precisely the processes and groups involved. E.P. Thompson's dictum that a unified class has to be 'made', i.e. constructed, is therefore validated *ex negativo*. This has important epistemological implications of how we see, and judge, rightwing populist voting and rise of attitudes, and what we as Sociologist can do about it politically.

Law, Modernisation and Nationalism

*Unai Urrastabaso Ruiz,
(The University of Edinburgh)*

National identity and cultural domination have become key issues that need constant negotiation and resolution in contemporary societies. The existence and meaning of these issues tend to be explained through modernist accounts of modern European state formation. However, historical research of processes of state formation in different countries, like that of Spain, often produce contradictory or paradoxical results. This, I argue, is partly produced by the influence exercised by the concept of law underlying modernist theories, which limit the meanings that can be attributed to certain instances of political action. I propose that some of these problems can be alleviated through the endorsement of a more empirical and critical approach to law, *Lega Realism*. This adds a broader analytical

framework into sociological analysis, which enables a more nuanced and varied interpretation of the meanings of political action.

Social Divisions / Social Identities B **W828**

Capitalism's Failed Promise and the Moral Economy of Neo-Nationalism: Premature Deindustrialization and the Remaking of Working Class Solidarities in Hungary

Gabor Scheiring,
(University of Cambridge)

Neo-nationalism is on the rise throughout the world but its roots remain contested. In this paper I utilise the strategic research site offered by workers' everyday experience in four deindustrialising towns in post-socialist Hungary to address the roots of rising neo-nationalism. I present the results of a computer-assisted qualitative content analysis of 82 semi-structured interviews with workers who were already employed in the towns' socialist companies before the regime change in 1989. I argue that rising precariousness, economic dislocation and downward social mobility are the major upstream determinants of neo-nationalism, but these are never translated automatically into political-cultural expressions. Utilising the notion of moral economy I argue that the vestigial post-socialist welfare state could slow down the disillusionment with capitalism in general and premature deindustrialisation in particular. By the second half of the 2000s it became clear that the realities of the new socio-economic order are irreconcilably at odds with the moral expectations of the post-socialist working class. The interviews also reveal that the technocrats of the Socialist Party and the liberal intelligentsia were seen as the main architects of the new order. In the absence of a progressive articulation of workers' experience the nation became the framework of imagined solidarity. I conclude that Hungary is not an isolated case but offers a natural experiment to study the everyday experience of emerging capitalist hierarchies and their political implications in a condensed way. As such, Hungary shows a potential capitalist future as much as the legacy of the region's socialist past.

Generalising the Particular: Social spaces across capitalist nations

William Atkinson, Will Atkinson
(University of Bristol)

This paper reports on an effort to test the contemporary applicability and generalisability of Pierre Bourdieu's model of class developed in *Distinction*. Specifically, it seeks to determine whether capital composition – that is, whether one possesses a greater weight of economic or cultural capital – is a salient axis of differentiation and domination alongside capital volume in developed capitalist nations. Subjecting data for nineteen countries drawn from the International Social Survey Programme to multiple correspondence analysis, Bourdieu's model is generally found to hold good for a wide range of nations in the 21st Century. There are, however, important national differences, particularly in relation to the strength of capital composition as a principle of division. Nations with a higher average length of education, greater proportion of professionals and managers in the workforce and lower economic inequality – such as Norway, Denmark and Sweden – have, statistically speaking, a strong and widespread capital composition principle, whereas nations with the opposite characteristics, such as the US, tend to have a weaker polarisation of capital composition localised largely at the top end of the capital volume axis. The principle is still there, though, and does seem to have observable empirical effects.

'They think we're stupid don't they' ? Are fractures in the moral economy leading to a more marginalised working class?

Su Jones
(Aston University)

In this paper I explore a radical change in the relationship between the state and 'the working class', looking specifically at a fracture in moral economy. Using Mau's (2003) concept of *homo recipricus* and *homo economicus* I draw on my PhD fieldwork outlining people's perceptions and experiences of state interventions and health initiatives in their lives that has led to a further fracturing of an already problematic relationship between working class people and state agencies. I will explore how the welfare state is seen as a right of modern economic life – reciprocity for unequal distribution of resources - *homo recipricus* -that is being eroded and replaced by an ideology of responsibility that not only penalises those who are the most dependent on a welfare state, but is leading to the right to welfare provision being replaced by the responsibility of people to take care of themselves and their communities. I argue that this fracturing of moral economy is not only leading us towards a more polarised society but continues a narrative blaming working class people for inequality.

Sociology of Education

W823

All imposters in the academy?

Yvette Taylor, Madeline Breeze
(University of Strathclyde)

This paper re-visits 'imposter syndrome' in connection to contemporary debates on academic career categories, and explores how contested categories such as early and established career, circulate alongside 'imposter' positions on social media. We draw on two contemporary and on-going moments/case studies from 'Academic Twitter' (Gregory and Saheli Singh 2018); the UK 2018 Universities and Colleges Union industrial action over USS pensions, and #immodestwomen which articulated around women using their academic titles, online and off. Both moments are fractured by academic career categories, and intertwine with everyday academic interactions and corridor talk as well as online spaces beyond Twitter, including academic blogs and media reports. By analysing these moments in relation to career categories, we reconsider how imposter positions are claimed and occupied. In doing so we highlight how the figure of the academic 'imposter' is reconstituted, reappearing and perhaps disappearing across career categories at times of 'crisis' in UK HE. Our analysis avoids any search for the authentic imposter and interrupts the idea that we are 'all imposters' in the academy, homogeneously and universally feeling the same across career stage and intersectional exclusions. We therefore shift away from understandings of 'imposter syndrome' as an individual feeling, towards imposter status as symptomatic of structural location. Asking what the circulation of imposter-feelings can tell us about academic hierarchies, inclusions and exclusions, across the career course.

On Quitting

Francesca Coin,
(Ca' Foscari University)

Over the past few years, there has been an ostensible growth in 'quit lit', a new genre of literature made of columns and opinion editorials detailing the reasons why scholars - with or without tenure - leave academia. This paper examines the impact of the neoliberal academia on the academic subject. In the neoliberal university, subjectivity is caught into a web of conflicting expectations. On the one hand, it is expected to live up to high standards of competition. On the other hand, the body experiences competition as a celebrated form of self-abuse. In this context, quitting is not merely about resigning an academic position. It is a symptom of the urge to create a space between the neoliberal discourse and the sense of self; an act of rebellion intended to abdicate the competitive rationality of neoliberal academia and embrace different values and principles.

Work, Employment & Economic Life

HANGING LANTERN ROOM

Making the case for creativity: Always different, always the same?

Peter Campbell,
(University of Liverpool)

This paper assesses the state of evidence and policy regarding 'creativity' and creative industries after twenty years of promotion and support. These demonstrate a remarkable consistency over this period and, despite a long-standing emphasis on research and advocacy, the case continues to be argued for the necessity of yet further research to convincingly make the case for creativity. Alongside this process, what are by now conventional (and questionable) assertions regarding the role of culture in economic and social regeneration continue to be made. It is argued that unless the concept of creativity is employed with more precision, this relative stagnation, and the challenges in reaping the benefits associated with creativity, will persist, as will the broader patterns of inequality which the rhetoric of openness around creativity can serve to mask.

'Women, creative labour and 'Etsy': An examination of freelance 'passionate' work under neo-liberal and post-Fordist capitalism

Anna Clover,
(University of Glasgow)

This paper seeks to explore the micro level effects of neo-liberal and post-Fordist models of contemporary work. Specifically, in regards to female encounters with the craft selling platform Etsy.com.

Through our current epoch of neo-liberal, post-Fordist capitalism, we are experiencing significant changes in how women are understood as economic actors. Within the UK there is a growing generation of young women seeking employment through creative forms of freelance labour. An example of this trend can be witnessed through the popularity of Etsy. The platform forms an example of the promises offered women by creative and craft based economics under neo-liberalism, such as the possibility of a 'democratic' version of home-based entrepreneurialism.

As Dawkins (2011), McRobbie (2016) state, there has been a lack of research regarding the lived experiences of young women engaging in the creative freelance labour. Etsy has largely been aligned with positive narratives regarding the pleasures and socially transformative qualities of 'making things for yourself' and the benefits of individualised entrepreneurialism (Dawkins, 2011:263). However, such positive qualities also arguably justify low pay, long hours and economic precariousness.

Through a qualitative paradigm and the use of semi-structured interviews this project seeks to investigate how 'liberating' Etsy home-based businesses are for the women who run them, and to situate such work in wider debates regarding neo-liberal and postFordist models of contemporary work.

Ultimately the argument will be presented that Etsy based entrepreneurialism is imbued with individualistic neo-liberal ideology, and contributes to a gendered 're-traditionalisation' of labour practices (Dawkins, 2011, Adkins, 1999).

What cuts through and what holds it together? Making sense of entrepreneurial work-life

*Karel Musilek,
(Durham University)*

What cuts through and what holds it together? Making sense of entrepreneurial work-life

Entrepreneurial work in tech and creative industries is characterised by long working hours, high commitment and high risk. In addition, it is characterised by high degree of integration of working and personal life when it comes to time, social ties, and space. Accounts explaining the blurring of life and work in this context focused on the role of discourse, affect and ethics. Moreover, some accounts privilege individual and subjective dynamics over wider economic and organisational factors present in the tech economy. This paper draws on ethnographic research of domestic and personal lives of entrepreneurs to add to the existing knowledge. Firstly, it explores how the logic of investment into future financial freedom replaces the logic of work-life balance and how this corresponds with the flows of capital within the tech economy. Secondly, it shows how 'passionate' commitment to entrepreneurial work is maintained by discursive and affective practices embedded within intermediary organisations (entrepreneurial community organisations, shared office spaces, festivals), rather than stemming solely from individual psychological states. More broadly, the paper argues for attention being paid to forces that bind personal and work life together, rather than focusing on the issue of balance and boundaries. In addition, it calls for greater focus on wider economic and organisational forces shaping the relation between entrepreneurial work and life.

The Division of Labour? Exploring the unequal career trajectories of young professional footballers

*Chris Platts, Melissa Jacobi, Andy Smith
(Sheffield Hallam University)*

Contemporary debate around professional footballers' working lives is dominated by dialogue surrounding supposed high wages, excessive endorsements and the resultant celebrity lifestyle. One consequence of this overly romanticised view of professional football is that the everyday realities of working in such highly neoliberal precarious spaces remains largely ignored (Roderick 2006; Roderick, Smith, and Potrac 2017; Platts and Smith 2018). The research explored the realities of working as a professional footballer by presenting longitudinal data that traces the career trajectories of 299 young males who were scholars (aged 16-18) at professional football clubs in 2009. By presenting data in this way, a more adequate picture is painted of the complex, precarious, unequal and relatively short careers of the majority of footballers. This study highlights that, for those players who 'made it', their labour has been characterised by geographical relocations, short-term contracts and, in the main, transfers down the leagues. For those players who were either unable to secure a professional contract at the age of 18 or were released from football after a few years, all were transitioned out the professional game in their late teens or early twenties, highlighting the potential hazards associated with the pursuit of a career in professional football.

POSTER PRESENTATIONS

Wednesday 24/04/2019 at 18:45 - 19:45

Cities, Mobilities, Space and Place

Historical Analysis of Spatial Segregation: Re-Study of Rowntree's Poorest Area from Environmental Risk Perspective

Naoko Takeda
(University of York)

Rowntree's pioneering poverty research shows poorest area in York on a map. Hungate and Walmgate are located at the both banks across the River Foss. Both districts were included poorest area on this map. In this presentation I focus on both districts and compare the changing process in both districts.

Though some slum clearance projects were conducted by city of York, the changing process in both districts was very different. Hungate is a representative redevelopment area at present. On the other hand Walmgate keeps old street structure.

Small shops attract many tourists. Walmgate is one of the bustling streets in tourist city of York. Why did both districts differ so much? In this presentation I explore the factors of the difference from an environmental perspective.

The River Foss was an important infrastructure for industry at that time. However, it was a cause of flooding, and it is still causing serious flooding even now. Environmental risk impacts people and economic assets, causes social inequalities.

Sanitation facilities were not good at that time, once flooding occurred, bacteria caused infectious diseases. Wealthy people did not live on the riverbank, moved out city wall to good environment area.

It is possible to read the contents expressed on the Rowntree's map deeply using other supplementary materials. While none of the schedules from Rowntree's first 1899 survey survive, sanitary inspection data set which was conducted by city of York during 1907-08 exists, I can understand the environmental risk impacted deeply on social segregation in York.

Sociology of Education

Visualising the policy-practice gap in widening participation through a research informed comic

Jon Rainford
(Staffordshire University)

This poster presentation is presented in the form of a research-informed comic, this paper summarises the findings and recommendations of a study into the gaps between policy and practice in widening participation outreach. Increasingly the research informed comic format is being used successfully in order to engage wider audiences with academic findings (e.g Vigurs 2016; Sousanis 2015)

The study presented in this paper a critical discourse analysis of ten access agreements with in-depth semi-structured interviews with sixteen practitioners to explore differences in widening participation policy and practices. The choice to develop a comic was driven by the interest expressed by participants in the visual methods incorporated in the interviews. The initial comic panels highlighted some of the competing demands and tensions that can limit the effectiveness of practice and was used with practitioners to discuss these. These included the challenges that were common to being able to fulfil their roles, key differences in approaches based on the type of institution, interpretations of the 'raising aspirations' agenda.

This has since been expanded further and additional panels added featuring the recommendations for improving policy and practice in the version presented here. In adopting an alternative mode of presentation, this paper also offers a visual form of presentation that is accessible to a wider audience than a traditional academic paper.

People Like Me: Understanding Systemic Inequalities In UK Higher Education Through A Personal Lens

Jessica Gagnon, Dr Emily Mason-Apps; Arif Mahmud
(University of Portsmouth)

This presentation will explore initial findings from the two-year Office for Students (OfS) funded attainment gap project titled 'Changing Mindsets: Reducing stereotype threat and implicit bias as barriers to student success'. The project is

focused on addressing unequal student outcomes for two student groups: Black and Minority Ethnic (BME) students and socio-economically disadvantaged students. The intervention and research is underpinned by sociological (Collins and Bilge, 2016; Bhopal and Preston, 2012), psychological (Dweck, 2017; Devine et al, 2012), and educational (Reay, 2017; Apple, 2015) concepts and theories. Initial analysis of data suggests that the attainment gaps cannot be explained by a student's tariff on entry (qualifications) into university which is consistent with findings from previous attainment gap research (Mountford-Zimdars et al, 2015). Additionally, our findings indicate that staff and students who have growth mindsets - the belief that traits such as intelligence are malleable - are more likely to want to create inclusion and to overcome bias. Staff and students with fixed mindsets are more likely to hold stereotype beliefs. The presentation will focus on the development and validation of a new 12-item survey measure, called People Like Me. The measure, which includes quantitative and qualitative responses, was designed to explore a sense of belonging and the impact of systemic inequalities on self-perception. This new measure is currently being validated and is intended to be useful in shaping future research. Findings from the project are intended to inform higher education policies and practices to address inequalities in students' experiences and outcomes.

Medicine, Health & Illness

Local authorities and child health inequalities - making sense of policy implementation in a rapidly changing landscape

Hannah Fairbrother, Katie Powell; Carolyn Summerbell; David Taylor-Robinson, Ruth Kipping, Jonathan Wistow (University of Sheffield)

Many health outcomes for children and young people in England remain poor compared to international peers, with persistent and widening socio-economic and ethnic inequalities across the country. A major challenge is that current research does not address the theoretical and practical uncertainties that decision-makers face when trying to implement policies to reduce inequalities in child health. Our project, part of an ambitious National Institute of Health Research School for Public Health Research programme, aims to understand rhetoric and practice in relation to reducing child health inequalities in the context of severely reduced budgets and wide scale organisational change. Through documentary analysis and ethnographic case studies we plan to explore the evolving practices within local authorities. We will draw on process sociology to better theorise the local public health system as it relates to children and young people. This perspective draws attention to the shifting power dynamics in the public health system (the product of ongoing organisational change), which shape everyday practices in the field of child health. Responding to critiques that the social sciences 'punch well below their weight' with respect to policy-relevant outputs, our paper aims to show how we can effectively mobilise theoretically-driven participatory research to contribute to reducing inequalities in child health.

Families & Relationships

No shit Sherlock! Human and nonhuman animals in the surveillant assemblage.

Delia Langstone (University of East London)

In the same way as human animals, nonhuman animals are increasingly finding themselves the objects of routine, technologically mediated scrutiny which situates them as significant elements of the surveillant assemblage. In 2016 a pioneering DNA registration scheme was launched in London: Poopprints™ is designed to systematically gather up samples from offending dogs and to identify them, and therefore their owners, for punitive action. The scheme has been flagged up as a badge of considerate dog ownership yet it is one that can be franchised to tie up with diverse income streams being described as advantageous in the age of austerity. In 2017 it was been reported that this scheme is to be rolled out in other areas and is moving from being voluntary to being mandatory with the enforcement of Public Space Protection Orders (PSPOs) necessitating outlay from dog owners to be able to access protected 'public' spaces. PSPOs have been described as 'geographically defined ASBOS' that have come into force under the Anti-social behaviour and policing Act (2014); they often work to criminalise activities that were not previously considered illegal. This paper argues that this animal surveillance is subject to considerable function creep going far outside the scheme's original objectives and acts as a conduit for more problematic surveillance of humans. This results in social sorting of people with subsequent unforeseen consequences leading to discrimination and curtailment of freedoms. Ultimately this opens people up to further intrusive scrutiny by commercial interests and, more alarmingly, law enforcement agencies.

Methodological Innovations

Self-portrait plus reflective interview: Opportunities for re-examining time, self and relationships in coercive control with women co-inquirers

*Sui-Ting Kong,
(Department of Sociology
Durham University)*

Drawing on the understanding that coercive control is a liberty crime that restricts women's (relational) autonomy and hence their space for action, this study aims at engaging women as co-inquirers in exploring (1) the impact of coercive control on women's ways of doing being oneself (relational personhood) and (2) how women have (un)successfully resisted coercive control during their stay-leave process. Answering these questions requires a methodology that brings women's voices into to the centre of knowledge making and demands methodological innovations that can generate safe spaces for women to express their experiences of coercive control. This study engaged with women co-inquirers who have experienced coercive control in Northeast England, social worker, art-facilitator and academic researcher in making sense of impact of coercive control and women's resistance together. The participatory approach highlights both the benefits and costs of constant communication, the care-'less'ness that conventional informed consent could convey and value of 'suspicion' in multidisciplinary collaboration. Meanwhile, the use of 'self-portrait plus reflective conversation', as a method, has shown potentials for translating the highly embodied experiences of coercive control into various forms of expression (i.e. symbolic and narrative) which (1) problematise linear temporality for organising experiences of coercive control; (2) visualise fluidity of (relational) self; and (3) identify social relationships that can support women's resistance against coercive control. Democratising research methods, therefore, should be considered as a form of scholar-activism that brings intersecting social hierarchies, such as gender, researcher-researched distinction and the dismissal of 'lay' knowledge, into question.